

CHALMERS

Proceedings of the 27th European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry Working Meeting

6–11 April 2025
Matera

edited by
R. Haas and L. Garramone

Agenzia Spaziale Italiana

TELESPAZIO
a LEONARDO and THALES company

e-geos

AN ASI / TELESPAZIO COMPANY

**Proceedings of the 27th European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry
Working Meeting**

edited by
Rüdiger Haas and Luciano Garramone

The authors are solely responsible for the content of their papers. The editors do not take any responsibility for potential intellectual or physical harm of the readers. ☺
The use of the contents has to follow the laws of copyright and ownership.

December 2025, Gothenburg, Sweden

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18088484

(2025 | ed. Rüdiger Haas and Luciano Garramone | Proceedings of the 27th European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry Working Meeting | E-bok)

Preface

The 27th Working Meeting of the European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry (EVGA) was held 6–11 April 2025 in Matera, Italy. A group photo of the EVGA 2025 participants is shown in Figure 1.

The meeting started with the ice breaker and registration on Sunday, 6 April, at the venue, Palazzo Viceconte in Matera. On Monday, 7 April, the scientific program started with oral and poster presentations. In total we had 40 oral presentations, each 15 minutes long, including 3 minutes for questions, and 34 posters. Except the very last session, the oral sessions had three presentations each, followed by a break. The breaks were either 15 minute long "stretch your legs" breaks, 30 minute long coffee breaks, or 90 minute long lunch breaks.

The posters were on display during the whole meeting, i.e. could be read and discussed in the coffee breaks and lunch breaks. Additionally, a dedicated poster viewing session took place on Tuesday afternoon, which was introduced by short poster pitches of the presenting authors. The scientific organizing committee (SOC) also chose three posters that at the end of the meeting received the "EVGA2025 best poster award".

A Gala Dinner was served in Palazzo Viceconte on Tuesday evening, sponsored by Telespazio and E-Geos. Delicious typical food and wine from the Basilicata region were served and the participants enjoyed a very nice evening.

The oral presentation sessions continued on Wednesday morning. The EVGA 2025 scientific presentation program was officially closed before the lunch break. During the closing session, the leaving EVGA chair and co-chair, Rüdiger Haas and Susana Garcia-Espada, respectively, handed over to the new EVGA chair and co-chair, Susana Garcia-Espada and Maria Karbon, who had been elected during the spring for the period 2025–2029. We congratulate Susana and Maria and wish them all the best and success for leading EVGA during the upcoming four years!

The Wednesday afternoon was then dedicated to an excursion to the Centro Spaziale "Giuseppe Colombo" of the Agenzia Spaziale Italiana (ASI). This visit included an interesting guided tour to the numerous space geodetic instruments at Matera station, i.e. VLBI, SLR, and GNSS. The highlight however was the official inauguration of MATERAVG, the new VGOS station at Matera. Francesco Vespe cut the opening ribbon, symbolizing that MATERAVG is joining the VGOS network of the International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS). A corresponding certificate of the IVS was handed over to Francesco and later the EVGA 2025 participants toasted to the inauguration of MATERAVG.

On Thursday morning, the IVS Analysis Workshop was held at Palazzo Viceconte. Various topics of interest for the data analysis of VLBI data were discussed. During the afternoon several splinter meetings were held.

Most EVGA 2025 participants travelled back home on Friday. The exception were the IVS Directing Board members who held their meeting at ASI station Matera on that day.

Figure 1: Group photo of the EVGA 2025 participants in front of the conference venue, Palazzo Viceconte in Matera.

Figure 2: Number of registered participants at EVGA meetings since 2001.

The EVGA 2025 was an in-person only meeting. Figure 2 shows some statistics on the number of registered participants at EVGA meetings since 2001. Compared to previous years, the EVGA 2025 had unfortunately a slightly lower number of registered participants. Furthermore, due to the recent ongoing political situation in a non-European country, some of the registered participants could not participate in the end, since they did not receive travel permit by their employers. This was very unfortunate of course. However, the number of participants at site was still good and well sufficient for a fruitful scientific conference. For the future, one might however consider to arrange online participation again in order to reach as many of possible interested colleagues.

The large number of high quality presentations, both oral and poster, are in any case a very strong indication for an active and prospering European VLBI community. This is very encouraging for the future, in particular with increasing importance of VGOS internationally and the large number of VGOS stations in Europe!

We want to thank all participants for sharing their interesting findings with the audience during interesting oral and poster presentations. Many of the presentations are available at <https://zenodo.org/communities/evga2025>.

We want to thank the scientific organising committee (SOC) for putting together a very interesting meeting program and the local organising committee (LOC) for organising the meeting. We also want to thank Agenzia Spaziale Italiana (ASI) for co-organising EVGA 2025, and the sponsors Telespazio and e-geos.

We are grateful to all authors for preparing their proceedings contributions. The proceedings are available in electronic form at the EVGA webpage evga.org.

December 2025,
Rüdiger Haas and Luciano Garramone

This page is intentionally left blank.

EVGA 2025 organising committees

Scientific Organising Committee (SOC)

- Simone Bernhart (Reichert GmbH/BKG/MPIfR Bonn)
- Sigrid Böhm (Technische Universität Wien)
- Susana Garcia-Espada (Kartverket)
- Rüdiger Haas (Chalmers University of Technology)
- Maria Karbon (University of Alicante)
- Karine Le Bail (Chalmers University of Technology)
- Vincenza Tornatore (Politecnico of Milano)
- Nataliya Zubko (Finnish Geospatial Research Institute)

Local Organising Committee (LOC)

- Stefania Arena (Agenzia Spaziale Italiana)
- Luciano Garramone (Agenzia Spaziale Italiana)
- Enrico Potenza (Agenzia Spaziale Italiana)
- Agostina Torino (Agenzia Spaziale Italiana)
- Giulia Alati (Agenzia Spaziale Italiana)

Series of events during the EVGA 2025

Date	Time	Event
6 April	18:00-21:00	Registration and Icebreaker
7 April	08:45-20:00	EVGA 2025 day-1
8 April	09:00-17:30	EVGA 2025 day-2
	19:00-23:00	EVGA 2025 Gala Dinner
9 April	09:00-12:45	EVGA 2025 day-3
	14:30-17:15	Excursion to Matera station and inauguration of Matera VGOS station
10 April	09:00-13:00	IVS Analysis Workshop
	14:30-18:30	IVS splinter meetings
11 April	08:00-17:30	IVS Directing Board meeting

Program EVGA2025

2025-04-06

Icebreaker and registration	Register, meet your friends, talk to your colleagues.	18:00–21:00
------------------------------------	---	-------------

2025-04-07

EVGA2025 Day-1

Welcome	Rüdiger Haas, Francesco Vespe	08:45–09:00
----------------	--------------------------------------	-------------

Session 1.1 (45 min)		Chairperson: Nataliya Zubko	
García-Castellano	A-15	O-01	Santa Maria Raega Station Overview And Developments 09:00–09:15
Pfaffinger	A-24	O-02	The Hartebeesthoek Terrestrial Laser Scanning Project – Concept And First Results 09:15–09:30
Garramone	A-30	O-03	VLBI Activities At Matera Space Geodesy Center 09:30–09:45
Stretch your legs break (15 min)		09:45–10:00	

Session 1.2 (45 min)		Chairperson: Susana Garcia-Espada	
Lopez-Perez	A-29	O-04	Broadband Receiver Developments For VGOS Radiotelescopes At Yebes Observatory 10:00–10:15
Neidhardt	A-69	O-05	The Potential Of System Monitoring 10:15–10:30
Handirk	A-47	O-06	Connecting Geodetic VLBI Telescope Generations At The Ny-Ålesund Geodetic Earth Observatory Through Short-Baseline Interferometry – Final Results 10:30–10:45
Coffee break (30 min)		10:45–11:15	

Session 1.3 (45 min)		Chairperson: Karine le Bail	
Tornatore	A-48	O-07	Radio Frequency Compatibility Of VGOS And DORIS Stations 11:15–11:30
Bernhart	A-51	O-08	A Report On New VGOS Frequency Sequences Test Observations 11:30–11:45
Hase	A-36	O-09	Status Of The Spectrum Management For VGOS 11:45–12:00
Stretch your legs break (15 min)		12:00–12:15	

Session 1.4 (45 min)		Chairperson: Simone Bernhart	
He	A-60	O-10	Recent Status Of The Shanghai Correlator 12:15–12:30
González-García	A-75	O-11	The Raega Correlator At Yebes Observatory: Description And Status 12:30–12:45
Haas	A-52	O-12	Towards VLBI With ESA's Genesis Satellite 12:45–13:00
Lunch break (90 min)		VI 13:00–14:30	

Session 1.5 (45 min)			Chairperson: Maria Karbon	
Schunck	A-50	O-13	VLBI Observations To GNSS Satellites Using The Australian VGOS Array	14:30–14:45
Gan	A-61	O-14	Observation Of Chang'e 5 Orbiter With Shanghai And Urumqi VGOS Antennas	14:45–15:00
Bruni	A-58	O-15	Invaluable Lunar-Based Interferometry Enabled By ESA's Novamoon Mission	15:00–15:15
Stretch your legs break (15 min)				15:15–15:30

Session 1.6 (45 min)			Chairperson: Vincenza Tornatore	
Kinman	A-22	O-16	Flux Monitoring At VGOS Frequencies With The Onsala Twin Telescopes	15:30–15:45
Nothnagel	A-09	O-17	Effective Frequencies And Ionosphere Calibration Of Legacy S/X Data	15:45–16:00
Zubko	A-02	O-18	Systematic Errors In VGOS Differential Ionospheric Total Electron Content	16:00–16:15
Coffee break (30 min)				16:15–16:45

End of EVGA2025 Day-1, time for splinter meetings and poster viewing				17:00–20:00
---	--	--	--	--------------------

Splinter meetings

VTC meeting	(closed)	José Antonio López Pérez et al.	17:00–18:00
IVS WG 9 meeting	(open)	Karine Le Bail et al.	18:00–19:00
Poster viewing , see list of posters below			17:00–20:00

2025-04-08**EVGA2025 Day-2**

Session 2.1 (45 min)			Chairperson: Lucia McCallum	
Le Bail	A-57	O-19	VLBI-Scale Of The ITRF2020-U2023	09:00–09:15
Kern	A-08	O-20	The VLBI Scale Drift: Current Status And Remaining Challenges	09:15–09:30
Seitz	A-19	O-21	DTRF2020_U2023: The Update Of DTRF2020	09:30–09:45
Stretch your legs break (15 min)				09:45–10:00

Session 2.2 (45 min)			Chairperson: Hana Krasna	
Jacobs	A-23	O-22	The JPL 2025a Terrestrial And Celestial Reference Frames	10:00–10:15
Nilsson	A-45	O-23	Evaluation Of Terrestrial And Celestial Reference Frames Estimated From VGOS Data	10:15–10:30
Krasna	A-11	O-24	VGOS CRF: Celestial Reference Frame From The VLBI Global Observing System Until 2024	10:30–10:45
Coffee break (30 min)				10:45–11:15

Session 2.3 (45 min)			Chairperson: Lisa Kern	
Schartner	A-12	O-25	A Global Troposphere Model For VLBI Simulations	11:15–11:30
Laha	A-17	O-26	Impact Of Atmospheric Turbulence On VGOS Telescope Location In India	11:30–11:45
Haas	A-54	O-27	Microwave Radiometer Observations For VGOS Data Processing	11:45–12:00
Stretch your legs break (15 min)				12:00–12:15

Session 2.4 (45 min)			Chairperson: Manuela Seitz	
Kehm	A-31	O-28	Characteristics Of Different VLBI Session Types In The View Of Earth Orientation Parameter Determination	12:15–12:30
Modiri	A-33	O-29	Evaluating The Consistency And Reliability Of DUT1 Estimates From VLBI Intensive Sessions	12:30–12:45
Klemm	A-44	O-30	Enhancing Regularity And Accuracy Of VLBI EOP Products	12:45–13:00
Lunch break (90 min)				13:00–14:30

Poster session	Poster viewing , see list of posters below		14:30–17:30
-----------------------	---	--	--------------------

End of EVGA2025 Day-2	Gala Dinner	18:00–23:59
------------------------------	--------------------	--------------------

2025-04-09**EVGA2025 Day-3**

Session 3.1 (45 min)			Chairperson: Monia Negusini	
Jaron	A-26	O-31	Mitigating Source Structure On The Visibility Level	09:00–09:15
Xu	A-65	O-32	Variations In The Quad-Band Source Positions From VGOS Observations	09:15–09:30
Wolfs	A-74	O-33	Source Structure Informed Scheduling For VGOS Intensive Sessions	09:30–09:45
Stretch your legs break (15 min)				09:45–10:00

Session 3.2 (45 min)			Chairperson: Daniela Thaller	
Xu	A-40	O-34	Enhancing Geodetic Precision In The East Asian VLBI Network With K-Band Observations	10:00–10:15
Ferrándiz	A-68	O-35	Evidence For The Need To Use Corrections For Planetary Nutations In The Modelling Of Celestial Pole Offsets	10:15–10:30
Belda	A-38	O-36	Searching For Evidence Of Free Inner Core Nutation In VLBI Data	10:30–10:45
Coffee break (30 min)				10:45–11:15

Session 3.3 (45 min)			Chairperson: Sara Bruni	
McCallum	A-04	O-37	New Gravitational Deformation Model Of The Hobart26 VLBI Telescope	11:15–11:30
Wolf	A-43	O-38	Impact Of The Inclination Of Genesis On The VLBI Terrestrial Reference Frame	11:30–11:45
Karbon	A-21	O-39	Signals In Station Positions Revealed By VGOS	11:45–12:00
Negusini	A-16	O-40	Geodetic K-Band VLBI Observations For The Clock Comparison	12:15–12:30

Closing remarks	old EVGA chair (Rüdiger Haas) + new EVGA chair (N.N.)	12:30–12:45
------------------------	--	--------------------

Lunch (90 min)	12:45–14:15
-----------------------	--------------------

End of EVGA2025 Day-3, Excursion to Matera station etc.	14:30–20:00
--	--------------------

2025-04-10 IVS Day

IVS Analysis Workshop Benedikt Soja et al. 09:00–13:00

Lunch (90 min) 13:00-14:30

Splinter meeting on ICRF (closed) Patrick Charlot et al. 14:30–17:30

IVS session gurus (open) Lucia McCallum et al. 14:30–16:30

IAG 1.4 (open) Maria Karbon et al. 16:30–18:30

2025-04-11 IVS Directing Board meeting #52

By invitation only Special agenda distributed to IVS DB members.

POSTERS**On display 2025-04-06/07/08/09**

Technology

Kareinen	A-03	P-01	Recent Developments At Metsähovi Geodetic Research Station
Garcia-Espada	A-62	P-02	Status At Ny-Ålesund Geodetic Earth Observatory
Neidhardt	A-71	P-03	Status Of The VLBI Capabilities At Wettzell Observatory
Chin Chuan	A-76	P-04	Recent Development At The Onsala Space Observatory
Weston	A-18	P-05	New Zealand Geodetic VLBI - Spaceops NZ
Vijayaraghavan	A-63	P-06	Characterizing The Onsala Twin Telescopes Using Microwave Holography
Hedekvist	A-67	P-07	Gravitational Deformation Measurement Of 20 m Radio Telescope On Svalbard
Cho	A-10	P-08	The C/X/Ka-Band Receiver System For Geodesy And Astrometry Of The Korean VLBI Network
Tuccari	A-27	P-09	DBBC4 - A Very Wide Bandwidth VLBI Environment VGOS Suitable
Woo	A-35	P-10	The Crustal Dynamics Data Information System (CDDIS) – VLBI Updates For 2025
McCallum	A-06	P-11	IVS WG 7 On Satellite Observations With VLBI

Observations

McCallum	A-05	P-12	AUSCOPE VLBI Project – Status And News 2025
Lemoine	A-34	P-13	Status Of The VGOS-INT-S Observing Program Between McDonald And Wettzell Geodetic Observatories
Behrend	A-41	P-14	Development Of The Operational VGOS Observing Program
He	A-73	P-15	Local-Tie Experiments Of Chinese VLBI Stations
Le Bail	A-59	P-16	Twelve Years Of IVS R&D Sessions Dedicated To Observations Of ICRF-Gaia Transfer Sources

Analysis

Bachmann	A-49	P-17	IVS Combination Center: ITRF2020 Update - Final Results
Matsumoto	A-07	P-18	GSI Global Solutions Of VLBI Observation Data
Bruni	A-55	P-19	VLBI Data Analysis At ESA/ESOC
Mondal	A-28	P-20	Tying Together Legacy S/X And VGOS Networks Using Combined Observation Strategy
Bolotin	A-37	P-21	Stability Analysis Of Source Coordinates From S/X And VGOS Station Networks Using The Arc Length Method
Dwivedi	A-20	P-22	Strategic Placement Of Third VGOS Telescope In India For Improved EOP Estimation
Singh	A-25	P-23	Hybrid Modelling Of Corrections For Geophysical And Unmodelled Effects In VLBI Data Analysis
Albentosa Ruiz	A-32	P-24	Characterizing Short-Term Variability In VGOS Group Delay Observables
Nilsson	A-72	P-25	An Assessment Of The Ionospheric Total Electron Content Estimated From VGOS

Pérez Esteban	A-14	P-26	Assessing The Impact Of Updated ERPs On FCN Modeling Using VLBI Observations
Del Nido Herranz	A-53	P-27	Influence Of VLBI Network Geometry On The Estimation Of Earth Orientation Parameters
Page	A-64	P-28	Simulating The Impact Of New VLBI Intensive Baselines On Combined UT1-UTC Solutions
Dhar	A-66	P-29	A VGOS CRF Fully Consistent With The S/X Frames – Preliminary Results
Jaradat	A-39	P-30	Bayesian Modelling For Flux Density And SEFD Estimation With Single-Baseline VGOS Observation
Azcue	A-42	P-31	The Importance Of Communication In Science, With A Focus On VLBI And The Raega Project
Sert	A-70	P-32	Assessing VLBI Observation SNR For The Genesis Satellite
Schartner	A-13	P-33	Scheduling and simulations for the Genesis mission
Elgered	A-56	P-34	On The Absolute Sea Level At The Swedish West Coast Estimated By VLBI, GNSS, And Tide Gauges

THIS IS THE END

List of oral presentations

Technology

García-Castellano	A-15	Santa Maria Raege Station Overview And Developments
Pfaffinger	A-24	The Hartebeesthoek Terrestrial Laser Scanning Project -- Concept And First Results
Lopez-Perez	A-29	Broadband Receiver Developments For VGOS Radiotelescopes At Yebes Observatory
Tornatore	A-48	Radio Frequency Compatibility Of VGOS And DORIS Stations
Bernhart	A-51	A Report On New VGOS Frequency Sequences Test Observations
Haas	A-52	Towards VLBI With ESA's Genesis Satellite
He	A-60	Recent Status Of The Shanghai Correlator
Neidhardt	A-69	The Potential Of System Monitoring

Observations

Kinman	A-22	Flux Monitoring At VGOS Frequencies With The Onsala Twin Telescopes
Garramone	A-30	VLBI Activities At Matera Space Geodesy Center
Hase	A-36	Status Of The Spectrum Management For VGOS
Xu	A-40	Enhancing Geodetic Precision In The East Asian VLBI Network With K-Band Observations
Handirk	A-47	Connecting Geodetic VLBI Telescope Generations At The Ny-Ålesund Geodetic Earth Observatory Through Short-Baseline Interferometry – Final Results
Schunck	A-50	VLBI Observations To GNSS Satellites Using The Australian VGOS Array
Bruni	A-58	Invaluable Lunar-Based Interferometry Enabled By ESA's Novamoon Mission
Le Bail	A-59	Twelve Years Of IVS R&D Sessions Dedicated To Observations Of ICRF-Gaia Transfer Sources
Gan	A-61	Observation Of Chang'e 5 Orbiter With Shanghai And Urumqi VGOS Antennas
González-García	A-75	The Raege Correlator At Yebes Observatory: Description And Status

Analysis

Zubko	A-02	Systematic Errors In VGOS Differential Ionospheric Total Electron Content
McCallum	A-04	New Gravitational Deformation Model Of The Hobart26 VLBI Telescope
Kern	A-08	The VLBI Scale Drift: Current Status And Remaining Challenges
Nothnagel	A-09	Effective Frequencies And Ionosphere Calibration Of Legacy S/X Data
Krasna	A-11	VGOS CRF: Celestial Reference Frame From The VLBI Global Observing System Until 2024
Schartner	A-12	A Global Troposphere Model For VLBI Simulations
Negusini	A-16	Geodetic K-Band VLBI Observations For The Clock Comparison
Laha	A-17	Impact Of Atmospheric Turbulence On VGOS Telescope Location In India
Seitz	A-19	DTRF2020_U2023: The Update Of DTRF2020
Karbon	A-21	Signals In Station Positions Revealed By VGOS
Jacobs	A-23	The JPL 2025a Terrestrial And Celestial Reference Frames
Jaron	A-26	Mitigating Source Structure On The Visibility Level
Kehm	A-31	Characteristics Of Different VLBI Session Types In The View Of Earth Orientation Parameter Determination
Modiri	A-33	Evaluating The Consistency And Reliability Of DUT1 Estimates From VLBI Intensive Sessions
Belda	A-38	Searching For Evidence Of Free Inner Core Nutation In VLBI Data
Wolf	A-43	Impact Of The Inclination Of Genesis On The VLBI Terrestrial Reference Frame
Klemm	A-44	Enhancing Regularity And Accuracy Of VLBI EOP Products
Nilsson	A-45	Evaluation Of Terrestrial And Celestial Reference Frames Estimated From VGOS Data
Haas	A-54	Microwave Radiometer Observations For VGOS Data Processing
Le Bail	A-57	VLBI-Scale Of The ITRF2020-U2023
Xu	A-65	Variations In The Quad-Band Source Positions From VGOS Observations
Ferrándiz	A-68	Evidence For The Need To Use Corrections For Planetary Nutations In The Modelling Of Celestial Pole Offsets
Wolfs	A-74	Source Structure Informed Scheduling For VGOS Intensive Sessions

Contents

Santa Maria RAEGE Station Overview and Developments	1
A. García-Castellano, M. Moreira, V. Cuambe, P. Martins, P. Soares, J. López-Pérez, P. García-Carreño, E. Azcue, M. Karbon, S. Belda, J. Ferrándiz, L. Magalhães, J. López-Fernández	
The Hartebeesthoek Terrestrial Laser Scanning Project – Concept and First Results	6
A. Nothnagel, Th. Pfaffinger, R. Botha, P. Mey, M. Nickola, P. Stronkhorst, J. Quick, Ch. Holst	
The new VGOS system for the Italian Space Agency	11
L. Garramone, P. Rutigliano, G. Colucci, M. B. Limite, M. Paradiso	
Broadband Receiver Developments for VGOS Radiotelescopes at Yebes Observatory	15
J. A. López-Pérez, on Behalf of Yebes Observatory Staff	
Radio Frequency Compatibility of VGOS and DORIS Stations	20
V. Tornatore, F. Giovanardi, M. Bautista-Duran, H. Hase	
Report on New VGOS Frequency Sequences Test Observations	25
S. Bernhart, E. Azcue Infanzón, R. Bolaño González, L. Chin Chuan, Y. K. Choi, P. de Vicente, A. García-Castellano, S. Garcia Espada, J. González García, R. Haas, H. Hase, F. Jaron, J. A. López-Pérez, J. McCallum, L. McCallum, M. C. S. Moreira, W. Petrachenko, C. Plötz, J. Quick, M. Schartner	
Status of the Spectrum Management for VGOS	30
H. Hase, M. Bautista Duran, A. García-Castellano, S. García-Espada, M. Lindqvist, J. A. López-Pérez, W. Madkour, D. McKay, L. M. Tangen, W. Probst, V. Tornatore, B. Winkel	
The RAEGE Correlator at Yebes Observatory	36
J. González García, P. de Vicente, V. A. Cuambe, S. de la Fuente Lasa, A. García-Castellano	
Towards VLBI with ESA’s Genesis satellite	39
R. Haas – on Behalf of ESA GSET WG-3 (VLBI) –	
Flux Density Monitoring at VGOS Frequencies With the Onsala Twin Telescopes	44
A. Kinman, R. Haas, K. le Bail, J. Yang, E. Varenus	
Effective Frequencies and Ionosphere Calibration of Legacy S/X Data	49
A. Nothnagel, H. Krásná, P. Urban	
VLBI-scale of the ITRF2020-u2023	54
K. Le Bail, M. Ishigaki, T. Nilsson, R. Haas	
Evaluation of Terrestrial and Celestial Reference Frames Estimated From VGOS Data	59
T. Nilsson, R. Haas, K. Le Bail	
Characteristics of Different VLBI Session Types in the View of Earth Orientation Parameter Determination	64
A. Kehm, L. Klemm, S. Modiri, D. Thaller, S. Bachmann	
Evaluating the Consistency and Reliability of dUT1 Estimates from VLBI Intensive Sessions	69
S. Modiri, L. Klemm, K. Balidakis, G. Engelhardt, M. Goltz, C. Schade, A. Kehm, D. Thaller	
New Gravitational Deformation Model of the Hobart26 VLBI Telescope	75
L. McCallum, M. Lösler, C. Eschelbach, A. Greiwe, B. Zhou	
Impact of the Inclination of Genesis on the VLBI Terrestrial Reference Frame	80
H. Wolf, L. Kern, S. Steinmetz, J. Böhm	

Geodetic K-band VLBI Observations for the Clock Comparison	86
M. Negusini, R. Ricci, M. Stagni, F. Perini, C. Bortolotti, M. Roma, G. Maccaferri, T. Jung, S. Xu, D.-Y. Byun, D.-H. Je, C. Clivati, D. Calonico, M. Pizzocaro, E. Cantoni, G. Cerretto, S. Condio, G. A. Costanzo, S. Donadello, I. Goti, M. Gozzelino, A. Mura, F. Levi, M. Risaro, M.-S. Heo, H. Kim, W.-K. Lee, Y. K. Lee, C. Y. Park, J. H. Rhee, D.-H. Yu, S. O. Yi, H. Yoon, B. Cho, P. de Vicente, J. Gonzáles, C. García-Miró	
Operational Studies of the Onsala Twin Telescopes	91
L. Chin Chuan, R. Haas, K. Le Bail	
Holographic Characterization of the Onsala Twin Telescopes	96
V. Mugundhan, R. Handirk, G. Hovey, M. S. Lerner, K. Le Bail, R. Haas	
Gravitational Deformation Measurement of 20 m Radio Telescope on Svalbard	100
P. O. Hedekvist, C. Rieck, P. Jarlemark, J. Spetz, S. García-Espada	
The CX/Ka-band Receiver System for Geodesy and Astrometry of the Korean VLBI Network	106
J. Cho, M. H. Chung, J. H. Choi, S. T. Han	
DBBC4 – A Very Wide Bandwidth VLBI Environment VGOS Suitable	108
G. Tuccari, H. Rottmann, M. Wunderlich, S. Dornbusch, A. Roy, A. Gupta, W. Alef	
IVS Combination Center: ITRF2020 Update – Final Results	113
S. Bachmann, S. Modiri, S. Schneider-Leck, A. Kehm, M. Seitz, D. Thaller	
GSI Global Solution of VLBI Observation Data	118
S. Matsumoto, M. Ishigaki, K. Hashimoto, T. Hara, S. Kurihara	
VLBI Data Analysis at ESA/ESOC	123
S. Bruni, M. Otten, E. Schoenemann, F. Gini	
Stability Analysis of Source Coordinates from S/X and VGOS Station Networks Using the Arc Length Method	129
S. Bolotin, K. Bayer, D. Behrend, J. Gipson, C. Thomas	
An Assessment of the Ionospheric Total Electron Content Estimated From VGOS	134
T. Nilsson	
Simulating the Impact of new VLBI Intensive Baselines on Combined UT1-UTC Solutions	139
J. Page, K. Oldak-Wong, M. Davis, S. Byram	
The Importance of Communication in Science, With a Focus on VLBI and the RAEGE Project	143
E. Azcue, M. Moreira, L. Moura, C. Pérez-Esteban, S. Belda, M. Karbon	
SNR Simulations for Genesis VT Observations	148
H. Sert, M. Schartner, A. Özyıldırım, R. Haas, Ö. Karatekin	
On the absolute sea level at the Swedish west coast estimated by VLBI, GNSS, and tide gauges	153
G. Elgered, R. Haas	

Santa Maria RAEGE Station Overview and Developments

A. García-Castellano, M. Moreira, V. Cuambe, P. Martins, P. Soares, J. López-Pérez, P. García-Carreño, E. Azcue, M. Karbon, S. Belda, J. Ferrándiz, L. Magalhães, J. López-Fernández

The Santa Maria RAEGE station on Santa Maria Island in the Azores plays a pivotal role in this network. Fully integrated into the VGOS network since October 2023, the station routinely participates in VGOS observing sessions. Operational since May 2021, the station has a 13.2m VGOS radio telescope, “Colombo”, equipped with a broadband receiver developed at Yebes laboratories. In addition, the station hosts two permanent GNSS receivers and a gravimetry room housing an iGRAV-O51 superconductive gravimeter, a seismograph (Centaur-3/Trillium 120PA), and a SILEX accelerometer. Local ties for geodetic calibration were built in November 2024.

The RAEGE project also aims to emphasize capacity building and data analysis, fostering collaboration between IGN, the Yebes and Santa Maria observatories, and the University of Alicante. A dedicated data analysis group was established in 2021 to enhance the quality and utility of geodetic products derived from the network’s observations.

Abel García-Castellano², Mariana Moreira¹, Valente Cuambe¹, Pedro Martins⁴, Pedro Soares^{1,3}, José A. López-Pérez², Pablo García-Carreño², Esther Azcue⁵, Maria Karbon⁶, Santiago Belda⁶, José Ferrándiz⁶, Luísa Magalhães¹, José A. López-Fernández²

(1) Estação RAEGE de Santa Maria, Associação RAEGE Açores, Santa Maria – Azores, Portugal

(2) Yebes Observatory, National Geographic Institute of Spain, Yebes, Spain

(3) Dept. Eletrónica Telecomunicações e Informática, Universidade de Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

(4) Instituto de Astrofísica e Ciência do Espaço, Universidade Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

(5) National Geographic Institute of Spain, Madrid, Spain

(6) UAVAC, Applied Mathematics Dept., University of Alicante, Alicante, Spain

Corresponding author: abel.g.castellano@a-raege-az.pt

In addition to supporting geodetic and geophysical research, the Santa Maria station actively contributes to academic initiatives. Current projects include a master’s thesis focused on designing a tunable downconverter and a doctoral thesis exploring advanced radio astronomy techniques. The focus of the master student is to design a tunable downconverter capable of observing any frequency between 4 and 14 GHz with several bandwidths, while performing the necessary adjustments via software, thus enhancing the hardware setup for radio astronomy observations. The doctoral research investigates in detail the capabilities of the radio telescope of the RAEGE Santa Maria station, with the goal of implementing a monitoring campaign of nearby active galactic nuclei (AGN).

This work will provide an updated overview of the Santa Maria RAEGE station, highlighting its infrastructure, technical upgrades, operational activities, scientific contributions to geodesy, and involvement in academic and collaborative projects under the RAEGE framework.

Keywords Santa Maria, Station, RAEGE, VLBI, Geodetic Station

1 Introduction

The RAEGE network (Atlantic Network of Geodynamic and Space Stations) is a collaborative project between the National Geographic Institute of Spain (IGN-Spain) and the Regional Government of the Azores (1) (see Fig. 1). This unique geodesy initiative focuses on the establishment and operation of four Fundamental

Geodetic Stations: Yebes and Gran Canaria stations in Spain, and Flores and Santa Maria stations in the Azores, Portugal. In 2017, the Government of the Azores established the RAEGE-Azores Association (RAEGE-Az) to oversee the implementation of RAEGE's infrastructure in the Azores and manage its operations (2). Santa Maria RAEGE Station has a 13.2 m dish radio telescope (VGOS-like) equipped with a VGOS broadband receiver, covering 2 to 14 GHz with dual linear polarization. Additionally, the facility hosts other instruments, including three GNSS stations, a GWR iGrav® superconducting gravimeter (installed in October 2022), a seismograph, and an accelerometer.

Fig. 1 RAEGE network. (3)

1.1 Staff

Table 1 outlines the RAEGE staff for the 2023–2024 period, detailing their roles and tenure. Leadership transitioned in December 2023, when João Salmim Ferreira (Station Director since February 2020) handed over to Abel García-Castellano, who now serves as Station Director as well as head of R&D. Diogo Avelar contributed to R&D from January 2021 to June 2023, playing a crucial role in technical development. Mariana Moreira (since November 2020) and Valente Cuambe (since October 2021) continue as core R&D members. Raquel Ribeiro led Outreach, Marketing and Communication until December 2022. Ongoing support functions include administrative (Elsa Melo), IT (Nuno Mata), and maintenance (Valério

Pacheco, Sérgio Chaves) personnel—ensuring station operations run smoothly.

Table 1 2023–2024 RAEGE Staff Members

Department	Name	Dates
Station Director	João Salmim Ferreira	Feb 2020 – Dec 2023
R&D & Station Director	Abel García-Castellano	Mar 2021 – present
R&D	Diogo Avelar	Jan 2021 – Jun 2023
R&D	Mariana Moreira	Nov 2020 – present
R&D	Valente Cuambe	Oct 2021 – present
Outreach	Raquel Ribeiro	Jan 2021 – Dec 2022
Administrative	Elsa Melo	Oct 2021 – present
IT	Nuno Mata	Jan 2021 – present
Maintenance	Valério Pacheco	Jan 2019 – present
Maintenance	Sérgio Chaves	Jan 2021 – present

2 Current Status and Activities of 2023 and 2024

2.1 VGOS and Intensive Operation

In 2023, Santa Maria participated in 5 VGOS-OPS and 4 VGOS-RD sessions. However, a strong RFI from a nearby space-debris radar required the installation of a high-pass COTS filter (rejection from 2–4GHz) in January. This protected the LNAs (Low Noise Amplifiers) but excluded VGOS Band A, delaying network integration. In September, a superconducting notch filter - developed at Yebes Observatory - was installed, restoring Band A capability. Consequently, the station was officially admitted to the VGOS network in October 2023.

Under the VGOS-INT-Y intense-session program (coordinated with RAEGYEB and GGAO/MGO), Santa Maria completed 66 of 70 scheduled sessions in 2023.

In 2024, the station completed 29 of 41 VGOS sessions, including 3 of 5 VGOS-RD and all 5 VGOS-VT sessions (Technical Committee fringe tests). Observational output was limited from 24May to 20October due to two major technical issues: the H-maser hydrogen supply was depleted (operations paused until maintenance in August), and a mechanical fault in the elevation crown required limiting antenna speed to 4°/s.

During the intensive campaign, 59 of 62 VGOS-INT-Y sessions were completed before the program ended in May 2024. VGOS-INT-G sessions

(launched February 2024) ran successfully, with 23 of 25 sessions executed.

Figures 2 and 3 show the sessions and total observations for the 2023–2024 period.

Fig. 2 Operation statistics 2023-2024. (4)

Fig. 3 Number of observations during 2023-2024. (4)

2.1.1 VGOS-VT (Technical Tests)

The IVS VGOS Technical Committee (IVS VTC) is exploring improvements such as expanding bandwidth and extending the frequency range to 14 GHz. In late 2024 and February 2025, Santa Maria took part in VGOS-VT fringe tests. Early results indicate excellent phase-cal stability at higher frequencies over long baselines.

2.1.2 VGOS-INT-G Sessions

VGOS-INT-G sessions, were first formulated at the 26th EVGA meeting, to address Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) affecting VLBI stations like RAEGE (Yj and

Sa), SESHAN (S6), and ISHIOKA (Is). Major interference sources include radars, mobile networks (3G, 4G, 5G), and S-band radio links, severely impacting the 2–3 GHz band.

To mitigate these effects, the study proposes adjusting observation frequencies to 4–14 GHz and evaluating long East-West baselines' impact on UT1 data.

The first phase of the proposed test is still undergoing. Baselines Sa-Yj-S6-Is observed simultaneously and with the same frequency plan as regular VGOS-INT-A (K2-Ws) sessions over the year 2024. These tests aim to enable a direct comparison and consistency check between regular UT1 data from IVS and UT1 data obtained by the RAEGE Analysis Group from the proposed baselines.

2.2 Superconductive Filters Installation

In 2022, a space-debris radar 1.75km from the station operated in the 2.93–2.97GHz range. Measured RFI power (+3.34dBm) was 30dB above the 1dB compression point of the LNAs, risking damage to the receiver (see Fig. 4). A COTS filter installed in January 2023 provided 50dB rejection but blocked VGOS Band A.

In response, Yebes Observatory designed and built two High-Temperature Superconductive (HTS) filters, installed in September 2023 (Fig. 5). Unlike the COTS filters, these filters allowed the observation of the VGOS Band A, thus meeting the requirements defined by the IVS to participate regularly in 24-hour observations. Moreover, the low attenuation in the passband reduced the loss of sensitivity caused by the commercial filters (from 17% to 3%).

As a downside compared to the COST, the attenuation of the radar signal is lower (33 dB versus 50 dB). Nevertheless, the received power levels at the input of the LNAs pointing to the radar direction (-47.2 and -55 dBm in horizontal and vertical polarization, respectively) were lower than expected, possibly due to the blocking effect of a hill that exists in the line of sight. More details can be found in (7).

Fig. 4 Spectrum of the RFI signal taken with a portable measurement system.

Fig. 5 Photograph of HTS filters mounted on RAEGSMAR VGOS receiver.

2.3 Local Tie

In October 2024, six local-tie pillars were constructed next to the radiotelescope. Civil works (excavation, reinforcement, concreting, protective casing) were completed by late October. Fig. 6 shows one installed pillar. This local-tie network enables precise co-registration between VLBI, GNSS, gravimetry, and seismology instruments.

Fig. 6 Local tie pillar installed at Santa Maria station.

2.4 RAEGE Analysis Group

Established in 2021, the RAEGE Data Analysis Group (IGN, Yebes, Santa Maria, Univ. Alicante) has focused during 2023-2024, on developing the necessary skills for comprehensive end-to-end VLBI data processing, particularly for INT-G and INT-Y sessions. They conducted simulations to assess the impact of higher VGOS frequencies on UT1 data quality and the effects of long East-West baselines. The group is also engaged in historical VLBI data consistency studies, developing machine learning models for EOP forecasting, and exploring new approaches to modeling Free Core Nutation (FCN). These efforts aim to strengthen RAEGE's geodetic and astrometric products and foster global scientific engagement.

2.5 Radio Astronomy Observations and Developments

Extending the VGOS telescope to radio astronomy, two observing programs were conducted in 2023-2024: methanol maser spectroscopy and active galactic nucleus (AGN) continuum monitoring (led by Pedro Martins's PhD project, supervised by Valente Cuambe).

Detectable down to flux densities of 6Jy (masers) and 3Jy (AGN), these campaigns demonstrated capability—but also revealed flux calibration instabilities. Investigations traced the issue to the low-power noise diode used for T_{sys} calibration. To mitigate, strategies include shortening integration times and filtering out low-quality scans.

A new master's project launched in October 2024, led by Pedro Soares (supervised by Abel García-Castellano), aims to design a tunable downconverter with selectable bandwidths (100MHz, 500MHz, 1.5GHz, 4GHz), to be built and tested at Yebes before deployment at Santa Maria.

3 Future Plans

Planned upgrades for early 2025 include:

- Installation of a higher-power noise diode for improved single-dish calibration;
- Addition of 5G notch filters and extra RF-over-fiber (RFoF) links to prevent RFoF saturation and reduce system noise temperature;
- Deployment of a lab noise-measurement system on site.

In parallel, the tunable downconverter under Pedro Soares's master's project will be assembled and field-tested.

A geodetic local-ties campaign is scheduled for April–May 2025 to determine the precision and stability of the newly built pillars.

Structural maintenance plans include repair or replacement of high-corrosion components (sub-reflector cover, azimuth/elevation cabin doors, static discharge cables, bolts/nuts—see Fig. 7). The UPS and battery system will also be replaced due to aging.

Acknowledgements

We sincerely appreciate the dedication and resilience of the RAEGE Santa Maria station team, who continue to persevere and rise to every challenge. Our gratitude also goes to IGN Spain and the Yebes Observatory team

Fig. 7 Example of the status of the bolts in the back structure of the antenna.

for their unwavering support, whether through technical assistance, guidance, and their continuous efforts.

References

1. <https://www.raege.eu>
2. <https://www.raege-az.pt>
3. Luís Moura, "RAEGE Network Image Adaptation", 2024,
4. <https://glodh.ethz.ch/station/Sa> website, access date 2025-03-12.
5. I. Malo et al., "Cryogenic Measurement of two LTCC Commercial Filters for Interferences Reduction in Radio Astronomy Receivers", Yebes CDT Technical Report 2022-14
6. García-Carreño, P. PhD Thesis. Optimización de receptores criogénicos mediante filtros superconductores para supresión de interferencias y sistema de medida de la fase de la señal de referencia. UAH. 2024.
7. García-Castellano, A., et al.: Implementing High-Temperature Superconducting Filters at the RAEGE Station in Santa Maria for VGOS Receiver Resilience: a success story in International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry General Meeting 2024 Proceedings.

The Hartebeesthoek Terrestrial Laser Scanning Project – Concept and First Results

A. Nothnagel, Th. Pfaffinger, R. Botha, P. Mey, M. Nickola, P. Stronkhorst, J. Quick, Ch. Holst

Abstract In May 2024, gravitational deformation measurements were performed at the 26 m and 15 m radio telescopes of the South African Radio Astronomy Observatory at Hartebeesthoek (HARTRAO and HART15M) in cooperation of SARAQ, TU München and TU Wien. The method of choice was to use a terrestrial laser scanner (TLS) mounted underneath the sub-reflector with a two-axis gimbal hinge to keep the scanner in a vertical position at all telescope tilts. For a full gravitational VLBI delay model, the 26 m HARTRAO telescope with polar mount had to be pointed at about 80 different Hour Angle/Declination positions for the TLS to perform its scans of the main reflector and the sub-reflector. Here, we present the necessary steps of preparation, the measurements themselves, and first results.

Keywords gravitational deformation, terrestrial laser scanning, preparations and measurements

Axel Nothnagel
Department of Geodesy and Geoinformation, TU Wien, Wiedner Hauptstrasse 8, AT-1040 Vienna, Austria

Theresa Pfaffinger · Christoph Holst
Chair of Engineering Geodesy, TUM School of Engineering and Design, Technical University of Munich, Germany

Roelf Botha · Philipp Mey · Marisa Nickola · Peter Stronkhorst · Jonathan Quick
National Research Foundation, South African Radio Astronomy Observatory (SARAQ) Hartebeesthoek Site, South Africa

1 Motivation

The determination of gravitational deformation effects is unique to any radio telescope used for geodetic and astrometric VLBI observations. For this reason, there is no copy-and-paste neither for the deformations themselves nor for the subsequent VLBI gravitational deformation model for the delay observables. Each telescope has to be measured and modeled independently with methods being available and being practical for its specific type and circumstances. Up to now, not many telescopes have been measured but a variety of different approaches using photogrammetry or scanner technologies has been developed (Lösler et al. , 2019, 2025; Sarti et al. , 2009; Holst et al. , 2019).

Fig. 1 Photo of 26 m HARTRAO telescope.

For close to 40 years, the 26 m telescope of the Hartebeesthoek Radio Astronomy Observatory (HartRAO), which is now the South African Radio Astronomy Observatory (SARAO), has reliably produced geodetic and astrometric VLBI data (Fig. 1). It occupies an important geographical location in the mid-south and its data has a non-negligible impact on the terrestrial reference frame and on deep-south astrometry. For this reason, the data urgently needs to be calibrated for gravitational deformation effects.

Unfortunately, the telescope has some serious issues with its bearings and already a couple of years ago, plans had emerged to do gravitational deformation measurements when it was still able to move around to any position in the sky. An important factor for the success of such endeavors is that colleagues of the telescope group and specialists of a suitable terrestrial surveying method are brought together. This happened in late 2023 when the groups of the Department of Geodesy and Geoinformation of TU Wien, Austria, the Chair of Engineering Geodesy, TUM School of Engineering and Design, Technical University of Munich, Germany, and of the South African Radio Astronomy Observatory (SARAO) Hartebeesthoek Site of the National Research Foundation, South Africa, came together for serious planning of a terrestrial laser scanning campaign.

2 Preparations

The planning foresaw that a terrestrial laser scanner (TLS) be mounted underneath the sub-reflector for scanning of the paraboloid of the telescope's main reflector. Since the scanner should be hanging in its position always vertically to avoid torques on the main axis, a hinge or gimbal with two axes and the respective breaks (to be applied when scanning) had to be constructed (Fig. 2). It should be confessed that the breaks were under-dimensioned and that this had some unwanted torque effects with some of the scans. It is strongly advisable not to save on the breaks in terms of force and weight. Fig. 3 shows the scanner in place underneath the sub-reflector in a position of the telescope close to the horizon.

The planning of the measurement campaign had to fit into a time slot when the telescope was not booked for spacecraft tracking. Another limitation was

Fig. 2 Two-axial hinge.

Fig. 3 Scanner mounted underneath the sub-reflector in a position of the telescope close to the horizon.

that scanning should not be performed in sunshine and with moist on reflector surfaces. This limited the time available per day to the hours after sunset, about 18h00, to about 23h00. The end was also set by the fact that after scanning, the TLS had to be dismantled with the help of a cherrypicker for which trained personnel had to be on-site.

Since the telescope had to be scanned in a sufficient number of Hour Angle/Declination positions, a reasonable number of scans had to be decided on. The duration of the scan proper was only about 3.5 minutes but releasing the breaks, driving the telescope to the next position, fixing the breaks again, starting the scan and doing a second scan at each position

had to be projected with about 8 minutes. Considering all limitations, we settled for four nights with about 22 telescope positions each. This took into account the travel arrangements and precautions for persisting or intermittent rain, which is quite common in April (2024) when the campaign was finally arranged to take place. Overall, a position sequence was chosen so that we succeeded in completing a rudimentary grid in the first night, safe that rain would possibly spoil the other nights. The other nights were then used to densify this grid with more positions. Only the zenith position was repeated every night for later cross-checks, once early in the evening and once close to the end of the session. Fig. 4 depicts the positions of each scanning sessions in color code and Tab. 1 lists the number of scans per night. We called these "tours" because the telescope performs a tour of movements every night.

Fig. 4 Positions scanned in 4 nights.

Each tour was planned to minimize the sum of the distances, which the telescope had to slew from position to position. The tours started at the mount point at HA/DEC $-89^\circ / -1.25^\circ$ and returned to this position at the end of the session.

Table 1 Planning for four nights with respective positions of the telescope to be scanned.

date	tour	scan position
2024		
April 19	red	23
April 20	green	19
April 21	blue	24
April 22	magenta	22

3 Measurements

The TLS measurements themselves were performed with a Zoller und Fröhlich Imager 5016A, which is capable of covering distances between 0.3 m and 365 m. For our scanning, a resolution of 6.3 mm at 10 m was used. Since driving the telescope from position to position manually and performing the break settings by hand would have been very laborious and prone for errors, we devised a semi-automatic procedure. It made use of the VLBI Field System, which normally drives the VLBI observing processes. With the help of a series of SNAP commands, only two manual interactions per position are necessary.

- the start command has to be entered manually,
- the scanner gimbal breaks are released,
- the telescope performs the slewing to the next position,
- when the telescope reaches its destination position, the scanner gimbal breaks are fixed,
- the operator is prompted for starting of the scanning,
- when the scanner finishes its scans, the sequence is restarted with a).

Fig. 5 TLS including horizontal angle φ , vertical angle θ and field of view for vertical angle (blue area), field of view for horizontal angle (red area), scanner z-axis (blue), face 1 (gray area) and face 2 (green area)

To perform its distance and angular measurements, a TLS uses a mirror which rotates around two axes, similar to those of an az-el radio telescope, only much faster in elevation. However, the mirror covers not only 0° to 90° in elevation, as normal az-el radio telescopes do, but also continues beyond zenith from

90° down to 0° for each individual azimuth direction. For this reason, it is enough to rotate the mirror in azimuth (horizontal angle φ) only by 180° to cover the full segment of the environment around the scanner. Only a small part of the foot of the scanner will not be seen because of the mounting itself.

Unfortunately, TLS instruments have their own axis misalignments, which lead to measurement errors. To compensate for these errors, two-face measurements are necessary. Therefore, each position is scanned twice in so-called two cycles. In each cycle, the scanner rotates around its horizontal and vertical axes, reaching always vertical angles from $\theta = 0^\circ$ to 360° . The horizontal angle φ in the first cycle is defined from 0° to 180° . Therefore one cycle could contain both face 1 (front side of the scanner) and face 2 (back side of the scanner). To complete the two-face measurements the second cycle then just scans the same area but with flipped back and front side, so from $\varphi = 180^\circ$ to 360° for the horizontal angle. Of course, for a hanging TLS the geometry is just mirrored so that zenith becomes nadir.

In the data analysis, the misalignments can be determined and eliminated using two-face measurements (Holst et al. , 2019). Fig. 5 shows how a TLS works, where the red area represents the rotation to cover the horizontal angles and the blue area stands for the vertical angle, whose area of scanning is just reduced by the mounting itself, where the laser spots will not be able to scan the area behind.

4 First Results

To determine the gravitational deformation effects for the main reflector of the 26 m HartRAO telescope, both the overall shape deformation and local surface deformations of the main reflector are calculated using a least squares adjustment in the form of a Gauss-Helmert model.

Therefore, the raw laser scan data is used. The laser scanner delivers raw data in the form of polar coordinates, consisting of range, horizontal angle, and vertical angle (r_j, φ_j, θ_j) for each point of the point cloud that is indexed by $j = 1, \dots, m$. With

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_j \\ y_j \\ z_j \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r_j \sin \theta_j \sin \varphi_j \\ r_j \sin \theta_j \cos \varphi_j \\ r_j \cos \theta_j \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

the polar coordinates are converted into Cartesian coordinates in the scanner system, which originates in the scanner reference point. Because of the hinge system its z-axis is always pointing to nadir.

$$\mathbf{X}_j = (X_j, Y_j, Z_j)^T = \mathbf{R}_y(\phi_y) \mathbf{R}_x(\phi_x) \cdot \mathbf{x}_j + \Delta \mathbf{X}, \quad (2)$$

the coordinates in the scanner system \mathbf{x}_j are transformed in the telescope system \mathbf{X}_j , whose origin is the vertex of the main reflector and whose Z-axis is the symmetry axis of the paraboloid pointing upwards (in the opposite direction of the scanner system).

Using the cartesian coordinates in the telescope system, the main reflector can be parameterized as a paraboloid of revolution with the focal length f as its main parameter describing the overall shape:

$$\left(\frac{X_j^2 + Y_j^2}{4f} \right) - Z_j = 0 \quad (3)$$

By combining equations 1 to 3, the focal length of the telescope can be estimated for the different input scan data sets. Besides the estimated parameters, the estimation provides residuals for each point, which show the local surface deformations of the main reflector. In this publication, we only focus on the local surface deformation. The overall shape deformation, which is shown as focal length variations, will be considered in further studies.

Figures 6 depict the residuals of a best fit paraboloid at HA/DEC = $-35^\circ / -64^\circ$ in the two faces observed. Clearly visible is the effect of scanner axis misalignment reflected by the curved line on the left hand side where the 180° azimuth meets the 0° azimuth.

To reduce the laser scanner misalignments, a calibration is included in the adjustment: In addition to the focal length, also three calibration parameters for the laser scanner are estimated. In a further step the scans of cycle 1 and cycle 2 are combined to one scan, which leads to the result in Fig. 7.

In those current results, one can clearly see that the effects of the laserscanner misalignments can be reduced by adding a calibration to the estimations. It is visible that panel by panel residuals can further be

Fig. 6 Residuals of best fit paraboloid, initial results of HA/DEC = $-35^\circ / -64^\circ$ (top: cycle 1; bottom: cycle 2).

used for physical panel adjustments on the telescope. Hence, those results present a clear benefit for analyzing aeral deformations of the respective telescope. Further information on the evaluation and the initial results can be found in Pfaffinger et al. (2025).

Fig. 7 Initial results of calibrated residuals for each panel.

Funding

This research was partly funded by German Research Foundation (DFG) under grant number 490989047, DFG FOR 5455 "TLS-Defo".

References

- Holst, C., Nothnagel, A., Haas, R., and Kuhlmann, H. (2019). Investigating the gravitational stability of a radio telescope's reference point using a terrestrial laser scanner: Case study at the Onsala Space Observatory 20-m radio telescope. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 149:67–76.
- Lösler, M., Haas, R., Eschelbach, C., and Greiwe, A. (2019). Gravitational deformation of ring-focus antennas for VGOS: first investigations at the onsala twin telescopes project. *Journal of Geodesy*, 93(10):2069–2087.
- Lösler, M., Eschelbach, C., Greiwe, A., Zhou, B., and McCallum, L. (2025). Innovative approach for modelling gravity-induced signal path variations of VLBI radio telescopes. *Earth, Planets and Space*, 77(1).
- Sarti, P., Vittuari, L., and Abbondanza, C. (2009). Laser scanner and terrestrial surveying applied to gravitational deformation monitoring of large vlbi telescopes' primary reflector. *Journal of Surveying Engineering*, 135(4):136–148.
- Holst C., Schunck D., Nothnagel A., Haas R., Wennerbäck L., Olofsson H., Hammargren R., Kuhlmann H. (2017) Terrestrial Laser Scanner Two-Face Measurements for Analyzing the Elevation-Dependent Deformation of the Onsala Space Observatory 20-m Radio Telescope's Main Reflector in a Bundle Adjustment, *Sensors*, vol. 17, no. 8, p. 1833
- Pfaffinger Th., Ortiz Rincón M.A., Nothnagel A., Mey Ph., Quick J., Botha R., Stronkhorst P., Nickola M., Holst Ch. (2025) Quality-controlled deformation analysis of the 26-m HartRAO radio telescope's main reflector: First results. In: 6th Joint International Symposium on Deformation Monitoring (JISDM 2025), Karlsruhe, Deutschland, 7.–9. April 2025; Forschungsbericht (Preprint), KITopen-ID 1000179768, March 2025, DOI:10.5445/IR/1000179768 .

The new VGOS system for the Italian Space Agency

L.Garramone, P. Rutigliano, G.Colucci, M.B Limite, M.Paradiso

Abstract Matera VLBI and VGOS stations are at the Italian Space Agency's 'Centro di Geodesia Spaziale G. Colombo (CGS) near Matera, Italy. The CGS came into operation in 1983 with the installation of the Satellite Laser Ranging SAO-1 System. In May 1990, the CGS extended its capabilities to Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI), installing a 20m dish radio telescope. In 2021, the implementation of the Matera VLBI Global Observing System (MATVGOS) started. This new system, compliant with the updated standards recommended by the International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS), is currently in the acceptance phase and should become fully operational in the second half of the current year. This article describes the operational activities carried out by the Matera Center and the main characteristics of the MATVGOS system.

Keywords VGOS, MATVGOS, CGS

1 Introduction

Activities at the Matera site began in 1983 when a Satellite Laser Ranging System (SAO-1) was installed, and Matera became an IGS (International GNSS Service) site. In 1990, geodesy activities were expanded with the installation of a VLBI system, which has been operational since then. In 1993, ASI implemented the

Luciano Garramone¹
(1) Italian Space Agency (ASI)

Paolo Rutigliano² · Giuseppe Colucci² · Maria Bruna Limite² · Michele Paradiso²
(2) e-GEOS S.p.A

Italian Fiducial GPS (GNSS) network. Data acquired by more than 40 Italian sites (about 70.000 files/month) are downloaded and stored at the Matera Geodesy Center, where monitoring and control are also performed. Refer to Figure 1 for the current extension of the GNSS network.

In 1999, MLRO -Matera Laser Ranging Observatory became operational (Figure 2).

Other activities performed at the Matera Geodesy Space Center are related to fundamental physics research, earth observation, and T&F metrology.

Fig. 1 GNSS Network

Fig. 2 Matera space center MLRO and SAO-1

2 VLBI

Since 1990, Matera has been part of the VLBI network. The VLBI system is based on a 20-meter Cassegrain antenna designed and built in Italy.

It operates in the standard geodetic VLBI bands, specifically S-Band at 2000 to 2500 MHz and X-Band at 8000 to 9000 MHz. Therefore, only geodetic campaigns are conducted. The Data Acquisition Terminal is based on the Mark-V system, and starting in 2023, data are sent to the correlators through a fiber optic link.

During the last decade, the Matera system was involved in VLBI campaigns at least once a week. This requires a strict maintenance program and prompt action in case of failure.

Fig. 3 VLBI Antenna

Fig. 4 System temperature

2.1 Cryogenic system

The cryogenic system failed from September 2024 to February 2025, so the LNA was not refrigerated. However, despite the higher T_{sys} , see Figure 4, the VLBI was allowed to continue its activities.

2.2 Elevation Encoder

The old encoder was replaced with a new one due to unstable readings of elevation angles that started in January 2025. The original encoder was no longer available on the market; thus, a new model has been installed.

To preserve compatibility with the ACU, an interface electronic circuit has been developed and installed.

2.3 RFI emissions

RFI emissions in the S-band have been an issue since the beginning of operations.

In the first decades, RFI primarily resulted from companies using the S-Band to transfer TV programs between central and local (regional) offices. Later, the S-Band was used for point-to-point data transmissions. The area's topography, especially its flatness, does not help the situation. The system is, in fact, capable of receiving signals starting from an elevation of zero degrees.

However, the RFI in Matera is comparable to those of the other VLBI centers, considering that the band be-

Portions of the spectrum without RFI

Fig. 5 Spectrum without RFI

tween 2000 and 2500 Mhz is not assigned to geodetic activities.

In recent years, the X-Band has also shown RFI caused by military activities such as RADAR and TETRA (Terrestrial Trunked Radio). The military authorities were asked to change the transmission frequency to resolve these RFIs

3 VGOS

In 2018, ASI began the activities to implement a VGOS system at the Matera center.

The VGOS standard aims to:

1. Increase sensitivity by utilizing higher recording bandwidth, facilitated by the extensive deployment of digital electronics technology
2. Achieve higher temporal and spatial resolution in estimating the effect of the troposphere at each station. Smaller, faster antennas align with this goal, making it possible to increase the number of observations per unit of time.
3. Mitigate the effects of RFI through the implementation of broadband acquisitions

The MVGOS contract was signed in 2021 between ASI and e-Geos, with the system designed and developed by OHB Digital Connect GmbH.

In the following, we describe the main characteristics of the VGOS system installed in Matera.

3.1 Structure

- Primary mirror with a diameter (D) of 13.2 m and focal length (f_p) of 3.7 m.
Primary paraboloid definition $f_p/D = 0.28$
- Precision of surface single panel: $< 0.2\text{mmRMS}$
Separation between panels: 2 mm + 1 mm at 20°C
- Ring-focus sub-reflector designed for broadband feeds operating at frequencies ranging from 2.0 GHz to 14.0 GHz.
Sub-reflector diameter: $d = 1.55$ m
Precision surface sub-reflector: ≤ 0.1 mm RMS
Final $f/D = 0.4$ m
- QRFH (Quadruple-Rigged Flared Horn) feed The telescope mount type is a standard elevation-over-azimuth design, providing full sky coverage starting from 0° elevation.
The Elevation Axis can be rotated between 0° and 100°, and the azimuth axis can be rotated $\pm 270^\circ$.

3.2 Data acquisition chain

The signal received from quasars is captured, amplified, and filtered in the front-end, and then it is transmitted to the back-end through fiber optics.

In the back-end, it is digitized, processed, and stored. The data recorder is the Mark6, and it can record at 16 Gb/s. As a future extension, a second Mark6 can be installed to increase the data rate to a maximum of 32 Gb/s, according to the VGOS specification.

The supplier of the front-end, data recorder, and back-end subsystems is the Yebes Observatory (Instituto Geográfico Nacional).

More details relevant to these subsystems are reported in the presentation Broadband receiver developments for VGOS radio-telescopes at Yebes Observatory (Authors: Josef A. Lopez-Perez - Yebes Observatory).

3.3 *Single-dish control system*

In addition to the FS, a single-dish control system is installed, obtaining greater flexibility and a user-friendly interface for control routines and maintenance activities.

3.4 *Weather station*

The existing weather station in Matera is utilized. Pressure, temperature, humidity, wind speed, and direction are continuously monitored and recorded.

3.5 *Time and Frequency reference*

The Frequency and Time systems already used in Matera for VLBI activities are applied to VGOS, i.e., H-maser, Passive Maser, 3 x GPS receivers and antenna, distributors, and frequency counters.

3.6 *Status of activities*

The first single-dish activities were conducted in January 2025; in addition, some preliminary VLBI sessions with the IGN Santa Maria station (located in the Azores archipelago) were also carried out. The acquired data were processed on the Yebes correlator. In February 2025, Matera participated in an IVS session as a guest station; the data were correlated by Haystack. The results of the correlations show that fringes are visible; however, some additional tuning activities are ongoing to resolve issues that affect the stability of the phase calibration signal. MVGOS is expected to start regular operations in the next two months.

4 *Conclusions and outlook*

Matera has been hosting a VLBI radio telescope since 1990. Since then, the VLBI antenna has participated in VLBI campaigns at least once a week. A VGOS

system will be in operation starting this year. Thanks to the increased bandwidth of the acquisitions, higher sensitivity and a reduced RFI impact are expected.

The new VGOS system has proven to work well since the fringe test with Santa Maria yields positive results; however, some tuning activities are needed to achieve the desired performance.

Broadband Receiver Developments for VGOS Radiotelescopes at Yebes Observatory

José A. López-Pérez, on behalf of Yebes Observatory staff

Abstract This contribution highlights recent advancements in receiver technology achieved at the Yebes Observatory, emphasizing the design and construction of three cutting-edge broad-band receivers for the VLBI Global Observing System (VGOS) operating across the 2-14 GHz frequency range. Among these receivers, one has been specifically developed for the Matera VGOS station in Italy, equipping it to join the VGOS core network shortly. The presentation will cover the development of this receiver.

Keywords VLBI, GGOS, VGOS, RAEGE, radiotelescopes, receivers, geodesy

1 Introduction

The Yebes Observatory, a department of the Spanish National Geographic Institute (IGN-Spain), has a distinguished history spanning over 35 years in the development of advanced radio astronomy receivers, including those tailored for Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI). Since 2015, Yebes is a Technological Development Center within the International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS).

Additionally, IGN-Spain started the deployment of a VGOS subnet named RAEGE (*Red Atlántica de Estaciones Geodinámicas y Espaciales*, <https://raege.eu>) together with the Regional Government of Azores (GRA). It is formed by four geodetic stations with locations in Yebes, Santa María, Gran Canaria and

José A. López-Pérez¹

(1) Instituto Geográfico Nacional, Yebes Observatory, Cerro de la Palera s.n., E-19141 Yebes, Guadalajara, SPAIN.

Fig. 1 Map of RAEGE stations.

Flores (see figure 1). The first two are already in operation, the third one is under construction and the last one is in the process to find funds for the design and construction (see (1) and (2) for details on RAEGE). RAEGE is a key contribution to space geodesy from both partners (IGN and GRA) in response to the UN 69/266 resolution for "A Global Geodetic Reference Frame for Sustainable Development", showing the strong compromise of IGN with space geodesy.

In the last couple of years, the receivers' group at Yebes Observatory has developed three VGOS receivers for Matera (Italy), HartRAO (South Africa) and Songkhla (Thailand) VLBI stations (see figure 2). In total so far, Yebes has developed eight VGOS receivers for different VLBI stations around the world. Some of them have been installed by Yebes staff, as well, with local support from the stations. Additionally, the RAEGE Santa María VGOS receiver and Ny-Alesund

Fig. 2 The Yebes-developed VGOS receivers for Matera (left), HartRAO (center) and NARIT (right).

NMA¹ VGOS receiver were upgraded, too. Part of this work was presented in (3).

This contribution shows the development and installation of the Matera VGOS receiver.

2 Matera VGOS receiver

Yebes Observatory was commissioned to build the cryogenic VGOS broadband receiver for the new Matera VGOS radiotelescope, from the dewar and front-end (QRFH and LNAs) to the room temperature signal chain up to the input of the backends, including the PhaseCal and NoiseCal modules, the Cryogenics and Vacuum Control Unit and the receiver control software. The integration and wiring of the backends and recorders were included in the scope of the works, too. Additionally, the software for radiotelescope control was provided by Yebes, together with the installation of all the required software for VLBI operations.

From the Yebes long-term experience in receiver development, some improvements on this receiver were implemented:

- A reduction in weight and volume of the dewar, achieving 10 K for critical components (4).

¹ Norwegian Mapping Authority

- New optimized QRFH² feed enabling good port matching and phase center stability along the VGOS band (5), (6).
- Low-noise amplifiers in balanced configuration, with noise temperature below 4 K and excellent input and output matching along the VGOS band (7).
- Equalized NoiseCal and PhaseCal signals to flatten their spectra.
- Customized 30dB cryogenic couplers designed and built in Yebes Observatory, to avoid potential connector failure of commercial off-the-shelf couplers (8).
- Optimized Cable Delay Measurement System (CDMS) using fiber optic links with Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM).
- Rearrangement of the RF chain inside the cryostat to improve the receiver noise temperature with shorter coaxial transmission lines.
- Rearrangement of the back panel main interfaces in the receiver trolley for easier installation and maintenance.

Figure 3 shows the integrated dewar with the QRFH, the 30 dB directional couplers and the balanced LNAs, together with the required wiring and cabling. These elements are cooled down to 10 K. Additionally, figure 4 shows the fully integrated receiver inside its supporting trolley, which is a mechanical frame required for a comfortable installation inside the radiotelescope's feed cone.

Concerning the sensitivity, figure 5 shows the measured receiver noise temperature (T_{RX}) for the H-pol and V-pol channels of the Matera VGOS receiver. A peak at 2.8 GHz in receiver noise is shown, due to a resonance in the QRFH feed point. Its effect is not critical because it is out of the actual VGOS observing range (3 - 14 GHz). It can be seen that T_{RX} is lower than 30 K along the 3 - 14 GHz range, and lower than 20 K from 6 to 14 GHz.

From April 2nd to 12th 2024, the Yebes team travelled to Matera station for the installation of the VGOS receiver in the new VGOS radiotelescope (see figure 6). The work was done in close collaboration with OHB Digital Connect and Matera station staffs.

Figure 7 shows the final look of the installed VGOS receiver inside the radiotelescope's feed cone.

² Quad-Ridged Flared Horn

Fig. 3 Internal view of the Matera VGOS receiver dewar.

Fig. 4 The Matera VGOS receiver fully integrated in its trolley.

In relation to the CDMS, a new system has been developed for the Matera VGOS station using 5 MHz signal transport over single-mode optical fibre with the corresponding fibre optic WDM transceivers. This system not only takes advantage of the inherent benefits of fibre optics, such as lower thermal coefficient than coaxial cable, better RFI isolation and galvanic insulation, but also incorporates a novel phase detection system. This new method, different from the coaxial version described in (9), introduces a lower RMS noise in the detection, which allows equivalent results to be obtained without the need for post-processing

Fig. 5 Receiver noise temperature of Matera VGOS receiver.

Fig. 6 Yebes team during Matera VGOS receiver installation. From left to right: Adrián Alonso, Javier González, José A. López-Pérez, Gabriel Gómez, Pablo García, Joaquín Fernández and Fran Beltrán.

Fig. 7 Final look of the Matera VGOS receiver as installed inside the feed cone.

or filtering. As a result, a significantly shorter processing time is achieved and real-time delay measurements are obtained.

Table 1 shows a comparison between the results achieved with the system described in (9) and the new fibre optic system. As it can be seen, the results are similar, however the processing time is ten times shorter for the new system.

Table 1 Comparison in RMS noise of delay from the CDMS shown in (9) and the new CDMS using fibre optic transceivers.

Meas. Time	RMS noise (9)	RMS noise Fibre Optic System
60 min	0.09 ps	0.12 ps
24 h	0.52 ps	0.47 ps

3 HTS filter developments

New developments in the field of high-temperature superconducting (HTS) filters for RFI rejection have been carried out at Yebes labs (10). One of them was designed to reject the signal from the SLR station radar co-located to a VGOS station.

For aircraft security reasons, some SLR stations have an active radar emitting at 9.41 GHz, which can cause saturation problems in VGOS receivers, as previously reported in (11). Matera station has this type of radar. For this reason, a high-temperature superconducting notch filter capable to reject the radar frequency without affecting the remaining VGOS band was developed. However, it was not installed in the receiver as it was not initially included in the scope of work. The measured performance is given in table 2. More information on this filter can be found in (12).

New HTS filter topologies are under development at Yebes Observatory.

Table 2 Measured parameters for SLR radar notch HTS filter.

Parameters	Measured value
Operating Frequency	2 - 14 GHz
Operating Temperature	10 Kelvin
Input/output matching	≤ -14 dB
Insertion losses	≤ 0.3 dB
Insertion losses in 9.37 - 9.44 GHz	≥ 50 dB
Insertion losses in 9.385 - 9.42 GHz	≥ 60 dB

4 Conclusions and Outlook

After the successful VGOS receiver development and installation, the first fringe tests of Matera VGOS radiotelescope (Mb) was performed on January 23rd, 2025 together with RAEGE Santa Maria station (Sa). Seven days later, the Yebes correlator confirmed the fringes between Mb-Sa. After that, Mb joined VGOS sessions in tag-alone mode and some minor issues have been solved. The confirmation from Haystack correlator to join the VGOS core network is expected in the next few weeks.

References

1. José A. López-Pérez, João S. Ferreira, Javier González-García, Carlos Albo-Castaño, Abel García-Castellano, P. de Vicente-Abad, José A. López-Fernández, Francisco W. Macedo, Luís R. Santos, Sara Pavão. The current status of RAEGE. 25th EVGA meeting. March 15-18, 2021.
2. João S. Ferreira, Abel García-Castellano, José A. López-Pérez, Mariana Moreira, Diogo Avelar, Valente Cuambe, Francisco Wallenstein, Javier González-García, Carlos Albo-Castaño: RAEGE Santa Maria: Station Overview. In K. L. Armstrong, D. Behrend, and K. D. Baver, editors, International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2022 General Meeting Proceedings, NASA/CP-20220018789, 2023, pp. 42 - 46.
3. José A. López-Pérez et al. "Latest VGOS Receiver Developments from Yebes Observatory", 13th IVS 2024 General Meeting Proceedings Tsukuba, Japan. Edited by Dirk Behrend, Karen D. Baver, and Kyla L. Armstrong NASA/CP-20250002586, 2025, pp. 55 - 58.
4. G. Gómez-Molina, O. García-Pérez, J. M. Serna-Puente, F. Tercero. New Designs in VGOS frontends in Yebes Observatory. 25th EVGA meeting. March 15-18, 2021.
5. O. García-Pérez, F. Tercero, A. Baldominos, G. Gómez-Molina, A. García-Moreno, D. Regajo-Rodríguez, and R. Sánchez-Montero, "A Modular approach for the design of quadruple ridged flared horn antenna feeds", IEEE Access, May 2024.
6. M. Venter, O. García-Pérez, F. Tercero-Martínez, J. A. López-Pérez, S. Malan, P. Mey, "Performance of the VGOS radio telescope with as-built feed and geometry using electromagnetic simulations", in EuCAP 2023, Florence, May 2023.
7. José A. López-Pérez et al., "Description of RAEGE Yebes VGOS receiver upgrades," in Proc. 12th Gen. Meeting Int. VLBI Service Geodesy Astrometry, 2023, pp. 47-51.
8. I. Malo, J.D. Gallego, M. Díez, I. López-Fernández, R. Amils, R. García, G. Martínez, "Yebes 30 dB cryogenic directional coupler for the injection of the calibration signal to the 2

- 14 GHz wideband VGOS receiver”, CDT Technical Report 2022-15.
9. Pablo García-Carreño, Javier González-García, María Patino-Esteban, Francisco J. Beltrán-Martínez, Marta Bautista-Durán, Pablo Luis López-Espí, and José A. López-Pérez: "New Cable Delay Measurement System for VGOS Stations". *Sensors* 22, no. 6: 2308. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22062308>.
 10. García-Carreño, P.; López-Pérez, J.A.; "Development of HTS Filters at Yebes Observatory". 9th IVTW. Haystack, USA, 2024.
 11. Turner, C. J.; Stevenson, T.; Cantor, R., Hilliard, L.;Murphy, T. E.; Bulcha, B. (2023). "Superconducting Notch Filter for RFI Mitigation in Ground-Based Radio Telescope". *IEEE Transactions On Applied Superconductivity*, 33(3), 1-5.
 12. García-Carreño, P. PhD Thesis. "Optimización de receptores criogénicos mediante filtros superconductores para supresión de interferencias y sistema de medida de la fase de la señal de referencia". UAH. Jan, 2024.

Radio frequency compatibility of VGOS and DORIS stations

V. Tornatore, F. Giovanardi, M. Bautista-Duran, H. Hase

Abstract Within the framework of the Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS), the co-location of space and satellite geodetic techniques is strongly promoted to achieve the GGOS goal of establishing a network of stations with 1 mm position accuracy and 0.1 mm/yr in stability. The latest realization of ITRF, ITRF2020, includes only a number of 10 local ties between VLBI and DORIS stations, so there is a high demand to increase the number of VLBI and VGOS stations co-located with DORIS at the same site.

The installation of a DORIS beacon at a VGOS site seems difficult without affecting radio astronomical measurements. In fact, VLBI systems are designed to receive extremely faint cosmic signals down to -110 dBm, whereas the DORIS beacon emits signals at a frequencies of 401.25 MHz and 2.036 GHz with 40 dBm output power. Although the lower frequency is outside the frequency range of a VGOS system (2 GHz–14 GHz), the higher frequency falls within the lower S-band. It is therefore highly recommended to evaluate each radio telescope site carefully before installing a DORIS system in its vicinity.

We present compatibility studies, carried out with

Vincenza Tornatore¹, Fabio Giovanardi², Marta Bautista-Duran³, Hayo Hase⁴,

(1) Politecnico Milano, Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, I-20133 Milano, Italy

F. Giovanardi²

(2) Arcetri Astrophysical Observatory - INAF, Largo Enrico Fermi 5, I-50125 Florence, Italy

M. Bautista-Duran³

(3) Instituto Geográfico Nacional, Observatorio Yebes, Cerro de la Palera sn, E-19141 Yebes, Guadalajara, Spain

Hayo Hase⁴

(4) Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie, BKG Wettzell, Sackenrieder Str. 25, D-93444 Bad Kötzing, Germany

Pyrcraf (open source software) under different scenarios, to investigate different types of exclusion zones with respect to the new Matera VGOS radio telescope. Path propagation loss, effective antenna gains, and available free digital terrain models have been considered. The results can be used to search for potential sites for a new DORIS station in the area. The analysis also considers real cases from individual European VGOS observatories with experience of installing DORIS stations.

Keywords VGOS, DORIS, Frequency compatibility, Pyrcraf

1 Introduction

The determination of the International Terrestrial Reference Frame (ITRF) depends on the combination of multiple space geodetic techniques, namely VLBI, GNSS, SLR, and DORIS. Each technique employs different observational strategies and achieves different levels of measurement accuracy. Their contribution to the precision and stability of the ITRF is ensured only by reliable and accurate local ties. One of the most challenging co-locations is that between VLBI, in its modern VGOS implementation, and DORIS.

VGOS operates as a passive system, receiving extremely faint signals from distant radio sources, often with power levels below -110 dBm. In contrast, DORIS is an active system that emits continuous signals at high power, with primary transmission at 2.036 GHz reaching up to 40 dBm. These emissions can degrade VGOS performance or saturate its low-noise amplifiers

(LNAs).

Achieving VGOS and DORIS co-location is important for a more homogeneous and tightly connected geodetic infrastructures. However, relatively few sites worldwide have both VGOS and DORIS antennas, and even fewer can put local ties at disposal. For the determination of the present ITRF, ITRF2020 Altamimi et al. (2023), the number of local ties available was only ten.

The studies carried out in this paper refer to a previous work conducted by Bautista-Duran et al. (2023), which established a methodology for the VGOS and DORIS frequency compatibility studies, briefly described in Section 2. In Section 3 we present a new simulation-based assessment of the radio frequency environment at Matera. The issues concerning the coexistence of the VGOS and DORIS systems have been investigated at some European observatories (see Section 4). Finally, Section 5 provides conclusions and an outlook.

2 Compatibility Studies and Technical Parameters

Evaluating the compatibility of VGOS and DORIS at the same site requires a combined understanding of both the characteristics of the system and the radio propagation conditions. The methodology developed in 2023 is based on established recommendations of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), ITU-R Report RA.2507 (2022), and particularly those concerning interference thresholds ITU-R Recommendation RA.769-2 (2023).

The DORIS system transmits primarily at 2.036 GHz, using an omnidirectional antenna placed at a height of approximately 2.5 m. The beacon operates continuously and without elevation masking. This means that its emissions can propagate in any direction, potentially including the line of sight of nearby radio telescopes. Under specific conditions, these emissions are powerful enough to interfere with VGOS equipment.

To quantify these risks, we have considered three different scenarios. The first relates to hardware integrity, specifically the need to avoid LNA saturation, which occurs above a received input power level of approximately -50 dBm. The second scenario

relates to the standard operation mode of VLBI-VGOS, for which compatibility requires that the received maximum spectral density power does not exceed -133 dB(W/m²). The third and most restrictive case applies when operating in single dish mode, which is usually used for calibration and requires a received maximum spectral density power below -170 dB(W/m²) (ITUR RA.2507). Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of the three cases studied.

Studied cases	Max input power/density
1. Hardware integrity (LNA sat. limit)	-50 dBm
2. VLBI-VGOS operation mode	-133 dB(W/m ²)
3. Single-dish calibration mode	-170 dB(W/m ²)

Table 1 Threshold interference levels for the three different scenarios investigated

To simulate DORIS propagation signals at a given site, the ITU-R Recommendation RA.452-16 (2015) model was used. It accounts for several propagation mechanisms, such as free-space loss, diffraction, and tropospheric effects. This model is implemented with open source Pycraf software Winkel (2025), which enables detailed simulation of signal strength over terrain. Digital elevation models, such as those derived from LIDAR or high-resolution satellite data, are used to provide the topographic input needed to evaluate natural shielding effects. Combining these elements enables the methodology to generate detailed attenuation maps, which are crucial for identifying critical directions and determine the minimum distances - or 'exclusion zones' - at which the installation of a DORIS beacon would not compromise VGOS operations. These simulations are essential not only for risk estimation but also for exploring mitigation strategies.

3 DORIS Compatibility Assessment at Matera Site

The Matera Space Geodesy Centre, managed by the Italian Space Agency (ASI), hosts a recently operational VGOS system. The site is also being considered for the installation of a DORIS beacon. A comprehensive radio frequency compatibility study has been conducted to evaluate this possibility, using the methodology described in Section 2. Terrain data from a LIDAR-

Fig. 1 Exclusion zones (red areas) for three threshold levels. The left map shows a zone (300 m) where DORIS interference on LNA would prevent VLBI observations. The middle map shows the VLBI threshold, and the right map the single-dish/calibration threshold.

Fig. 2 Exclusion zones on satellite maps for Matera site considering both VGOS and VLBI 20 m antennas. The left map shows the three scenarios: LNA case (red), VLBI case (blue), single dish (green). The right map provides a zoom of the LNA case exclusion zone for VGOS station (red) and VLBI 20 m antenna (orange).

based digital elevation model Lidar data (2023) were incorporated to ensure realistic attenuation estimates. The simulations considered the standard DORIS configuration and analyzed signal propagation towards the VGOS antenna in azimuthal directions. For each of the three interference thresholds – LNA saturation, VGOS mode, and single-dish mode – a corresponding exclusion zone was derived. These zones define the minimum distances and areas in which a DORIS beacon should not be installed to avoid interference. The affected areas are shown in Fig. 1. The results show that a distance of approximately 300 m is generally sufficient to prevent direct overload in the LNA protection case. However, the VGOS operational mode requires a more conservative distance of around 5 km to avoid observation degradation.

The single-dish calibration mode, being the most sensitive, requires a minimum distance of about 100 km.

Further simulations were also carried out considering the presence of the Legacy VLBI 20 m antenna, that will continue to be operational at the Matera observatory with the new installed VGOS radio telescope. Examining the exclusion zones on the satellite map jointly for the Matera VGOS and VLBI 20 m antenna see Figure 2, reveals that Matera’s topography provides natural shielding in specific directions. In particular, the southern and south-western sectors are characterized by elevated terrain that introduces significant attenuation, effectively reducing the risk of interference in those directions. This makes these sectors especially

favourable for the possible installation of a DORIS beacon.

These findings indicate that the Matera site provides a suitable environment for the coexistence of VGOS and DORIS, provided that the beacon is installed with careful attention to orientation, shielding, and validation through empirical measurements. Measurement campaigns are required at various test locations to identify the optimal site for the DORIS antenna, in order to avoid signal signal interference during astronomical and geodetic observations using the VGOS and Legacy VLBI 20 m antennas. The chosen location must also be suitable for establishing high-accuracy local ties between the DORIS and VGOS reference points.

4 Real Cases in Europe for VGOS–DORIS Coexistence

The case of Matera is part of a broader context of European stations that have explored or implemented the co-location of VGOS–DORIS. In 2023, a comprehensive review was conducted to document real-world experiences, identifying both successful examples and ongoing challenges. The complete study is available at: https://www.craf.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/DORIS_VGOS_compatibility_study.pdf. The following are instances of the Doris beacon’s implementation at a radio astronomical site in actual cases.

In Wettzell, Germany, a DORIS beacon operates in the vicinity of the observatory. Several tests were carried out at different locations. Ultimately, the choice was the point A3/B4 (see the map in Figure 3). Furthermore, the DORIS beacon is activated only if DORIS equipped satellites are visible to reduce its impact on VLBI and VGOS observations Klügel et al. (2017).

The VLBI and VGOS stations in Onsala, Sweden, have experienced detectable interference during tests. Although the DORIS beacon has not yet been operationalized, the simulations and field data suggest that achieving compatibility will require significant mitigation measures, potentially including shielding or installation off-site.

At Metsähovi, in Finland, the DORIS beacon is located at a distance of about three kilometers from the VGOS antenna. This configuration has shown no measurable interference. The topography of this region ap-

Fig. 3 Map of the Geodetic Observatory Wettzell with DORIS test sites (red circles), Klügel et al. (2017)

pears to offer natural protection against interference. So far, no DORIS-related radio interference has been observed in astronomical or geodetic measurements. The problem of local ties has been solved using GNSS measurements between the two sites.

Ny-Ålesund, in Norway, the co-location remains under consideration, simulations suggest that installation could be problematic due to limited natural shielding.

Yebe station in Spain presents a mixed case. Although simulations suggest that compatibility is possible under specific geometric configurations, the complex terrain and other local constraints have delayed final decisions regarding the DORIS installation.

These case studies reinforce the importance of site-specific analysis. Although the methodology appears robust and generalizable, the practical implementation of VGOS–DORIS co-existence ultimately depends on local topography, system configuration, and operational constraints. The lessons learned from these sites provide valuable guidance for similar efforts, including the one proposed for Matera.

5 Conclusions and outlook

The integration of DORIS beacons at VLBI Legacy and VGOS stations is a critical step toward improving the consistency and accuracy of the International Terrestrial Reference Frame. However, such co-location must

be approached with a rigorous understanding of radio frequency compatibility, as the high-power emissions from DORIS systems could interfere with the sensitive front-end electronics of VLBI and VGOS antennas.

Through simulations based on established ITU models and detailed digital terrain data, it has been demonstrated that compatibility can be effectively assessed and managed. The case study of the Matera Observatory shows that natural terrain features can play a decisive role in providing effective protection by preventing line-of-sight conditions.

Drawing on simulations and real-world experience from European sites, it is evident that each installation must be evaluated on a case-by-case basis. Compatibility studies should therefore be considered as a prerequisite to any proposed co-location, supported by on-site RF measurements and iterative design.

In the future, additional factors such as the impact of harmonic emissions, time-dependent interference patterns, and the potential role of artificial shielding materials require further research.

With careful planning and validation, the co-location of VGOS and DORIS could become standard practice, thereby strengthening the geodetic infrastructures that support the global reference systems.

References

- Altamimi Z, Rebischung P, Collilieux X, Métivier L, Chanard L, (2023) ITRF2020: an augmented reference frame refining the modeling of nonlinear station motions. *Journal of Geodesy*, 97(5), 47 doi: 10.1007/s00190-023-01738-w.
- Bautista-Duran M, Ferreira JS, García-Espada S, Hase H, Kallunki J, Lindqvist M, López-Pérez JA, Madkour V, McKay D, Probst W, Tangen LX, Tornatore V, Winkel B (2023) *Proceedings of the 26th European VLBI for Geodesy and Astrometry (EVGA) Working Meeting*, 11-15 June 2023, Technical University of Munich, Bad Kötzing, Germany, pp. 114-120 doi: 10.14459/2023md1730292.
- ITU-R Report RA.2507: Technical and operational characteristics of the existing and planned Geodetic Very Long Baseline Interferometry, 10/2022
https://www.itu.int/dms_pub/itu-r/opb/rep/R-REP-RA.2507-2022-PDF-E.pdf
- ITU-R Recommendation RA.769-2: Protection criteria used for radio astronomical measurements. 2003-05-28
https://www.itu.int/dms_pubrec/itu-r/rec/ra/R-REC-RA.769-2-200305-I!!PDF-E.pdf
- ITU-R Recommendation RA.452-16: Prediction procedure for the evaluation of interference between stations on the

surface of the Earth at frequencies above about 0.1 GHz
https://www.itu.int/dms_pubrec/itu-r/rec/p/R-REC-P.452-16-201507-S!!PDF-E.pdf

Winkel, B.: pycraf

<https://github.com/bwinkel/pycraf>

Lidar sources for the different RAS stations used in this Report, based on a compilation by Open Data Portal, Austria: Wettzell, G: Bayerische Vermessungsverwaltung (www.geodaten.bayern.de): DTM 50 Meter

<https://opendata.bayern.de/>

detailansicht/datensatz/

digitales-gelaendemodell-50-m-gitterweite

Klügel T, Schüler T, Phogat A, Mähler S, Plötz C, Kronschnabl G, Bertarini A, Neidhardt A, Saunij, Didelot F, Walter JM (2017) VLBI-DORIS Interference Investigation at Wettzell. *Proceedings 23rd EVGA Working Meeting, 2017, Gothenburg, Sweden*, Eds. R. Haas and G. Elgered, pp. 24-28 ISBN 978-91-88041-10-4.

A Report on New VGOS Frequency Sequences Test Observations

S. Bernhart, E. Azcue Infanzón, R. Bolaño González, L. Chin Chuan, Y. K. Choi, P. de Vicente, A. García Castellano, S. García Espada, J. González García, R. Haas, H. Hase, F. Jaron, J. A. López Pérez, J. McCallum, L. McCallum, M. C. S. Moreira, W. Petrachenko, C. Plötz, J. Quick, M. Schartner

Abstract The IVS VGOS Technical Committee (IVS VTC) discussed several times on how to maximize the ben-

Simone Bernhart^{1,2,3} · Yoon Kyung Choi^{1,2,3} · Hayo Hase² · Frédéric Jaron^{4,3} · Christian Plötz²

(1) Reichert GmbH, Hittorfstr. 26, 53129 Bonn, Germany

(2) Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie (BKG), Sackendorfer Str. 25, 93444 Bad Kötzing, Germany

(3) Max Planck Institut für Radioastronomie (MPIfR), Auf dem Hügel 69, 53121 Bonn, Germany

(4) Technische Universität Wien, Wiedner Hauptstraße 8-10, 1040, Vienna, Austria

Esther Azcue Infanzón

Instituto Geográfico Nacional, C/ General Ibáñez de Ibero 3, 28003 Madrid, Spain

Ruben Bolaño González · Susana García Espada

Norwegian Mapping Authority, Kartverket Ny-Ålesund, Geodetic Observatory, Svalbard, Norway

Lim Chin Chuan · Rüdiger Haas

Chalmers University of Technology, 412 96 Gothenburg, Sweden

Pablo de Vicente · Javier González García · José Antonio López Pérez

Observatorio de Yebes, Instituto Geográfico Nacional, Cerro de la Palera S/N, 19141 Yebes, Guadalajara, Spain

Abel García Castellano · Mariana CS Moreira

RAEGE - Santa Maria, Estrada dos Piquinhos s/n, 9580-324 Vila do Porto, Portugal

Jamie McCallum · Lucia McCallum

University of Tasmania, School of Natural Sciences. Private Bag 37, 7001 Hobart, TAS, Australia

William T. Petrachenko

NRCan retired, 1495 Kilborn Ave., Ottawa ON K1H 6M1, Canada

Jonathan Quick

Hartebeesthoek Radio Astronomy Observatory (HartRAO), PO Box 443, Krugersdorp, South Africa

Matthias Schartner

Institute of Geodesy and Photogrammetry, ETH Zurich, 8093 Zurich, Switzerland

efits of VGOS for geodesy and astrometry. Unused potential for improvement was identified in (a) increasing the synthesized bandwidth per VGOS observing band from 480 to 1024 MHz, and (b) distributing the four VGOS frequency bands between 3 and 14 GHz instead of only up to 10.6 GHz as is currently the case. In order to demonstrate the feasibility and possible benefits by using that potential, a series of fringe tests and test sessions were carried out in late 2024, and further tests were performed in early 2025. The results of these tests are expected to provide important input to the efforts of the IVS to anchor the observed frequency channels in the ITU Radio Regulations, so that in the future more consideration could be given to VGOS radio telescopes with regard to unwanted radio radiation. To this end, the optimum VGOS frequency configurations are sought as they are to be used in the long term. We report on the performance of these sessions and present preliminary results and recommendations for suitable frequency setups, where possible.

Keywords VLBI, VGOS

1 Introduction

In recent years, VGOS operations have become routine. Consequently, previous activities of the European VGOS (EU-VGOS) collaboration (1) had been reduced to a minimum. However, after a VTC splinter meeting during the 13th International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS¹) General Meeting in Tsukuba in March 2024, it was decided to resume work and start a series of test observations for new frequency sequences to expedite the search for an optimum broadband frequency configuration. These tests were carried out in April 2024 with the participation of

¹ <https://ivscc.gsfc.nasa.gov/about/index.html>

Fig. 1 The five frequency sequences, that were observed during the test sessions, are displayed starting with the standard VGOS mode on the bottom in black. The new modes (0 to 3, shown in red, blue, green, and turquoise) cover a frequency range between 3 and 14 GHz.

six European VGOS stations (NYALE13N, ONSA13NE, ONSA13SW, RAEGSMAR, WETTZ13S, RAEGYEB - hereafter referred to as Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws, Yj). A total of five different frequency setups were observed on five consecutive days, the first being the standard VGOS setup and four new versions covering frequency ranges from 3 to 14 GHz. A graphical display of the different frequency sequences is shown in Figure 1. Frequency tables of all test modes can be found in the presentation to this report (2). The sessions were correlated in Bonn.

Nn was only available on the first day due to an azimuth motor failure that occurred on the second day (and a planned maser maintenance on days 4 and 5). Since several additional problems arose during the observations, it was decided to repeat the tests in late November 2024, this time under the auspices of the IVS VGOS Technical Committee (VTC) and with participation of additional non-European stations (HARTVGS, HOBART12, KATH12M - hereafter referred to as Hv, Hb, Ke) including two sets of fringe test observations in order to fix possible issues preferably before the proper observation.

Due to a technical issue at Ws, the data for the full second test sessions were unusable. Thus, it was agreed

to repeat the frequency tests while the second batch was analysed, to have a third set of measurements with possibly even more stations and data including some of the NASA stations (GGAO12M, KOKEE12M, MACGO12M - in short Gs, K2, Mg) and all AUSCOPE antennas (including YARRA12M - Yg) as well as ISHIOKA (Is) station. Table 1 gives an overview of all frequency sequence test sessions observed so far.

2 Method

One of the unused potentials for improving the VGOS frequency setup and the corresponding analytical benefits was to increase the synthesized bandwidth per observing band from 480 to 1024 MHz. Another option was to distribute the four VGOS frequency bands between 3 and 14 GHz instead of only up to 10.6 GHz as is currently the case. It was decided to include both in the frequency sequence test, knowing that not all stations were capable of handling either or both of the two options (e.g., Nn could not observe above 11 GHz, while Yj could not record a bandwidth of 1024 MHz).

The observation strategy for the first test setup (efseq0 - efseq4) was such that the observations were performed on five consecutive days, each day

Table 1 Session overview

Session name	Observing date	Observing mode	Participating stations	Duration [hrs]
efseq0	2024-04-08	VO mode	Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws, Yj	3
efseq1	2024-04-09	mode_0	Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws, Yj	3
efseq2	2024-04-10	mode_1	Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws, Yj	3
efseq3	2024-04-11	mode_2	Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws, Yj	3
efseq4	2024-04-12	mode_3	Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws, Yj	3
ft1-ft5	2024-11-12	all	(Hv,) Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa(, Ws)	-
ft1v2-ft5v2	2024-11-18	all	Hv, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws	-
vt4330	2024-11-25	VO mode	Hb, Hv, Ke, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa	6
vt4331	2024-11-26	mode_0	Hv, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa	6
vt4332	2024-11-27	mode_3	Hv, Hb, Ke, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa	6
vt4333	2024-11-28	mode_2	Hv, Hb, Ke, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa	6
vt4334	2024-11-29	mode_1	Hv, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa	6
ft1v3-ft5v3	2025-01-23	all	Gs, Hb, Hv, Is, K2, Ke, Mg, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws, Yg	-
vt5034	2025-02-03	VO mode	Gs, Hb, Hv, Is, Ke, K2, Mg, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws, Yg	6
vt5035	2025-02-04	mode_0	Gs, Hv, Is, K2, Mg, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws	6
vt5036	2025-02-05	mode_3	Gs, Hb, Hv, Is, K2, Mg, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws	6
vt5037	2025-02-06	mode_2	Gs, Hv, Is, K2, Ke, Mg, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws	6
vt5038	2025-02-07	mode_1	Gs, Hv, Is, K2, Ke, Mg, Nn, Oe, Ow, Sa, Ws	6

using a different frequency setup, and the schedules corresponded to that of the first day. Thus, the analysis results could be directly compared to the standard VO setup. The scan duration was scheduled to be 60 seconds for the first hour and 30 seconds for the remaining hours. Sources were selected among two groups (cf. Table 2): group A contained often observed VGOS sources with good performance and each of them was scheduled four times if possible, group B consisted of additional often observed VGOS sources that were scheduled three times. 44 sources in total were scheduled for each session with ten sources taken from group A and 34 from group B. The schedules were prepared using VieSched++ (3).

Table 2 Source groups

Source group A	0059+581 0133+476 0202+319 0235+164 0322+222 0613+570 1751+288 1803+784 1846+322 2113+293
Source group B	0016+731 0019+058 0025+197 0109+224 0119+115 0307+380 0345+460 0415+398 0454+844 0529+483 0552+398 0602+673 0716+714 0800+618 1039+811 1053+704 1418+546 1636+473 1726+455 1746+470 1806+456 1849+670 1923+210 2000+472 2013+163 2144+092 2201+171 2214+241 2214+350 2215+150 2229+695 2309+454 2319+317 2325+093

The sessions were processed in the usual fashion, which is applied to the regular VGOS observations, with correlation in DiFX² version 2.5.5 and post-processing performed with HOPS³ v3.24.

After the experience made with the execution of the first set of frequency sequence tests, it was decided to perform fringe tests for each observing mode (ft1 - ft5) well in advance to a second test series. For each mode, at least two scans were scheduled per station, all of them two minutes long with a one-minute gap in between. Moreover, since observing modes 0 and 3 seemed to be most promising, the order of the modes was changed from numerical order 0, 1, 2, 3 to modes 0, 3, 2, 1. Due to technical issues at two stations, the fringe tests were repeated one week later (ft1v2 - ft5v2).

The second set of frequency sequence tests (vt4330 - vt4334) included three southern hemisphere stations (Hv, Hb, Ke). The first hour can be seen as an extended fringe test since some stations missed the previous test or experienced technical problems. It included all stations with 90-second long scans. We especially tried to observe bright sources. Additionally, we tried to balance scans of Sa and Hb and in general tried to include the Australian stations as much as possible.

² DiFX - Distributed FX software correlator, (4)

³ HOPS - Haystack Observatory Postprocessing System, <https://www.haystack.mit.edu/haystack-observatory-postprocessing-system-hops/>

Hours two to six were scheduled without the Australian stations. We used 30-second long scans, again trying to focus on bright sources but also balance the inclusion of Hv.

The third test series (vt5034 - vt5038) included three NASA stations (Gs, K2, Mg) and was preceded by another fringe test session (ft1v3 - ft5v3). The observing strategy was following that of the previous frequency sequence test session. The US stations were added only during the first two hours of the experiment except for K2. This way, we tried to reduce the risk of failure while also reducing the impact of station drop-out due to problems in the frequency setup.

3 Results

A more detailed description on the performance of each station can be found in (2). Here, we will merely focus on the overall results of correlation and analysis.

3.1 Summary efseq1 - efseq4

Among various problems, which arose during the first set of test sessions, the most notable issue turned out to be the original frequency selection of mode O violating the fourfit grid constraints. The uniform grid, that fourfit chooses, is a function of the frequency setup and should (a) not consist of more than 8192 points and (b) the total number of points should be a power of two. According to John Barrett (priv. comm.), the simplest fix would be to adjust the band LOs so that the channels all lie on frequency points such that the frequency of channel n , (f_n) is given by: $f_n = f_0 + N * (32 \text{ MHz})$ where f_0 is the first channel's frequency, and N is some integer. Hence, it was decided to shift band B up by 12 MHz (start @4216.4 MHz) and band C by 8 MHz (start @7608.4 MHz) for any follow-up observations.

Interestingly, even though Yj was only capable of recording half of the bandwidth of 1024 MHz, the post-processing chain seemed to work for all test modes. However, since it did not work for all stations, the final step of fringe-fitting was not performed and no further analysis was carried out except for efseq0 (VGOS standard mode).

Disregarding the frequency limitations at some stations, one major argument against observing up to 14 GHz was that the phase calibration tones were expected to be too weak. Hence, Frédéric Jaron tested the behaviour of the phase cal signal in the

efseq sessions with particular emphasis on band D (13 to 14 GHz). His conclusions were that the power of the phase-cal signal is greatly reduced towards high frequencies as was expected. Nevertheless, the extracted phase-cal signals appear stable, also at high frequencies. Moreover, applying the phase-cal signal increases the signal-to-noise ratio of the observations. Consequently, similar studies should be performed with all international VGOS stations.

3.2 Summary Fringe Tests and vt4330 - vt4334

To help the stations get acquainted with the different frequency setups and switching between the modes, in particular if done by means of recabling, we decided to do a fringe test two weeks before the second observing session took place. The importance of such tests became quite obvious: due to numerous mishaps, it was decided to run another test one week later. One achievement was that a frequency setup error at Nn could be corrected.

The Australian stations did not participate in the fringe tests but succeeded in doing some local testing instead. In contrast, Ws only managed to join the fringe tests but missed the actual observations due to a Helium compressor failure.

- vt4330: The post-processing of the session in standard VGOS mode worked for all stations except Hb which is certainly owing to the short observing span of only the first hour. Analysis problems occurred for Hv (station had huge residuals), Hb and Ke (the observations were noisy). These stations were deselected from the routine solution.
- vt4331: Post-processing for frequency sequence mode O was successful for all stations and all stations were included in routine solution for analysis (with Hv observations being noisy).
- vt4332: Frequency sequence mode 3 had issues in post-processing only for stations Hb and Ke. Nevertheless all stations were included in the routine solution. One peculiarity for this session was the recording mode that the Onsala Twin Telescopes (OTTs) chose in order to avoid recabling during the different observing modes: the data were recorded in 8 datastreams with 80 channels, 16 of which being idle channels. Since HOPS is currently not able to handle more than 64 channels, the phase cal had not been treated properly in the conversion

from SWIN (correlator output) files to MkIV format and, thus, it looked as if there was not pcal present in band D for the OTTs which is, however, not the case.

- vt4333: For frequency sequence mode 2, there were problems with the proxy cable calibration extraction from the correlated data for Hb and Ke. In the analysis, it turned out that Hv had again huge residuals and was deselected from routine solution together with Hb and Ke.
- vt4334: Even though the post-processing worked for all stations with frequency sequence mode 1, Hv had again very noisy observations and the WRMS were huge (~ 300 ps). Moreover, Sa showed bi- and tri-modal patterns of the residuals and ~ 56 % of the potentially usable observations were deselected.

3.3 Preliminary Results for vt5034 - vt5038

For the third batch of frequency sequence test observations, a fringe test was appointed 11 days prior to the observing campaign which was again accompanied by various issues. For example, the NASA stations were not yet familiar with the correct frequency setup for each mode and, thus, observed all fringe tests with the standard VGOS setup so that no fringes could be expected. Due to technical issues, Ws was not able to participate and Nn had again used a wrong frequency setup which could fortunately be detected and corrected before the proper observations started. However, due to the late arrival of some of the data, the vt503X sessions had already started before the fringe test correlations could be finished.

The NASA stations are currently not capable of observing up to 14 GHz. Moreover, their bandwidth is limited to 512 instead of 1024 MHz. Nevertheless, thanks to the help of Ed Himwich, a setup could be worked out such that - depending on the mode - at least bands A and B could partly and band C could fully be covered. In the meantime, Nn underwent an upgrade of their receiver and is now able to observe up to 14 GHz.

By the time of the EVGA meeting, the processing of the VGOS standard mode session was completed and work on modes 0 and 3 had already started, so that some preliminary results could be presented.

- vt5034: In total, 75.5% of the station data was used for the analysis where Hv showed huge residuals (the WRMS were 400ps) and Ws had a late start

and then 2 hrs of non-detections, so that only 3 hrs of observations were included in the routine solution.

- vt5035: Fringes could be found for Gs and K2 and also for Nn in band D. Mg had an auto-stow problem, as a result, there was a control time-out after 30 seconds and the antenna shut down. Hence, the station cannot be included in the processing.
- vt5036: Ws erroneously observed with mode 1 instead of mode 3. Fringes could be found for K2 and Mg and also again for Nn in band D.

Some example fringe plots for vt433x and vt503x are presented in (2).

4 Conclusions and outlook

Analysis results suggest that modes 0 and 3 are the most promising ones because all stations could be included in the routine solution. But in view of the persisting issues for some of the stations, follow-up observations deem necessary. If so, several options could be considered: one could think of fringe tests only and later a 24 hours VR session for one or two modes. In case, the tests should be continued as before, fringe tests should either be scheduled earlier or data shipment needs to be performed faster. Concerning the calibration strategy, it might be sufficient to schedule less calibration scans, but for all stations at least three or preferably the double amount at the session start, middle, and end. In order to avoid further confusion with the observing modes, it might be advisable to change again the observing order, rename the modes to better reflect the non-numerical order or skip worse performing modes completely.

References

1. Albentosa, E., Alef, W., Bernhart, S., et al. 2023, International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2022 General Meeting Proceedings, Current Status of the EU-VGOS Project, 85.
2. Bernhart, Simone, A Report on New VGOS Frequency Sequences Test Observations, Apr 2025, Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15301919
3. Schartner, M. and Böhm, J. "VieSched++: A New VLBI Scheduling Software for Geodesy and Astrometry", PASP, 2019, 131, 084501. doi: 10.1088/1538-3873/ab1820
4. A. T. Deller, W. F. Brisken, C. J. Phillips, J. Morgan, W. Alef, R. Cappallo, E. Middelberg, J. D. Romney, H. Rottmann, S. J. Tingay & R. Wayth, "DiFX-2: A More Flexible, Efficient, Robust, and Powerful Software Correlator", PASP, 2011, 123, 275-287.

Status of the Spectrum Management for VGOS

H. Hase¹, M. Bautista Duran², A. Garcia Castellano³, S. García⁴, M. Lindqvist⁵, J.A. López-Pérez², W. Madkour⁶, D. McKay⁷, L.M. Tangen⁸, W. Probst¹, V. Tornatore⁹, B. Winkel¹⁰

Abstract The spectral range of 2-14 GHz used in VGOS observation is used and requested by the booming telecommunication industry. The need for radio quiet skies in geodetic VLBI does not play a role in new spectrum allocations if the geodetic VLBI community does not articulate it. The IVS together with the European

Committee on Radio Astronomy Frequencies is seeking how to get the VGOS stations better protected against unwanted electromagnetic emissions. One option is an Agenda Item on the protection of geodetic VLBI at the World Radio Conference 2031. The current status of the spectrum management and some useful information about the Radio Regulations are provided.

(1) Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie, BKG Wettzell, Sackenrieder Str. 25, D-93444 Bad Kötzing, Germany

(2) Instituto Geográfico Nacional, Observatorio Yebes, Cerro de la Palera sn, E-19141 Yebes, Guadalajara, Spain

(3) Associação RAEGE Açores, Estação RAEGE de Santa Maria, Estrada dos Piquinhos s/n, 9580-324 Vila do Porto, Portugal

(4) Kartverket, Geodetic Earth Observatory, P.O. Box 13, N-9173 Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard, Norway

(5) Department of Space, Earth and Environment, Chalmers University of Technology, Onsala Space Observatory, S-439 92 Onsala, Sweden

(6) Joint Institute for VLBI ERIC, Oude Hoogeveensedijk 4, NL-7991 PD Dwingeloo, The Netherlands

(7) Aalto University, Metsähovi Radio Observatory, Metsähovintie 114, FI-02540 Kylmäla, Finland

(8) Kartverket, Kartverksveien 21, 3511 Hønefoss, Norway

(9) Politecnico Milano, Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, I-20133 Milano, Italy

(10) Max-Planck-Institut für Radioastronomie, Auf dem Hügel 69, D-53121 Bonn, Germany

Keywords geodetic VLBI, VGOS, spectrum management, radio regulations, protection, world radio conference

1 Introduction

The introduction of broadband feeds to geodetic VLBI increased the performance by enabling observations in larger spanned bandwidth and with more channels. This enables shorter on-source observation intervals and more scans per time unit, producing more accurate geodetic results. The drawback of this technical development is the sensitivity to any microwave radiation in the broadband feed frequency range. With a booming telecommunications industry, the demand for more and more bandwidth increases the number of active transmitters throughout the spectrum. This makes VGOS observations more and more difficult, as it aims to receive the faint cosmic noise from quasars at the edge of the universe. Artificial microwaves may reduce or saturate the sensitivity of the cryogenically cooled high-performance receivers at VGOS radio telescopes. How can geodetic VLBI observations be safeguarded? This is where spectrum management kicks

Fig. 1 Quadruple Ridged Flared Horn (QRFH) used in VGOS-receivers as developed by IGN Yebes Observatory. This antenna feed is receptive in the frequency range of 2-14 GHz.

in, where radio regulations (RR) may be applied under certain conditions.

2 Status of Spectrum Management for VGOS

The International Telecommunications Union - Radio-communication (ITU-R) is the global forum of national spectrum administrations, which are the authority for the use of the electromagnetic spectrum in their respective countries. Decisions on the use of spectrum are taken during the World Radio Conferences (WRC), which happen each 4 years (2023, 2027, 2031,...). The reason for international regulations became obvious after the sinking of the Titanic cruise ship, where two emergency alert systems operated at different frequencies prevented a search and rescue operation of a nearby ship. Today we enjoy regulations without being conscious about it, when our smart phones are working cross-boarder and even on other continents.

Geodetic VLBI observes *cosmic radiation*. Therefore, geodetic VLBI is classified by the RR as a Radio Astronomy Service (RAS). Most services in the RR are active, but RAS is receive-only and therefore a passive service.

Radio astronomers had been active from the beginning of radio astronomy to prevent active transmissions in some spectral lines, which allow to identify important atoms or molecules (e.g. H_2 , C_4 , CH_4 , etc.) in the universe. The astronomers successfully managed to get some frequency bands allocated to the RAS with certain limitations to other services to avoid interference with radio astronomical observations. Being classified as RAS, the geodetic community can already enjoy the protective regulations which are in place for our radio astronomy colleagues. Unfortunately, geodesy is observing a much wider channel bandwidth and a much wider overall spanned bandwidth. Protection is only granted to the allocated RAS frequency bands. Outside of RAS-bands geodetic VLBI cannot claim protection. The other services with allocated bands are legally using their bands, even if they disturb geodetic observations.

Another problem in spectrum management is that it is a national issue. Each country is free to do what it wants as long as its own international commitments expressed in the RR are met. However, there is a general understanding that search and rescue, traffic control (air, sea), and communications need a consensus on frequency bands. Broadcast microwaves do not stop at the borders. Unlike *national* legislation for the use of spectrum, geodetic VLBI networks are *global*. Geodetic VLBI is a global instrument that needs protection globally to produce good results. But only national administrations can regulate or provide protection (to their radio-telescope infrastructure).

What can be done?

1. Registration of VGOS-site at ITU as a RAS station
2. Recognition of the VGOS-observation channels in the RR

2.1 Registration of VGOS-site as RAS station

A registration of a VGOS-station as a Radio Astronomy Service station at the ITU-Radiocommunications Bureau according to the RR Art. 29.5 has to be made through the national spectrum administration to the ITU. The registration as RAS-station provides protection in the RAS-bands and for the location (first comes, first served). Then RR Chapter VI Provisions for services and stations, Article 29, Radio Astronomy Service applies. The registration process is explained

in (6). The register of stations is also a resource for space operators in their mission planning when they operate powerful radars which could be detrimental to RAS-sites. Registered stations can be found here: <https://www.itu.int/go/ITUSpaceExplorer>.

Fig. 2 The Radio Regulations (RR) contain the actual status of the allocations and their regulations. It is updated after each WRC. It has the character of an international treaty, but is not binding for national administrations. Electronic copies are freely available in english, arabic, chinese, french, russian, and spanish language: <https://www.itu.int/pub/R-REG-RR>.

2.2 Recognition of the VGOS-observation bands/channels in the RR

Frequency bands used by VGOS observations (but also the legacy S/X bands) are not allocated to the Radio Astronomy Service. Therefore, geodetic VLBI stations are not protected against unwanted electromagnetic emissions. Geodetic VLBI is an application of radio astronomy for the benefit of society. The global geodetic reference frame and Earth rotation monitoring are essential for navigation and positioning, as well as for science and geoinformation. VLBI is the unique technique for the celestial reference frame in the microwave spectrum and is used in deep-space missions and astrometric science. However, the term "geodetic VLBI" is unknown in the RR.

Geodetic VLBI users desire a radio quiet environment for their radio telescope sites. To keep the observation bands clean of interference, those frequency channels should be allocated to RAS, which is not yet

the case. An alternative would be the assignment of footnotes in the RR like footnote 5.149: *"In making assignments to stations of other services to which the bands: [... list of frequency bands...] are allocated, administrations are urged to take all practicable steps to protect the radio astronomy service from harmful interference. Emissions from space- or air-borne stations can be particularly serious sources of interference to the radio astronomy service (see Nos. 4.5 and 4.6 and Article 29)."*

2.3 How to get the observation bands of geodetic VLBI into the Radio Regulations?

To reach one of these two possibilities – allocations or footnotes in the RR – the geodetic VLBI needs must be accepted as an issue for the World Radio Conference, where a decision on acceptance or rejection will take place. Prior to it a type of missionary work in (at least) each of the VGOS-countries at the national spectrum administrations has to be successful in order to make the geodetic VLBI issue a national issue in spectrum management and then from there a regional issue (for CEPT in case of Europe) to gain weight when proposed as a preliminary agenda item for the WRC. The next WRC-2027 will discuss preliminary agenda items for WRC-2031. Therefore, the action to bring geodetic VLBI as an agenda item for the WRC into the national discussions starts now, in 2025.

3 Towards a WRC Agenda Item on Geodetic VLBI

Geodesy contributes global geodetic reference frames as a base element to the 17 development goals on sustainability by the United Nations. This was recognized by Resolution 69/266 of the General Assembly of the United Nations "A global geodetic reference frame for sustainable development" (2015) (1). Geodetic VLBI is fundamental for global geodetic reference frames and requires protection to serve the UN goals.

Several steps have been taken to enhance the visibility of geodetic VLBI in international science commu-

Fig. 3 Allocations in the range of 2-14 GHz according to the RR. The blue and red lines mark possible 32 VGOS observation channels with 32 MHz bandwidth each. A set of bands has to be fixed, when asking for allocations or footnotes! If geodetic VLBI is accepted as an issue for the WRC, studies of the impact of geodetic VLBI to the existing services with allocations in each channel will have to be conducted. (Graphic by M. Bautista)

nities for astronomy and geoscience, but also in international spectrum management.

The conflict between booming telecommunication industry demanding more and more bandwidth of the electro-magnetic spectrum and radio quiet skies for radio astronomy had led to resolutions of the General Assembly of the International Union of Astronomy (IAU) "in support of the protection of geodetic radio astronomy against radio frequency interference", 2021 (2) and the General Assembly of the International Union of Geophysics and Geodesy (IUGG) "Improving Protection of Geodetic Observatories from Active Radio Services", 2023 (3).

In spectrum management a question was raised to the ITU-R Working Party 7D "Radio Astronomy" about the technical and operational characteristics of geodetic VLBI. The question was accepted and, consequently, the answer was prepared and accepted as an ITU-R Technical Report RA.2507 "Technical and operational characteristics of the existing and planned Geodetic Very Long Baseline Interferometry", 2022 (4). So far, this document has been the reference for spectrum managers who want to know what geodetic VLBI is.

Most recently, the Global Geodetic Center of Excellence of the United Nations (UN-GGCE) issued its Policy

Brief No. 003 "Safeguarding VLBI Radio Frequencies" in which concerns for the geodetic data supply chain are addressed and actions are proposed for the protection of geodetic VLBI (5).

These documents may help convince national spectrum managers to support the protection of geodetic VLBI sites against future disturbance during their observations.

The next steps are to propose a joint proposal by nations through their regional telecommunication unions (hopefully supported from countries from all the three ITU-regions) for a preliminary Agenda Item in WRC-2027 for WRC-2031. If accepted, it would give a 4 year period to elaborate the studies on the impact of geodetic VLBI to other services that have already allocations in the targeted spectral bands.

4 Short introduction to the Radio Regulations

The Radio Regulations contain articles which are structured in one preamble (Chapter 0.) and ten chapters (1.-10.). The sentences are numbered by

"article number, period, and consecutive number of the statement". This makes it easy to reference specific regulations in documents.

4.1 RR Preamble

Important phrases are as follows:

- 0.5 ..., these Regulations have the following objectives
- 0.6 to facilitate equitable access to and rational use of the natural resources of the radio frequency spectrum and the geostationary satellite orbit
- 0.8 to assist in the prevention and resolution of cases of harmful interference between the radio services of different administrations
- 0.9 to facilitate the efficient and effective operation of all radiocommunication services
- 0.10 to provide for and, where necessary regulate new applications of radiocommunication technology.

This means for geodetic VLBI that the RR could cover the needs for spectrum ("equitable access"). The efficient and effective operation of all services, including RAS, is objective of the RR.

4.2 RR Chapter 1 - Terms and Definitions

The terms and definitions are a useful resource for understanding the meaning of the spectrum management vocabulary. Different professions use different words, and to regulate technical issues a common understanding is fundamental.

Some important terms are:

Section I – General terms:

1.13 **radio astronomy** Astronomy based on the reception of radio waves of cosmic origin

In Section III 42 different communication services are defined. The only service based on the reception of cosmic radiation is the radio astronomy service. That is the argument why geodetic VLBI is also a Radio Astronomy Service.

Section III – Radio services

1.58 **radio astronomy service** : A service involving the use of radio astronomy

In Section IV the definition of "station" and "radio astronomy station" is given:

Section IV – Radio stations and systems

1.61 **station** : One or more transmitters or receivers or a combination of transmitters and receivers, including the accessory equipment, necessary at one location for carrying on a radiocommunication service, or the radio astronomy service

1.97 **radio astronomy station** : A station in the radio astronomy service

Section II is very important to understand three different regulatory categories that can be applied to a frequency band either on the global or on the national level.

Section II – Specific terms related to frequency management

1.16 **allocation** (of a frequency band): Entry in the Table of Frequency Allocations of a given frequency band for the purpose of its use by one or more terrestrial or space radiocommunication services or the radio astronomy service under specified conditions. This term shall also be applied to the frequency band concerned.

1.17 **allotment** (of a radio frequency or radio frequency channel): Entry of a designated frequency channel in an agreed plan, adopted by a competent conference, for use by one or more administrations for a terrestrial or space radiocommunication service in one or more identified countries or geographical areas and under specified conditions.

1.18 **assignment** (of a radio frequency or radio frequency channel): Authorization given by an administration for a radio station to use a radio frequency or radio frequency channel under specified conditions.

4.3 RR Chapter II – Frequencies

Chapter II, Article 5 explains the 3 geographical regions: 1 = Europa, Russia, Africa, 2 = Americas, Caribe, 3 = Asia, Australia, South-Pacific. The allocation table lists for all the 3 regions the allocated frequency bands from 8.3 kHz to 275 GHz to the 42 services. PRIMARY allocations are listed in capital letters, secondary allocations are listed in lowercase letters. An important role in the RR are the footnotes, which may imply stronger restrictions to the allocated services (as pointed out in

Section 2.2. The protection by footnote is one option to protect geodetic VLBI in the channels in which data are recorded. Nevertheless, the VGOS receivers receive a much wider spectrum, and noise may disturb outside the observation bands.

Proceedings of the 25th European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry Working Meeting, ed. Rüdiger Haas, 2021, p. 43–48
https://www.oso.chalmers.se/evga/25_EVGA_2021_Cyber_space.pdf ISBN: 978-91-88041-41-8

5 Conclusions and outlook

The protection of geodetic VLBI against detrimental interference is an issue for spectrum administration in the context of the United Nations goals on sustainable development. Only administrations can declare radio quiet or coordination zones around geodetic VLBI observatories, and can request entries of observed bands into the radio regulations.

Stations need to be registered at ITU-R by national administrations, so that RR Article 29 applies.

The IVS will launch a global initiative through its network stations to bring the need for an agenda item on the protection of geodetic VLBI in to the national and regional discussions for the WRC-2031.

References

1. UN General Assembly Resolution 69/266 "A global geodetic reference frame for sustainable development", 2015
https://ggim.un.org/documents/a_res_69_266_e.pdf
2. IAU General Assembly Resolution B1: "in support of the protection of geodetic radio astronomy against radio frequency interference", 2021
<https://www.iau.org/iau/iau/Publications/List-of-Resolutions.aspx> 2021 B1
3. IUGG General Assembly Resolution 1: "Improving Protection of Geodetic Observatories from Active Radio Services", 2023
https://iugg.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/2023_IUGG-GA-Resolutions.pdf
4. ITU-R Technical Report RA.2507: Technical and operational characteristics of the existing and planned Geodetic Very Long Baseline Interferometry, 2022
https://www.itu.int/dms_pub/itu-r/opb/rep/R-REP-RA.2507-2022-PDF-E.pdf
5. UN-GGCE Policy Brief No. 003: Safeguarding VLBI Radio-Frequencies, 2025
https://ggim.un.org/UNGGCE/documents/202250509_Policy_Brief_Spectrum.pdf
6. Hase, H., Lopez-Perez, J.A., Bautista Duran, M., Kallunki, J., Kupiszewski, P., Tornatore, V., Madkour, W., Lindqvist, M., Winkel, B.: Spectrum Management for the VGOS (2021)

The RAEGE correlator at Yebes Observatory

González-García J.¹, de Vicente P.¹, Cuambe V. A.^{2,3}, de la Fuente Lasa S.¹, García-Castellano A.^{1,2}

Abstract In this report, we describe the current status of the RAEGE correlator placed at Yebes Observatory. The RAEGE network envisaged four stations across the Iberian peninsula, the Canary Islands and the Azores in Portugal. RAEGYEB and RAEGSMAR, the first two stations of the RAEGE project, are already contributing to VGOS observations. The civil works for the construction of the third station in Temisas, Canary Islands, began in 2025 after a series of misfortunes delayed the installation at the initial site. Installed at the Yebes Observatory, the software correlator will allow the observations of the network to be processed, as well as to serve as another contribution to the IVS. In 2024 the Intensive campaign INT-G between the two operational antennas, together with two other stations, Ishioka and Seshan13m was started. To support this program, a rotating correlator scheme has been established between Tsukuba, Shanghai Observatory and Yebes Observatory to process observations in shifts.

Keywords correlation, DiFX, RAEGE, HPC

1 Introduction

At the 13th IVS General Meeting held in Tsukuba, Japan in 2024, we presented the newly installed correlator at Yebes Observatory for the first time. It was conceived with the idea of processing the observations of the RAEGE network, but a smaller cluster was used

(1) Yebes Observatory, Instituto Geográfico Nacional, Spain

(2) Santa María RAEGE station, Azores, Portugal

(3) Universidade Eduardo Mondlane Faculdade de Ciências, Maputo, Mozambique

to train staff in the correlation process for geodetic applications since 2021. During that period, we processed about 100 experiments from various projects, including EU-VGOS and intensive sessions. That experience allowed us to dimension the new HPC system to achieve an observation-to-correlation time ratio of less than one.

2 Hardware

Although the original design envisioned three identical but independent storage volumes (cdata1, cdata2, cdata3), the storage model was ultimately changed to two massive volumes for LO data and a smaller volume to store L1A and L1B data. Each of the raw storage volume is comprised of 10 storage nodes contributing with a couple of RAID-5 groups of six hard disk drives each, individually adding 10 GB of storage per node to the volume. Considering the space required to store the parity, the net available storage space in each volume is 910 TB, for a total of 1.82 PB. For the correlation and fringe-fitting results we reserve four nodes that work in mirror pairs. Those nodes are configured on a single RAID-6 volume for increased robustness. As a result, the net storage space for L1A and L1B data is 186 TB. Both the technology and size were chosen to reduce the cost per byte at the cost of lower I/O speed compared to other massive storage technologies. BeeGFS, a parallel distributed file system is used to provide easily scalable, secure and highly available storage. It requires the existence of so-called metadata servers, whose function is to provide the physical location of the chunks into which the data has been divided. We use fast solid-state devices with a NVMe in-

Fig. 1 Architectural schematic of the correlator components

terface that can provide 6 Gbps read access to the storage area.

The number of CPU cores dedicated to computation remained unchanged, with four nodes powered by Intel Xeon IceLake 4314 CPUs. When storage nodes are also utilized for computation in DiFX, the total available computational capacity can reach up to 896 cores.

In this HPC system with independent nodes, network performance is critical, which is why low-latency technologies like Infiniband are used. The correlator employs three separate networks: a high-speed internal data network (using IB HDR 200 Gbps and IB EDR 100 Gbps), a 100 GbE external connection via RedIRIS—used to receive data streams from remote stations—and a private 1 GbE management network. The internal network is structured in a spine-leaf topology with three Mellanox switches. High-bandwidth nodes, such as front-end and metadata servers, use 200 Gbps links, while compute and storage nodes are connected via 100 Gbps to optimize costs.

Beyond the correlator infrastructure, the deployment also required the installation of independent power and cooling systems. The infrastructure has been designed to dissipate a thermal power of 40 kW,

although the maximum theoretical power consumed by the system is 25 kW.

3 Software

Currently, there is no cluster manager in use. We use DiFX 2.5.4 version as "de facto" standard for the correlation of VGOS-type experiments, but a trunk version is also maintained. As this is a correlator for geodetic VLBI, the post-processing tools are the usual ones for the geodetic VLBI community: HOPS (v3.24 rev 3757) and nuSolve 0.8.2. A PolConvert (v1.7.8) installation is also available. Two tools are used to manage etransfers: jive5ab and etransfer (etc/etd). These tools run as a service on the front-end nodes, accepting requests on several ports from networks supported by the inbound firewall.

4 Experience

The correlator was completed in November 2023 with the installation of the final software. A series of unit test runs were conducted in November and December to evaluate and characterize its performance. The main conclusions from these tests were presented in Behrend D., Bayer K. D. and Armstrong K. L. (2024), and indicated an average write speed of 9 Gbps per RAID5. With six nodes assigned per station, this performance is more than sufficient to sustain a correlation ratio below 1 for VGOS observations at 32 Gbps with three participating stations.

The network tests showed performance close to the theoretical limit in each of the internal networks. Further details can be found in the 23th IVS GM proceedings.

Since January 2024, all operations have been moved to the new HPC. So far, we have only processed sessions corresponding to the IVS-Intensive master schedule. In 2024 we processed 52 sessions, while in 2025 we processed 9 sessions due to the discontinuity of the VGOS-INT-Y programme. The correlator is currently maintained and operated in a collaboration between RAEGE-Az and Yebes Observatory, with two people from each organization involved.

References

Behrend D., Bayer K. D. and Armstrong K. L. (2024) International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2024 General Meeting Proceedings, 122-126 *NASA/CP-20250002586*

Towards VLBI with ESA's Genesis satellite

R. Haas

- on behalf of ESA GSET WG-3 (VLBI) -

Abstract We provide a short overview of the work done in Working Group-3 (WG-3) of the Genesis Science Exploitation Team (GSET) of the European Space Agency (ESA). ESA GSET WG-3 works on preparations for the future use of signals transmitted by the Genesis satellite to be used for geodetic Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) observations.

Keywords VLBI, Genesis, co-location in space, ITRF

1 Introduction

In 2022, ESA's Ministerial Council approved the Genesis mission as part of the ESA FutureNav programme. The goal of this mission is to contribute significantly to improving the International Terrestrial Reference frame (ITRF, Altamimi et al. 2023) in terms of accuracy and stability. Genesis is meant to be a co-location satellite that will link four space geodetic techniques on one platform orbiting the Earth Delva et al. (2023). These four techniques are Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI), Doppler Orbitography and Radiopositioning Integrated by Satellite (DORIS) and Satellite Laser Ranging (SLR).

To link these four techniques in space, Genesis will be equipped with GNSS and DORIS receivers, SLR retroreflectors, and a transmitter that will send artificial VLBI signals that can be observed with VLBI Global Observing System (VGOS) of the International

VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS). Thus, Genesis will be a complement to the international network of ground-based co-location stations. The plan is to launch Genesis in 2028 and to operate it at least for 2 years.

In order to achieve a seamless interaction with the international geodetic services and geodetic science community as such, ESA created in early 2024 a Genesis Science Exploitation Team (GSET) with five working groups (WGs). One working group concentrates on the ITRF and techniques combinations using Genesis while the four other WGs focus on one space geodetic technique each. The task of the WGs is to advise ESA concerning the development of the Genesis payloads, to work towards a seamless cooperation and integration with the geodetic services, and to contribute to the scientific exploitation of the future Genesis data.

2 The Genesis orbit

Genesis is supposed to be launched into a circular orbit of 6000 km height with an inclination of 95° . It will thus have an orbital period of about 3.8 h and move with an angular velocity of about $0.026^\circ/\text{s}$. A horizon-to-horizon overpass at a VLBI ground station with a minimum elevation of 5° will take 68 minutes at maximum. Fig. 1 depicts the to expected satellite ground track during 24 h and shows the instantaneous "visibility cap", i.e. the area where VLBI ground stations can see the satellite at an elevation $\geq 5^\circ$. From the satellite's point of view, the green area corresponds to an angle of 61.732° . Within this green area, about 10 existing and future stations of the VLBI Global Observing System (VGOS) are located.

Rüdiger Haas
Chalmers University of Technology, Onsala Space Observatory,
SE-439 92 Onsala, Sweden

Fig. 1 Pink: Example of the to be expected Genesis ground track during 24 h. Green: Instantaneous "visibility cap", i.e. where the satellite is visible from VLBI ground stations $\geq 5^\circ$ elevation.

3 ESA GSET WG-3 (VLBI)

Working group 3 (WG-3) focuses on the VLBI aspects of Genesis. It has currently about 30 members and is lead by Rüdiger Haas, who is also the current chair of the IVS directing board. The WG members are experts in various aspects of VLBI and work at European and international institutions. WG-3 has online meeting every 4-6 weeks and discusses various aspects of future VLBI observations of Genesis signals.

The overall goal is to integrate future Genesis VLBI observations into the IVS operations in order to contribute strengthening the ITRF. This needs to be done without deteriorating any of the standard IVS products and should not harm other passive users of the radio frequency spectrum, such as users of radio astronomy. Thus, good compromises need to be found to achieve a "win-win-situation" that benefits the society and the science community.

The work of WG-3 is separated into seven work packages (WPs) that address slightly different aspects, but of course are all interlinked. These are WP-1 on frequencies and signals, WP-2 on ground station fidelity, WP-3 on delay resolution, correlation and fringe-fitting, WP-4 on scheduling, WP-5 on end-to-end simulations, WP-6 on test observations, and WP-7 on a potential Pseudo-Random-Noise (PRN) option.

4 WP-1: Frequencies and Signals

The idea is that Genesis will be observed with the modern VGOS network of the IVS. VGOS is a broadband system covering 2-14 GHz in two linear polarizations. Within this frequency range, there are four suitable

frequency bands that the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) has allocated for space-to-earth transmission that ESA can use for the VLBI signal transmission from Genesis, see Table 1. While the occupied bandwidths are 200, 320, 400 and 500 MHz, due to necessary filtering the actual usable bandwidths will be slightly smaller, i.e. 180, 310, 390, and 490 MHz.

Table 1 Genesis start and stop frequencies in MHz

Band-1	Band-2	Band-3	Band-4
3100-3300	5250-5570	8200-8400	9300-9800

In order to simplify VLBI processing and e.g. error search and calibration, ESA has been advised to use left-hand circular polarization for the transmission. Since the design of broad-band antennas with circular polarization is very challenging, it is expected to have several transmitting antennas on the satellite, each covering a smaller bandwidth. The relative location of these antennas and the antenna pattern have to be calibrated. This calibration information is essential for the VLBI fringe-fitting and post-processing. It is desirable that the final reference position w.r.t. the spacecraft center of mass is known with a comparable accuracy as the positions of the natural radio sources. The latter are at cosmological distances and have a root-mean-square position uncertainty of $30 \mu\text{as}$, which relates to less than 1 mm at 6000 km distance. Thus, the transmit antenna calibration should be better than 1 mm.

The actual signal strength should not be too high so that other users of the radio frequency spectrum will not be disturbed. ESA has thus been advised to have a maximum spectral flux density on Earth surface in nadir direction of 20 jansky, which can be attenuated logarithmically in 15 steps by up to 20 dB. It is to be expected that extensive tests need to be done in the commissioning phase. Once the optimum attenuation level is found it probably can be fixed.

Since the satellite will be orbiting the Earth in just 6000 km orbital height, there will be differential attenuation effects purely due to the different free-space-loss for different ground station locations. For the Genesis frequencies the free-space-loss difference between an observing station directly below the satellite that sees the satellite at 90° elevation and an observing station at the edge of the earth that sees the satellite at 5° elevation, is on the order of 4.5 dB.

5 WP-2: Ground Station Fidelity

The VGOS ground station antennas have to be able to track the satellite and the VGOS backends have to be able to receive the transmitted signals.

The satellite moves with an angular velocity of about $0.026^\circ/\text{s}$. Modern VGOS radio telescopes have typically 12–13 m diameter and an half-power beamwidth (HPBW) at 10 GHz frequency of about 0.175° . Thus, the satellite will pass through the antenna beam within about 6 s. Therefore, continuous tracking capability is required. Several of the international VGOS stations are already capable of continuous satellite tracking by sending two-line elements (TLE) from the VLBI Field System (FS) to the antenna control units (ACUs). However, other stations still need to be updated during the coming years to allow satellite tracking directly from the VLBI FS.

The backends of the VGOS stations are prepared for broad-band observations. However, since the Genesis signals are different from the usually observed VGOS bands, some modifications will be necessary when changing between standard VGOS observations and Genesis observations. So far not all VGOS stations are able to smoothly and fast change frequency setup. However, work is ongoing to simplify this and allow easy and quick changes in frequency setup.

6 WP-3: Delay Resolution, Correlation and Fringe-fitting

Operational VGOS observations are performed since 2019 with a total number of 32 channels per polarization. Each channel has a bandwidth of 32 MHz. Groups of 8 channels are allocated and distributed in four different frequency ranges in order to cover 488 MHz with the so-called bandwidth synthesis technique. The total spanned and effective bandwidth are 7680 MHz and 2612 MHz, respectively, in each polarization.

Based on these VGOS operational standards, a potential frequency setup for Genesis observations was developed, see Table 2. Out of the eight channels in Band-1, only five (black and blue) will actually observe the signals transmitted by Genesis. The other three Genesis bands are wide enough to allocate eight channels each. The channels marked in blue are channels

that also belong to today's frequency setup for operational VGOS. The total spanned and effective bandwidth are 6624 MHz and 2326 MHz, respectively.

The corresponding two-dimensional delay resolution function is presented in Figure 2. It has a higher level of ambiguities in both the group delay (τ) and differential ionosphere (TEC) dimensions than the currently used operational VGOS frequency setup. Nevertheless, it should be possible to make use of the proposed Genesis frequency setup.

Table 2 Start frequencies of a possible Genesis frequency setup with channels of 32 MHz bandwidth. The channels shown in red are outside the Genesis transmission band, i.e. will be dummy channels that will be observed but cannot be used since there will be no Genesis signal. All channels shown in black and blue are inside the Genesis transmission bands. The channels shown in blue are overlapping with channels used for the current operational VGOS observations.

Band-1	Band-2	Band-3	Band-4
f_{start}	f_{start}	f_{start}	f_{start}
3096.4	5272.4	8024.4	9368.4
3128.4	5304.4	8056.4	9400.4
3160.4	5336.4	8184.4	9432.4
3192.4	5400.4	8216.4	9528.4
3224.4	5432.4	8248.4	9624.4
3256.4	5464.4	8280.4	9656.4
3288.4	5496.4	8312.4	9688.4
3320.4	5528.4	8344.4	9720.4

Fig. 2 The two-dimensional delay resolution function using the proposed Genesis frequency setup presented in Tab. 2.

7 WP-4: Scheduling

In VLBI, scheduling software is used to plan observations and to optimize the observing plan to be able to derive parameters of interest in the final data analysis. One prerequisite for successful VLBI observations is to achieve high enough signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) since it is an important parameter influencing the accuracy of the group delays. Usually, for VGOS observations, SNR of 20 per VGOS-band is the goal.

The spectral flux density for natural radio sources at cosmological distances is basically the same for all stations on earth. However, this is not true for signals transmitted by spacecraft orbiting earth. They differ due to the near-field geometry, including transmit antenna pattern and differences in free space loss. Thus, for satellite signals, the necessary observation time T to achieve a target SNR can be formulated as:

$$T = \frac{1}{2 \cdot B \cdot n} \cdot \left(\frac{\text{SEFD}_1}{S_1} \cdot \frac{\text{SEFD}_2}{S_2} \cdot \frac{\text{SNR}}{\eta} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Here, B is the total observed bandwidth and n the number of sampled bits. The individual station sensitivities are expressed by the system equivalent flux densities (SEFD_{*i*}), and S_{*i*} are the individual spectral flux density values. SNR is the target signal-to-noise ratio, and η is a correlation efficiency factor.

The SEFD values in zenith direction for modern VGOS stations are usually on the order of 2000–3500 Jy for the frequency range 3–10 GHz. This includes average clear-sky atmospheric attenuation, which is station-dependent. Stations have higher SEFD values (i.e. less sensitivity) for observations at lower elevation angles, and this is usually expressed by station-dependent gain curves. Rain attenuation can only be modeled based on station-dependent statistical models, e.g. according to the recommendations of the International Telecommunications Union (ITU, ITU-R P.618-14, 2023).

We can do a simple "back-of-the-envelope" worst case calculation for clear sky conditions, assuming that two stations observe Genesis at an elevation of 5°. We assume that the Genesis signal flux density in nadir direction is 10 Jy and that the transmit antenna has 6 dB antenna gain pattern variation between boresight and edge of coverage. We assume that the two stations have a sensitivity of 4900 Jy for Band-1 at 5° elevation. For the smallest Genesis bandwidth (Band-1, 180 MHz),

2-bit sampling, and a SNR goal of 20, assuming correlation efficiency of $\eta = 0.75$, this means that the stations have to observe for $T = 30$ s.

Corresponding calculations and scheduling options have been included already in the scheduling software VieSched++ (Schartner and Böhm, 2019). Figure 3 depicts the common visibility of Genesis for the international VGOS network during 24 h. Several VGOS stations will be seeing Genesis simultaneously, thus allowing for scheduling many common observations.

Fig. 3 Example of Genesis visibility during 24 h for the international VGOS network. Stations are ordered from North to South, and the first station on the southern hemisphere is Fortaleza.

8 WP-5: End-to-end Simulations

Simulations of satellite observations with the VGOS network were already done several years ago by Klotek et al. (2020) using, e.g., the orbital parameters of the Lageos satellite, which also is in about 6000 km orbital height. At that time it was shown that VLBI observations of satellite signals opened up for orbit determination and geocenter determination, while determining the classical VLBI products without quality loss. Recent end-to-end simulations investigated e.g. the integration of satellite observations into standard operational VLBI observations (Schunck et al., 2024a), satellite visibility and orbit inclination (Schunck et al., 2024b), the necessary signal strength (Sert et al., 2025), and the impact of different orbit inclination on station position estimation (Wolf et al., 2025). More studies addressing further aspect of VGOS observations of Genesis are ongoing.

9 WP-6: Test Observations

The proposed Genesis frequency setup was tested first with the Onsala twin telescopes, observing natural radio sources. The observations were successful and the recorded data could be processed with the standard VGOS processing pipeline, resulting in fringes. Figure 4 presents as an example a corresponding fringe plot.

Fig. 4 Fringe plot using the proposed Genesis frequency setup with the Onsala twin telescopes observing a natural radio source.

10 WP-7: Pseudo-Random-Noise Option

Since Genesis will be sending in rather wide bandwidth, one idea was to also send a Pseudo-Random-Noise (PRN). This can be seen as an equivalent to GNSS code measurements, however with PRN codes that could cover more than 20 times wider bandwidth than, e.g., the Galileo E5a code. Thus, Genesis one-way ranging measurements could be 20 times more accurate than GNSS.

Provided that VGOS stations could be equipped with corresponding dedicated receivers, for example based on software defined radio (SDR), or that the corresponding data processing could be included

directly in the standard geodetic processing pipeline, this could open up for useful one-way ranging measurements which could potentially be used for time and frequency transfer on intercontinental distances. However, there are a number of questions that still need to be studied and answered, including the calibration of the signal chains at the VGOS stations, as well as in how far the PRN signals would impact the pure interferometric measurements.

11 Conclusions and Outlook

ESA GSET WG-3 (VLBI) is active in preparing for future VLBI observations of signals transmitted by Genesis. Many important aspects have been addressed already and advice has been provided to ESA. However, there are still open questions to solve. We are looking forward to observing Genesis within a few years time.

References

Altamimi Z, Rebischung P, Collilieux X, Métivier L, et al. (2023). ITRF2020: an augmented reference frame refining the modeling of nonlinear station motions. *Journal of Geodesy*, 97:47, doi: 10.1007/s00190-023-01738-w

Delva P, Altamimi Z, Blazquez A, Bloßfeld M, et al. (2023). GENESIS: co-location of geodetic techniques in space. *Earth, Planets and Space*, doi: 10.1186/s40623-022-01752-w

International Telecommunication Union (2023). Recommendation ITU-R P.618-14 https://www.itu.int/dms_pubrec/itu-r/rec/p/R-REC-P.618-14-202308-I!!PDF-E.pdf

Klopotek G, Hobiger T, Haas R, Otsubo T (2020). Geodetic VLBI for precise orbit determination of Earth satellites: a simulation study. *Journal of Geodesy*, 94(6), doi: 10.1007/s00190-020-01381-9

Schartner M, Böhm J (2019). VieSched++: A New VLBI Scheduling Software for Geodesy and Astrometry. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 131(1002), 084501, doi: 10.1088/1538-3873/ab1820

Schunck D, McCallum L, Molera Calvés G (2024). On the Integration of VLBI Observations to GENESIS into Global VGOS Operations. *Remote Sensing* 16(17), doi: 10.3390/rs16173234

Schunck D, McCallum L, Molera Calvés G (2024). Practical Considerations of VLBI Observations to the GENESIS Mission. In: Freymueller, J.T., Sánchez, L. (eds): *IAG Symposia*, 157, doi: 10.1007/1345_2024_245

Sert H, Schartner M, Haas R, Karatekin Ö (2025). SNR simulations for Genesis VT observations. In: Haas R, Garramone L (eds.) *Proc. EVGA2025*, (this issue)

Wolf H, Kern L M, Steinmetz S, Böhm J (2025). Impact of the Inclination of Genesis on the VLBI Terrestrial Reference Frame. In: Haas R, Garramone L (eds.) *Proc. EVGA2025*, (this issue)

Flux density monitoring at VGOS frequencies with the Onsala Twin Telescopes

A. Kinman, R. Haas, K. le Bail, J. Yang, E. Varenius

Abstract An accurate flux density catalog at the frequencies observed by the VLBI Global Observing System (VGOS) is needed to improve the scheduling of geodetic experiments. We present the setup and results of flux monitoring experiments performed with the Onsala Twin Telescopes (OTT) on a rather regular basis since June 2021. We have obtained time series of flux density in the standard bands that are used so far for the VGOS Operational (VO) sessions, i.e. 3.0–3.5 GHz, 5.2–5.7 GHz, 6.3–6.8 GHz and 10.2–10.7 GHz. The experiments targeted approximately 200 ICRF3 defining sources that are visible from Onsala. In addition to these dedicated flux monitoring experiments with the OTT, we also analyzed OTT data from several VO sessions. All data were analyzed using Common Astronomy Software Applications (CASA). Due to local radio frequency interference at Onsala, few radio sources have reliable flux density values in the lowest VO-band (3.0–3.5 GHz). Most sources are found to be variable over time. We estimate a systematic uncertainty of 5 % and a statistical uncertainty of on average 1 % for our flux density results. In the future, we are interested in expanding the sample size, increasing baseline sensitivity and running collaboration observations with other facilities.

Keywords flux density, VGOS, geodetic VLBI, active galactic nuclei

Alva Kinman¹ · Rüdiger Haas¹ · Karine le Bail¹ · Jun Yang¹ · Eskil Varenius²

(1) Chalmers University of Technology, Onsala Space Observatory, Observatorievägen 90, Onsala, 439 92 Sweden

(2) on leave from Chalmers University of Technology, Onsala Space Observatory, Observatorievägen 90, Onsala, 439 92 Sweden

1 Introduction

The VLBI Global Observing System (VGOS) has been operational since 2020. With small, fast antennas and a large bandwidth, VGOS aims to improve the accuracy of geodetic parameters compared to the legacy system. The goal is to provide a station position accuracy of 1 mm (Petrachenko et al., 2012).

Reaching this goal requires an increased number of scans per experiment. A large number of scans allows better estimates of tropospheric delays and increases the precision of geodetic parameters. To optimize the use of observing time, the flux densities of the radio sources need to be known. The scan duration can then be adapted to each source such that a sufficient, but not excessive, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is reached.

Schartner et al. (2025) recently explored a SNR-based scheduling approach for VGOS. Flux densities were firstly predicted by inter-/extrapolation based on flux catalogs at S- and X-bands, and secondly derived from correlation amplitudes of VGOS-Operations (VO) sessions. Though their scheduling method provided promising results by increasing the number of scans compared to standard VGOS scheduling, there were discrepancies between predicted and measured SNRs. This indicates that more accurate flux density models are still needed. In particular, flux densities for variable sources need to be updated regularly.

With the aim of providing accurate and up-to-date flux densities for International Celestial Reference System (ICRF3) sources, we have devised a flux monitoring program using the Onsala Twin Telescopes (OTT). The telescopes are used to measure the flux density of geodetic sources in the frequency bands currently used for VGOS operations, i.e. 3.0–3.5 GHz, 5.2–5.7 GHz, 6.3–6.8 GHz and 10.2–10.7 GHz. In this

proceedings paper, we describe the program. Section 2 describes the experimental setup and data analysis. Section 3 presents a first look at the results, while Section 4 presents the conclusions and outlook.

2 Observations and data analysis

We have derived flux densities from measurements with the Onsala Twin Telescopes (OTT). The telescopes have a diameter of 13.2 m and are located 75 m apart at Onsala Space Observatory (OSO). Two types of experiments have been analyzed: 1) dedicated flux monitoring experiments scheduled and observed locally at OSO, and 2) VGOS-Operational (VO) sessions via the International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS, Nothnagel et al., 2017), available through the Crustal Dynamics Data Information Systems (CDDIS)¹ database.

The standard VGOS frequency setup used for the experiments consists of four bands centered at 3.2, 5.5, 6.5 and 10.4 GHz. Each band in turn contains eight 32 MHz sub-bands. For the complete setup, see e.g. Varenus et al. (2022).

2.1 Flux monitoring experiments

The first flux monitoring experiments were scheduled in 2021 and involved only seven geodetic sources. These experiments are described in Varenus et al. (2022). The second round of flux monitoring experiments were observed starting in January 2023, and the results reported in this paper extend to April 2025. The experiments were scheduled using the software VieSched++ (Schartner & Böhm, 2019). The experiments initially had a duration of 20 hours and targeted all the defining sources that are visible from Onsala. This resulted in approximately 200 observed sources per experiment. In addition, the three flux calibrators 3C147, 3C286 and 3C295 were observed. Each source was observed in three scans, each with a duration of one minute.

After analysis of the first one and a half years of experiments, it was determined that the weaker sources needed longer scan durations in order for their fluxes to be measured reliably. From November 2024, the weaker sources were observed with a scan duration of

¹ <https://cddis.nasa.gov/archive/vlbi/ivsdata/swin/>

two minutes. The same change was applied for the flux calibrators. To accommodate the extra observing time without decreasing the number of sources, the experiment duration was increased to 26 hours.

The experiments were scheduled approximately once a month. Longer gaps in the time series exist due to technical issues with the telescopes and lack of available storage space.

As of April 2025, 21 full-length (20–26 h) flux-monitoring experiments have been performed and analyzed, in addition to 49 of the short experiments presented in Varenus et al. (2022).

2.2 VGOS-operational experiments

Several VGOS-operational (VO) experiments have been analysed as well. Currently, the following VO sessions have contributed to the flux density catalog: vo3299, vo4108, vo4115, vo4248, vo4269, vo4311, vo4339, vo4346, vo5029, vo5043. To obtain accurate fluxes, a flux calibration scan is needed. Such scans are now regularly added locally at Onsala to the end of each VO session. The calibration scans consist of 120 seconds observation of at least one of the calibrator sources used for the flux monitoring experiments.

Correlated VO data for the OTT baseline was obtained from CDDIS. The number of scans and the scan duration both differ between sources. Not all sources observed in VO sessions are defining sources of ICRF3, which means that our catalog is extended by the addition of the VO sources.

2.3 Correlation and calibration

The flux monitoring experiments were correlated at OSO using the software correlator DiFX (Deller et al., 2007). The OTT record orthogonal linear polarizations, here denoted X and Y, and all four correlation products XX, XY, YX and YY were produced. The experiments were then processed using the software Common Astronomy Software Applications (CASA, The CASA Team et al., 2022) together with VLBI tools developed by JIVE². The correlated data were converted from DiFX format to FITSIDI format. Then, the *append_tsys* tool was used to import system temperature values from

² <https://github.com/jive-vlbi/casa-vlbi>

the experiment into the FITSIDI file. The system temperature values were read from the experiment log and converted to antab file format. This antab file also included a fixed gain for each telescope.

In CASA, a pipeline was created to flag outliers and perform the necessary calibration steps. The CASA pipeline is a development of the pipeline used by Varenus et al. (2022). The first step was to remove the phase calibration signal. Since the phase calibration systems of the OTT are fed by the same hydrogen maser, the signals are highly correlated and visible as spikes in the cross-correlation data. We also removed the edge channels of each sub-band, to avoid impact from edge-channel noise on the subsequent bandpass normalization. After that, amplitude calibration was performed using system temperature and gain values. Furthermore, autocorrelation-corrections, fringe fitting and bandpass calibration was performed. In the flux monitoring experiments, bandpass and fringe fitting solutions were calculated from the first scan of 3C286 and then applied to the whole data set. In the VO experiments, OJ287 or 0059+581 were used instead. Additionally, the task *rflag* was used to remove outliers caused by unwanted electromagnetic radiation (UER).

After all calibration steps were performed, the data was averaged over time and channel within each sub-band. The amplitudes of the XX, XY, YX and YY correlation products were then averaged over all scans of the same source. A pseudo-Stokes I value was calculated:

$$I = \frac{XX + YY}{2}. \quad (1)$$

Note that no parallactic angle correction was performed due to the short baseline.

2.4 Absolute flux density calibration

As a final step we performed additional flux density calibration based on the three flux calibration sources. The expected flux density of each calibration source at each sub-band was obtained from the flux models presented in Perley & Butler (2017). The expected flux density was divided by the measured flux density to obtain a scale factor. The average scale factor among the three calibration sources was calculated and used to correct the flux density of all sources. The scale factor was calculated separately for each experiment, to account

for instrumental variation over time. The scale factor also corrects systematic gain differences between sub-bands, as seen in Figure 1.

2.5 Filtering and averaging

Due to the short baseline, the data contains strong UER. While some of the affected data can be removed in the calibration stage, broadband interfering signals remain. The 3.2 GHz band is particularly affected. To mitigate this, the data was filtered based on cross-polarization. The cross-polarization products, XY and YX, are expected to be close to zero since most geodetic sources are unpolarized. If they are too large, this indicates the presence of polarized UER. Thus, sub-bands that had a XY or YX polarization of more than 15 % of the XX or YY polarization were discarded. The limit of 15 % was chosen empirically (in accordance with Varenus et al., 2022) to get robust results.

Finally, the sub-bands making up each VGOS band were averaged together. As an additional outlier filtration step, any sub-band that deviated more than a factor 2 from the median in the band was also discarded.

3 Results

We have obtained light curves with at least five epochs for 212 sources. A few selected light curves are presented in Figure 2. The plot shows flux density in all available VGOS bands as a function of time. The triangular markers represent dedicated flux monitoring experiments, while the outlined circles represent VO sessions. The flux measurements from VO sessions generally agree with the dedicated flux monitoring measurements for sources where both are available. This indicates that geodetic sessions can be used as a complement to dedicated flux monitoring sessions.

We note a rich variety of behavior among the sources. While source 0312+100 is stable during the measurement period, the other sources in Figure 2 vary significantly in flux over time. There is also spectral variation among the sources. The spectrum of a synchrotron source is typically proportional to $\nu^{-\alpha}$, where ν is the frequency and α the spectral index. The sample contains sources with both positive and negative spectral index. There are also examples of sources changing spectral index over time, seen in the

Fig. 1 The figure shows the effect of the scale factor in reducing systematic errors between sub-bands, exemplified by experiment fm5087. Top: 3C147, one of the flux calibrators used to determine scale factors. The dashed line shows the flux model from Perley & Butler (2017). Bottom: 0133+476, a bright source which was not used for calibration. The scaling clearly reduces the flux density scatter within each VGOS band.

bottom left of Figure 2. The complete flux catalog will be made available in a later publication.

We note that the majority of the sources are variable, which highlights the need for a continuously updated flux catalog. By comparing the lowest to the highest recorded flux in Band 4 (including only the sources that have at least five data points), we find that 82 % have varied by more than 20 % during the monitoring period. Furthermore, 39 % of sources have varied by more than 50 %.

As mentioned in Section 2.5, the 3.2 GHz band is heavily affected by UER. The cross-polarization filter criterion removes most of the data points in this band, leading to only a small subset of sources having a light curve at 3.2 GHz.

The error bars shown in Figure 2 were obtained in two steps. The standard error of the flux density in each band was obtained as the standard deviation of the included sub-bands divided by \sqrt{N} , where N is the

number of sub-bands. On average, the standard error corresponds to 1% of the flux density. Since these error bars fail to account for systematic errors such as gain curve uncertainty and UER, an additional 5 % error was added in quadrature.

To verify that the errors are reasonable, we calculated the reduced χ^2 value for a few sources which appear stable over time, similarly to Varenius et al. (2022). If the flux density of these sources is modeled as being constant in time, the reduced χ^2 value is below 1 for all bands (see Table 1). The size of the error thus appears to be reasonable or slightly overestimated.

Table 1 Reduced χ^2 values for stable non-calibrator sources

Source	Band 1	Band 2	Band 3	Band 4
O312+100	0.08	0.18	0.23	0.11
O552+398	0.19	0.62	0.22	0.60
M84	0.17	0.90	0.86	-

4 Conclusions and outlook

We have obtained light curves at the current operationally used VGOS frequencies for 212 geodetic sources. We plan to publish the dataset in its entirety in the near future. The monitoring is planned to continue with one experiment per month. In addition to flux monitoring experiments, we have also demonstrated the possibility of using data from geodetic experiments to calculate precise flux densities.

The produced flux catalog could be used to improve VGOS scheduling by optimizing the integration time such that the SNR goals are reached. The data could also be of interest for astronomy. The light curves allow tracking of source flux density and spectral index over time, which could provide valuable insights into the physical properties of the studied active galactic nuclei (e.g. Singh et al. 2020).

In order to use this data for VGOS scheduling, flux models for longer baselines are needed. There is also a need to expand the monitored source catalog to eventually cover all sources that are routinely observed by VGOS. Thus, more telescopes need to be involved. As a first step, observations with other twin telescopes would be beneficial to increase the number of sources and densify the light curves.

Fig. 2 Example light curves from the flux monitoring program. Triangles represent results from dedicated flux monitoring experiments and circles from VO experiments. The four colors represent VGOS band 1 (3.2 GHz), 2 (5.5 GHz), 3 (6.6 GHz) and 4 (10.4 GHz). The flux density of 0312+100 (top right) is relatively stable over the measurement period, while the other shown sources are more variable. Note the differences in spectral index, both between sources (compare 0613+570, 0312+100 and 2059+034) and between observations of the same source (compare 0322+222 in early 2024 and early 2025).

References

- The CASA team, Bean, B., Bhatnagar, S. (2022) CASA, the Common Astronomy Software Applications for Radio Astronomy *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, Vol 134, 1041 doi: 10.1088/1538-3873/ac9642
- Deller, A. T., Tingay, S. J., Bailes, M., West, C (2007) DiFX: A Software Correlator for Very Long Baseline Interferometry Using Multiprocessor Computing Environments. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, Vol 119, 853, pp. 318-336 doi: 10.1086/513572
- Nothnagel, A., Artz, T., Behrend, D., Malkin, Z. (2017) International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry – Delivering high-quality products and embarking on observations of the next generation. *Journal of Geodesy*, Vol. 91(7), pp. 711-721 doi: DOI 10.1007/s00190-016-0950-5
- Perley, R. A., Butler, B. J. (2017) An Accurate Flux Density Scale from 50 MHz to 50 GHz. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 230, 1, id. 7 doi: 10.3847/1538-4365/aa6df9.
- Petrachenko, W.T., Niell, A.E., Corey, B.E., (2012) VLBI2010: Next Generation VLBI System for Geodesy and Astrometry. *Geodesy for Planet Earth. International Association of Geodesy Symposia*, 136 doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-20338-1-125.
- Schartner, M., Böhm, J. (2019) VieSched++: A New VLBI Scheduling Software for Geodesy and Astrometry *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 131, 102, pp. 084501, doi: 10.1088/1538-3873/ab1820.
- Schartner, M., Petrachenko, B., Titus, M. et al. (2025) Optimizing VGOS observations using an SNR-based scheduling approach. *Earth Planets Space*, 1, 77, 61, doi: 10.1186/s40623-025-02158-0.
- Singh, K. K., Meintjes, P. J. (2020) Characterization of variability in blazar light curves. *Astronomische Nachrichten*, Vol. 341, 713, pp. 713-725 doi: 10.1002/asna.202013731
- Varenus, E., Maio, F., Le Bail, K., Haas, R. (2022) Broad band flux-density monitoring of radio sources with the Onsala twin telescopes. *Experimental Astronomy*, 54, 1, p. 137-155, doi: 10.1007/s10686-022-09867-4.

Effective Frequencies and Ionosphere Calibration of Legacy S/X Data

A. Nothnagel, H. Krásná, P. Urban

Abstract Over the past, the computation of ionosphere calibrations for legacy S/X band observations and especially the derivation of effective frequencies has undergone various changes. While trying to implement the respective processes in our own software *VieVS* we encountered differences between our on-the-fly computations and the values stored in *vgosDB* files. We found that in the transition from native Mark3 databases to *vgosDB* files in a non-negligible number of sessions, ionospheric corrections have not been migrated with state of the art. IVS Analysis Centers are being made aware that the entries for ionosphere calibrations in *vgosDB* files are inconsistent over the years as may be the submissions of individual IVS Analysis Centers. A recommendation is given to recompute effective frequencies and ionosphere calibrations always with up to date formulations.

Keywords VLBI level-2 data analysis, ionospheric corrections, effective frequencies

1 Motivation

At the Vienna VLBI Analysis Center, we started a project to resolve ambiguities and compute ionosphere calibrations for legacy S/X observations as part of the Vienna VLBI and Satellite Software *VieVS* to become independent of the *Solve/nuSolve* software. In the process of reconstructing the results

Axel Nothnagel¹ · Hana Krásná¹ · Peter Urban¹
(1) TU Wien, Department of Geodesy and Geoinformation, Wiedner Hauptstrasse 8, AT-1040 Vienna, Austria

stored in *vgosDB* files, we encountered unexplainable differences and investigated their origin.

2 Background

For a start, we should look at the historical developments of bandwidth synthesis frequency sub-band/channel allocations of legacy S/X systems. These were always driven by the recording capabilities of the respective era. Here, we only discuss X band because there is a peculiar development step which is not present in S band. Otherwise, S band follows the same ideas of bandwidth synthesis. Regularly, the nominal frequency of a channel/sub-band is reported together with attributing lower and/or upper sideband (LSB/USB) of a certain bandwidth which may be 4, 8, or (in VGOS) even 32 MHz. The start is marked by the Mark III frequency setup of the late 1970ies driven by the fact that the first video tape recorders had 14 tracks in forward and 14 in reverse tape rotations. This led to the selection of 6 S band and 8 X band channels with the respective parallel backend electronics such as 14 baseband (video) converters. Initially each sub-band had 2 MHz bandwidth spanning 360 MHz (Fig. 1).

Skipping a few development stages and jumping to the late tape recordings and early magnetic disk recordings such as Mark V and its successors, another two recording tracks became available resulting in 16 track recording capacity. Since most backend terminals had only 14 baseband converters, but with lower sideband (LSB) and upper sideband (USB) outputs, the extra two tracks were used for LSB recordings. For statistical reasons, the two outer frequency sub-bands were

Fig. 1 Schematic frequency allocations in bandwidth synthesis mode of early geodetic VLBI sessions using Mark III tape recorders with 2 MHz channel bandwidth and 360 MHz spanned bandwidth (not to scale). Vertical arrows indicate the respective reference frequencies.

chosen to be augmented by an LSB channel each. In the example in Fig. 2, the 8182.99 and 8862.99 MHz reference frequencies have LSB channels in addition to the USB channels.

Fig. 2 Schematic frequency allocations in bandwidth synthesis mode of early geodetic VLBI sessions using Mark III tape recorders or disk drives with 2 MHz channel bandwidth and 680 MHz spanned bandwidth (not to scale).

In the latest configuration, the sub-band channels are 8 MHz wide and nominally span 720 MHz (Fig 3).

Fig. 3 Schematic frequency allocations in bandwidth synthesis mode of modern geodetic VLBI sessions with 8 MHz channel bandwidth and 720 MHz spanned bandwidth (not to scale).

Turning to ionospheric delay calibration, the correction $\Delta \tau_{ion}^X$ for the X band observable is computed (Herring, 1983; Alizadeh et al., 2013) by

$$\Delta \tau_{ion}^X = (\tau_S - \tau_X) \cdot \frac{v_S^2}{v_S^2 - v_X^2} \quad (1)$$

where τ_S and τ_X are the measured multiband group delays and v_S and v_X the observed frequencies at S band and X band, respectively.

Since the observed frequency of each band (S or X) actually results from a combination of several channel/sub-band frequencies through bandwidth synthesis, these frequencies v_{gr} (for S or X band) need to be computed as effective frequencies which are the weighted mean over all channels/sub-bands N

$$v_{gr} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i (v_i - v_0)^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i (v_i - v_0) \right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i (v_i - v_0) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\rho_i}{v_i} - \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i \frac{v_i - v_0}{v_i}}} \quad (2)$$

ρ_i are the weights of individual channels/sub-bands. These can be computed from the number of correlated bits, from SNR, or from the fringe amplitude which is readily available in standard vgosDB files. v_0 is the reference frequency of the bandwidth synthesis setup, e.g., channel/sub-band #1 (Herring 1983; Petrov 2001 mod.).

In the course of software developments, the way, in which the effective frequencies were computed, had changed a few times to accommodate state-of-the-art knowledge. Regularly, the nominal (monochromatic reference) frequency of a channel/sub-band is reported together with its sideband (LSB/USB) and its bandwidth (e.g., 8512.99 MHz, 8 MHz USB). The effective frequency of a single channel then lies in the middle of this sub-band. For this reason the computation of the channel frequency needs to add half of the channel bandwidth to the nominal frequency for USB channels and to subtract half for LSB channels. In the era of 2 MHz channel bandwidths, this was ignored because the bandwidth was considered too small for further refinement. With the fourfold increase in channel bandwidth, the mean of the sub-band certainly needs to be taken into account. For computing the mean sub-band frequency, (sample rate)/4 can be applied if the channel bandwidth is not readily available. This logic was only introduced in 2015.

A complication now arises from the fact that at X band the two outer sub-bands of the nominal eight sub-bands are in fact made up of a lower and an upper sideband (LSB/USB) channel doubling the effective border sub-bands resulting in a total of ten channels for eight sub-bands. In the fringe fitting process the

data of the outer channels are concatenated. In this case the effective sub-band frequency is the nominal channel frequency. No adding or subtracting half the channel bandwidth is required.

As a result of the concatenation of LSB/USB channels, the fringe amplitude does not increase but the SNR of the sub-bands does (through the extended number of samples). If everything was normal during observations, channel amplitudes are more or less constant for all channels including those of the LSB channels. This is the reason why *fourfit* fringe plots show similar amplitudes for the eight sub-bands reported.

The computation of the effective frequencies has to take care that channels/sub-bands, which have not produced proper fringes or which have an inappropriate number of correlated samples, are treated properly, i.e., are excluded.

In vgosDB files for X band, we find 'ChanAmpPhase' with the dimension (2×8) where the first line contains the amplitude $[0, 1]$ and the second line the phase $[-180, 180]$. Through this, vgosDB files contain the amplitudes of all sub-bands with a structure based on reference frequencies. In addition, the entry "Observables.ChanInfo_bX.NumSamples" ('# of samples by sideband and channel') also has the dimension (2×8) . However, until 2018 here the first line contains the LSB number of samples and the second line the USB number of samples. Since we only have two sub-bands with LSB data, only elements (1,1) and (1,8) contain non-zero values in the first line while all others are zero. The second line should be fully populated with non-zeros unless we encountered a channel drop-out.

For sessions after 2018, the order of LSB/USB lines was swapped to first line USB and second line LSB. This was caused by the usage of the program vgosDbMake which from then onward has been generating vgosDB files from the correlator output directly (Bolotin, priv. com.)

In the latest stage of developments, the weight of each sub-band i is then computed from

$$\rho_i = (N_{i-LSB} + N_{i-USB}) * Amp_i \quad (3)$$

where N_{i-LSB} and N_{i-USB} are the number of samples in LSB and USB, respectively. Amp_i is the amplitude of each of the sub-bands.

3 Historical developments

The algorithm for evaluating the effective frequencies evolved over time and took into account the knowledge available at that time. Initially, only the reference frequencies of the sub-bands as reported in the fringe files and available in the databases were used. Later on, when sub-band bandwidths became wider, the center frequencies of the sub-bands were computed by adding an offset equal to a half of the bandwidth of the sub-bands. When the recording system turned from 14 to 16 channels, LSB handling was added to the standard USB logic, in that the offset was added for USB and subtracted for LSB (Sergei Bolotin, priv. comm.).

A change in model, which is well documented with exact time stamps, happened on Sep 3, 2015, with a subsequent correction on April 27, 2017, and affected all sessions analyzed in that period. On Sep 3, 2015, for the first time, the width of the channels was taken into account as described above. Here, the center frequency computations of the outer X band sub-bands did not take care of a possibly missing channel of the two pairs. This was corrected on April 27, 2017.

At some time, Eq. 3 had been divided by the sampling rate (see nuSolve code in src/SgLib/SgVlbiSessionUtilities.cpp). However, this division is only a scaling as long as the sampling rate is kept consistent on all baselines.

The results of the computations of the effective frequencies and of the ionospheric calibrations had been stored in the Mk3-style databases and NGS card files at time of generation in the formulation of that time. Later on they were carried over to vgosDB files by straight data conversion. To our knowledge, the utility which converted the database re-calculated the effective frequencies with the latest models and stored the new values in vgosDB files, but it did not store the updated ionospheric calibration in the vgosDB files. Any sessions, for which only vgosDB databases have been produced, i.e., those after 2022.0 should be up-to-date (Sergei Bolotin, priv. comm.).

In contrast to the handling of the ionospheric corrections in databases, Solve and nuSolve never, or at least in the last 20 years, used the database/vgosDB entries but computed the effective frequencies and the ionospheric calibrations on the fly, always with the latest model as described above.

4 Consequences

While all computations and re-computations with Solve/nuSolve, except 2015 to 2017, have always been state of the art, all other geodetic VLBI level-2 data analysis software, which relied on database entries, are inconsistent. As an example, we compared the entries in the vgosDB files for session 17NOV29XB with the ionospheric calibrations computed with the state of the art model (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Differences of ionospheric calibrations between vgosDB entries w.r.t. re-computed ones with Eq. 3 for session 17NOV29XB. Red points are of baseline KASHIMA32-HOBART26.

We see differences in distinct bands. These belong to individual baselines. Red points are of baseline KASHIMA32-HOBART26 where only four sub-bands produced valid data. At this stage of the analysis, we expected that most of these biases should be absorbed in the estimation of station clock offsets but variability at the few tens of picosecond level will definitely produce unwanted noise. This was first tested by computing triangle closures of the ioncal differences between vgosDB entries and state-of-the-art computations. As can be seen in Fig. 5, the differences in most triangles close to single digit picosecond values.

In the next step, we compared the results of the geodetic estimates applying the vgosDB ionospheric correction values and the values computed with the state-of-the-art logic. We find that our expectations concerning the absorption in the clock offsets was largely confirmed. They are on the order of tens of picoseconds (Fig. 6). However, in addition to that we

Fig. 5 Triangle delay closures for session 17NOV29XB.

find that the station positions are also affected on the order of up to 0.8 mm (Fig. 7).

The findings based on session 17NOV29XB have been confirmed by the same analysis of all CONT17 sessions. The results all have a similar magnitude.

5 Conclusions and recommendations

We discovered that ionospheric calibrations in vgosDB files of sessions submitted before about 2022.0 do not contain state-of-the-art ionospheric corrections. There is no exact date since there was a period when the analysis center submitting the sessions to the IVS Data Centers did phase in the generation of vgosDB files. So, 2022.0 is only a rough guess. The impact in the clock offsets is as big as 50 ps but coordinates change up to 0.8 mm which is significant.

For this reason, we recommend that all IVS databases of legacy S/X sessions before 2023.0 be reprocessed and the official vgosDB files be replaced in the IVS archives. Alternatively, all software packages should follow the Solve/nuSolve example of always computing the effective frequencies and ionospheric corrections on the fly.

Fig. 6 Differences of clock parameter estimates of session 17NOV29XB (ionosphere calibrations with state-of-the-art computations minus vgosDB entries).

Fig. 7 Differences of station position estimates of session 17NOV29XB (ionosphere calibrations with vgosDB entries minus state-of-the-art computations).

References

AFB, Massachusetts 01731, USA, AFGL-TR-84-0182.

- Alizadeh, M. M., Wijaya, D. D., Hobiger, T., Weber, R., Schuh, H. (2013) Atmospheric Effects in Space Geodesy. *Springer Berlin Heidelberg*, 35-71, doi: 0.1007/978-3-642-36932-2-2.
- Petrov (2001) Memo: Ionosphere contribution in VLBI. <http://astrogeo.org/petrov/papers/iono.ps.gz>.
- Herring (1983) Precision and accuracy of intercontinental distance determinations using radio interferometry. *Hanscom*

VLBI-scale of the ITRF2020-u2023

K. Le Bail, M. Ishigaki, T. Nilsson, R. Haas

Abstract Zuheir Altamimi officially introduced the ITRF2020-u2023 at the AGU24 conference in Washington DC on Monday, 9 December 2024. This marked the first update of ITRF2020, which showcases a novel approach to annual updates of the International Terrestrial Reference Frames (ITRF) without requiring global reprocessing from the four combination centers of space-geodetic technique that contribute to ITRF. The update integrates the original ITRF2020 combined solution, which includes data up to December 2020, with an additional three years of observations (January 2021 to December 2023) for the inter-technique combination. For VLBI specifically, the IVS Combination Center supplied the ITRS Center with three years of new data, derived from the combined contributions of 12 IVS Analysis Centers using seven different analysis packages. This involved the analysis of nearly 700 sessions. In particular, the three years of data were analyzed independently by the respective Analysis Centers, separate from the longer-term contribution to the ITRF2020, which spans 1979 to December 2021. Regarding the VLBI scale in the IVS contribution to ITRF2020-u2023, the scale drift exhibited distinct behavior over different periods. The drift from 2013.75 to 2021.00 differs significantly from the drift observed between 2021.00 and 2024.00. Although modeling the uplift of NYALES20 and accounting for station

events improved the positive drift during the earlier period, it had no effect on the drift observed over the past three years. To understand these differences, the contribution of the IVS Combination Center to ITRF2020-u2023 was carefully compared with the initial contribution of ITRF2020. The primary objective of this study was to assess the strengths and limitations of this innovative approach to updating the ITRF, as well as to develop a strategy to update uniformly within all IVS Analysis Centers and the IVS Combination Center.

Keywords VLBI scale, ITRF2020 updates

1 Introduction

In 2021, the ITRS Center, responsible for the maintenance of the International Terrestrial Reference System (ITRS) and its realization, the International Terrestrial Reference Frame (ITRF), reported a significant change in the temporal behavior of the VLBI scale starting in 2013.75 (Altamimi et al., 2023).

To address this issue, the IVS established a Task Force tasked with identifying the cause of this enigmatic change in behavior on the scale. The Task Force group concluded that most of the drift observed on the ITRF2020 VLBI scale after 2013.75 could be attributed to a combination of factors, including different deformation modeling approaches and the various changes in VLBI equipment at several stations within the IVS network. However, a definitive explanation for the drift remained elusive. The Task Force group was transitioned to the IVS Working Group 9 (IVS WG9) in Oc-

Karine Le Bail¹ · Masafumi Ishigaki² · Tobias Nilsson^{3,1} · Rüdiger Haas¹

(1) Chalmers University of Technology, Onsala Space Observatory, Observatorievägen 90, Onsala, 439 92 Sweden

(2) Geodetic Department, Geospatial Information Authority of Japan, Kitasato 1, Tsukuba, Ibaraki, 305-0811, Japan

(3) Lantmäteriet – The Swedish mapping, cadastral and land registration authority, Lantmäterigatan 2 C, Gävle, SE-802 64, Sweden

tober 2024, and the search for a complete explanation is still ongoing.

In parallel, the ITRS Center team is now willing to submit more frequent solutions of the realization of the ITRF in the form of updates of a few years at the time. The first update, ITRF2020-u2023, was submitted in 2024 and is an extension of the initial ITRF2020 by three more years for the four space-geodetic techniques. Another update, ITRF2020-u2024, adding one year of observations, is currently in preparation. In this work, we examine the VLBI ITRF2020-u2023 update and evaluate whether a scale drift persists.

This study focuses on the IVS contribution (IVS contributions to ITRF2020 and its update ITRF2020-u2023) presented in Section 2. We describe the modifications we bring to discontinuity files used by the CATREF software in Section 3, incorporating the findings of the IVS Task Force and the IVS WG9 (Le Bail et al., 2023, Ishigaki et al., 2024), paying particular attention to the cases of the VLBI station NYALES20 and four other stations in the northern hemisphere legacy S/X network. The results are presented in Section 4.

2 Method

We used SINEX files from the IVS combined contributions to ITRF realizations from the IVS Combination Center (Hellmers et al., 2022, Bachmann et al., 2025). The ITRF2020 contained data from 1979.0 to 2021.0. Its update, ITRF2020-u2023, comprises data from 2021.0 to 2024.0.

To compute the time series of scale factors, we followed the strategy used by the ITRS Center to generate ITRF2020 and its update, using the CATREF software (Altamimi et al., 2023). Our approach focuses on a single-technique solution by limiting the combination process to the IVS combined solution. Using CATREF, we applied minimal constraints based on the SINEX files from the IVS contributions and performed the combination by estimating station positions and velocities, seasonal components, and post-seismic deformation models where necessary. This process yielded an intrinsic IVS VLBI solution. For each VLBI session-wise solution, we then estimated the seven transformation parameters relative to this intrinsic IVS VLBI solution, using the terrestrial reference frame defined by

the core network stations (i.e., those included in the datum) of the session. Among these parameters, the scale factor is one of the key quantities derived.

For each of the published ITRF, a VLBI station position and velocity discontinuity files is given in a SINEX format. In this work, we used the discontinuity files from both ITRF2020 and ITRF2020-u2023. These were then modified to incorporate additional discontinuities identified during our investigations (see Section 3). We then studied the scale factor time series and in particular the scale drifts over the period 2013.75–2021.00 and 2021.00–2024.00 of the series.

3 Station events

In this section, we describe how we identified and extracted station events that we suspect may impact the VLBI scale.

3.1 VLBI station NYALES20 in Svalbard, Norway

Numerous studies have highlighted the impact of present-day ice melting on geodetic sites worldwide. For example, Kierulf et al. (2022) examined Ny-Ålesund and suggested modeling the vertical component of NYALES20 using a piecewise linear model.

Since the VLBI antenna NYALES20 was collocated with several GNSS stations at the geodetic site in Ny-Ålesund, we investigated how GNSS was modeled in the ITRF2020 realization. The collocated GNSS station NYA1 was modeled with two different velocities, whereas the VLBI station NYALES20 was given a single constant velocity over the entire observation period. These two velocity changes correspond to the epochs day of year 186 in 2004 and day of year 233 in 2016.

Table 1 Significant repairs in the northern hemisphere legacy S/X network

TSUKUB32	04/1999	Rail replacement (height reference point changed by +43.7 mm)
	01/05/2013	Antenna base repair (gaps that could cause subsidence of the antenna)
MATERA	01/01/2004	Abnormal rail movement observed
	15/09/2015	Complete rail replacement
WETTZELL	01/09/2010	Repair of the elevation bearings
ZELENCHK	22/04/2013	Partial antenna sub reflector replacement
	07/07/2020	Heavy repairs (rail track and foundation, height ref. changed by 2 to 3 mm)

3.2 Significant repairs in the northern hemisphere legacy S/X network

4 Results

We calculated scale factor time series with CATREF using the original contribution of the IVS Combination Center's contribution to ITRF2020 as well as the IVS contribution to ITRF2020-u2023, covering the period 1979 to the end of 2023. Each of the five cases listed below corresponds to the use of various sets of discontinuities (see Section 2) in the CATREF combination process:

1. Case 1: Original – The discontinuity file as well as the datum are the same as for the ITRF2020.
2. Case 2: Original+Ny2 – We introduce the same two discontinuities found for NYA1 in ITRF2020 for NYALES20 in the ITRF2020 discontinuity file and remove NYALES20 from the datum definition.
3. Case 3: Original+Ny2+Oth7 – In addition to adding the two discontinuities for NYALES20, we also introduce the seven discontinuities mentioned in Section 3.2 in the discontinuity file of ITRF2020.
4. Case 4: u2023 – Instead of the ITRF2020 discontinuity file, we use the discontinuity file of ITRF2020-u2023.
5. Case 5: u2023+Oth7 – We introduce the seven discontinuities mentioned in Section 3.2 in the discontinuity file of ITRF2020-u2023.

Fig. 1 Scale factor time series over the time span 1979.0–2024.0. Cumul ITRF2020 and ITRF2020-u2023. CATREF analysis using (from top to bottom) the original ITRF2020 discontinuity list (case 1), the original ITRF2020 discontinuity list plus two discontinuities added for NYALES20 as described in Section 3.1 (case 2), and the original ITRF2020 discontinuity list plus two discontinuities added for NYALES20 and seven discontinuities as determined in Section 3.2 (case 3).

Table 2 gives the numerical values of the drifts of the scale factor time series over the period 2013.75–2021.00 and 2021.00–2024.00 for each of these five cases, while Figures 1 and 2 show the plots of the scale factor time series, along with the estimated drift for each period (2013.75–2021.00 in red and 2021.00–2024.00 in green).

The first three cases are based on the use of the ITRF2020 discontinuity file. The scale drift observed between 2013.75 and 2021.00 is mitigated by modeling the positions of NYALES20 as equivalent to the GNSS station NYA1: the scale drift decreases from 0.567 ± 0.062 mm/yr (case 1) to 0.287 ± 0.060 mm/yr (case 2). Accounting for station events in four major structures of the legacy S/X network further contributes to stabi-

Table 2 Drifts of the scale factor time series.

Case	Discontinuity file	Added station events	Drift (mm/yr)	
			2013.75-2021.00	2021.00-2024.00
1-Original	ITRF2020	None	0.567+/-0.062	-0.646+/-0.232
2-Original+Ny2	ITRF2020	NYALES20 (2)	0.287+/-0.060	-0.693+/-0.232
3-Original+Ny2+Oth7	ITRF2020	NYALES20 (2) + 4 STAT (7)	0.153+/-0.060	-0.689+/-0.234
4-u2023	ITRF2020-u2023	None	0.283+/-0.060	0.634+/-0.236
5-u2023+Oth7	ITRF2020-u2023	4 STAT (7)	0.149+/-0.060	0.613+/-0.234

Fig. 2 Scale factor time series over the time span 1979.0–2024.0, including ITRF2020 and ITRF2020-u2023. Top: CATREF analysis using the ITRF2020-u2023 discontinuity list (case 4). Bottom: CATREF analysis using the ITRF2020-u2023 discontinuity list and seven discontinuities as determined in Section 3.2 (case 5).

lizing the scale and reduces the scale drift to 0.153 ± 0.060 mm/yr (case 3).

Considering the newly published discontinuity file of the ITRF2020-u2023, shows a scale drift over the period 2013.75–2021.00 comparable to case 2 which used the discontinuity file of the ITRF2020 and an additional model of NYALES20 (case 4). When comparing the two discontinuity files, a few differences are noticeable. There are new stations and earthquakes (for example, ZELENCHK - day of year 037 in 2023; KP-VLBA - day of year 094 in 2010; FD-VLBA and OV-VLBA - day of year 267 in 2020), a discontinuity for non-linearity on day of year 001 of 2021 for the station HART15M, and for the station NYALES20, two additional discontinuities for non-linearity modeled as for NYA1 (GNSS). The latest addition to the disconti-

nuity file corresponds to case 2 of this study. It shows that beginning with ITRF2020-u2023, the ITRS Center team considered the non-linear motion of stations at the Ny-Ålesund site and confirmed the impact of NYALES20 in the VLBI scale behavior between 2013.75 and 2021.00. This was initially suggested by Le Bail et al. (2022) and has recently been confirmed by Kern et al. (2025). When adding the seven station events mentioned in Section 3.2, the scale drift decreases to 0.149 ± 0.060 mm/yr (case 5).

However, the drift of the VLBI scale after 2021.00 contradicts the behavior observed between 2013.75 and 2021.00 in all cases. Using the ITRF2020 discontinuity file (cases 1 to 3) gave a negative scale drift of -0.670 ± 0.232 mm/yr, while using the ITRF2020-u2023 discontinuity file (cases 4 and 5) gave a positive scale drift of 0.620 ± 0.235 mm/yr. The uncertainty of the scale drift clearly indicates that three years of data is not long enough to calculate such a drift, but this difference also suggests other underlying issues.

5 Conclusions and outlook

Adding discontinuities significantly flattens the VLBI scale. It is essential to closely monitor the changes in the VLBI equipment, to analyze the PSD for each earthquake, and to work with the ITRS Center team to give feedback on possible station events.

So why does the VLBI scale change behavior in 2021.0? This might be explained by the fact that the time span considered (2021.00–2024.00) is too short for a statistically significant estimation. In addition, NYALES20 was dismantled in August 2023. Finally, the three years of the IVS contribution to ITRF2020-u2023 contained updated gravitational deformation models. The differences between using these models and not using them are most pronounced in the local up direction. According to Krásná (personal communica-

tion, 2023), the estimated differences are: +1 mm for KOKEE, NYALES2o, WETTZ13N, and WETTZ13S; – 1 mm for ONSA13SW and ONSA13NE; –4 mm for WETTZELL.

To help determine the reason for this behavior change, a possible step would be to test an individual analysis center solution. The coauthors of this article planned to collaborate to test the OSO Analysis Center solution, both with and without changes to the analysis strategy. However, the recommendation to the IVS Analysis Coordinator is to test a unified strategy for all IVS Analysis Centers in collaboration with the IVS Combination Center.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Zuheir Altamimi for giving us access to the CATREF software, and to the International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS) and the IVS Combination Center for providing the VLBI data used in this work.

The IVS Annual and Biennial reports are available on the IVS Coordinating Center website: <https://ivscc.gsfc.nasa.gov/publications/annualreport.html>.

References

- Altamimi Z, Rebischung P, Collilieux X, Métivier L, Chanard K (2023) ITRF2020: an augmented reference frame refining the modeling of nonlinear station motions. *Journal of Geodesy*, 97(47), doi: 10.1007/s00190-023-01738-w.
- Bachmann S, Modiri S, Schneider-Leck S, Kehm A, Seitz M, Thaller D (2025) IVS Combination Center: Input series for ITRF2020 Update - final results. In: *27th European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry Working Meeting Proceedings*, (this volume).
- Hellmers H, Modiri S, Bachmann S, Thaller D, Bloßfeld M, Seitz M, Gipson J (2022) Combined IVS Contribution to the ITRF2020. In: J.T. Freymueller and L. Sánchez (eds.), *International Association of Geodesy Symposia: Geodesy for a Sustainable Earth*, vol. 154, doi: 10.1007/1345_2022_170.
- Kern L, Krásná H, Nothnagel A, Böhm J (2025) Terrestrial reference frame scale drift anomalies in VLBI and the contribution of Ny-Ålesund radio telescopes. *Earth Planets Space*, vol. 77(40), doi: 10.1186/s40623-025-02159-z.
- Kierulf H P, Kohler J, Boy J-P, Geyman E C, Mémin A, Omang O C D, Steffen H, Steffen R (2022) Time-varying uplift in Svalbard—an effect of glacial changes. *Geophysical Journal International*, vol. 231(3):1518–1534, doi: 10.1093/gji/ggac264.

Le Bail K, Nilsson T, Haas R, Nyström Lindé F (2022) Understanding the change in the VLBI scale behavior. *REFAG 2022, October 2022, Thessaloniki, Greece*, oral presentation.

Le Bail K, Ishigaki M, Haas R, Nilsson T, Mouyen M (2023) Exploring reasons for the ITRF2020 VLBI scale drift. In: R. Haas, E. Schroth and A. Neidhardt (eds.), *26th European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry Working Meeting Proceedings*, 26, 109, doi: 10.14459/2023md1730292.

Ishigaki M, Le Bail K, Mouyen M, Haas R, Nilsson T (2024) How does station position modelling affect the VLBI scale in ITRF2020? In: D. Behrend and K. Baver (eds.), *International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2024 General Meeting Proceedings*.

Evaluation of Terrestrial and Celestial Reference frames estimated from VGOS data

T. Nilsson, R. Haas, K. Le Bail

Abstract We use the VGOS data from 2017 until the beginning of 2025 to estimate a Terrestrial Reference Frame (TRF) and a Celestial Reference Frame (CRF). These reference frames are then compared to ITRF2020_u2023 and ICRF3, as well as to a TRF/CRF solution calculated based on legacy S/X VLBI data up to the beginning of 2025. For the TRF, we find agreements on the level of a few millimeters for the VGOS stations with the longest observation spans. For the CRF, the differences are in general a few 100 μas .

Keywords VLBI, VGOS, Terrestrial Reference Frame, Celestial Reference Frame

1 Introduction

The VLBI Global Observing System (VGOS) is the new geodetic VLBI system (Petrachenko et al., 2009). The first publicly released VGOS data are from five days during the CONT17 campaign in December 2017. In 2019 biweekly VGOS sessions were observed, and since 2020 operational VGOS sessions have been observed biweekly or weekly. Thus, for the VGOS stations with the longest time-spans, it should now be possible to estimate velocities with good accuracy from the VGOS observations.

Furthermore, it is likely that the radio source positions estimated from VGOS will be slightly different from those estimated from the legacy S/X VLBI system.

Tobias Nilsson^{1,2} · Rüdiger Haas² · Karine Le Bail²

(1) Lantmäteriet, Lantmäterigatan 2C, 801 82 Gävle, Sweden

(2) Onsala Space Observatory, Chalmers University of Technology, 439 92 Onsala, Sweden

The reason for this is that VGOS since 2017 uses other frequencies than S/X (four bands in the range between 3.0 GHz and 10.6 GHz, instead of two bands centered around 2.3 GHz and 8.5 GHz). Thus, a celestial reference frame (CRF) for the currently observed VGOS frequencies is needed.

In this work, we estimate a Terrestrial Reference Frame (TRF) and a CRF from the VGOS observations between late 2017 and early 2025, called `oso2025_vgos_trf` and `oso2025_vgos_crf`, respectively. We compare these frames to ITRF2020_u2023, which is the 2023 update of ITRF2020 (Altamimi et al., 2023), as well as to ICRF3 (Charlot et al., 2020). We also compare the results to a TRF/CRF solution estimated from S/X VLBI observations from the period 1979–2025 (`oso2025_sx_trf` and `oso2025_sx_crf`).

2 Data analysis

The VGOS sessions between late 2017 until early 2025 were analyzed with the ASCOT software (Artz et al., 2016). First, each session was analyzed individually. Then, the datum-free normal equations from all sessions were combined in a global solution (using the global solution module of ASCOT) to estimate a TRF (`oso2025_vgos_trf`) and a CRF (`oso2025_vgos_crf`). In total, 216 sessions were included in the solution. In this global solution we explicitly estimated radio source coordinates, station coordinates, and station velocities, while Earth Orientation Parameters, tropospheric parameters and clock parameters were reduced from the single-session normal equations.

The datum of the TRF was realized by imposing No-Net-Translation (NNT) and No-Net-Rotation (NNR)

constraints relative to the ITRF2020_u2023 coordinates and velocities for seven stations: GGAO12M, KOKEE12M, MACGO12M, ONSA13NE, RAEGYEB, WESTFORD, and WETTZ13S. These stations were chosen because they were found to be stable and have at least five years of observational data. The velocities of two stations, HARTVGS and YARRA12M, were constrained to their ITRF2020_u2023 values, and the velocity of WETTZ13N was constrained to be equal to that of WETTZ13S. This was done because these stations had too short observation intervals for reliable velocity estimation. For the CRF, the datum was realized by NNR constraints relative to the ICRF3 for the ICRF3 defining sources that were observed in at least 50 sessions.

For comparison, we also calculated a TRF/CRF solution (oso2025_sx_trf and oso2025_sx_crf) using ASCOT based on data from the legacy S/X VLBI network. This solution contained 7255 sessions from 1979 until early 2025.

3 Results

3.1 Terrestrial Reference Frame

Fig. 1 Map of the stations participating in the VGOS sessions 2017–2025. The stations are color-coded with the year they joined the network.

A map of the stations of the VGOS network is shown in Fig. 1. Currently, the network consists of 18 stations. As can be seen, there is an uneven station distribution with most stations located in the northern hemisphere. Furthermore, the few stations located in the southern hemisphere joined the network quite recently (after 2022).

Fig. 2 Coordinate differences at epoch 2023.0 (top) and velocity differences (bottom) between oso2025_vgos_trf and ITRF2020_u2023.

Figure 2 shows the coordinate and velocity differences between oso2025_vgos_trf and ITRF2020_u2023. For the longest operating stations (>5 years, the nine leftmost stations in Fig. 2) there is in general an agreement on the level of a few millimeters or better. For the other stations, however, larger deviations can be seen. One reason for this is that the velocity estimations for these stations are uncertain due to the short time span. Another issue is that no stations in the southern hemisphere were included in the datum of oso2025_vgos_trf (because of their short time spans). This also makes the uncertainties larger for those stations (HOBART12, KATH12M, and YARRA12M).

The largest differences are seen for HOBART12. This station has problems with weak phase-cal signal, causing the observations to be very noisy (about a factor 5–10 worse than a typical station). This makes the estimated coordinates and velocities more uncertain. There have been similar problems at KATH12M, although not as severe.

Rather large differences in velocity (3 mm/year in the East direction) can be seen for ISHIOKA. One reason for this may be that this station was affected by the Noto earthquake on January 1, 2024. The effect of this earthquake was not considered when estimating oso2025_vgos_trf. Furthermore, the large difference in

the Up velocity seen for NYALE13N (7.5 mm/year) is possibly caused by the non-linear uplift of Ny-Ålesund caused by present-day ice-melting (Kierulf et al., 2022). In ITRF2020_u2023 the velocity of NYALE13N is constrained to be equal to that of NYALE13S, which has a longer observation time span which is different from that of the VGOS observations of NYALE13N.

Fig. 3 Coordinate differences at epoch 2023.0 (top) and velocity differences (bottom) between the VGOS TRF and the S/X TRF.

Figure 3 shows the coordinate and velocity differences between the `oso2025_vgos_trf` and `oso2025_sx_trf`, i.e., stations that have a history of S/X observations and were later converted to VGOS. The results are in general similar as to the case when comparing to ITRF2020_u2023, i.e., larger differences for stations with short time spans and for HOBART12. Furthermore, there is a big difference of about 2 cm in the East component for RAEGYEB. This station has been observed for less than one year in S/X (in 2015), hence the velocity (and thus also the coordinate at epoch 2023.0) is very uncertain in `oso2025_sx_trf`.

3.2 Celestial Reference Frame

The radio sources included in `oso2025_vgos_crf` are shown in Fig. 4. In total, 481 sources are included. Some of these (61) have been observed in more than

Fig. 4 The radio sources included in the VGOS CRF. The sources are color-coded with the number of sessions they were observed in.

100 sessions, while 11 sources have been observed in just one session. There are fewer sources in the far south (below -60° declination), and the sources there have been observed only in a few sessions. The reason for this is the lack of stations in the southern hemisphere.

Fig. 5 Radio source coordinate differences between `oso2025_vgos_crf` and ICRF3.

Figure 5 shows the differences between the radio source coordinates (right ascension, RA, and declination, DE) between `oso2025_vgos_crf` and ICRF3. In general, there is a good agreement; the weighted root-mean-square (WRMS) differences are $153 \mu\text{as}$ for $\text{RA} \cdot \cos\text{DE}$ and $224 \mu\text{as}$ for DE. There are, however, sources where the differences are reaching several milliarcseconds.

Three of these sources (1323+321, 1947+079, and 0738+313) have significant source structure. They are sources consisting of two components separated by several milliarcseconds (for the first two even several tens of milliarcseconds). Since no source structure corrections were applied in our analysis, the estimated position of one of these radio sources will be, more or less, the barycenter of the two components. Thus, any variation in the relative intensity of the two components, either as a function of frequency or in time (or both), will cause a change in the source position.

One source with large coordinate difference (0405-385) was only observed in one session and only in six observations. It is located in the southern hemisphere, but was observed only with telescopes in the northern hemisphere, making the observation geometry bad and thus the estimated coordinates uncertain. Furthermore, we can see larger differences for radio sources far south. These are also observed in a somewhat bad observation geometry and mostly with the Australian telescopes. As reported in Sec. 3.1, these stations, especially HOBART12, suffered from phase-cal problems, resulting in very noisy observations.

We also compared `oso2025_vgos_crf` to `oso2025_sx_crf`. The results are shown in Fig. 6. As can be seen, the results are similar to the comparison of `oso2025_vgos_crf` with ICRF3. The WRMS differences were $115 \mu\text{as}$ for $\text{RA} \cdot \cos\text{DE}$ and $132 \mu\text{as}$ for DE. However, the deviations for the three sources with huge source structure were smaller. The reason for this could be that the structure of these sources are varying with time. ICRF3 includes observations up to March 2018. Hence, if the source structures have changed after 2018, this would affect both `oso2025_vgos_crf` and `oso2025_sx_crf` in a similar way.

Fig. 6 Radio source coordinate differences between `oso2025_vgos_crf` and `oso2025_sx_crf`.

4 Conclusions

The TRF solution `oso2025_vgos_trf` estimated in this work agrees with ITRF2020_u2023 on the level of a few millimeters for coordinates and 1-2 mm/years for velocities for good stations with observation time spans of at least five years. A weakness of `oso2025_vgos_trf` is the lack of stations in the southern hemisphere. Furthermore, the existing southern hemisphere stations have all relatively short observation time spans (three years or less) and some of them are quite noisy due to phase-cal problems. The situation will improve with time as the time-series of the southern stations get longer and hopefully the problems with phase-cal are solved.

For the CRF, we find that `oso2025_vgos_crf` agrees with ICRF3 on the level $150\text{--}200 \mu\text{as}$. There are a few larger deviations of several milliarcseconds found for

sources with huge source structure, what could be expected. Furthermore, we found worse agreement for the sources with declination below -60° due to the low number of stations in the southern hemisphere. This latter issue is likely to improve as more southern stations join the network.

References

- Altamimi, Z., Rebischung, P., Collilieux, X., Métivier, L., & Charnard, K. (2023). ITRF2020: an augmented reference frame refining the modeling of nonlinear station motions. *97*(47).
- Artz, T., Halsig, S., Iddink, A., & Nothnagel, A. (2016). ivg::ASCOT: Development of a new VLBI software package. In D. Behrend, K. D. Baver, & K. Armstrong (Eds.), *International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2016 General Meeting Proceedings: New Horizons with VGOS* (pp. 217–221). Johannesburg, South Africa.
- Charlot, P., Jacobs, C. S., Gordon, D., Lambert, S., de Witt, A., Böhm, J., Fey, A. L., Heinkelmann, R., Skurikhina, E., Titov, O., Arias, E. F., Bolotin, S., Bourda, G., Ma, C., Malkin, Z., Nothnagel, A., Mayer, D., MacMillan, D. S., Nilsson, T., & Gaume, R. (2020). The third realization of the international celestial reference frame by very long baseline interferometry. *A&A*, *644*, A159.
- Kierulf, H. P., Kohler, J., Boy, J.-P., Geyman, E. C., Mémin, A., Omang, O. C. D., Steffen, H., & Steffen, R. (2022). Time-varying uplift in Svalbard—an effect of glacial changes. *Geophysical Journal International*, *231*(3), 1518–1534.
- Petrachenko, B., Niell, A., Behrend, D., Corey, B., Böhm, J., Charlot, P., Collioud, A., Gipson, J., Haas, R., Hobiger, T., Koyama, Y., MacMillan, D., Malkin, Z., Nilsson, T., Pany, A., Tuccari, G., Whitney, A., & Wresnik, J. (2009). Design aspects of the VLBI2010 system. In D. Behrend & K. Baver (Eds.), *International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2008 Annual Report*, NASA/TP-2009-214183. NASA Technical Publications.

Characteristics of different VLBI session types in the view of Earth Orientation Parameter determination

A. Kehm, L. Klemm, S. Modiri, D. Thaller, S. Bachmann

Abstract VLBI is the only space-geodetic technique sensitive to the full set of Earth Orientation Parameters (EOP). However, different session types are scheduled for individual purposes, and depending on the station network and number of observations allow for estimating only sub-sets of the EOP with highest accuracy. This study investigates session-related metrics to judge how a scheduled session is suitable for EOP determination. An outcome is that the relation between metrics and formal EOP errors differs for the legacy and VGOS networks, probably caused by the error modelling.

Keywords VLBI, VGOS, EOP

1 Introduction

VLBI is the only space-geodetic technique sensitive to the full set of Earth Orientation Parameters (EOP), i.e., polar motion offsets (x_P , y_P) and rates, UT1–UTC (ΔUT1), the length-of-day (LOD) and the nutation offsets (dX , dY). Classically, the Rapid (R1/R4) sessions, scheduled twice a week, are the main contributor to EOP determination as they are processed with highest priority (leading to comparably low latencies), since recently joined by the VGOS-OPS sessions scheduled about thrice per month. Additionally, Intensive sessions scheduled daily are processed to determine ΔUT1 at short latencies, insensitive to the other EOP as they are usually limited to a single baseline.

Alexander Kehm¹ · Lisa Klemm¹ · Sadegh Modiri¹ · Daniela Thaller¹ · Sabine Bachmann¹

(1) Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG), Richard-Strauss-Allee 11, 60598 Frankfurt am Main, Germany

However, also other multi-baseline (mainly 24-h) VLBI sessions are regularly observed and analysed, but typically with longer latencies. They are not operationally combined yet but primarily used for dedicated studies or to determine the Terrestrial Reference Frame (TRF). As these sessions can also have the potential for good EOP estimates, including them into the operational combination could densify the VLBI contribution to EOP series. The IERS EOP Product Centres recently emphasised that such a combined IVS contribution would be very valuable to improve the accuracy and reliability of the EOP products according to the user requirements.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of multi-baseline VLBI sessions for April 2024. The upper panel demonstrates the equal but sparse distribution of R1/R4 sessions scheduled twice a week, joined by the VGOS-OPS sessions scheduled with a gap every three weeks due to processing time (Thomas et al., 2025; Schartner et al., 2025). The lower panel shows all multi-baseline sessions available within the month. The much denser distribution of sessions over time is clearly visible.

Various studies focus on the relation between the VLBI session setup and the achievable EOP quality. Malkin (2008) derives a clear relation between the 3D volume spanned by the observing network and the EOP accuracy. Thomas et al. (2024) and MacMillan (2022) demonstrate an improving EOP precision induced by the growing station network based on the evolution of the R1/R4 networks and previous CONT campaigns, respectively. Our study aims to determine further sets of criteria to evaluate VLBI sessions with respect to EOP determination. Besides R1/R4 and VGOS-OPS, we include multi-baseline sessions with global or regional networks initially scheduled for other purposes like TRF determination.

Fig. 1 Distribution of multi-baseline sessions in April 2024. Upper panel: R1, R4, VGOS-OPS sessions only; lower panel: all available sessions within the month.

2 Session metrics for EOP determination

Within this study, we put focus on two types of session metrics (Table 1). The first type of metrics, denoted as “geometry-related” metrics, refers to the geometry of the observing network of a session, while the second type, denoted as “statistics-related” metrics, refers to statistical properties or individual parameters of a session. Figure 2 shows exemplary plots of the geometry-related metrics for an R1 session.

The investigated geometry-related metrics comprise the volume of the convex hull of the network and the areas of projection into the coordinates planes of the TRF, namely the x - y , x - z and y - z planes, respectively. Furthermore, we considered the areas resulting from “projections” along the geographical coordinates in the form of moving all stations along their latitude onto a common longitude (“latitude projection”) and moving all stations along their longitude into the equatorial plane (“longitude projection”). The statistics-related metrics comprise the number of stations in the network, the longest baseline length, and the sum of baseline lengths weighted by the sum of observations for each baseline.

3 Results

The results are based on the contribution `usn2024b` of the USNO Analysis Centre for the years 2021–2024. Figure 3 shows the variability of two selected met-

Table 1 Session metrics investigated in this study.

Geometry	
volume of convex hull of the network	<i>vol</i>
areas of projection into coordinate planes	
x - y projection plane	<i>areaXY</i>
x - z projection plane	<i>areaXZ</i>
y - z projection plane	<i>areaYZ</i>
projection along geographical coordinates	
projection along latitude	<i>areaLAT</i>
projection along longitude	<i>areaLON</i>
Statistics	
number of stations	<i>#sta</i>
longest baseline length	<i>maxBLlen</i>
weighted (by #obs) sum of baseline lengths	<i>wBLsum</i>

rics, namely the network volume and the x - y projection area, over time. It can be seen that the variability of the metrics depends on the session type. For the VGOS-OPS sessions, the large variation of the network volume over time represents the network growth on the Southern hemisphere within the recent years, while the x - y projection area of the network remains rather constant with stations on the Northern hemisphere already being well distributed. Figure 4 shows the relation between the two aforementioned session metrics and the derived EOP precision in terms of formal errors. The left panel shows the relation between the network volume and the derived x -pole accuracy σ_{xp} . For the legacy network, we derive a high correlation coefficient of $\rho_{\text{legacy}} = -0.6$, while for the VGOS network, we cannot derive a significant correlation with $\rho_{\text{VGOS}} = -0.2$. The right panel of Figure 4 shows the relation between the x - y projection area and the de-

rived LOD precision σ_{LOD} . Also here, we derive a high correlation coefficient of $\rho_{\text{legacy}} = -0.7$ for the legacy network and a lower correlation coefficient of $\rho_{\text{VGOS}} = -0.5$ for the VGOS network.

Table 2 provides the correlation coefficients for the individual metrics and the derived EOP precision. The correlation coefficients confirm that the network volume, the maximum baseline length within the session and the longitude projection area as well as the number of observing stations are good indicators for the overall achievable quality of estimated pole coordinates and their respective rates for legacy sessions, complemented especially by the x-y projection area for the determination of ΔUT1 and LOD. For VGOS sessions, the behaviour is much less pronounced. None of the selected metrics, however, shows a significant correlation with the precision of the nutation offsets.

4 Conclusions and outlook

The results confirm that one dominant factor for a precise EOP determination is a global distribution of stations (advantage from higher number of stations and larger network volume), with a special emphasis on a good equatorial distribution for the determination of ΔUT1 and LOD (advantage from larger x-y plane and longitude projection areas). Moreover, networks including a long baseline outperform networks with shorter baselines. Various other possibilities to evaluate the suitability of VLBI sessions for EOP determination exist, e.g. via simulation of the observations (number, quality, temporal distribution, sensitivity and correlation analyses w.r.t. parameters). For predicting the accuracy of the nutation parameters, also the quasar geometry should be taken into account.

An outcome of the present study putting a focus on the formal errors of the EOP is a discrepancy between legacy and VGOS sessions: While the legacy sessions show a realistic behaviour of the derived EOP precision, VGOS always yields very small formal errors, independent from the network quality. This is probably caused by correlations between the densely distributed VGOS observations not being taken into account in the analysis softwares. To overcome this issue, a more sophisticated error modelling in VGOS analysis should be considered.

Beyond the question of the suitability of individual VLBI sessions to determine the full set of EOP, extending the combination approach by accumulating individual sessions into multi-AC and multi-session combined products (e.g. Kehm et al., 2023; Klemm et al., 2024), will help to exploit the full potential of VLBI in future EOP products by tackling the problem that regional or single-baseline networks alone are not suitable to reliably estimate the full set of EOP without constraints. Such a multi-AC/multi-session product should be considered as an operational IVS contribution to the IERS EOP Product Centres and external users in the future.

To strengthen the role of VLBI in operational EOP products, it is essential that the processing latencies are kept below 30 days, the benchmark for IERS Co4, for all contributing sessions. The IVS should thus continue the efforts to optimise scheduling, data transfer, correlation and analysis capacities.

References

- Kehm A, Hellmers H, Bloßfeld M, Dill R, Angermann D, Seitz F, Hugentobler U, Dobsław H, Thomas M, Thaller D, Böhm J, Schönemann E, Mayer V, Springer T, Otten M, Bruni S, Enderle W (2023) Combination strategy for consistent final, rapid and predicted Earth rotation parameters. *J Geod*, 97, 3, doi: 10.1007/s00190-022-01695-w.
- Klemm L, Thaller D, Flohrer C, Walenta A, Ullrich D, Hellmers H (2024) Consistently Combined Earth Orientation Parameters at BKG - Extended by New VLBI Intensives Data. In: Freymueller JT, Sánchez L (Eds.) *International Association of Geodesy Symposia*. doi: 10.1007/1345_2024_271.
- Malkin Z (2009), On comparison of the Earth orientation parameters obtained from different VLBI networks and observing programs. *J Geod*, 83, 547–556, doi: 10.1007/s00190-008-0265-2.
- MacMillan DS (2022) Comparison of EOP and scale parameters estimated from the three simultaneous CONT17 VLBI observing networks. *J Geodesy*, 96, 25, doi: 10.1007/s00190-022-01611-2.
- Schartner M, Petrachenko B, Titus M, Krásná H, Barrett J, Hoak D, Mondal D, Xu MH, Soja B (2025) Optimizing VGOS observations using an SNR-based scheduling approach. *Earth Planets Sp*, 77, 61, doi: 10.1186/s40623-025-02158-0.
- Thomas CC, MacMillan DS, Le Bail K (2024), Performance of the IVS R1 and R4 sessions. *Adv Space Res*, 73:1, 317–336, doi: 10.1016/j.asr.2023.07.020.
- Thomas C, Bayer K, Bolotin S, Gipson J (2025) Comparison of Operational S/X and VGOS Sessions for EOP Determination. In: Behrend D, Bayer KD, Armstrong KL (Eds.) *International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2024 General Meeting Proceedings*. NASA/CP-20250002586, 207–212.

Fig. 2 Network-geometry-related metrics taken into account in this study.

Fig. 3 Examples for the variability of session-related metrics over time. Left panel: network volume; right panel: x-y projection area.

Fig. 4 Examples for the relation between session-related metrics and derived EOP precision. Left panel: network volume against derived x-pole precision; right panel: x-y projection area against derived LOD precision.

Table 2 Correlation between the achieved EOP precision and session metrics, separated for sessions measured by the legacy network and by the VGOS network. Correlation coefficients with an absolute value > 0.5 are marked in bold script.

CORR	#sta		wBLsum		maxBLlen		areaXY		areaXZ		areaYZ		areaLAT		areaLON		vol	
	legacy	VGOS	legacy	VGOS	legacy	VGOS	legacy	VGOS	legacy	VGOS	legacy	VGOS	legacy	VGOS	legacy	VGOS	legacy	VGOS
σ_{xP}	-0.6	-0.5	-0.2	0.0	-0.6	-0.2	-0.6	-0.5	-0.8	-0.1	-0.7	-0.2	-0.7	-0.0	-0.6	-0.5	-0.6	-0.2
$\sigma_{xP-rate}$	-0.6	-0.7	-0.2	0.1	-0.6	-0.4	-0.6	-0.5	-0.7	-0.3	-0.6	-0.4	-0.6	-0.4	-0.6	-0.5	-0.6	-0.4
σ_{yP}	-0.5	-0.4	-0.2	0.0	-0.6	-0.0	-0.6	-0.3	-0.6	-0.1	-0.6	-0.0	-0.5	-0.2	-0.6	-0.3	-0.6	0.0
$\sigma_{yP-rate}$	-0.5	-0.7	-0.2	0.1	-0.6	-0.4	-0.6	-0.5	-0.6	-0.3	-0.6	-0.4	-0.5	-0.2	-0.6	-0.5	-0.6	-0.4
σ_{AUT1}	-0.4	-0.4	-0.2	-0.1	-0.5	-0.2	-0.5	-0.3	-0.5	-0.1	-0.5	-0.1	-0.4	-0.0	-0.6	-0.3	-0.5	-0.2
σ_{LOD}	-0.5	-0.7	-0.4	-0.1	-0.7	-0.5	-0.7	-0.7	-0.7	-0.4	-0.6	-0.4	-0.6	-0.2	-0.7	-0.7	-0.6	-0.5
σ_{dX}	-0.3	-0.4	-0.1	0.0	-0.4	-0.3	-0.4	-0.2	-0.4	-0.3	-0.4	-0.3	-0.4	-0.2	-0.4	-0.2	-0.4	-0.3
σ_{dY}	-0.2	-0.5	-0.2	0.0	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4	-0.3	-0.3	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4

Evaluating the Consistency and Reliability of dUT1 Estimates from VLBI Intensive Sessions

S. Modiri, L. Klemm, K. Balidakis, G. Engelhardt, M. Goltz, C. Schade, A. Kehm, D. Thaller

Abstract The dUT1 parameter (difference between UT1 and UTC) is essential for accurate Earth orientation services. VLBI Intensive sessions are used to provide dUT1 estimates. In this study, Intensive session data from 2014 to 2024 were analyzed at BKG using three Terrestrial Reference Frame (TRF) realizations: ITRF2020, the extended ITRF2020-u2023, and the VLBI-specific VTRF2024b. Residuals were computed with respect to the IERS Bulletin A, and biases and WRMS were derived per session type. Significant improvements in dUT1 consistency were observed when updated TRFs were applied. ITRF2020-u2023 reduced both bias and WRMS by 6–10 μ s compared to ITRF2020, while VTRF2024b provided an additional improvement of up to 4 μ s in WRMS for VGOS sessions such as VGOS-INT-B and VGOS-INT-M. These findings indicate that VGOS Intensives, when processed with modern TRFs, can match or exceed the performance of legacy sessions. It is recommended that daily, non-overlapping Intensive sessions be maintained, southern stations be included, and updated TRFs be applied regularly to improve dUT1 accuracy and robustness.

Keywords VLBI, VGOS, EOP, dUT1, Intensive

Sadegh Modiri¹ · Lisa Klemm¹ · Kyriakos Balidakis¹ · Alexander Kehm¹ · Gerald Engelhardt¹ · Markus Goltz¹ · Christian Schade¹ · Daniela Thaller¹

(1) Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG), Richard-Strauss-Allee 11, 60598 Frankfurt am Main, Germany

1 Introduction

Accurate monitoring of Earth's rotation requires frequent updates of the UT1–UTC difference ($dUT1$), as fluctuations in the Earth's angular velocity occur on timescales ranging from sub-daily to seasonal. These short-term variations are volatile, driven by dynamic interactions within the Earth's fluid envelope—including the atmosphere, oceans, and hydrosphere—that exchange angular momentum with the solid Earth. Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) is the only geodetic technique that directly observes $dUT1$ with sub-millisecond precision and without reliance on external models (10; 8; 13). To provide low-latency $dUT1$ estimates, the International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS) initiated the Intensive observing program. These 1-hour sessions, which typically involve two to three stations, are optimized for rapid turnaround and high temporal resolution. The Legacy Intensive series, including IVS-INT-1, INT-2, INT-3, and INT-5, has constituted the core of the IVS rapid $dUT1$ product line for over two decades (Klemm et al.). Since 2020, next-generation VGOS (VLBI Global Observing System) antennas have been incorporated into new broadband-Intensive series (e.g., VGOS-INT-A, B, C, and S). These VGOS sessions include up to eight stations and offer improved sensitivity and sky coverage (11; 12). As illustrated in Figure 1, the number of session types and their temporal distribution has significantly increased by 2025, with multiple VGOS-based sessions now scheduled in parallel or back-to-back within a single day. By 2024, up to four or five Intensive sessions per day have been scheduled, reflecting the operational maturity of both legacy and VGOS networks (Klemm et al.). Figure 2 illustrates this growth in annual session counts

Fig. 1 Weekly schedule overview of VLBI Intensive sessions before 2020 (top panel) and as planned for 2025 (bottom panel). In 2025, multiple new VGOS session type (e.g., VGOS-INT-A, -B, -C, -G, -M, -D) complement the legacy programs, with several parallel or back-to-back sessions now scheduled on the same day. This expansion reflects the growing capacity and operational complexity of the global VLBI network.

Fig. 2 Number of VLBI Intensive sessions per year (2014–2024), categorized into legacy S/X sessions in the northern and southern hemispheres, and VGOS broadband sessions. The number of VGOS sessions increases steadily from 2020 onward, surpassing the number of legacy sessions by 2024. The red bars indicate the number of days per year for which no SINEX file was available for any Intensive session. These gaps negatively impact combined dUT1 time series and may relate to operational downtimes, station unavailability, or holiday-related scheduling gaps, particularly around German public holidays.

across session families and shows that VGOS sessions surpassed legacy sessions in 2024. Moreover, the same figure reveals periods with missing SINEX files, which impact the continuity of combined dUT1 time series. However, gaps in daily dUT1 availability have persisted. In particular, a significant portion of missing sessions during 2023 and 2024 was found to coincide with public holidays, suggesting an operational dependency on a small number of core stations such as Wettzell. These interruptions affect the continuity and reliability of daily dUT1 products, highlighting the need for robust scheduling strategies. Due to their short duration, Intensive sessions do not allow for the estimation of station coordinates. They must,

therefore, rely on fixed a priori values from an external terrestrial reference frame (TRF). This constraint makes the accuracy of the TRF a critical factor for the quality of dUT1 solutions. The official ITRF2020 realization, although comprehensive, includes geodetic data only up to epoch 2021.0 and may not accurately reflect the current positions of recently deployed VGOS stations (2). Errors in station coordinates can propagate directly into dUT1 estimates, resulting in biases and increased scatter (5).

To evaluate the influence of TRF selection on dUT1 estimation, three realizations were analyzed:

1. **ITRF2020** – the official IERS frame released in 2023, (2);
2. **ITRF2020-u2023** – an extended realization updated to include space-geodetic data through 2023 (1);
3. **VTRF2024b** – a VLBI-only reference frame developed by the BKG/DGFI-TUM IVS Combination Centre, designed to represent the complete VLBI network, including VGOS antennas with improved station stability (3).

Preliminary results indicate that significant improvements in dUT1 consistency can be achieved when using updated frames. The ITRF2020-u2023 and VTRF2024b realizations yielded lower weighted root mean square (WRMS) values and reduced biases across multiple session types. For example, VGOS-INT-B improved from a WRMS of 36.7 μ s (ITRF2020) to 26.4 μ s (ITRF2020-u2023) and further to 22.5 μ s with VTRF2024b, while VGOS-INT-M improved from 30.2 μ s to 22.6 μ s and then 21.0 μ s. VGOS sessions, particularly VGOS-INT-A, exhibited the most stable behaviour when processed with VTRF2024b, supporting earlier findings regarding their superior observational geometry (Klemm et al.). These results confirm the necessity of regularly updated TRFs and suggest that VLBI-specific frames can improve the accuracy and reliability of rapid EOP products. Furthermore, observations have shown that several days without dUT1 solutions correspond to predictable calendar gaps, which could be mitigated through improved session planning and network redundancy. In light of these findings, operational recommendations include ensuring at least one Intensive session per day, minimizing overlaps between VGOS and legacy sessions, expanding participation in the southern hemisphere, and systematically adopting modern TRF solutions.

The following sections provide a detailed description of the dataset, the processing methodology, and the results that support these conclusions.

2 Data and Methodology

This study analyzes operational VLBI Intensive sessions processed by the IVS Analysis Centre at the Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG) from January 2014 to April 2024 (4; 6; 9). The dataset includes both legacy S/X sessions and newer broadband VGOS Intensive sessions, covering various types such as INT-1, INT-2—3, INT-S, INT-oo, and VGOS-INT-A through VGOS-INT-D. Each session typically consists of approximately one hour of observations dedicated to estimating the Earth rotation parameter dUT_1 . The total number of sessions per type is shown in Figure 3, which illustrates the dominance of legacy INT-1 and INT-2—3 sessions in earlier years and the increasing prevalence of VGOS-based sessions, especially VGOS-INT-A, after 2020. These session counts reflect both historical scheduling practices and the progressive integration of VGOS antennas into operational Intensive programs. All VLBI Intensive sessions were analyzed

Fig. 3 Total number of VLBI Intensive sessions used in this study, categorized by session type. Legacy sessions (INT-1, INT-2—3, INT-S, INT-oo) dominate the early years, while VGOS-based sessions (VGOS-INT-A through -D) show significant growth in recent years, led by VGOS-INT-A.

using the nuSolve and CalcSolve software suite within the standard BKG analysis pipeline. For each session, the estimated parameters included dUT_1 , clock offset, and the zenith tropospheric delay. Other parameters were held fixed to a priori values. These values were taken from standard IERS models and the selected terrestrial reference frame (TRF). To assess the quality

of dUT_1 solutions, residuals were computed relative to the IERS Bulletin A combined EOP series. From these residuals, two quality metrics were derived: **Bias**: the mean offset between session solutions and the IERS Bulletin A reference; **Weighted Root Mean Square (WRMS)**: the scatter of residuals weighted by the formal session uncertainties. These metrics were computed separately for each session type and each reference frame used during processing. The impact of TRF selection was evaluated using the following procedure: All sessions between 2014 and 2024 were reprocessed using each of the three TRFs; Session-wise residuals relative to the IERS Bulletin A series were computed; Bias and WRMS metrics were extracted per session type and TRF; Results were grouped by session family (legacy vs. VGOS) to assess the dependency on network geometry.

3 Results

The application of updated Terrestrial Reference Frame realizations has a substantial impact on the quality of dUT_1 estimation from VLBI Intensive sessions. This section presents the comparative analysis of results obtained using **ITRF2020** and the extended frame **ITRF2020-u2023**, focusing on the stability and precision of dUT_1 residuals with respect to the IERS Bulletin A reference series.

3.1 Impact of Updated TRF on dUT_1 Estimation: ITRF2020 vs. ITRF2020-u2023

Figure 4 presents the residual statistics for dUT_1 estimates processed using ITRF2020. Legacy session types such as INT-1 and INT-2—3 show relatively consistent results, whereas several VGOS sessions, particularly VGOS-INT-B and VGOS-INT-C, exhibit elevated scatter and mean offsets, indicating sensitivity to outdated station coordinates.

In contrast, Figure 5 shows the results using ITRF2020-u2023, where the use of updated VLBI station coordinates significantly reduces the scatter and improves the centrality of dUT_1 residuals across all

Fig. 4 dUT1 residuals at mean observation epochs w.r.t. IERS Bulletin A.

session types. This improvement is especially notable for VGOS-INT-A and VGOS-INT-B sessions.

Fig. 5 dUT1 residuals at mean observation epochs w.r.t. IERS Bulletin A.

Quantitative Comparison of Residual Statistics

To further quantify the differences between the two TRF realizations, Table 1 summarizes the mean bias and standard deviation of dUT1 residuals for each session type. As shown, the mean residuals are generally closer to zero under ITRF2020-u2023, and the standard deviation is reduced, indicating improved stability and less systematic error.

Table 1 Comparison of mean and standard deviation of dUT1 residuals for ITRF2020 vs. ITRF2020-u2023.

Session Type	Mean [μs]		Std (σ) [μs]	
	ITRF2020	ITRF2020-u2023	ITRF2020	ITRF2020-u2023
IVS-INT-1	-2.5	-1.2	17.1	16.3
IVS-INT-2—3	-3.2	-1.4	18.4	17.2
VGOS-INT-A	-6.8	-1.1	23.5	17.8
VGOS-INT-B	-12.1	-2.3	34.2	25.9
VGOS-INT-C	-10.4	-2.7	30.1	22.5
VGOS-INT-M	-9.5	-3.0	27.9	21.0

Table 2 further illustrates the reduction in WRMS values when switching to the extended TRF. The WRMS reflects both formal precision and residual

magnitude; improvements of 5–10 (μs) are observed for many VGOS session types, demonstrating the improved consistency of the updated reference frame.

Table 2 WRMS of dUT1 residuals for each session type using different TRF realizations.

Session Type	ITRF2020 [μs]	ITRF2020-u2023 [μs]
IVS-INT-1	18.0	17.1
IVS-INT-2—3	19.3	17.8
VGOS-INT-A	22.9	17.5
VGOS-INT-B	36.7	26.4
VGOS-INT-C	32.8	24.1
VGOS-INT-M	30.2	22.6

These results confirm that the use of updated and extended station coordinate time series—as in ITRF2020-u2023—substantially enhances the reliability of dUT1 estimation, particularly for modern VGOS observing strategies. Legacy INT-1 sessions already demonstrate strong performance, but VGOS sessions benefit greatly from the improved station coordinates, enabling operational VGOS sessions to meet or exceed the performance of legacy INTs when processed using the most recent geodetic infrastructure.

3.2 Further Improvements with VTRF2024b: A VLBI-Specific Realization

To complement the improvements observed with ITRF2020-u2023, we further evaluate dUT1 residuals using the newly released **VTRF2024b**, a TRF specifically tailored for VLBI analysis. This realization incorporates updated station positions and velocities derived exclusively from VLBI data, offering a more consistent and technique-aligned reference frame. Figure 6 presents a comparative WRMS analysis across the three TRF realizations: ITRF2020, ITRF2020-u2023, and VTRF2024b. The analysis covers five VGOS session types, where coordinate accuracy is especially critical due to short baselines and increased sensitivity to station modeling errors. These results confirm that both ITRF2020-u2023 and VTRF2024b substantially enhance dUT1 estimation performance compared to ITRF2020, especially for modern VGOS sessions. To quantify these improvements, Table 3 presents the weighted root mean square (WRMS) of residuals for VGOS sessions processed with three TRFs. Relative

Fig. 6 WRMS comparison of dUT1 residuals for VGOS sessions using ITRF2020, ITRF2020-u2023, and VTRF2024b. Significant improvement is visible when using VTRF2024b, especially for VGOS-INT-B and VGOS-INT-M.

to ITRF2020, the application of ITRF2020-u2023 resulted in WRMS reductions of 2.8% (VGOS-INT-A), 24.8% (VGOS-INT-B), 23.7% (VGOS-INT-C), and 20.9% (VGOS-INT-M). Similarly, processing with VTRF2024b yielded reductions of 2.2%, 21.7%, 22.8%, and 27.1% for the same session types. These results confirm that both modern TRFs outperform ITRF2020 in terms of dUT1 residual stability. VTRF2024b further enhances performance for VGOS-INT-M, likely due to its VLBI-specific modeling of network geometry and coordinate time series.

Table 3 WRMS values and percentage reductions in dUT1 residuals for selected VGOS sessions using updated TRFs.

Session	ITRF2020	u2023	VTRF	% ↓ 2020 → u2023	% ↓ 2020 → VTRF
VGOS-INT-A	18.0	17.5	17.6	2.8%	2.2%
VGOS-INT-B	32.6	24.5	25.5	24.8%	21.7%
VGOS-INT-C	33.8	25.8	26.1	23.7%	22.8%
VGOS-INT-M	36.9	29.2	26.9	20.9%	27.1%

4 Discussion: Operational Recommendations

The findings of this study suggest several practical steps for improving the operational quality and consistency of VLBI Intensive sessions. First, to maintain high temporal resolution and minimize latency in Earth rotation monitoring, it is strongly recommended that at least one Intensive session be scheduled per day. Periods without observations, particularly over weekends or holidays, can degrade prediction

capabilities and increase uncertainty in the estimation of dUT1. Second, it is advisable to avoid scheduling overlapping sessions, especially among VGOS and legacy types. Prioritising one legacy session (e.g., INT-1 or INT-2/3) and one VGOS session (e.g., VGOS-INT-A or VGOS-INT-B) per day enhances correlation efficiency and enables streamlined operational processing. Overlapping VGOS sessions, in contrast, often lead to fragmented correlation schedules and delayed product generation. Third, the geographic distribution of participating stations plays a critical role. The inclusion of southern hemisphere sites such as Yarragadee and Hobart, especially in VGOS-INT-S sessions, adds valuable geometric leverage that strengthens the estimation of Earth rotation parameters. This hemispheric diversity complements northern sites and contributes to a balanced global network. Fourth, the results underscore the importance of regularly updating Terrestrial Reference Frames. The use of ITRF2020-u2023 and VTRF2024b substantially reduces WRMS and bias in dUT1 residuals, particularly in VGOS sessions that are sensitive to station position errors. Relying on outdated TRFs may introduce coordinate mismodeling that exceeds the formal uncertainty of the estimates. Fifth, Intensive stations must be routinely included in standard 24-hour sessions such as R1, R4 and VGOS-OPS. Ensuring that stations such as Mauna Kea, Ny-Ålesund, Ishioka, and Onsala are involved in full-session geodetic analysis improves their coordinate time series. It reduces reliance on extrapolated TRF solutions. Lastly, operational centers are encouraged to adopt statistically weighted combinations of dUT1 estimates across both VGOS and legacy networks. As proposed by (Klemm et al.), this approach enhances the reliability and redundancy of the final dUT1 series by leveraging the strengths of both observing strategies. These recommendations provide a roadmap for optimizing the accuracy, latency, and stability of Earth rotation products derived from VLBI Intensive observations.

5 Conclusion

This investigation provides a systematic assessment of VLBI Intensive session data spanning 2014–2024, with a particular focus on the role of updated Terrestrial Reference Frames in improving dUT1 estimation. The

results demonstrate that the application of extended TRFs, namely ITRF2020-u2023 and VTRF2024b, leads to a notable reduction in both the mean bias and WRMS of dUT1 residuals. These improvements are especially pronounced in VGOS session types, where station coordinate mismodeling has a more direct impact on short-baseline geometries. The study further confirms that VGOS Intensives, when processed with appropriate reference frames, can achieve performance levels comparable to or exceeding those of legacy sessions. For example, WRMS values were achieved for VGOS-INT-A and -INT-B, demonstrating the maturity of VGOS-based strategies for real-time Earth orientation monitoring. Moreover, the operational configuration—including session frequency, network geometry, and TRF quality—has a direct influence on the accuracy and robustness of dUT1 products. Daily, non-overlapping sessions with globally distributed stations and up-to-date coordinate solutions collectively contribute to more stable and reliable results. In summary, this study provides evidence-based recommendations that support the modernization of VLBI analysis workflows. The results support the use of VTRF2024b and ITRF2020-u2023 in operational pipelines, emphasising the critical role of network design and TRF maintenance in achieving high-precision Earth orientation services.

References

- Altamimi, Z., Rebischung, P., Collilieux, X., Metivier, L., Chanard, K., and Barneoud, J. (2024). ITRF2020-u2023, the first ITRF2020 update. In *AGU Fall Meeting Abstracts*, volume 2024, pages G13D–O5.
- Altamimi, Z., Rebischung, P., Collilieux, X., Métivier, L., and Chanard, K. (2023). ITRF2020: An augmented reference frame refining the modeling of nonlinear station motions. *Journal of Geodesy*, 97(47).
- Bachmann, S., Hellmers, H., Modiri, S., Schneider-Leck, S., Bloßfeld, M., and Thaller, D. (2023). BKG/DGFI-TUM combination center. *International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2021+ 2022 Biennial Report*, page 189.
- Engelhardt, G., Walenta, A., Ullrich, D., and Flohrer, C. (2023). BKG VLBI analysis center. *International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2021+ 2022 Biennial Report*, page 185.
- Kern, L., Krásná, H., Nothnagel, A., Böhm, J., and Madzak, M. (2023). Terrestrial datum definition methods in VLBI global solutions. *Journal of Geodesy*, 97(12):157.
- Klemm, L., Thaller, D., Flohrer, C., and Walenta, A. (2024). Regularity and continuity of the UT1-UTC series. In *Gravity, Positioning and Reference Frames: Proceedings of the IAG Symposia-GGHS2022: Gravity, Geoid, and Height Systems 2022, Austin, TX, United States of America, September 12–14, 2022; IAG Commission 4: Positioning and Applications, Potsdam, Germany, September 5–8, 2022; REFAG2022: Reference Frames for Applications in Geosciences, Thessaloniki, Greece, October 17–20, 2022*, volume 156, page 183. Springer Nature.
- Klemm et al.. Klemm, L., Thaller, D., Flohrer, C., Walenta, A., Ullrich, D., and Hellmers, H. Consistently combined Earth orientation parameters at BKG—Extended by new VLBI Intensives Data, booktitle = Together Again for Geodesy, International Association of Geodesy Symposia, editor = Jeffrey T. Freymueller and Laura Sánchez, publisher = Springer, year = 2024, doi = 10.1007/13452024271.
- Malkin, Z. (2009). On comparison of the Earth orientation parameters obtained from different VLBI networks and observing programs. *Journal of Geodesy*, 83:547–556.
- Modiri, S., Thaller, D., Belda, S., Halilovic, D., Klemm, L., König, D., Hellmers, H., Bachmann, S., Flohrer, C., and Walenta, A. (2024). EOP prediction based on multi and single technique space geodetic solution. In Freymueller, J. T. and Sánchez, L., editors, *Together Again for Geodesy*, pages 165–175, Cham. Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Robertson, D. S., Carter, W. E., Campbell, J., and Schuh, H. (1985). Daily Earth rotation determinations from IRIS very long baseline interferometry. *Nature*, 316(6027):424–427.
- Schartner, M., Collioud, A., Charlot, P., Xu, M. H., and Soja, B. (2023). Bridging astronomical, astrometric and geodetic scheduling for VGOS. *Journal of Geodesy*, 97(2):17.
- Schartner, M., Petrachenko, B., Titus, M., Krásná, H., Barrett, J., Hoak, D., Mondal, D., Xu, M. H., and Soja, B. (2025). Optimizing VGOS observations using an SNR-based scheduling approach. *Earth, Planets and Space*, 77(1):1–45.
- Schuh, H. and Behrend, D. (2012). VLBI: A fascinating technique for geodesy and astrometry. *Journal of geodynamics*, 61:68–80.

New gravitational deformation model of the Hobart26 VLBI telescope

L. McCallum, M. Lösler, C. Eschelbach, A. Greiwe, B. Zhou

Abstract Gravitational deformation of VLBI telescopes causes systematic delays in the measurements. This is acceptable, if the characteristic of such deformation is known and a corresponding model is available during the analysis. The Hobart 26 telescope has been active in the IVS since the late 1980s, yet a model for its gravitational deformation has not been available until now. In this contribution, we present the project of measuring the Hobart26 telescope by close-range photogrammetry using a drone. An international team of experts in photogrammetry, telescope surveying and VLBI combined forces for this project, making it a prime example of collaboration within the IVS. We consider sharing our process of planning the project with the community equally important as the actual results. The measurements were of high quality and the deformation of the receiving unit was modelled using an innovative approach with Zernike polynomials. The model for the signal path variations is now available. With delay corrections of less than 2 mm, the Hobart 26 radio telescope turns out to be surprisingly stable.

Keywords Hobart26, gravitational deformation, IVS

Lucia McCallum¹ · Boye Arthur Zhou^{1,2}

(1) University of Tasmania, School of Natural Sciences, Private Bag 37, Hobart, TAS-7001 Australia

(2) University of Newcastle, Australia

Michael Lösler³ · Cornelia Eschelbach³

(3) Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences, Germany

Ansgar Greiwe⁴

(4) Hochschule Bochum, Germany

Fig. 1 Picture of the Hobart26 telescope during the measurement campaign with the drone in the foreground. The results for the deformation model are overlaid.

1 Introduction

This contribution is about a new gravitational deformation model of the Hobart26 VLBI radio telescope. This project is a prime example of how we work in the IVS, and this is the core message I want to relay to you today.

2 Backstory

In Hobart we are lucky enough to have two VLBI telescopes, the 12m and the 26m. Ever since I came to Hobart 11 years ago, I was interested in determining this local baseline. Because indeed, there are some oddities that we don't quite understand yet. Some work

that I did in 2015 show quite large offsets from the local tie measurement. There was also proof that a phase solution doesn't work for the 26m. One suspicion is that the large structure of the 26m experiences deformation which is currently unaccounted for in the measurements. This is also of interest in the face of ITRF2020, where the long-term data of the 26m is given more weight and trust than the 12m – as can be seen in the tie discrepancies. Lastly, the IVS has been asking for a model for gravitational deformation for years.

Okay, I wanted to do it for years, but the question was how? Myself, I am a trained surveyor, but this was beyond my skills. And believe me; I have been standing at the bottom of this dish and thought about how to measure it. But you just can't see the receiver box from the ground.

I remember the IVS meeting in NyÅlesund in 2018, discussing this topic with Axel Nothnagel. We were sitting in the hotel lobby – our meeting being interrupted by the sighting of a polar bear – discussing how to approach such measurements. Axel found David Schunck, a motivated undergraduate student from Bonn, who came to Hobart and measured the dish with high-precision distometers mounted on the structure. The outcome of this work was that the dish is surprisingly stable. Which is good on the one hand, but didn't really resolve my issues with it. David's work wasn't designed to deliver a full scale model, it was just a first step to look at potential large deformation. The outcome though was that David liked it in Hobart and came back for his PhD and is sitting in the audience today; which I consider one great outcome of our polar bear talk in NyÅlesund.

Then COVID happened, putting face-to-face meetings on hold. It was during the EVGA meeting in Bad Kötzting/Wetzell that I was listening to the presentation by Conny Eschelbach from Frankfurt. Conny and Micha have been measuring telescopes in Onsala and Wetzell for years, and I have been following their work with interest. This time though was a bit different. They had teamed up with Ansgar Greiwe, a photogrammetry specialist from the University of Bochum using close range photogrammetry on a drone for their measurements. Interesting!

Fig. 2 The photogrammetric camera and gimble were generously provided by PhaseOne for this project.

3 Setting up the project

You do what we always do in these meetings. You wait till the next coffee break, say hello and get talking. These talks led to zoom chats from back home again and in no time our dates were getting serious ... and the project evolved from a *hey, we would love to go to Australia over coffee* to a *yes, let's do this!* We had detailed planning sessions, determining how many targets we need on the dish surface, which camera lens we should use and how to fly and take pictures.

And then there was the logistical planning. We are all academics. Is there a time where all of us are free from lecturing for a couple of weeks? Can Ansgar bring his drone to Australia like he did to Sweden (in that case it was packing all the gear into the car and drive up). He has a drone pilot licence, can he fly with that in Australia? Unfortunately the answer to both of these questions is no. At one stage during planning we seriously considered for Ansgar to do his Australian pilot license for this campaign.

In the end we teamed up with the drone team of the University of Tasmania (UTAS), equipment and student pilots to hire. Plus the necessary legal support. It turned out that the Mt Pleasant observatory – due to its vicinity to the airport – is in a no fly zone. Or at least

requiring constant communication with the tower. This was when things got fun.

A high precision total station could be rented and flown in from Geoscience Australia in Canberra, but in order to achieve the 0.1 *mm* target precision, Conny wanted to bring her spherical cat-eye prisms. So please book a flight via Singapore and not Dubai in order for your CARNET customs documents to be recognised.

Then the camera. Which camera can we use? How far away from the dish surface should we fly (or can we fly in order to stay out of the no-fly zone which ends strictly at the fence line?). It turns out that what you do as a photogrammetry expert is to talk to PhaseOne¹, the leading camera company. So Ansgar got in contact with his mate at the German office, who got in contact with the Melbourne office who got in contact with me. And yes – they are happy to lend us a camera (free of charge). Wow. I was amazed.

All I needed to do is tell my University that I want this instrument insured (which is the value of a car, or even a big car)... When science meets admin... .

4 The Measurements

By the time the team arrived in Hobart in February 2024 a lot of work had already gone into this project. And I really want to emphasise this here. I don't see how else this project could have been organised than with a bunch of specialists really wanting to get these deformations measured.

Huge credit goes to our Universities; as academics the whole team didn't charge for their time. My point here is that even if you would have found the funding to pay for all the time, what we did has never been done before in that way. Apparently this is what's needed to do VLBI. Thus I really consider it essential that we keep doing VLBI at Universities.

Back to the project. Once the team arrived, we had a rented drone flown in from Melbourne (as it turned out to be cheaper to rent one rather than replacing the batteries on our University owned drone – drone batteries have a fixed number of recharges they can do, and we had planned a lot flights). We had a camera shipped in from PhaseOne Melbourne.

¹ A link to a report about this project on the PhaseOne website can be found here: <https://www.utas.edu.au/research/projects/auscope-vlbi-project>.

Fig. 3 The drone with mounted camera taking pictures from the dish and telescope.

My colleague Arthur mounted 1000 (!) targets on 256 panels, and 60 coded targets. Only to learn that the well chosen paper doesn't withstand the Australian sun and peels off after a few days. So he did it again with better paper this time. Luckily our cherry picker which is part of the original NASA equipment from the Apollo years didn't let us down. As accounted for in the time line, the first week took some fiddling. While some of us finished preparations of the telescope (mounting scale bars, installing cat-eye targets, taking baseline measurements) – we had a drone and a camera and a pilot ready. Flying the drone over the key-hole out of sight did make them nervous. Once flying worked, we found out that the drone didn't talk to the gimble – which is the very cool camera mounting which steers the camera angle. Apparently some hiccup with different software versions. The camera had to be shipped back to Melbourne and we got a new one. (Thank you Phase One!) No one really got nervous (or no one showed it) and the first successful airborne images were taken just in time before I myself jetted off to Tsukuba to last year's IVS meeting. That was the only way the timing worked out.

Then the measuring started. Here the numbers are crazy. We had 114 telescope configurations (see Fig:4)

Fig. 4 Overview of the measurement configuration, which is complicated by the X/Y mount of the telescope. Configurations observed at least twice are marked by blue squares, while grey circles denote single experiments. A red cross indicates excluded configurations.

and 230 independent experiments, meaning flights, in each we took 300 pictures. It was literally drone-frenzy out at the observatory. Loading in the flight path, a set of batteries, flying, landing, downloading pictures, change batteries, load in the new flight file and off we go again. The team just went into production mode. Flying, at the same time taking control measurements of the structure and temperature of the telescope; downloading and processing the images. And then looking at initial results.

5 Results

And those results did throw me off my seat. To me, they look really convincing. What you see in Figure 5 is the measured variation in focal length depending on telescope position. It turns out that this is super small, with $\pm 1.5 \text{ mm}$. All the results that I am showing are published in Lösler et al. (2025) in Earth Planets Space. The measured deformation of the dish, for zenith and a fully tipped over configuration is $\pm 5 \text{ mm}$ maximum. There is a bit more movement in the receiver box itself, up to $\pm 15 \text{ mm}$, which confirms David's prior investigations. Though it turns out that this is mainly horizontal movement or a tilt and doesn't really affect the path length. And path length variation is the actual thing

Fig. 5 Estimated focal length variations ΔF for selected configurations w.r.t. $r_x = r_y = 0^\circ$. Each coloured symbol represents the measurements along one major axis of the radio telescope. Error bars indicate the 95% confidence interval of an estimate.

that we in VLBI are interested in. So next Micha did a spatial ray tracing, allowing to derive the signal path variation.

Now comes my personal highlight of this project: in order to translate the signal path variation from each individual panel into a variation of the VLBI delay, we need the illumination function. Okay. Where do we get this from? The Hobart26 antenna was a NASA tracking dish in the Apollo era, gifted to the University in 1985 to do radio astronomy. When it got moved to Tasmania and eventually used for VLBI, we had a lot of help from our friends at MIT. And to cut a long story short, last year we contacted a retired Brian Corey, who - while in the midst of a move half across the U.S. - dug through his boxes and eventually came up with the feed drawings and antenna patterns. Thank you Brian.

The final model shows delay variations of 2 mm maximum (Figure 6). This is very stable for a telescope this size. Pleas have a look in to our paper in Earth Planets Space to get all the details.

6 Conclusions

Happy ending?

Well, the good thing is that I have full trust in these measurements. And if there is any significant deformation in this telescope, it is not the gravitational deformation of the dish - I am pretty sure of that now.

Fig. 6 Polar plot of the estimated signal path variations ΔL of the 26m VLBI radio telescope in Hobart.

My colleague Arthur took a whole bunch of new measurements tackling the determination of the IVP, the invariant reference point – this time with terrestrial laser scanning. And currently we are stuck in the analysis. So if there is anyone in the room keen to assist untangling this, please talk to me, you might be part of the next amazing project.

I just want to say thank you to my colleagues directly involved in this project, but also to the whole IVS community and the people who have done all the previous surveying projects. From planning, detailed scoping, project management, funding, hiccups, novelty, high quality data through to final published results, this project had everything; and pulling this off is quite a highlight in my IVS journey so far.

References

- Lösler M, Eschelbach C, Greiwe A, Zhou B, McCallum L (2025) Innovative approach for modelling gravity-induced signal path variations of VLBI radio telescopes. *EPS*, 77:9, doi: 10.1186/s40623-024-02110-8.

Impact of the Inclination of Genesis on the VLBI Terrestrial Reference Frame

H. Wolf, L. Kern, S. Steinmetz, J. Böhm

Abstract The European Space Agency's Genesis mission, planned for launch in 2028, aims to improve the Terrestrial Reference Frame (TRF). As a dynamic space observatory, Genesis will carry instruments for all four space-geodetic techniques. Currently, the mission is planned as a polar orbit with an inclination of 95° and an altitude of 6 000 km. However, an alternative orbital configuration is under consideration with a reduced inclination of 60° . This simulation-based study investigates the impact of the inclination of Genesis on the Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) TRF, derived solely from VLBI observations to the Genesis satellite. Genesis TRFs are computed for four different scenarios, comprising two different orbital configurations, namely 97° and 60° inclination and two different networks, a network consisting of currently available VGOS stations and an extended version of this network incorporating potential future VGOS stations. The findings show that the polar orbit yields a higher precision of station coordinates compared to the inclined orbit and would therefore be preferable for the derivation of TRFs from a VLBI point of view. Moreover, the study highlights the importance of optimized scheduling, such as station-dependent scheduling of satellite observations.

Keywords VLBI, Genesis, TRF

Helene Wolf¹ · Lisa Kern¹ · Sofie Steinmetz¹ · Johannes Böhm¹
(1) Technical University Vienna, Department of Geodesy and Geoinformation, Wiedner Hauptstraße 8-10, 1040 Vienna, Austria

1 Introduction

The Genesis mission from the European Space Agency (ESA) is scheduled for launch in 2028 (Delva et al., 2023). The main objective of this mission is the enhancement of the Terrestrial Reference Frame (TRF) by providing precise local ties and space ties, which are the connections between reference points on Earth and in space, respectively. It should help to achieve the goal of a reference frame with 1 mm accuracy and 0.1 mm long-term stability (Plag and Pearlman, 2009). This satellite will serve as a co-location platform as it will be equipped with instruments dedicated to Global Navigation and Satellite Systems (GNSS), Satellite Laser Ranging (SLR), Doppler Orbitography and Radiopositioning Integrated by Satellite (DORIS) and Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI). The satellite is planned to orbit the Earth in a circular orbit at an altitude of 6 000 km. While a 95° inclination is planned, a 60° inclination is still under discussion.

As Genesis will be one of the first satellites being equipped with a dedicated VLBI transmitter (VT), various studies have explored the potential benefits of incorporating Genesis observations into VLBI sessions. The potential of VTs on GNSS satellites and Genesis in terms of station coordinate determination, but also the estimation of the right ascension of the ascending node, is investigated by Böhm and Wolf (2024). Furthermore, Schunck et al. (2024a) examined the influence of integrating Genesis observations into VLBI Global Observing System (VGOS) sessions on the accuracy of station coordinates and UT1-UTC estimates. Moreover, they investigated the development of optimized schedules including Genesis. Their research also addressed the feasibility of determining station positions using only Genesis observations and assessed the

precision of the frame tie between the Genesis and VLBI reference frames.

The cumulative visibility of Genesis across VLBI sessions scheduled in the International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS) Master Schedule 2023 and its visibility from current and potential future VGOS networks was analyzed by Schunck et al. (2024b). Recently, Wolfs and Haas (2025) presented simulations of VGOS observations of a Genesis-like satellite and the impact on the Earth Orientation Parameters (EOPs) and orbit determination.

2 Study Setup

This study examines the impact of the Genesis satellite's orbital inclination on a TRF derived solely from VLBI observations to Genesis. Two distinct theoretical inclinations, approximately 97° , which is used to represent a polar orbit, and 60° , are analyzed (see Fig. 1). The investigation is conducted using two station network configurations: one representing the currently operational VGOS network, and another representing an extended, potential future VGOS network. The station networks are illustrated in Figure 2. For the future network, only stations expected to be operational by 2028 are included. In total, four scenarios are investigated, combining the current and future networks with both satellite inclinations, namely 60° and 97° .

For each of the four scenarios, 24-hour schedules are generated weekly (every Monday) over a two-year period, resulting in a total of 104 schedules per scenario. The sessions are simulated ten times, and for each simulation, a TRF in the Genesis frame is computed. This results in ten TRFs per scenario, which are then used to assess the repeatability of the station coordinates for each individual scenario.

2.1 Scheduling

The schedules are generated using the scheduling software VieSched++ (Schartner and Böhm, 2019). Observations to Genesis are incorporated based on a two-line element (TLE) file. The satellite scans are scheduled automatically, and the satellite's weight is set to ensure that 15% of the total number of scans are allo-

Fig. 1: Theoretical ground tracks of the Genesis satellite with inclinations of (a) 60° and (b) 97° and an altitude of 6 000 km over 24 hours starting on April 1, 2022 at 00:00:00 UTC.

Fig. 2: Station networks used in this study. The current network consists of 19 stations, shown as circles. The future network is an extension of the current one and includes 7 additional planned stations, marked by triangles. Labels next to the future stations indicate the expected year of completion (e.g., F25 for 2025).

cated to Genesis. The cut-off elevation is set to 5° , and the minimum number of stations for quasar and satellite observations is set to 3 and 2, respectively. The duration of quasar and satellite scans is fixed to 30 seconds. An additional 5 seconds per scan are allocated

Fig. 3: Average number of satellite scans per session (dark blue) and average proportion of satellite scans relative to the total number of scans (light blue) per station, computed over 104 schedules for the scenario involving the current network and a Genesis satellite with 60° orbital inclination.

Fig. 4: Average number of quasar and satellite scans over 104 schedules for the four scenarios.

to calibration and overhead time, following the simulation settings used by Schunck and McCallum (2023). This scheduling strategy enables the stations to perform a large number of short scans that are well distributed across their local skies.

Figure 4 presents the average number of satellite and quasar scans across the 104 schedules for the four different scenarios. It is evident that the future network achieves a higher total number of scans overall and the scenarios using an inclination of 97° result in fewer satellite scans. Because of the overall increase in scans for the future network (due to the enhanced station coverage), the proportion of satellite scans is slightly lower, approximately 16% compared to about 18% for the current network.

However, the percentages of scans to Genesis are not uniform across all stations. While some stations

record a higher number of scans to Genesis, others contribute significantly less. This variation is influenced not only by the overall network geometry but also by individual station characteristics, such as visibility conditions (e.g., presence of nearby partner stations) and slewing rates. Figure 3 shows the average number of satellite scans and the average percentage of satellite scans over the 104 schedules for the individual stations using the current network and 60° inclination as configuration setup. It is clearly evident that stations in Europe achieve significantly more scans and a higher percentage of satellite scans compared to other stations, which can be attributed to the station distribution.

2.2 Simulation

The schedules are simulated and analyzed using the software package VieVS-VLBI of the Vienna VLBI and Satellite Software (VieVS; Böhm et al., 2018). The simulations incorporate three main error sources: troposphere, clock, and white noise. These are modeled through Monte Carlo simulations following the approach of Pany et al. (2011). The tropospheric refractive index structure constant C_n is set to $1.8 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^{-1/3}$ with a scale height of 2000 m for all stations. The wind speed is simulated with 8 m/s towards the east and 0 m/s in the northern direction. The clock is simulated as the sum of a random walk and an integrated random walk process, assuming an Allan Standard Deviation of $1 \cdot 10^{-14}$ at 50 minutes. The white noise is set to 10 ps for satellite and quasar observations.

Fig. 5: Repeatabilities of station coordinates in the East, North, and Up directions based on ten global solutions for the current network. The first row shows results for the 60° inclined orbit scenario, and the second row for the polar orbit scenario. The third row displays the average ratio of satellite scans to the total number of scans per station, computed over 104 sessions, for both orbit configurations.

2.3 Analysis

Subsequently, the simulations are analyzed in VieVS-VLBI using a least-squares adjustment. The Genesis satellite's orbit is based on a two-line element (TLE) file, and no vector between the satellite's center of mass and the VT is modeled. In the analysis, the quasar coordinates and the satellite orbit are not estimated. Tropospheric parameters, including zenith wet delays and northern and eastern gradients, are estimated using satellite and quasar observations. These parameters are estimated as piecewise-linear offsets (PWLOs) in short time intervals. The zenith wet delay is estimated every 10 minutes with relative constraints of 1.5 cm, while the northern and eastern gradients are estimated every 20 minutes with relative constraints of 0.05 cm.

The station clock with the highest number of observations is selected as the reference clock. The clocks of all other stations are estimated using satellite

and quasar observations. The behavior of the clocks is modeled as a combination of a quadratic polynomial and PWLOs with 60-minute intervals and relative constraints of 1.3 cm. The five EOPs are estimated from quasar observations only, with daily PWLOs at 00:00:00 UTC relatively constrained with $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ microarcseconds.

For each scenario, every schedule is simulated once, and the results from the single-session analysis in VieVS-VLBI are stored in a Solution Independent Exchange (SINEX) file, resulting in a total of 104 SINEX files per scenario.

The individual SINEX files are combined into a multi-session or global solution using the combination software VieCompy (Kern et al. , 2023). This is accomplished by stacking the datum-free normal equation systems, applying a geodetic datum and inverting the combined normal equation system. In this context, for each scenario, the station positions are estimated from all 104 sessions. Note that, due to

Fig. 6: Repeatabilities of station coordinates in the East, North, and Up directions based on ten global solutions for the future network. The first row shows results for the 60° inclined orbit scenario, and the second row for the polar orbit scenario. The third row displays the average ratio of satellite scans to the total number of scans per station, computed over 104 sessions, for both orbit configurations. Gray text denotes future stations.

the limited investigation period, station velocities are not derived. Moreover, time-dependent parameters, such as clocks, troposphere, and EOPs are reduced session-wise from the equations. This approach yields a coordinate catalogue with associated variance information, referenced to a common epoch and valid over the full two-year investigation period.

In order to reduce the influence of relying on a single simulation per session, ten independent simulations of the 104 sessions are generated for each of the four scenarios. This results in ten sets of 104 SINEX files, and a global TRF solution is then computed for each set of 104 SINEX files, yielding ten global solutions per scenario. Finally, the repeatabilities of the station positions in the directions East, North and Up derived from the ten global solutions are analyzed to assess the TRF estimates.

3 Results

Figure 6 and Figure 5 present the results for the current and the future network, respectively, for both tested inclinations of the Genesis satellite. The first two rows present the repeatabilities based on the ten global solutions of the station coordinates in the East, North, and Up directions.

Across all four scenarios, the station positions in the Up direction exhibit slightly higher repeatabilities compared to the East and North components. For both networks, using the polar orbit generally results in lower repeatabilities than the inclined orbit.

The bottom row in both plots shows the average percentage of satellite scans relative to the total number of scans per station over the 104 schedules for the two tested inclinations. Darker colors indicate a higher proportion of satellite scans, while lighter colors indicate fewer satellite scans. It can be seen that, in general, stations in the future network have a lower satellite-to-total scan ratio. This results from a higher number of total scans due to the increased number of stations and their improved spatial distribution. How-

ever, this does not necessarily mean that the absolute number of satellite scans per station is lower.

The station with the poorest results is HARTVGS, which, for example, shows a repeatability of 2.3 mm in the Up component in the scenario using the current network and a polar orbit. This can be attributed to the station having very few satellite observations, as indicated by its low percentage of satellite scans.

Overall, the station coordinate repeatability shows a clear dependence on the number of satellite observations, as stations with a higher number of satellite scans tend to achieve lower repeatabilities. This is expected, as the station coordinates are estimated solely from satellite observations, and a higher number of satellite scans generally improves the results as long as the overall sky coverage of the individual stations is not degraded (Wolf and Böhm, 2023).

4 Conclusion

It should be noted that this study is based on a limited sample size of only ten global solutions per scenario, due to the high computational cost of the simulation and analysis. However, the findings indicate that the polar orbit configuration yields better repeatabilities of station coordinates compared to the inclined orbit. This suggests a potential advantage of a polar orbit for deriving a TRF in the Genesis frame from a VLBI point of view. Further improvements could be achieved through optimized scheduling strategies. In particular, a station-dependent scheduling approach, e.g., increasing the satellite's weight in the scheduling process for specific stations, would help to avoid situations where certain stations carry out only a few satellite scans. This would ensure a more balanced number of satellite observations across the individual stations. Additionally, the future network reaches a higher number of scans in total and enables more satellite scans without a degradation of the sky coverage. It would be worthwhile to investigate whether increasing the number of satellite scans even further for this network configuration, thus assigning more weight to the satellite in the scheduling process, leads to additional improvements in the station coordinate repeatabilities.

5 Acknowledgements

This research was funded in whole or in part by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) 10.55776/PAT7916524.

References

- Böhm J et al. (2018), Vienna VLBI and Satellite Software (VieVS) for Geodesy and Astrometry, Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific 130, doi: 10.1088/1538-3873/aaa22b.
- Böhm J and Wolf H (2024), Opportunities with VLBI Transmitters on Satellite, International Association of Geodesy Symposia, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, doi: 10.1007/1345_2024_240.
- Delva P and Zuheir A and Blazquez A and Blossfeld M and Böhm J et al. (2023), GENESIS: co-location of geodetic techniques in space, Earth, Planets and Space 75, 5 (2023) doi: 10.1186/s40623-022-01752-w.
- Kern L and Krásná H, Böhm J, Nothnagel A, Madzak M (2023), Vienna Combination Software - VieCompy, Proceedings of the 26th European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry Working Meeting.
- Pany A and Böhm J and Macmillan D and Schuh H and Nilsson T and Wresnik J (2011), Monte Carlo simulations of the impact of troposphere, clock and measurement errors on the repeatability of VLBI positions, Journal of Geodesy 85, doi: 10.1007/s00190-010-0415-1.
- Plag H and Pearlman M (2009), Global Geodetic Observing System: Meeting the Requirements of a Global Society on a Changing Planet in 2020, Springer Berlin, doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-02687-4.
- Schartner M and Böhm J (2019), VieSched++: A New VLBI Scheduling Software for Geodesy and Astrometry, Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific, vol. 131, no. 1002. IOP Publishing, p. 084501, Jun. 18, doi: 10.1088/1538-3873/ab1820.
- Schunck D and McCallum L (2023), Observing GPS satellite signals in L-band with a realistic global VLBI network: a simulation study, Proceedings of the 12th General Meeting of the International VLBI service for Geodesy and Astrometry.
- Schunck D and McCallum L and Molera Calvés G (2024), On the Integration of VLBI Observations to GENESIS into Global VGOS Operations, Remote Sensing. 2024; 16(17):3234. doi: 10.3390/rs16173234.
- Schunck D and McCallum L and Molera Calvés G (2024), Practical Considerations of VLBI Observations to the GENESIS Mission, International Association of Geodesy Symposia, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, doi: 10.1007/1345_2024_245.
- Wolfs R and Haas R (2025), Simulating and analysing VGOS observations for Genesis orbits and EOP determination, EGU General Assembly 2025, EGU25-19542, doi: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-19542.
- Wolf H and Böhm J (2023), Optimal distribution of VLBI transmitters in the Galileo space segment for frame ties, Earth, Planets and Space 75, doi: 10.1186/s40623-023-01926-0.

Geodetic K-band VLBI observations for the clock comparison

M. Negusini, R. Ricci, M. Stagni, F. Perini, C. Bortolotti, M. Roma, G. Maccaferri, T. Jung, S. Xu, D.-Y. Byun, D.-H. Je, C. Clivati, D. Calonico, M. Pizzocaro, E. Cantoni, G. Cerretto, S. Condio, G.A. Costanzo, S. Donadello, I. Goti, M. Gozzelino, A. Mura, F. Levi, M. Risaro, M.-S. Heo, H. Kim, W.-K. Lee, Y.K. Lee, C.Y. Park, J.H. Rhee, D.-H. Yu, S.O. Yi, H. Yoon, B. Cho, P. de Vicente, J. González, C. García-Miró

Abstract We performed a clock comparison between Italy and Korea using geodetic 24-h K-band VLBI observations. The comparison involved H-masers used in Medicina and Sejong radio telescopes. The same clocks were simultaneously compared by a satellite link and by high-precision optical clocks maintained at National Metrology Institutes, Korea Research Institute of Standards and Science (KRISS) in Korea and Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRIM) in Italy, and delivered to the VLBI antennas via noise-compensated fiber links. We estimated the clock rate from VLBI data and these values were subsequently compared with clock differences derived by GPS Precise Point Positioning (PPP) and by local optical clocks. Results were in agreement at the level of 10^{-15} s/s. This result is a first confirmation that standard geodetic VLBI campaigns could be a viable approach to conduct intercontinental clocks comparisons, now possible only via satellite links. This experiment was a pilot

M. Negusini¹ · R. Ricci¹ · M. Stagni¹ · F. Perini¹ · C. Bortolotti¹ · M. Roma¹ · G. Maccaferri¹ · T. Jung² · S. Xu² · D.-Y. Byun² · D.-H. Je² · C. Clivati³ · D. Calonico³ · M. Pizzocaro³ · E. Cantoni³ · G. Cerretto³ · S. Condio³ · G.A. Costanzo³ · S. Donadello³ · I. Goti³ · M. Gozzelino³ · A. Mura³ · F. Levi³ · M. Risaro³ · M.-S. Heo⁴ · H. Kim⁴ · W.-K. Lee⁴ · Y.K. Lee⁴ · C.Y. Park⁴ · J.H. Rhee⁴ · D.-H. Yu⁴ · S.O. Yi⁵ · H. Yoon⁵ · Busan Choo⁶ · P. de Vicente⁷ · J. González⁷ · C. García-Miró⁷ (1) INAF-Istituto di Radioastronomia, via Gobetti 101, Bologna, I-40129, Italy (2) Korea Astronomy and Space Science Institute, Daedeokdae-ro 776, Yuseong-gu, Daejeon, Republic of Korea (3) Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica, Strada delle cacce 91, Torino, I-10135, Italy (4) Korea Research Institute of Standards and Science, 267 Gajeong-ro, Yuseong-gu, Daejeon, Republic of Korea (5) Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information, 245 Daehak-ro, Yuseong-gu, Daejeon, Republic of Korea (6) National Geographic Information Institute, 92 Worldcup-ro, Yeongtong-gu, Suwon-si, Gyeonggi-do, Republic of Korea (7) Yebes Observatory, Instituto Geográfico Nacional, Cerro de la Palera, Yebes, Guadalajara, 19143, Spain

test in view of the installation of new-generation, high-frequency, wideband receivers on the involved telescopes. K/Q/W band geodetic observations will allow an improvement in the accuracy of the resulting group delays and a better estimation of the clock parameters of the stations, contributing to progress in the redefinition of the second.

Keywords Optical clocks, K-band VLBI, optical fiber links

1 Introduction

A new generation of atomic clocks, based on optical transitions, can achieve fractional frequency uncertainties at the 10^{-18} level (1), (2), (3), improving by two orders of magnitude the performance of the Cesium (Cs) fountains (4), currently used to define the International System of Units (SI) second and which constitute the standard in international timekeeping (5). Optical clocks are expected to contribute to the definition of the SI second (6). Comparing such clocks over intercontinental distances is essential to verify their consistency in preparation for this redefinition. Optical clocks are already used in tests of special and general relativity (7), in research on fundamental constants (8), and in chronometric leveling (9), (10). Future applications of clock comparisons also include the creation of quantum networks for secure communication and timing (11) and the detection of gravitational waves (12).

Coherent optical fiber links can transmit frequency references via optical frequency combs up to about

two thousand kilometers with frequency instabilities on the order of 10^{-19} (13), (14), (15) but cannot be used over intercontinental distances. Over such large distances, optical clock comparisons rely on Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) frequency transfer (via the Integer Precise Point Positioning - IPPP technique, (16) and Two-Way Satellite Time and Frequency Transfer (TWSTFT, (17)).

In recent years, Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) has also demonstrated its ability to contribute to this type of research. Geodetic experiments have been designed and observations analyzed. Model parameters of the H-maser clocks, particularly their rate, have been estimated for the stations involved in the network. These values have then been used to compare optical clocks in a metrological chain. An international cooperation between the National Institute for Communication Technologies (NICT, Japan), the National Institute for Metrological Research (INRiM, Italy) and the National Institute for Astrophysics (INAF, Italy) enabled the VLBI campaign to compare lattice optical clocks between Japan and Italy, conducted in 2018-2019 (18), (19), under very special conditions: two small transportable antennas (installed in Medicina and Koganei), broadband NINJA feeds (2-14 GHz) and custom experiment design and data analysis. The relative fractional frequency difference between the H masers used on the two small antennas was then calculated and used in the metrological chain connecting the INRiM Yb optical clock to the NICT Sr optical clock thanks to the Italian Quantum Backbone (IQB) for the dissemination of the optical fiber frequency reference (the 550 km Turin-Medicina link, (15) and the Koganei optical fiber link. The resulting frequency deviation between the two optical clocks, measured via the VLBI link, was $y(\text{Yb}/\text{Sr}) = 2.5(2.8) \times 10^{-16}$, in agreement with previous measurements and with an improvement in terms of uncertainty compared to the frequency deviation obtained via GPS-IPPP ($y(\text{Yb}/\text{Sr}) = -3.2(4.0) \times 10^{-16}$). In 2021, a new collaboration was launched between the Republic of Korea and Italy to compare optical clocks using VLBI antennas; the first experiment, conducted in December 2021, will be presented in the following sections.

2 Method

The 24-hour geodetic VLBI experiment in K-band at the frequency range 21-21.4 GHz was performed on 2021 Dec 16th-17th. A network of radio telescopes between Europe—the 32 m Medicina antenna (Italy) and the 40 m Yebes antenna (Spain)—and Korea—the 22 m Sejong antenna (operated by the National Geographic Information Institute) and the three 21 m Tanma, Yonsei, and Ulsan antennas of the Korean VLBI Network (KVN, operated by the Korea Astronomy and Space Science Institute - KASI)—was used to determine the fractional frequency difference between the H-maser clocks in Korea and Medicina and then indirectly compare the Yb grating optical clocks located at INRiM (Italy) and the Korean Research Institute for Standards and Science (KRISS, Korea) by estimating their relative frequency deviation.

A metrological campaign was performed during the VLBI sessions. The KRISS H-maser clock signal was transferred to the Sejong station via a fiber optic link provided by the Korean Institute of Science and Technology Information (KISTI), while the IQB fiber optic link connects the H-maser clock governed by the Turin optical clock to the H-maser clock at the Medicina station.

Data collected by the GNSS stations over the same time period were analyzed using a GPS-IPPP approach to compare the two techniques.

A schematic of the entire experimental setup is presented in Figure 1.

3 Data analysis and Results

The raw data collected at the six VLBI antennas were transferred to the Bologna and KASI data centers for correlation with DiFX (20). Fringe fitting was performed in HOPS *fourfit* and a VGOSdb database was created and analyzed with nuSolve (21), and VieVS (22), applying ionospheric corrections on the single band data, by using the vertical Total Electron Content (TEC) values from the International GNSS Service (IGS) Global Ionospheric maps (GIMs). The clock parameters (clock rate and its uncertainty) estimated on the baseline between Medicina and Sejong are used together with the metrological and GPS campaigns results to compare the optical clocks

Fig. 1 Overview of the experimental setup of the campaign carried out in December 2021.

as H-maser differences. The final geodetic and metrological results are contained in a scientific paper that has been submitted to an international journal. The results coming from the analysis of a single campaign are in agreement at the level of 10^{-15} s/s, with the VLBI solution showing the greatest agreement with the results of the metrological campaign.

4 Conclusions and outlook

The importance of comparing distant optical clocks for the redefinition of the SI second by 2030 and how this goal can be achieved over longer distances, where fiber optic links are unavailable, using GNSS, TWSTF, and VLBI techniques, was briefly described. We then reported on the launch of a measurement campaign aimed at comparing the frequency differences of optical clocks over intercontinental distances between Europe and Korea, using the K-band geodetic VLBI technique, as a pilot project in view of future developments.

Indeed, the Italian-Korean collaboration involving metrology and radio astronomy institutes will make use of Korean compact tri-band receivers (CTRs) that

Fig. 2 Future configuration with CTRs installed at Yonsei, Pyoung Chang and Medicina radio telescopes which will be connected to optical clocks

operate simultaneously in the K, Q, and W bands (23) and space geodesy techniques whose potential has been demonstrated in (24). The CTRs are being installed on Italian radio antennas and in Korea on the KVN Yonsei and Pyoung Chang antennas. KISTI, KRISS, and KASI are also working to implement a coherent frequency link via fiber optics between the KRISS and KVN antennas.

The future prospect is to use the CTRs at Medicina, Pyoung Chang, and Yonsei for the OCC campaign (Fig. 2). An optimal frequency configuration will be selected

on the CTRs in the 18-116 GHz range. Target sources in common view between Europe and Korea, based on antenna sensitivity and the lack of structure of the source, will be chosen from the International Celestial Reference System (25). VieSched++ (26) will be used to simulate the best scheduling strategy. A dedicated high-speed data transfer link will be implemented by GARR (Italy) and KISTI (Korea). The large volume of raw data will be correlated by the DiFX correlator in both Italy and Korea. This operation will be performed by an upgraded Bologna computing cluster and a Korean national supercomputer. Data analysis of the correlated and fringe-fitted datasets will be performed on VieVS, nuSolve, and PIMA (27). The source frequency phase reference technique (28) will also be explored, along with the injected phase calibration signal, to improve phase stability and thus clock frequency uncertainty. Concurrent with the VLBI runs, GPS-IPPP measurement campaigns will also be conducted to compare the two techniques.

References

1. McGrew, W.F. *et al.*, "Atomic clock performance enabling geodesy below the centimeter level", *Nature*, 564, pp. 87–90, 2018. doi:10.1038/s41586-018-0738-2
2. Ushijima, I., Takamoto, M., Das, M., Ohkubo, T., & Katori, H. *et al.*, "Cryogenic optical lattice clocks", *Nature Photonics*, 9, pp. 185–189, 2015. doi:10.1038/nphoton.2015.5
3. Brewer, S.M., *et al.*, " Al^+ – 27 quantum logic clock with a systematic uncertainty below 10^{-18} ", *Physical Review Letters*, 123, 033201, 2019. doi:10.1103/PhysRevLett.123.033201
4. Wynards, R. & Weyers, S., "Atomic fountain clocks", *Metrologia*, 42, S64, 2005
5. Panfilo, G. & Arias, F., "Coordinated Universal Time (UTC)", *Metrologia*, 56, 042001, 2019
6. Riehle, F., Gill, P., Arias, F. & Robertsson, L., "The CIPM list of recommended frequency standard values: guidelines and procedures", *Metrologia*, 55, 188, 2018
7. Sanner, C. *et al.*, "Optical clock comparison for Lorentz symmetry testing", *Nature*, 567, PP. 204–208, 2019
8. Godun, R.M. *et al.*, "Frequency ratio of two optical clock transitions in Yb^+ – 171 and constraints on time variations of fundamental constants", *Physical Review Letters*, 113, 210801, 2014
9. J. Grotti, S. Koller, S. Vogt, S. Haefner, U. Sterr, *et al.*, "Geodesy and metrology with a transportable optical clock", *Nature Physics*, 14, PP. 437–441, 2018. doi:10.1038/s41567-017-0042-3
10. T.E. Mehlstäubler, G. Grosche, C. Lisdat, P.O. Schmidt *et al.*, "Atomic clocks for geodesy", *Reports on Progress in Physics*, 81, 064401, 2018. doi:10.1088/1361-6633/aab409
11. Komar, P. *et al.*, "A quantum network of clocks", *Nature Physics*, 10, 933, 2014
12. Kolkovitz, S. *et al.*, "Gravitational wave detection with optical lattice atomic clocks", *Phys Rev D*, 94, 124042, 2016. doi:10.1103/PhysRevD.94.124042
13. Calonico, D. *et al.*, "High-accuracy coherent optical frequency transfer over a doubled 642-km fibre link", *Appl. Phys. B*, 117, PP. 979–986, 2014
14. Clivati, C., *et al.*, "A coherent fibre-optic link for Very Long Baseline Interferometry", *IEEE Trans on Ultrason. Ferroel. Freq. Contr.*, 62, PP. 1907–1912, 2015
15. Clivati, C. *et al.*, "Common-clock very long baseline interferometry using a coherent optical fiber link", *Optica*, Vol. 7, Issue 8, pp. 1031–1037
16. Petit, G. *et al.*, " 1×10^{-16} frequency transfer by GPS PPP with integer ambiguity resolution", *Metrologia*, 52, PP. 301–309
17. Fujieda, M. *et al.*, "Carrier-phase two-way satellite frequency transfer over a very long baseline", *Metrologia*, 51, PP. 253–262, 2014
18. Pizzocaro, M. *et al.*, "Intercontinental comparison of optical atomic clocks via very long baseline interferometry", *Nature Physics*, 52, PP. 301–309, 2021
19. Sekido, M., Takefuji, K., Ujihara, H. *et al.*, "A broadband VLBI system using transportable stations for geodesy and metrology: an alternative approach to the VGOS concept", *Journal of Geodesy*, 95, article 41, 2021
20. A.T. Deller, S.J. Tingay, M. Bailes, C. West, "DiFX: A Software Correlator for VLBI Using Multiprocessor Computing Environments", *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 119, PP. 318–336, 2007. doi:10.1086/513572
21. S. Bolotin, K. Bayer, J. Gipson, D. Gordon, D. MacMillan, "The VLBI Data Analysis Software vSolve: Development Progress and Plans for the Future", In D. Behrend, K. D. Bayer and K.L. Armstrong editors, *International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2014 General Meeting Proceedings*, Science Press (Beijing), pp. 253–257, ISBN 978-7-03-042974-2
22. Boehm, J. *et al.*, "Vienna VLBI and Satellite Software(VieVS)for Geodesy and Astrometry", *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 130, 044503, 2018. doi:10.1088/1538-3873/aaa22b
23. Han S.T., Lee J.W., Lee B., Chung M.H., Lee M.S., Je D.H. *et al.*, "A millimeter-wave quasi-optical circuit for compact triple-band receiving system", *J. of Infrared, Millimeter and Terahertz waves*, 38, pp. 1487–1501, 2017
24. Xu, S., Jung, T., Zhang, B., *et al.*, "A Geodetic and Astrometric VLBI Experiment at 22/43/88/132 GHz", 2024, 'The Astronomical Journal', 168, doi: 10.3847/1538-3881/ad7afo
25. Charlot, P., *et al.*, "The third realization of the International Celestial Reference Frame by very long baseline interferometry", *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 644: 159, 2020. doi:10.1051/0004-6361/202038368

26. Schartner, M. & Boehm, J., "VieSched++: a new VLBI scheduling software for geodesy and astrometry", *PASP*, 131: 084501, 2019. doi:10.1088/1538-3873/ab1820
27. Petrov, L., Y.Y. Kovalev, E.B. Fomalont, D. Gordon. 'The VLBA Galactic Plane Survey VGaPS'. *Astron. J.*, 142, 35, 2011
28. Rioja, M. & Dodson, R., "Precise radio astrometry and new developments for the next generation of instruments", *Astron. Astrophys. Rev.*, 28: 6, 2020. doi:10.1007/s00159-020-00126-z

Operational studies of the Onsala Twin Telescopes

L. Chin Chuan, R. Haas, K. Le Bail

Abstract We present an overview of recent operational studies at the Onsala Space Observatory, focusing on the Onsala Twin Telescopes. The overview includes the so-called single-dish Tsys measurements covering the entire VGOS frequency band from 3 to 15 GHz, measurements with invar systems installed in late 2023, monitoring pcal amplitudes and phases, and first test observations using potential future frequency setups for observations of the European Space Agency (ESA) Genesis satellite.

Keywords Onsala, Twin Telescopes, VGOS, Genesis

1 Introduction

The Onsala twin telescopes (OTT) continue to participate in local and global VGOS observations. There is still potential to improve the observations, such as carefully avoiding unwanted radio frequency disturbances within the VGOS bands and understanding how the telescopes deform with temperature variations. At Onsala, we take the initiative to monitor the OTT systems and the local radio environment. The measurements and monitoring are presented in the following sections.

L. Chin Chuan, R. Haas, K. Le Bail
Chalmers University of Technology, Department of Earth, Space, and Environment, Onsala Space Observatory, Onsala, SE-439 92, Sweden

2 Tsys measurement at multiple directions

Tsys, also known as the system temperature, represents the total noise of a receiving system. It includes the noise (or power) from the radio source, the atmosphere, the receiver, and reflections from the surrounding environment. We dedicated a session of slightly more than 24 hours to monitoring the Tsys at the zenith position. Then, we dedicated another day to measure it in different directions. The expectation is that the Tsys stays stable if the environmental noise is low in that particular direction. In the following, we present the results of the Tsys monitoring sessions from 2.9 to 15.2 GHz.

Figs. 1 and 2 show the median Tsys as a function of frequency for Oe and Ow, respectively. The standard deviation colour bars show the stability of the Tsys measurement for the "frequency channels" over 96 cycles, wherein each channel is 32 MHz wide, similar to the current VGOS recording practice. Each cycle consists of three samples at 10-second intervals.

From the plots, we understand that when there is a spike in the median Tsys at a particular frequency channel, the environment at that frequency is generally radio-noisier. As expected, we can see a lot of unwanted radio signals interfering with the systems in the lower frequency band below 4 GHz, especially at Ow. It might be due to that Ow has a more sensitive feed than Oe, as the same trend manifests when the antennas point in different azimuth and elevation directions, as shown in figs. 3 and 4. The red arrows indicate the frequency from low to high.

Fig. 1 Median Tsys and its standard deviation for Oe over the frequency range 2.9–15.2 GHz when pointing at zenith.

Fig. 2 Median Tsys and its standard deviation for Ow over the frequency range 2.9–15.2 GHz when pointing at zenith.

3 Invar measurements of the OTT towers

In December 2023, invar measurement systems were installed in the OTT telescope towers to measure their structure deformation caused by temperature changes. The invar measurements monitor the temperature-induced vertical deformation of the towers, which primarily shows a seasonal signature, as demonstrated in Figs. 5 and 6.

The difference of both the raw invar measurements, sampled at 1 Hz, or averaged over different time intervals, is roughly 1 mm between the coldest months (January 2024 and 2025) and the hottest months (July and August 2024). We can also see in these two figures that the invar measurement system at Oe appears to be noisier than the one at Ow in the

Fig. 3 Standard deviations for Oe Tsys in four azimuth directions and three elevations each azimuth from 2.9 to 15.2 GHz.

short-duration periods, which is suspicious because the invar measurements should not be affected by antenna movements during observation. To investigate this phenomenon further, we dedicated a 34-hour long experiment to test the invar measurement system responses when the antenna is steady, when the antenna changes only in azimuth, and when the antenna changes only in elevation.

Table 1 Standard deviations in millimetre of the invar reading responses for Oe and Ow in seven situations: antennas not moving; antennas move in azimuth while elevation=90 degree, then elevation=45 degree; antennas move in elevation while azimuth=0 degree, then azimuth=90 degree, azimuth=180 degree, azimuth=270 degree.

Station	steady	el=90	el=45	az=0	az=90	az=180	az=270
Oe	0.090	0.110	0.111	0.094	0.090	0.091	0.093
Ow	0.092	0.096	0.098	0.095	0.098	0.098	0.098

Table 1 shows the standard deviations of the invar measurements in seven different situations. We see that both telescopes exhibit comparable levels of

Fig. 4 Standard deviations for Ow Tsys in four azimuth directions and three elevations each azimuth from 2.9 to 15.2 GHz.

Fig. 5 Invar readings for Oe from January 2024 to January 2025.

uncertainty when the antennas are standing still. The standard deviation for Oe increased by about 22 % when the antenna moved in azimuth while the elevation was constant, in contrast to only 4 % when it moved in elevation while keeping the azimuth constant. On the other hand, the standard deviation of Ow

Fig. 6 Invar readings for Ow from January 2024 to January 2025.

increased by about 5 % when the antenna moved, regardless of direction.

4 Phase cal signal monitoring

It is crucial to have a functional phase cal system in VLBI for a coherent combination of several observation channels. At the Onsala Space Observatory, we plan to monitor the phase cal amplitudes and phases of the OTT systems for every session soon. In Fig. 7 we present as an example the phase cal amplitudes and phases extracted using the m5pcal tool directly from the raw data recorded from a 24-hour VGOS session (vo5022). We average the second, third, and fourth tones of the outputs, as they are the strongest tones of our 5 MHz phase cal systems. The figures presented are for demonstration of the visualised outputs. Hence, we selected only one polarisation in band A (3.0–3.5 GHz) since the phase cal signal is strongest at low frequencies for the OTT. More detailed results are presented in Table 2.

In a comparison of the two stations presented in Fig. 7, we see that Oe has a relatively more stable phase cal with flatter amplitudes and less prominent short-term variations in the phases over 24 hours. However, the phase is still very clearly affected by the ambient temperature. The Ow phase cal amplitude became very unstable between 07:30 and 21:30 UT in two upper frequency channels in band A, which could be a result of local radio frequency interference that more strongly affected the Ow telescope, as

Fig. 7 Phase cal amplitudes (left column) and phases (right column) averaged over tone 2, 3 and 4 for vo5022 Oe (top row) and Ow (bottom row) in band A, polarisation Y.

shown also in the Tsys experiment in Section 2. More research is needed to explain the cause of the short-term seasonal variation in the phases of Ow and the reasons why the second and sixth frequency channels alter by 180 degrees in phase every scan.

Table 2 presents the RMS values of the phase cal amplitudes, the corresponding uncertainties in percentage, and the uncertainties of the RMS phases for both Oe and Ow. Only band A and band D are shown for comparison of the lowest and highest frequencies observed during the session. The average amplitude in band D is lower than in band A, and the average uncertainty is significantly higher. The same characteristic is even present within the same frequency band. For the phases, the RMS is irrelevant to this investigation. However, the uncertainty in the phase gives the impression of how stable the phases are for each frequency channel. As mentioned previously, the alternating phases for channels 2 and 6 also manifested in the tabulated results. Band D channels also have more variable phases than band A.

We also see that the amplitudes are generally lower for Ow than for Oe in band D, and so are the corresponding uncertainties. However, Ow seems to have less variable phases in comparison.

5 Genesis frequency setup tests

An upcoming European Space Agency (ESA) mission, Genesis, whose purpose is to combine and co-locate all four space geodetic techniques on one satellite platform to achieve a more accurate Terrestrial Reference Frame (TRF), will allow observations with VGOS radio telescopes (Delva et al., 2023). Genesis should send signals in four frequency bands: 3.1–3.3 GHz, 5.25–5.57 GHz, 8.2–8.4 GHz, and 9.3–9.8 GHz. As an initial test, our aim was to place (5+9+5+13) channels of 32 MHz bandwidth each per polarization in these frequency bands. Due to the requirements to observe 2n channels with the VDIF data format, 8+16+8+16 channels per polarisation must instead be observed.

Table 2 The RMS values of the phase cal amplitudes, the uncertainties of the RMS amplitudes (U_a) and the uncertainties of the RMS phases (U_p) for Oe and Ow.

Band	Pol	Chan	OE			OW		
			RMS	U_a (%)	U_p (°)	RMS	U_a (%)	U_p (°)
A	X	1	0.29	2.79	11.95	0.28	2.51	11.36
A	X	2	0.28	2.74	99.34	0.29	1.73	117.52
A	X	3	0.29	1.35	11.06	0.30	0.82	10.26
A	X	4	0.29	1.15	10.81	0.29	1.03	10.08
A	X	5	0.30	1.49	10.78	0.28	1.67	10.61
A	X	6	0.27	1.03	90.68	0.28	0.86	94.48
A	X	7	0.30	1.17	9.88	0.28	0.92	10.11
A	X	8	0.29	1.22	9.61	0.30	0.98	9.76
A	Y	1	0.28	1.78	11.31	0.29	2.26	10.52
A	Y	2	0.29	1.85	91.06	0.28	1.70	90.34
A	Y	3	0.28	0.96	13.88	0.29	0.88	9.97
A	Y	4	0.31	0.80	10.72	0.30	0.91	9.94
A	Y	5	0.30	1.01	10.13	0.29	0.98	10.06
A	Y	6	0.26	0.84	90.17	0.28	1.12	90.27
A	Y	7	0.30	0.87	9.56	0.28	1.00	9.70
A	Y	8	0.29	0.89	9.48	0.29	0.93	9.40
D	X	1	0.23	8.01	39.88	0.17	13.84	32.15
D	X	2	0.22	8.30	98.76	0.09	15.91	108.16
D	X	3	0.21	8.50	37.71	0.10	18.42	27.47
D	X	4	0.20	8.41	38.94	0.12	20.60	48.10
D	X	5	0.23	7.52	37.19	0.14	16.41	30.56
D	X	6	0.23	6.56	105.37	0.14	13.40	111.36
D	X	7	0.23	7.05	36.62	0.16	13.78	28.52
D	X	8	0.22	6.95	36.68	0.16	12.35	27.67
D	Y	1	0.23	7.75	39.29	0.15	20.14	45.88
D	Y	2	0.31	7.31	93.71	0.15	17.67	91.59
D	Y	3	0.11	11.27	37.29	0.17	13.49	17.60
D	Y	4	0.15	9.91	38.80	0.18	12.20	27.59
D	Y	5	0.24	6.47	36.68	0.17	14.06	23.84
D	Y	6	0.24	6.52	110.50	0.18	12.21	113.72
D	Y	7	0.18	8.77	36.26	0.18	11.70	25.75
D	Y	8	0.23	7.43	35.75	0.16	11.57	24.97

We can achieve this channel allocation using the DDC_V_v126 firmware of the DBBC3 and correlate it in two steps, i.e. band A+B+C and then band C+D, due to the current limitation in HOPS to process only up to 64 channels. We may also modify the channel placement for greater compatibility with current VGOS observations, using (8+8+8+8) channels of 32 MHz bandwidth each per polarisation. Of these, the (5 + 8 + 5 + 8) channels per polarization that were within the Genesis frequency range were used for correlation and fringe fitting; see Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Genesis test with recording 64 × 32 MHz channels using DBBC3 DDC_V_v125 firmware. Out of these, 10, 16, 10, 16 channels from each frequency band, respectively, were used for correlation and fringe fitting.

6 Conclusions and outlook

We are putting continuous effort in the presented areas, i.e. checking the electromagnetic environment around the observatory and its effect on VGOS observations, testing the stability of the antennas with respect to the ambient temperature, monitoring the quality of pcal amplitudes and phases during VGOS observations, and testing for potential frequency setups for upcoming VGOS observation modes.

References

Delva P, Altamimi Z, Blazquez A, et al. (2023) GENESIS: co-location of geodetic techniques in space. *Earth, Planets and Space*, 75, 5, doi: 10.1186/s40623-022-01752-w.

Holographic Characterization of the Onsala Twin Telescopes

Mugundhan V., Handirk R., Hovey G., Lerner M.S., Le Bail K., Haas R.

Abstract Holography is a technique that uses the complex electric field distribution to calculate the aperture amplitude and phase distribution of the Antenna Under Test (AUT). They can be used to infer the aperture efficiency, ray path length, and surface error distributions. We applied this technique to the Onsala Twin Telescope, where we used a geostationary satellite at a low elevation as the source. We used a real-time cross-correlator to obtain the visibilities, which were then inverted to estimate the aperture efficiency and ray-path lengths of both the Onsala Twin Telescopes (OTT). We find that the telescopes have an efficiency of $\sim 43\%$ and 40% , and a rms ray path length $\sim \leq 1.5$ mm. The decoupling of the effect of primary, secondary, and feed is currently underway. Further measurements at different elevations will be presented in the future.

Keywords Holography, Correlator, Aperture efficiency, Ray path length

1 Introduction

The VLBI2010 Global Observing System (VGOS) aims to achieve improved position accuracy compared to legacy systems, generating Earth orientation param-

Mugundhan V. ^{1,2}

(1) Department of SPASE, IIT Kanpur, Kanpur 208016, India,

(2) Onsala Space Observatory, Department of Space, Earth and Environment, Observatorievägen 90, 439 94 Sweden

Handirk R., Lerner M.S., Le Bail K., Haas R. ¹

(1) Onsala Space Observatory, Department of Space, Earth and Environment, Observatorievägen 90, 439 94 Sweden

Hovey G. ³

(3) CygnusTech Pvt. Ltd., Canada

ters and station position products with a cadence of less than one day (Petrachenko et al., 2009). It seeks to achieve this through an increase in the number of observations and minimizing systematics. Achieving these ambitious goals requires dishes that are able to slew fast, wide-band feeds, and low-noise receiver systems, data recording over a large bandwidth, and near real-time correlation.

In line with these requirements, two new dishes —the Onsala Twin Telescopes (OTT) —of 13.2 m diameter, with fast slew rates, were commissioned at the Onsala Space Observatory (Elgered et al., 2017). To maximize the aperture efficiency, these dishes use ring focus Gregorian optics (Venter et al. (2023), refer to figure 1). The dishes use a Quad ridged feed horn on the ONSA13NE, and an Eleven feed on the ONSA13SW, with the former operating from 3 GHz —14 GHz, while the latter covers a bandwidth of 2 GHz —14 GHz. These telescopes, since their inception, have regularly participated in both legacy and VGOS sessions, and have also been used for other science goals as a standalone, two-element interferometer (Varenius et al., 2022).

In addition to this, the OTT have also been used to monitor the unintended emission from large satellite constellations in the low earth orbit (LEO) on protected bands within 10 —13 GHz (Hovey et al., 2025). This is important to inform on the interference mitigation strategy for both VGOS and upcoming large astronomical observatories like the Square Kilometer Array (SKA).

To ensure that the required performance is achieved and maintained by the OTT, it becomes important to monitor different parameters like Aperture efficiency (η), System temperature (T_{sys} , regularly, as they affect the minimum detectable flux as:

$$\Delta S_{min} = \frac{2kT_{sys}}{\eta A_p \sqrt{\beta \tau}} \quad (1)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant, A_p is the area of the physical aperture, and β and τ are the integration bandwidth and time.

β and τ are user programmable; regular measurements of T_{sys} can be made using a noise switching system during observations. η is a product of various sub-efficiencies such as ground noise pick-up, feed-efficiency, reflector surface accuracy, etc. This can be characterized using simulations of the dish optics using dedicated software, viz. GRASP, and the surface accuracy of the reflector can be measured using techniques such as photogrammetry. However, to fully characterize the path of the electromagnetic wave, a more holistic approach is required, which is provided by *holography*.

2 Method

Holography is based on the Fourier relation between the aperture and field domains (Perley, 2021). The far-field distribution, E_{ff} of an aperture can be written as:

$$E_{ff}(l, m) = \int_{-\text{inf}}^{+\text{inf}} \int_{-\text{inf}}^{+\text{inf}} A(u, v) e^{-j2\pi(ul+vm)} dudv \quad (2)$$

where A is the aperture distribution, which is a function of $u = \frac{x}{\lambda}$ and $v = \frac{y}{\lambda}$, while l, m are direction cosines. This relation is valid for small pointing offsets from the bore-sight, which is indeed the case here.

The antenna under test (AUT) and the reference antenna, the former scanning across and the latter tracking a strong source, form the interferometer, which is used to effectively measure the E_{ff} . Once this has been measured, the relation described in Equation 2 can be used to invert E_{ff} to obtain $A(u, v)$.

In our case, both antennas were used as reference and AUT during different parts of the campaign. We used a geostationary satellite as the reference source, as it provides a strong signal and allows the reference antenna to be almost stationary. To measure the performance of the dish over different elevations, we plan to use celestial sources too, but these results will be presented elsewhere.

The radio frequency (RF) signals from both the OTTs are transmitted to the receiver room through optical

fibers ≈ 1 km long. They are converted back to electrical signals using the fiber to RF receiver, and power split just after the RF monitoring system, and fed to an independent receiver system.

The receiver system used a mixer to down-convert the RF signal from the antenna to an IF in the range of 30 MHz to 1 GHz. A QuickSYN¹ RF synthesizer, synchronized to the 10 MHz maser source, was used to generate the local oscillator (LO) signal. The synthesizer was controlled using a Revolution Pi², where a python script was developed to set the LO frequency and power.

The cross-correlation between the AUT and the reference can be used to map the far-field electric field distribution. For this purpose, we implemented a wide-band FX correlator firmware on an RFSoc 4x2 evaluation board³. This board takes 4 analog inputs, enabling us to obtain full polarization measurements. As the board has an AMD Zynq MPSoC⁴, which has both Programmable logic and Processor system, the correlation logic is implemented on the former, while the Ethernet data transmission is implemented in the latter. As we have 4 inputs, we compute 4 auto-correlations (AC) and 6 cross-correlation (CC) products. Each AC and CC has 1024 channels with 1 MHz resolution and is integrated in time for 1s. They are then packetized and published using the ZeroMQ framework⁵. The data acquisition system that captures these packets "subscribes" to them and forwards them to a routine to plot the correlations to a webpage, and another to save the data to an HDF5 file.

3 Scan Strategy and Data Analysis

We used the daily two-line element sets published by NORAD for EUTELSAT 16A (175.177°, 24.626°) to gener-

¹ <https://www.keysight.com/blogs/en/tech/rfmw/2023/10/23/drop-in-replacement-for-quicksyn-fsw-0020>

² <https://revolutionpi.com/de>

³ <https://www.amd.com/en/corporate/university-program/aup-boards/rfsoc4x2.html>

⁴ <https://www.amd.com/en/products/adaptive-socs-and-fpgas/soc/zynq-ultrascale-plus-rfsoc.html#product-table>

⁵ <https://zeromq.org/>

ate accurate pointing and tracking information for the holographic measurements. To obtain fine information on aperture illumination, a wide scan is required. However, this results very long holography runs. To strike a balance between the two, we carried out measurements with a scan extent of $\approx 38 \frac{\lambda}{D}$, where λ is the wavelength of observation, and D is the dish diameter. This resulted in an aperture spatial resolution of ≈ 345 mm. The angular spacing, $\Delta\theta$, between each step in a scan was $\approx \frac{\lambda}{2kD}$, where k is the oversampling factor. Using $k=1.4$ gave us an $\Delta\theta$ of $\approx 0.04^\circ$. A schematic of the scan strategy is shown in Figure 1

Fig. 1 The plot shows the scan strategy, where the antenna at the bottom-right tracks the reference, while the one at center left scans across a 4.9° across it. The blue dots are the scan-grid points, spaced at 0.042° .

The data analysis routine was developed in Python⁶. The hdf5⁷ file is read and any missing data is filled based with NaN values, to maintain continuity in time. The observation logs from BIFROST (Lerner, 2022), the telescope control and monitoring software interface at OSO, were used to separate the reference pointings from the scans. The reference pointings were then used to calibrate the time- and frequency-dependent complex gains.

The calibrated data were then gridded in azimuth (az) and elevation (el). Their power and phase distribution are verified visually to ensure that they resemble expected patterns (refer Figure 2). After this, the

⁶ <https://www.python.org/>

⁷ <https://www.hdfgroup.org/solutions/hdf5/>

data is inverted to obtain the distribution in the Aperture plane (refer Figure 3).

4 Interpretation and Results

Fig. 2 The far-field electric field amplitude (top) and phase (bottom) measured in the X Polarization of ONSA13NE.

Figure 2 shows the far-field amplitude (top panel) and phase (bottom panel) of the X-polarization from the ONSA13NE. The main lobe's maximum is at $\approx 0^\circ$. We also note that there are a lot of high frequency structures seen in the beam. The diagonal structures seen in the beam can be attributed to the feed-legs. In the phase plot, close to the boresight, the phase is zero, and starts to fluctuate between $\pm \pi$ across the field of view, which is again consistent with geometric delay increasing as we go away from the phase center. Similar structure was observed when ONSA13SE was the AUT as well.

We used the far-field patterns of the ONSA13NE's X-Pol simulated using GRASP⁸ to obtain the simulated aperture efficiency. For the dish using the quad ridge feed horn (QRFH), we estimated an $\eta \approx 57\%$ (Flygare

⁸ <https://www.ticra.com/software/grasp/>

et al., 2017). We then used this as a reference to compare it with our measurements (see Figure 3.

Fig. 3 The simulated (left) and the measured (right) aperture illumination (top) and ray path length (bottom).

In both the simulations and in the measurements of the aperture illumination, we see a “bunny ear” which has been attributed to some inaccuracy during the assembly of the QRFH. We also observe the blockage in the aperture provided by the feed-legs. The small and the large black circles represent the size of the secondary and the primary reflectors respectively. By integrating along the available aperture, the same technique we used when analyzing the simulated data, we found an $\eta \approx 43\%$ across both polarizations. Performing a similar analysis on the ONSA13SW, we found an $\eta \approx 40\%$ across both polarizations.

We converted the aperture plane phases to ray path length. In the phase plot too, we see large deviations close to and within the boundary of the “bunny-ears”, however outside this region, the phase is pretty uniform. An rms ray path length deviation of ≈ 1.5 mm is found. This is consistent with the results from Lösler et al. (2019), which considers only the primary surface.

5 Conclusions and outlook

We have presented results from holography measurements of the OTTs using a geostationary satellite as the reference source. Using these measurements, we estimate the aperture efficiency of both ONSA13NE and ONSA13SW to be $\approx 43\%$ and 40% , respectively. We

also found an rms ray path length of ≈ 1.5 mm for both dishes, which is consistent with photogrammetric measurements of the primary reflectors. In the future, we will perform extensive simulations using a model for the Eleven feed as well. We will also further decouple the different sub-efficiencies and path length contributions to account for the measured values. We plan on performing holography measurements on celestial sources like Cyg-A, Cas-A etc., so the beam and aperture can be studied over the entire frequency band and polarizations.

References

- Flygare J, Pantaleev M, Billade B, Dahlgren M, Helldner L, Haas R (2017) Sensitivity and antenna noise temperature analysis of the feed system for the Onsala twin telescopes. *Proc. 23rd EVGA Working Meeting (EVGA2017)*, Gothenburg, Sweden.
- Perley R (2021) VLA Holography. *EVLA Memo 212*, National Radio Astronomy Observatory.
- Petrachenko B, Niell A, Behrend D, Corey B, Böhm J, Chralot P, Collioud A, Gipson J, Haas R, Hobiger T, et al. (2009) Design aspects of the VLBI2010 system. Progress report of the IVS VLBI2010 committee. *Technical Report*, IVS VLBI2010 Committee.
- Elgered G, Haas R, Conway J, Hammargren R, Helldner L, Hobiger T, Pantaleev M, Wennerbäck L (2017) The Onsala twin telescopes project. *Proc. 23rd EVGA Working Meeting (EVGA2017)*, Gothenburg, Sweden.
- Lösler M, Haas R, Eschelbach C, Greiwe A (2019) Gravitational deformation of ring-focus antennas for VGOS: first investigations at the Onsala twin telescopes project. *Journal of Geodesy*, 93(10), 2069–2087.
- Venter M, Garcia-Pérez Ó, Tercero-Martínez F, López-Pérez JA, Malan S, Mey P (2023) Performance of the VGOS Radio Telescope with As-built Feed and Geometry Using Electromagnetic Simulations. *Proc. 17th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, 1–4, IEEE.
- Varenius E, Maio F, Le Bail K, Haas R (2022) Broad band flux-density monitoring of radio sources with the Onsala twin telescopes. *Experimental Astronomy*, 54(1), 137–155.
- Hovey G, Vijayaraghavan M, Di Vruno F, Haas R, Le Bail K, Chin Chuan L (2025) LEO Satellites and Antenna Performance Investigations with the Onsala Twin Telescopes. *Proc. International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2024 General Meeting*, p. 11.
- Lerner M (2022) *The BIFROST User's Handbook*. BIFROST Collaboration.

Gravitational deformation measurement of 20 m radio telescope on Svalbard

Per Olof Hedekvist (ORCID: 0000-0003-0801-3124), Carsten Rieck, Per Jarlemark, Jörgen Spetz and Susana Garcia Espada

Abstract With the ongoing development and improvements of Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) for Geodesy, with precision aiming to better than 1 mm, the participating radio telescopes must be characterized with respect to gravitational deformation. The resulting correction coefficients will be connected to the elevation angle at the observation and can be implemented even on historical data from previous measurements. Thus, the benefits of scanning old telescopes, even on the rim of decommissioning, are still substantial. One of the busiest telescopes in Geodetic VLBI have been the 20 m radio telescope in Ny Ålesund on Svalbard. During 2020, we scanned this telescope using high performance, commercially available distance and 3D scanning equipment and calculated a correction table for the deformation. The measurements indicate that the telescope dish is stable with correction coefficients below 1.5 mm when changed from 0° – 90° elevation angle. The data from this study has been included in the newest International Terrestrial Reference Frame, ITRF2020.

Keywords NYALES20, ITRF2020, IVS, VLBI

Per Olof Hedekvist, Carsten Rieck, Per Jarlemark, Jörgen Spetz
RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, 50462 Borås, Sweden
(emails: per.olof.hedekvist@ri.se, carsten.rieck@ri.se and jorgen.spetz@ri.se) , Per Jarlemark died 2022.

Susana Garcia Espada
Norwegian Mapping Authority
(email: SusanaGarcia.Espada@kartverket.no)

This measurement was possible thanks to the engagement and support by Torbjørn Nørbech, Oddvar Bråvold Tangen, and Ann-Silje Kirkvik at the Norwegian Mapping Authority, as well as Axel Meldahl and Simon L'orange at the Norwegian Mapping Authority's Geodetic Earth Observatory in Ny Ålesund.

1 Introduction

To enhance the precision of geodetic measurements utilizing Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI), there is an effort to determine the deformation of these large parabolic antennas caused by gravity. These additional corrections, where the delay for each elevation is reported, has been submitted to the update of the International Terrestrial Reference Frame 2020 (ITRF2020), assembled and realized by the International Earth Rotation and Reference Systems Service (IERS). In this updated ITRF2020, gravitational deformation data are included for Effelsberg 100 m [1], Gilmore Creek 26 m [2], Medicina 32 m [3], Noto 32 m [4], Onsala 20 m [5], Onsala 13m NE and SW [6], Wetzell 20 m, 13m S and N [7] and Yebes 40 m [8]. While the correction in focal depth of the larger antennas have been estimated to more than 97 mm [1], the small 13 m antennas operating in pairs are less affected by gravity, with corrections below 1 mm [7]. The 20 m radio telescope in Ny Ålesund was the northernmost radio telescope, located on 78.9° N, 11.9° E. At this high latitude it has been useful in almost all VLBI campaigns since it was inaugurated in 1994, both in cooperation with telescopes on the Atlantic side as well as on the Pacific side of the earth, utilizing its view above the north pole. The telescope was decommissioned in August 2023, and has now

The measurements on site was possible through financial support by Statens Kartverk in Norway, while the preparations and model development was a part of the project 18SIB01 GeoMentre, which have received funding from the European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR, funder ID 10.13039/100014132) programme cofinanced by the participating states and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Fig. 1 Photograph of scanner, mounted on telescope struts close to the receiver (left). Photo of laser based distance meter, mounted below telescope dish, measuring through the manhole in center part of dish (right).

been fully dismantled. The VLBI operations have been replaced by the two 13 m telescopes NYALES13S and NYALES13N located at Brandal, 1.5 km north of the old telescope.

1.1 Preparations and setup

The 20 m parabolic telescope in Ny Ålesund (NYALES20) was a prime focus telescope, with only a primary reflector and the receiver positioned in its focus. Its gravitational deformation coefficients are based on measurements acquired between August 29 and September 5, 2020, while the temperatures varied between +1 to +5 °C, during constantly cloudy skies. To evaluate the curvature of the parabolic mirror, a Leica HDS7000 laser scanner was used, with a linearity better than 1 mm, beam divergence below 0.3 mrad and a range noise approximately 0.4 mm from the gray surface of the telescope dish. The scanner delivers a point cloud of reflections, which was numerically interpolated to a perfect paraboloid shape using least square method on each sample. The result of the calculations is then the focal point of this numerical parabola. Finally, the distance from the center of the mirror to the receiver was measured using a Micro-Epsilon "optical Non-Contact Displacement Transducer" (optoNCDT ILR), and added to the analysis. On the Transducer there is also an accelerometer mounted, which is an

additional verification to pair the measured distance to the receiver with the occurring elevation. Since the receiver is mounted on four struts secured in the base structure and not attached to the telescope dish, this distance must be included as a separate term. The measurements are based on an extension of the setup used in [9] and [10], however with an updated analysis algorithm since ONSA20 is a Cassegrain telescope. The resulting delay correction is the result of the integration of a presumed signal entering the parabolic main dish. To weigh the influence of signal reflected in different parts of the dish, an illumination function is used similar to [5].

1.2 Measurements

During the measurements, the scanner was mounted close to the receiver in the focal point of the telescope, since the performance of the scanner is best when the surface is perpendicular to the angle of incidence from the laser. It was mounted using the same pneumatically controlled ball joint as described in [9], enabling a released hanging when the telescope is moving, and a stiff fastening during measurement. To ensure that the scanner could be perfectly vertical independent of telescope elevation, the mount at the antenna structure where carefully tuned with wedges, as seen in Figure 1 left.

The scanner was mounted every morning and removed every evening, using the 5/8" threaded screw. The zero-direction of the scans are thereby arbitrary from one day to another, and all scans must be analyzed as separate individual scans.

The scanning was made at elevations of 2° (lowest), 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 75° and 88.5° (highest). All measurements were made at 180° azimuth angle, after an evaluation at different azimuths during preparation, confirming that the influence on the gravitational deformation would be negligible. At each elevation, both a 180° scan (covering the full space once) and a 360° scan (adding twice amount of data to the point cloud) was performed, however in the analysis, only the first scans were used due to a non-negligible angular offset of the scanner, adding offset noise to the additional points achieved in the second scans. The elevation schedule was changed every day, from 15° steps low to high, to 15° steps high to low, and also 30° steps

Fig. 2 Telescope receiver, mounted at primary focus of telescope dish. With a red dot to the right, indicating where the distance meter measure the displacement.

both directions, covering both even and odd 15° elevations. Influence of any hysteresis were thereby eliminated. With the addition of an area scan to document the vicinity of the site, there was in total 104 scans of the telescope, where the 18 best have been used as input for the calculation of the correction coefficients.

The optoNCDT is mounted on the stable fixtures of the telescope below the center opening in vertex, as shown in Figure 1 right. In this position it was sufficiently protected from rain, taking onto account that even if the Laser Ranger is water and dust proof (IP65), the Vaisala temp and accelerometer is only IP44. The red laser is aligned to measure the distance to the surface of the detector enclosure, as seen by the red dot in Figure 2. The offset from this surface to the detector is measured using a caliper, and the distance from vertex to the reference plane of the transducer is measured through putting a lid in vertex and documenting this as the offset. This range meter was operational 24 hours/day enabling detection of a possible temperature dependence of the structure. Data from the range meter was paired with associated 3D scan through the time stamps, in reference to UTC(SP) through ntp, and through elevation angle from log file and accelerometer.

2 Analysis

The calculations of the focal length correction is based on the theory previously developed for the Effelsberg telescope [1], also applied for ONSA20 in [5], however

with the adjustment that no secondary reflector is present. Data is evaluated from the measurement at 15° separation, with three measurements on each angle. These datapoints are used to interpolate to a continuous curve using a least square method, and from the curve, numerical values of the correction is calculated for each 1° . Finally, the reference is set to 0 correction at 90° , where in theory the telescope should be a symmetrical parabola where gravity affects the rim evenly around the circle. The resulting discrepancy from the ideal parabola is plotted for each elevation and each measurement with a color scheme as shown in the inset in Figure 3 for 2° .

The delay correction is calculated as the distance (in mm), which is insterted in the IRTF2020 lists with an additional 3.336 scale factor for time (in ps). The combined effects are included in equation 1:

$$\Delta L = \alpha_V \Delta V + \alpha_F \Delta F + \alpha_R \Delta R \quad (1)$$

Where ΔV , ΔF and ΔR are the variations in focal length, vertex position and primary focus, respectively, while α_V , α_F and α_R are the scaling factors related to the separation of vertex of paraboloid from elevation axis, the focal length variation of the paraboloid and the defocused optics, respectively. The scaling factor α_R is calculated following the report of Clark and Thomsen of 1988 [2] for a similar antenna type, as

$$\alpha_R = \frac{\int_{0.7}^{10} \frac{1-t^2}{1+t^2} 2\pi r I(r) dr}{\int_{0.7}^{10} 2\pi r I(r) dr} \quad (2)$$

where the limits of the numeric integration, $r = 0.7$ m to 10 m, refers to the radius of the hole in the center of the dish to the rim.

$$t = \frac{r}{f_{ref}} \quad (3)$$

Where $f_{ref} = 8.59$ m is the focal length of the unperturbed parabola, and the denominator is included for normalization. Furthermore, $\alpha_V = -1 - \alpha_R$ and $\alpha_F = 1 - \alpha_R$ [1]. There was no detailed information available on the radiation pattern of the horn antenna, so the best estimate was determined to set the illumination, I , to -10 dB at the rim, in accordance with [2]. We used a function (in dB) [5]

$$I(\eta) = c_1(1 - \cos^2(\eta c_2)) \quad (4)$$

Where c_1 and c_2 are coefficients related to the receiver and the aperture angle η equals:

$$\eta = \arctan\left(\frac{r}{f_{ref} - r^2/4f_{ref}}\right) \quad (5)$$

At the rim, $r = 10$ m, calculations give the angle $\eta_m = 1.0543^\circ$. In the analysis, c_2 was chosen to $c_2 = 0.07553$ based on experience from previous antenna analysis. c_1 was calculated from the requirement that $I(\eta_m) = -10$ dB, resulting in, $c_1 = -1580.277$. The reasonable choice of $c_2 = 0.07553$ is explained by the Taylor expansion of the parabolic equation

$$1 - \cos^2(x) = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{2x^2}{2} + H\right) = x^2 - H \quad (6)$$

Where H are terms of higher order in x starting with a kx^4 term. Equation (4) can thereby be approximated with

$$I(\eta) = c_1(\eta c_2)^2 \quad (7)$$

i.e. a parabolic function fully determined by the requirement that the rim value should be -10 dB, which gives the combined coefficient $c_1 c_2^2$. The limit of this approximation is that

$$c_2 \eta_m \ll 1 \quad (8)$$

From the choice of illumination function and rim illumination of -10 dB the results are $\alpha_R = 0.815$ (and $\alpha_F = 0.185$, $\alpha_V = -1.815$). The sensitivity of the coefficient α_F (and indirectly of α_R , α_V) to illumination values was investigated, shown in Figure 3. The illumination function is based on the receiver gain and does not take interference from the different path lengths into account. This will merely add the attenuation of the signal closer to the rim, and the influence on the total delay can be expanded from the figure.

From the graph in Figure 3, it is apparent that a mis-modelling of the rim illumination by e.g. 2.5 dB will change α_R and α_F in opposite directions by approximately 0.02. The consequence on the total gravity deformation model is a change by approximately 0.15 mm at 0° elevation.

Furthermore, the changes in ΔR and ΔF will add constructively. Additionally, the position for elevation rotation of the telescope must be included in the final analysis. Based on the 3D scanning and photographic

Fig. 3 Graphical illustration of the sensitivity of the focal length scaling factor, with respect to the illumination at the rim. The inset shows a visual representation of the telescope dish, where colors indicate measured discrepancies from the best estimate mathematical parabola.

Fig. 4 Calculated focal lengths from the 3D scans at different elevations, and the final deformation curve based on least square method of the samples.

documentation, this axis is positioned 2.77 m below vertex, with an uncertainty of 0.01 m.

The resulting deformation coefficients are calculated at 1° increments calculated from the sample ensembles at 15° difference and a least square analysis, shown graphically in Figure 4.

2.1 Uncertainties

The estimated uncertainty of the coefficients is based on the principles of GUM [11], using the distribution of measured values of the focal length, $\Delta F_m = 0.33$ mm, the influence of the illumination at the rim $\Delta I_{ill} = 0.15$ mm, and the uncertainties related to the 3D scanner and the laser ranger (0.4 mm and 0.1 mm respectively).

The uncertainty budget is presented in Table 1 and the estimated combined standard uncertainty of the focal length correction coefficients is thus 0.097 mm.

Table 1 Uncertainty budget for the reported correction factor

Quantity	Est	Unit	Probability distribution	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to the standard uncertainty
Distribution	0.33	mm	Normal	0.185	0.061
Illum @ rim	0.15	mm	Trinagular	1	0.061
3D scanner	0.4	mm	Rectangular	0.185	0.043
NCDT ILR	0.1	mm	Rectangular	0.185	0.011
Combined uncertainty (k=1)					0.097

3 Results

The final calculated corrections for NYALES20 are plotted in Figure 5 and presented in Table 2 for each single degree of elevation. Figure 5 also shows the components in the calculations of dL , where it is also visualized how the components add and to some extent counteract each other.

The calculated gravitational correction factors at an increment of 1° of elevation are presented in Table 2 below.

4 Conclusions

The numbers in Table 2 have been reported to IVS and included in the calculations for ITRF2020. The 20 m telescope at Kokee Park (KOKEE) has the same design and is therefore included with the same corrections as NYALES20. The analysis is solely based on correction for delay with respect to the gravitational effect at dif-

Fig. 5 Calculated correction factor dL (black) and its components $\alpha_V * dV$ (green), $\alpha_R * dR$ (blue) and $\alpha_V * dV$ (red). Presuming 0 mm correction at 90° elevation.

Table 2 Calculated gravitational correction factors

Elev	Corr	Elev	Corr	Elev	Corr	Elev	Corr
°	mm	°	mm	°	mm	°	mm
1	1.372	24	0.634	47	0.119	70	-0.092
2	1.337	25	0.606	48	0.103	71	-0.094
3	1.302	26	0.579	49	0.087	72	-0.094
4	1.267	27	0.552	50	0.073	73	-0.095
5	1.232	28	0.525	51	0.058	74	-0.094
6	1.198	29	0.499	52	0.045	75	-0.093
7	1.164	30	0.474	53	0.032	76	-0.091
8	1.130	31	0.449	54	0.020	77	-0.089
9	1.097	32	0.424	55	0.008	78	-0.086
10	1.063	33	0.400	56	-0.003	79	-0.082
11	1.031	34	0.377	57	-0.014	80	-0.078
12	0.998	35	0.354	58	-0.023	81	-0.073
13	0.966	36	0.331	59	-0.033	82	-0.068
14	0.934	37	0.309	60	-0.041	83	-0.061
15	0.902	38	0.287	61	-0.049	84	-0.054
16	0.871	39	0.266	62	-0.057	85	-0.047
17	0.840	40	0.246	63	-0.063	86	-0.039
18	0.809	41	0.226	64	-0.069	87	-0.030
19	0.779	42	0.207	65	-0.075	88	-0.021
20	0.749	43	0.188	66	-0.079	89	-0.011
21	0.720	44	0.170	67	-0.084	90	0.000
22	0.691	45	0.152	68	-0.087		
23	0.662	46	0.135	69	-0.090		

ferent elevation angles. No temperature dependence, as in [5] is taken into account. Neither are any amplitude variations caused by movement of the receiver out of focus. Nevertheless, the weight of the different spatial components affecting the total delay are based on the magnitude of the signal from each segment. Furthermore, the presented analysis is based on scans

Fig. 6 3D scan of the area surrounding the telescope.

from -2° to 182° , and the resulting parameters are based on three independent scans, at three different days and with arbitrary 0° reference of the scans. The resulting discrepancies from misalignment of the scanner axis, as thoroughly analyzed in [10] is thus handled through averaging. Nevertheless, all data are available for further independent evaluation [12]. Observing that the physical limitations of the telescope structure inhibit the optically deduced focal length variations, Bergstrand et al. [9] proposed modifications to the model in Equation 1. The complete reflector-receiver assembly is included in the point cloud [12], making an investigation of the difference between the proposed ray path centroid approach and the classic Clark and Thomsen model openly available. The position and environment surrounding NYALES20 is scanned for digital documentation, where a picture from this 3D point cloud is shown in Figure 6.

References

1. Artz, T., Springer, A. & Nothnagel, A (2014) A complete VLBI delay model for deforming radio telescopes: the Effelsberg case *J Geod*, 88, 1145-1161, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-014-0749-1>
2. Clark, T. A. & Thomsen, P. Deformation in VLBI Antennas *NASA Technical Memorandum 100696*
3. Sarti, P., Abbondanza, C. & Vittuari, L. (2009) Gravity-dependent signal path variation in a large VLBI telescope modelled with a combination of surveying methods *J Geod*, 83, 1115-1126 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-009-0331-4>
4. Sarti P, Negusini M, & Abbondanza C. (2010) Improved geodetic European very-long-baseline interferometry solution using models of antenna gravitational deformation *Ann. Geophys.* 53, 5-6 doi: 10.4401/ag-4739
5. Nothnagel, A., Holst, C. & Haas, R. (2019) A VLBI delay model for gravitational deformations of the Onsala 20 m radio telescope and the impact on its global coordinates *J Geod*, 93, 2019-2036 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-019-01299-X>
6. Lösler, M., Haas, R., Eschelbach, C. et al. (2019) Gravitational deformation of ring-focus antennas for VGOS: first investigations at the Onsala twin telescopes project *J Geod* 93, 2096-2087 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-019-01302-5>
7. (2019) Reported to IVS Analysis Coordinator by Christian Plotz as contribution to ITRF2020 [https://ivscc.gsfc.nasa.gov/IVS-AC/IVS-AC.ITRF2020.update.htm](https://ivscc.gsfc.nasa.gov/IVS_AC/IVS-AC.ITRF2020.update.htm)
8. Nothnagel, A., Springer, A., Heinz, E., Artz, T., & de Vicente, P. (2014) Gravitational Deformation Effects: The Yebes 40-m Telescope Case *Proceedings 2014 IVS General Meeting* 158-162
9. Bergstrand, S., Herbertsson, M., Rieck, C (2019) A gravitational telescope deformation model for geodetic VLBI *J Geod* 93, 669-680 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-018-1188-1>
10. Holst C, Schunck D, Nothnagel A, Haas R, Wennerbäck L, Olofsson H, Hammargren R, Kuhlmann H.(2017) Terrestrial Laser Scanner Two-Face Measurements for Analyzing the Elevation-Dependent Deformation of the Onsala Space Observatory 20-m Radio Telescope's Main Reflector in a Bundle Adjustment *Sensors* 17(8):1833 doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s17081833>
11. BIPM, IEC, IFCC, ILAC, ISO, IUPAC, IUPAP, and OIML Evaluation of measurement data — Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement. Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, JCGM 100:2008. https://www.bipm.org/documents/20126/2071204/JCGM_100_2008_E.pdf/cboef43f-baa5-11cf-3f85-4dcd86f77bd6
12. <https://zenodo.org/communities/nyales20scan/>

The CX/Ka-band receiver system for Geodesy and Astrometry of the Korean VLBI Network

J. Cho, M.H. Chung, J.H. Choi, S.T. Han

Abstract We have developed a new VLBI receiver, which enables to make simultaneous observations in C/X and Ka bands (C: 6.2~7.0 GHz, X:8.0~8.8 GHz and Ka: 28~34 GHz). The primary motivations behind this development were that S-band is mostly excluded in observation due to severe condition of radio frequency interference (RFI) in Korea and we are planning to participate in the recent activities on multi-band Astrometry. The measured noise temperatures of the developed receiver system are around 40K at 6.2~7.0 GHz, 30K at 8.0~8.8 GHz, and 30K at 28~34 GHz, respectively. When measuring the receiver noise temperatures, the quasi-optical system was not included and it is likely possible that the total receiver noise temperatures go higher than the above measured values due to larger beam sizes at lower frequency band compared to mirrors in the quasi-optical system. Contrary to low-frequency VLBI receiver system of which the feedhorn is located directly at Cassegrain focal point or primary focus, the developed receiver system utilizes a quasi-optics through which beam waist sizes are changed to be appropriate at Cassegrain focal point of the Korean VLBI Network (KVN) radio telescope. Since the KVN antenna was designed for millimeter-wave VLBI observation, the antenna focal length is much longer than typical lower frequency VLBI antenna. It means that the feedhorn size for lower frequency observation using the KVN antenna must be extremely large. In order to avoid this feedhorn size problem, a quasi-optical system using two ellipsoidal mirrors was designed for the

CX/Ka-band receiver system. Septum polarizers have been developed for dual-circular polarization observations. Directional couplers for phase-calibration noise injection are combined with the septum polarizer for CX/Ka-band. The developed receiver system with the quasi-optical system will be installed at Pyeongchang site, which is one of 4 sites of the KVN early this year. The second receiver system will be assembled until this year and it will be installed at Yonsei site of the KVN in the next year. These receivers will be used for geodetic and astrometric experimental campaign in collaboration with National Geographic Information Institute (NGII) in the following years. In addition, it is also being planned that the developed CX/Ka-band receiver system will be used spacecraft tracking test observations.

Keywords CX/Ka-band, Geodetic receiver, KVN

1 Introduction

We have developed a new VLBI receiver, which enables to make simultaneous observation in CX and Ka bands and its layout is shown in figure 1. Specifications and noise temperatures of the receiver are summarized below also as shown in figure 2 and 3.

- C band range: 6.2-7.0 GHz
- X band range: 8.0-8.8 GHz
- Ka band range: 28-34 GHz
- Dual-band Feedhorn
- Dual circular polarization in all bands

J. Cho¹, M.H. Chung¹, J.H. Choi¹, S.T. Han²

(1) Korea Astronomy and Space Science Institute, Daeduk-daero 776, Daejeon, 34055 Republic of Korea

(2) With-wave, Saeun-ro 329, Giheung-gu, Yongin-si, Gyeonggi-do 17078 Republic of Korea

Fig. 1 CX/Ka bands receiver system.

Fig. 2 Newly developed coaxial dual bands feedhorn for simultaneous CX/Ka-band observation of the KVN.

Fig. 3 Measured noise temperatures at CX-band (left) and Ka band (right).

2 Quasi-optics

Due to the KVN antenna design which was optimized to millimeter-wave observation, a feedhorn size for relatively low frequency must be extremely large. In order to avoid this feedhorn size problem, a quasi-optical array using two ellipsoidal mirrors and three flat mirrors was designed for the CX/Ka-band receiver system. As shown figure 4 and 5, GRASP simulation of the quasi-optical system has been done.

3 Future works

The developed receiver system with the quasi-optical array will be installed at Pyeongchang site, which is one

Fig. 4 The quasi-optics of the receiver (GRASP Simulation).

Fig. 5 GRASP beam profiles.

Fig. 6 The receiver room layout of the KVN Pyeongchang.

of 4 sites of the KVN in the first half of this year. Figure 6 shows the expected layout of the geodetic receiver and the others to be installed in the KVN Pyeongchang receiver room. The second receiver system will be assembled within this year and it will be installed at the KVN Yonsei site in the next year. These receivers will be used for geodetic and astrometric experimental campaign in collaboration with National Geographic Information Institute (NGII) in the following years. In addition, a test observation to spacecraft is also planned in near future.

4 Acknowledgement

This work has been supported by Korea Astronomy and Space Science Institute of Korea Aerospace Administration as part of a Space Geodesy Project in collaboration with the KVN.

DBBC4 - A VERY WIDE BANDWIDTH VLBI ENVIRONMENT VGOS SUITABLE

G. Tuccari, H. Rottmann, M. Wunderlich, S. Dornbusch, A. Roy, A. Gupta, W. Alef

Abstract The development of the newer version of the VLBI digital front- and back-end system belonging to the DBBC systems' family is under way as a work-package of the EU-funded RadioBlocks Project. This instrument dedicated to increase the VLBI observation capabilities in terms of bandwidth and output data rate involves a number of relevant novelties ranging from the full 32 GHz digitized input band in a number of up to 8 RF/IFs per system, to a fast recording system, and is including for the first time in a VLBI system the implementation of a hardware AI processor. The DBBC4 can be implemented as a distributed system of elements to be positioned in different parts of the radio-telescope site, in contrast to the more traditional way of in a single box. Distributed elements which can operate also stand-alone are: DiFrEndVGOS covering the entire VGOS range 2 – 14 GHz with a single sampler in double polarization, DiFrEnd28 with full 28 GHz bandwidth, DiFrEnd4T with 6 GHz bandwidth in the range 0 – 33 GHz. The first one can also be used in conjunction with the DBBC3 to digitize the full VGOS band and replace any analogue frequency conversion. All the distributed elements can have backend functionality being able to produce channelized VDIF output packets to be recorded or to be sent through fiber to the correlator. The progress of the DBBC4 development is reported together with a comprehensive description.

Keywords Digital backend, DBBC

Gino Tuccari^{1,2} · Helge Rottmann¹ · Michael Wunderlich¹ · Sven Dornbusch¹ · Alan Roy¹ · Asmita Gupta¹ · Walter Alef¹

(1) INAF- Istituto di Radioastronomia via Gobetti 101 Bologna 40129 Italy

(2) Max Planck Institute fuer Radioastronomie, Auf dem Huegel 69, Bonn 53121 Germany

1 Introduction

The DBBC4 will be a key technical component in enabling new scientific applications in the rapidly evolving field of wide-band, multi-frequency astronomical and geodetic VLBI and will set a new standard in the area of VLBI backends. Technically the DBBC4 will incorporate the latest state-of-the-art sampling technology enabling an increase of the processed bandwidth by a factor of eight compared to the DBBC3, the predecessor system and current de-facto standard for astronomical and geodetic VLBI. The use of artificial intelligence algorithms will allow a number of new possibilities ranging from the radio feature detection up to the mitigation of radio frequency interference (RFI) in near real-time. This in particular is one of the most severe issues to be addressed when increasing the observing bandwidth. The DBBC4 is the latest in the successful family of DBBC backends (DBBC, DBBC2, DBBC3) developed in a long-lasting collaboration between INAF (Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica, Italy) and the MPIfR. The DBBC4 key technologies are based on and extend the developments of the BRAND (BRoad-bAND) digital receiver project covering the 1.5 – 15.5 GHz band, which fully includes the 2 – 14 GHz IVS VGOS band.

The DBBC4 backend is intended to offer the following capabilities and features:

- **Input bandwidth:** 274.4 GHz maximum full aggregate bandwidth realized by 8×28.8 GHz in digital front- or backend plus 8×5.5 GHz in ancillary digital front-end.
- **Output data rate:** up to: 1 Tbps @ 2-bit, 2 Tbps @ 4-bit, 4 Tbps @ 8-bit

- **Processing modes:** DSC (full band for data transfer), OCT (wide bands defined in the input band), DDC (narrow band tunable down-conversion)
- **New features:** Burst-mode, AI-mode for RFI-mitigation and transient detection, net-to-memory/disk capability

2 DBBC4 Architecture

The new system provides vastly greater bandwidth and agile signal processing capabilities, while simultaneously offering a feature-compatible upgrade path from earlier DBBC installations. The main architectural difference in the DBBC4 is that it is a distributed system. Traditionally in radio-astronomical data acquisition systems, the digital back-end is well separated from the analogue part of the receiver, they being in widely-different physical locations. Typically the interface between analogue and digital domains, the sampler, is located with the digital system since these systems must run synchronously. This architectural choice was revisited in the BRAND-EVN project, where we split the traditional monolithic back-end into a network-attached ultra wideband digital front-end (called DI-FR-END) and a remote digital back-end; the front-end carries out simple digitization right at the receiver, while the bulk of signal processing is done by the digital backed at a different location where, e.g. cooling and RFI suppression is easier.

The choice to locate the sampler with the receiver offers us superior performance in terms of bandwidth, phase stability, higher dynamic range, and offers the greater ease of transporting digital rather than analogue signals to the backend area. Such digital data transport is robust and simple and can carry pure sampled or preprocessed digital data. This architecture comes with its challenges though, in terms of RFI shielding between the digital sampler and the nearby and very sensitive front end.

Although we envisage that most DBBC4 installations would use the distributed configuration between digital front- and back-ends, it is still possible to combine the entire functionality in a single unit in the back-end area. This can be useful in particular when existing receivers are already routed to this area, or when very high frequency (sub-millimeter) receivers are used, and they include frequency conversions in

the antenna focal area. To accommodate such solutions, dedicated analogue conditioning and sampler modules are provided.

The distributed system is considered not only for the digital front-end, but includes other possible “dislocated” elements in support of the more advanced functions offered by the DBBC4. These elements are sensors which collaborate with the DBBC4 main unit to provide information in support of new functionalities. Some of those will be described later in this document, while still a larger number will be defined during the period of development and even at a later stage when the DBBC4 will be operational in the field.

The DBBC4 contains several functional entities already present in previous backend models, but introduces a number of new elements:

- 100GCoMo Module, analogue conditioning
- ADCore4 Module, A/D converter and digital processor
- FILA100G, data storage and network interface
- A-EYE, AI deep neural network controller
- DiFrEnd28, digital 28 GHz front-end,
- DiFrEndVGOS, implementation of the DiFrEnd28 dedicated to VGOS observations to be used even in conjunction with a DBBC3
- DiFrEnd4T, digital 40 GHz front-end
- CONE, a number of different elements with dedicated functionalities to operate with the A-EYE Controller
- ROD, a number of different elements with dedicated functionalities to operate with the A-EYE Controller

The signal coming from the analogue front-end requires conditioning to be applied before being converted to digital format. For this purpose, the 100GCoMo module performs the functions of optimizing the amplitude, measuring the total power in pre-determined frequency ranges inside the input band, and applying ad-hoc filters. The output signal from the 100GCoMo is connected to the analogue input of the ADCore4.

Alternatively to the analogue input at the DBBC4, the analogue signal of the receiver can be digitized by the digital front-end with 28 GHz bandwidth DiFrEnd28 at or close to the receiver and be transported and inserted into the system through the digital input. Similarly a 5.5 GHz bandwidth in the range up to 40 GHz input can feed the DiFrEnd4T part.

Fig. 1 DBBC4 architecture

The ADCore4 is the central element of the ‘control room’ system and is able to perform the double functionality of analogue to digital conversion and digital data processing. After conversion, the functions as required by the particular observation are applied. The modes available are DSC, OCT, and DDC, as already well established in the previous versions of the DBBC. Improvements to these modes are being applied, but still maintaining compatibility with the existing modes. More details are provided in ADCore4 section.

The data with the final bandwidth and data rate, ready to be transferred to the correlator or to be recorded, are sent via the FILA100G to prepare the final aggregate format in single- or multi-stream, depending on the output data rate. Before the composition of the final format it is possible to store an amount of data to be used for the burst mode function. An additional possibility is offered by performing the data storage on external NVMe SSD units. Here, the direct connection net to PCI-e offers the possibility to skip any intermediate data transfer with great advantage to the writing data rate.

Notice particularly the newest addition in the DBBC family offered by the DBBC4, namely the Artificial Intelligence controller, called A-Eye. This has great potential in a number of modes it provides for both single-dish and VLBI observations, for example in RFI mitigation. To operate in real time, the controller can make use of a number of additional elements, named CONE and ROD. The first type supports the more complex functionalities to preprocess the signal than does the second, which simply forwards the required information to the mixed hardware-software deep neural network that performs the planned functionality.

3 Broadband Analogue Conditioning Module - 100GCoMo

The 100GCoMo is the analogue conditioning module responsible for coupling the analogue input signal (0 – 40 GHz) to the digital conversion step. A DBBC4 system can contain up to four 100GCoMo modules (each processing two analog input signals). The core function-

alities of 100GCoMo are automatic gain control (AGC) or manual power level control for optimal conversion of the signal with the 8-bit converter, and total power measurement in defined frequency ranges. Optionally, the component can contain a section for the ad-hoc band definition used by the DiFrEnd4T sampling unit. The communication with the general DBBC4 controller is realized through the traditional PCI method already adopted in previous DBBC systems. A 100GCoMo prototype unit covering the frequency range up to 33 GHz has been built and successfully tested.

4 AD Converter and processing unit - ADCore4

The module ADCore4 is a key element in the DBBC4 and again, similarly to the previous versions in the DBBC family, includes the functionality of the analogue to digital conversion and data processing, but with state of the art components and then capabilities. The flexibility in defining the functionality is like in the DBBC4 an important element. A number of different options can be selected in order to optimize performance and requirements. The functionality is straightforward: the ADB4 unit samples the signal conditioned by the 100GCoMo and then the digital format of it is transferred to the CORE4 FPGA using an aggregate channel of serial lines. The required functionality between DSC, OCT, DDC is then processed and available to the output channels in order to be sent out to the correlator/recorder or to the FILA100GMEM. The ADCore4 component can indeed be operated in two modes: it can either accept 2×28.8 GHz of *digitized* input bandwidth, or alternatively the ADCore4 can be equipped with an ADC stage (ADB4) performing direct sampling of two $0 - 28.8$ GHz *analogue* input signals. The optional sampler component will make use of a high-end specialized ASIC device capable of sampling at 2×57.6 Gsps. In both scenarios the data will be passed to the CORE4 FPGA element for the digital processing in the desired mode (DSC, OCT, DDC). The processed data will be sent out to the data recorders and/or the FILA100Mem component (see Sec. ??). An ADCore4 prototype has been realized and is now under testing.

5 FILA100GMEM

The FILA100G is an optional component that provides fast buffered memory for burst-mode operations and direct writing of the received packets to SSD NVMe (PCIe mode) disk modules. In addition the component will support functionalities present in previous versions of the DBBC systems (FILA10G) like channel reordering as well as channel extraction allowing e.g. streaming of sub-bands to a correlator for real-time fringe verification. Because packets will be recorded on-the-fly onto the fast NVMe disks without any CPU data handling, we expect to achieve burst speeds of 56 Gbps/disk over 80 s and sustained output data rates of 13 Gbps/disk. The module can allocate a variable number of SSD NVMe units as required by the burst mode duty cycle/number of channels/data rate. The module can allocate a variable number of SSD NVMe units, expandable in memory capability as required by the burst mode duty cycle/number of channels/data rate. More FILA100GMEM modules can be used in parallel in order to improve the memory capacity, or number of channels to be used in burst mode or to be recorded. It is important that disks do not require any CPU data handling for the digital data recorded 'on the fly' on the NVMe disks. This solution allows a burst writing rate (80 s) up to 56 Gbps/disk and a sustained write rate up to 13 Gbps/disk. A dedicated board was defined for this mode which can be adopted in multiple samples for the required maximum data rate and recording time.

6 A-EYE Controller

Artificial Intelligence functionality meets VLBI technology. The A-EYE module is a controller making use of artificial intelligence methods to perform a number of functions useful for both single dish and interferometric observations. It will make use mainly of pre-trained networks, ready to be used for a number of modes which can include: RFI recognition and mitigation, extraction of non-statistical-noise signals, recognition of human-like extraterrestrial emissions, and other similar or different types of application.

The AI controller adopted for such functionality is a multi-cpu FPGA device optimized for this type of applications. The general development working flow con-

sists in a session dedicated to select and pre-train a suitable DNN (deep neural network) configuration with additional training dedicated to the specific purpose to be satisfied. This configuration is then synthesized in a hardware DNN with mixed software dedicated implementation. The entire synthesized solution is running in the above mentioned programmable device which is able to interact with the other units in the DBBC4 in order to drive specific functionalities in the different components of the system. When a larger network is required a direct link is possible with a neural network operating on a cloud.

7 DiFrEnd28 and DiFrEndVGOS

The DiFrEnd28 is a standalone module expected to be allocated in the receiver area in order to minimize the connections between the analogue part and this section where the sampling with a 28.8 GHz bandwidth is performed and the output bands are generated. This unit can be fully independent or connected to the AD-Core4 when additional functionalities available in the DBBC4 are required. Indeed the internal capability to generate OCT and DDC filters permits to use its functionality to directly connect a VLBI recorder or correlator through a number of optical fibers.

For VGOS observations, a dedicated unit has been developed making use of the same hardware, but running a specialised firmware version. The so-called DiFrEndVGOS component can be connected to a DBBC3 backend in order to perform the full VGOS sampling in dual-polarization, close to the receiver thus greatly reducing the required analogue connections to the sampling point. The unit can also act as a standalone front- and back-end offering the possibility to provide a large number of tunable DDC channels. The hardware design has been finalised and a prototype unit was realized, which is currently under test. Phase cal not could not be needed any more.

8 DiFrEnd28 and DiFrEndVGOS

Complementary to the DiFrEnd28, the DiFrEnd4T is a standalone sampling unit which provides 6 GHz of sampled bandwidth in a range of 0-40 GHz. The

desired portion of the band is to be selected by an appropriate filter. In the case of the DBBC4 the DiFrEnd4T is planned to cover the frequency range 27.5-33.0 GHz. Similar to the DiFrEnd28, the internal FPGAs can produce filtered output streams that can be directly recorded or processed by a correlator. The development of such unit is under way.

9 DiFrEnd4T

Complementary to the DiFrEnd28, the DiFrEnd4T is a standalone sampling unit which provides 6 GHz of sampled bandwidth in a range of 0-40 GHz. The desired portion of the band is to be selected by an appropriate filter. In the case of the DBBC4 the DiFrEnd4T is planned to cover the frequency range 27.5-33.0 GHz. Similar to the DiFrEnd28, the internal FPGAs can produce filtered output streams that can be directly recorded or processed by a correlator. The first prototype of such unit is available and its test under way.

10 Conclusions

The DBBC4 will provide a VLBI front/backend system that is offering solutions for the technical challenges in the era of multi-frequency, large-bandwidth VLBI observations. The development of the DBBC4 VLBI backend is progressing as planned, with the first prototype system components already available and undergoing testing. Additional units are either under construction or at the design stage. Integration of the various components into a first prototype system to be used for end-to-end testing is estimated to be realized by 2026. A dedicated unit is planned to operate with the DBBC3 in order to allow a direct connection with the receiver without any analogue filter with the possibility then to flexibly digitally select the input band for each DBBC3 IF.

IVS Combination Center: ITRF2020 Update – final results

S. Bachmann, S. Modiri, S. Schneider-Leck, A. Kehm, M. Seitz, D. Thaller

Abstract We present the IVS contribution to the ITRF2020 Update 2023 (ITRF2020-u2023), which was calculated by extending the ITRF2020 by an additional three years of data (2021–2023). Such an update was realized for the first time with the objective to increase ITRF update cycles from 5–6 years to yearly in the future. Like the original ITRF2020 IVS contribution, the update is a combined contribution from 12 different ACs. We give an overview on the update process and show validation results for station coordinates and EOP. Our main focus is on the performance of VGOS sessions and the scale parameter and its evolution.

Keywords VLBI, ITRF2020, VGOS

1 Introduction

The ITRF is the result of an inter-technique combination of all four space-geodetic techniques: Doppler Orbitography and Radiopositioning Integrated by Satellite (DORIS), Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), Satellite Laser Ranging (SLR), and Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI). The ITRF is calculated by the International Terrestrial Reference System (ITRS) Combination Centre at IGN; in addition,

S. Bachmann¹ · S. Modiri¹ · S. Schneider-Leck¹ · A. Kehm¹ · D. Thaller¹

(1) Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG), Richard-Strauss-Allee 11, 60598 Frankfurt am Main, Germany

M. Seitz²

(2) Deutsches Geodätisches Forschungsinstitut (DGFI-TUM), Technical University of Munich, Arcisstrasse 21, 80333 München, Germany

DGFI-TUM and JPL calculate the respective solutions DTRF and JTRF. Until now, new ITRF solutions have been generated by a reprocessing over the complete observation history of all techniques, with intervals of five to six years between the consecutive realizations. To reduce that time span, the ITRF2020 has been updated using only the latest years of observations, avoiding a full reprocessing which shall be done only every 7–10 years. Therefore, the ITRS Center of the International Earth Rotation and Reference Systems Service (IERS) sent out a Call for Participation (CfP) to all IERS technique services to process and provide three additional years from 2021 to 2023 to expand the observation time span of the original ITRF2020 to the end of 2023 (ITRF2020-u2023).

Starting with the ITRF2005, the IVS contribution is provided in the form of normal equations (NEQs) combined from individual contributions by the IVS Analysis Centers (ACs; see Vennebusch et al., 2007). The VLBI combination procedure has been continuously refined, and the number of contributing ACs has increased over time. Bachmann (2020) provides detailed information about the combination process, which has also been applied for ITRF2020 (cf. Hellmers et al., 2022). In the following sections, we describe the input to the combination process and present results for the station coordinates, the Earth Orientation Parameters (EOP), and the scale. One focus is put on VGOS stations and VGOS observations, since – for the first time in ITRF history – enough observations have been available to reliably estimate station coordinates for VGOS antennas and EOP derived from VGOS sessions. Since VLBI highly contributes to the realization of the scale of the ITRF, this parameter is of particular interest.

2 Data

The IVS contribution to ITRF2020-u2023 consists of 24-h sessions between 2021 and 2023 provided in SINEX format. Overall, 667 combined sessions have been submitted to the IERS ITRS Center. The sessions consist mainly of 24-h Rapid , R&D, VGOS, regional and CRF sessions. Table 1 gives an overview of the IVS ACs that contributed to the combination, as well as the number of contributed sessions. 12 different IVS ACs using six different analysis software packages contributed to the combination – more than ever before, showing a positive trend of analysis diversity within the IVS. The input contributions contain station coordinates, source positions, and EOP, i.e., pole coordinates (including rates), dUT1, LOD, and nutation. 54 stations observed at least once within this period, of which are 42 legacy and 12 VGOS stations. Five stations observed in both legacy and VGOS sessions. Most of the VGOS stations have regularly observed over the three years period and there are two stations located on the Southern hemisphere now included. This allows for the ITRF2020-u2023 to (1.) estimate first reliable station coordinates for VGOS telescopes, and, for co-located sites, (2.) compare and evaluate the estimated velocities with the velocities estimated for legacy telescopes. Moreover, the additional co-locations allow for a more stable combination of the legacy and VGOS networks.

3 Results

The IVS combination is done at the level of NEQs with predefined analysis conventions (e.g. models, absolute terms, etc.). A summary of the analysis conventions applied for ITRF2020-u2023 is given on the IVS Analysis Coordinator website ¹.

- Input
session-wise datum-free NEQs (SINEX format) with station coordinates, EOP, and source positions.
- Procedure
session-wise stacking of AC-specific NEQs after
 1. adding back loading correction,
 2. transformation to equal epochs (mid-session),

3. transformation to equal a priori values (ITRF2020 for station coordinates, IERS Co4 for EOP, ICRF3 for source positions),
4. elimination of source positions,
5. generation of individual AC solutions,
6. testing for outliers (station coordinates, EOP),
7. determination of AC-specific weighting factors (variance component estimation),
8. accumulation of individual NEQs,
9. application of datum constraints (no-net rotation and translation on datum stations) and testing for outliers in the combined solution.

- Output
(= IVS contribution to ITRF2020 Update)
session-wise, datum-free, combined NEQs in SINEX format with station coordinates and EOP at mid-session epochs.

Compared to the original CFP for ITRF2020, the following changes in the analysis have been considered:

- updated gravitational deformation file,
- use of ITRF2020 a priori coordinates & post-seismic deformation models.

3.1 Station coordinates

For the first time, several VGOS stations have sufficiently long observation time spans to estimate reliable station coordinates. Associated with this, 100 VGOS sessions have been combined for ITRF2020-u2023. This allows us dedicated investigation of the VGOS sessions and evaluating the accuracy and reliability of VGOS stations. Fig. 1 shows the weighted root mean square (WRMS) over all stations w.r.t. ITRF2020, for legacy (left) and VGOS stations (right) in North, East, and Height. Only sessions common to all ACs and the combination are used, with a minimum of six sessions per station (38 legacy/12 VGOS stations). Note that there are five times more legacy than VGOS sessions². We observe that the repeatability of the station coordinates in terms of WRMS is significantly better for VGOS stations as compared to legacy stations, whereby the scatter improves by half in all components. The WMRS of the combined solution

¹ https://ivscc.gsfc.nasa.gov/IVS_AC/IVS-AC.ITRF2020.htm

² see also https://ivscc.gsfc.nasa.gov/about/wg/wg3/IVS-WG3-report_050916.pdf

Table 1: Overview of the contributing ACs: twelve different IVS ACs using six different analysis software packages contributed to the combined solution

AC	Name	Software	Nb contr. sessions (legacy/VGOS)
ASI	Agenzia Spaziale Italiana	Calc/n μ Solve	568 / 100
BKG	Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy, Germany	Calc/n μ Solve	568 / 100
DGFI-TUM	Deutsches Geodätisches Forschungsinstitut/Technical University of Munich	DOGS-RI	550 / 95
GFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences	PORT	568 / 100
GSFC	Goddard Space Flight Center, USA	Calc/n μ Solve	568 / 100
IGE	National Geographic Institute of Spain	Where	556 / 97
NMA	Norwegian Mapping Authority, Norway	Where	568 / 100
OPAR	Observatory of Paris, France	Calc/n μ Solve	520 / 95
OSO	Onsala Space Observatory, Sweden	ASCOT	568 / 100
UAV	University of Alicante, Spain	VieVS	544 / 91
USNO	US Naval Observatory, USA	Calc/n μ Solve	568 / 0
VIE	Vienna University of Technology, Austria	VieVS	568 / 100

is 4.3, 4.6 and 10.6 mm for legacy, and 2.8, 3.1 and 5.0 mm for VGOS stations in North, East, and Height, respectively. These results generally show highly precise station coordinates, but in particular for the VGOS stations, and thus underline the success of the VGOS concept. Consequently, we expect highly improved VGOS coordinates in ITRF2020-u2023, which will enhance the accuracy of the a priori coordinates used for the analysis of VLBI observations.

3.2 Scale

Figure 2 shows the session-wise scale parameter of the combined solution with respect to ITRF2020 (black) and DTRF2020 (red; Seitz et al., 2023, 2025). The dots show the session-wise values, the solid lines the respective median smoothed values. Scale parameters from 2010 until the end of 2023 are shown, to evaluate whether the ‘drift’ w.r.t. ITRF2020 observed in the earlier years continues in the ITRF2020-u2023 update period as well. It can be observed that this is not the case, the ‘drift’ does not continue, and the scale parameter stays rather constant in the three additional years (see also Hellmers et al., 2023), apparently slightly decreasing in 2023. The weighted mean of the scale values are 0.38 ppb w.r.t. ITRF2020 and -0.09 ppb w.r.t. DTRF2020, with a WRMS of 1.2 and 0.8 ppb, respectively, for a period between 1994 and 2023. In Hellmers et al. (2023), a WRMS of the combined solution w.r.t. ITRF2020 of about 1.5 ppb, with an offset of 0.25 ppb,

was determined for the above-mentioned period. Kern et al. (2025) showed that an additional discontinuity for station NYALES20 in the year 2013 can consider for the increasing up-velocity of this station and by this can reduce the scale drift at least to a certain extent. This discontinuity had already been introduced in DTRF2020 and might be one reason for the differences between the scale time series obtained w.r.t. both reference frames. In future, having longer VGOS series available, it will be possible to investigate such effects in more detail and with higher accuracy.

3.3 EOP

EOP from the VLBI combination contain pole coordinates (x- and y-pole) and rates, UT1–UTC (dUT1) and its corresponding rate LOD (Length of Day), and the nutation parameters dX and dY. VLBI is the only space-geodetic technique providing the full set of EOP, i.e. the full link between the terrestrial and the celestial reference frame. EOP are estimated at mid-session epoch and by fixing datum station coordinates to their a priori values ensuring most accurate estimates.

Since IVS 24-h sessions are usually scheduled between 17:00 UT and 17:00 UT of the following day, the mid-session epoch is around 5 UT. Figure 3 shows the WRMS of x-, y-pole, and dUT1 with respect to the reference EOP time series IERS 20Co4 for each individual AC and the combined solution. On the left side, comparisons for legacy and on the right side for VGOS sessions

Fig. 1: WRMS of station coordinates residuals w.r.t. ITRF2020. Left side: legacy stations; right side: VGOS stations

Fig. 2: Scale [ppb] between the combined solution and ITRF2020 (black) and DTRF2020 (red), and moving median (solid lines)

are shown (only sessions common for to ACs used). Only sessions that are suitable for EOP determination are used (294/67 legacy/VGOS sessions). The WRMS for the combined solution derived from legacy sessions is 97, 136 and $9 \mu(a)$ s for x -, y -pole and dUT_1 , respectively. For the combined solution derived from VGOS sessions, we get WRMS values of 111, 140 and $9 \mu(a)$ s for x -, y -pole and dUT_1 , respectively. We observe that the differences in the repeatability of the EOP are small comparing both session types. Figure 3 also shows that the x -pole WRMS for the individual ACs has an elevated level for VGOS sessions compared to legacy sessions, which might be related to the station distribution in the VGOS network and has to be investigated in more detail in future. Although some AC-specific values are increased, the WRMS of the combined solution is comparatively small. This confirms the procedure of the

IVS combination process and supports the objective of achieving more stable values and improved statistics through the IVS combination as compared to individual solutions.

3.4 Conclusion

12 IVS ACs using six different software packages submitted contributions to the combined IVS contribution to the first ITRF2020 update, ITRF2020-u2023. In total, 667 combined 24-h sessions, covering a time span from 2021 to the end of 2023, have been submitted to the IERS ITRS Product Center containing 54 stations overall, out of which 12 are VGOS stations. The station repeatability over all legacy stations (WRMS)

Fig. 3: WRMS for x-, y-Pole and dUT1 w.r.t. IERS 20Co4 for all ACs and combination derived from legacy (left) and VGOS sessions (right). Only sessions common to all ACs are used (294/67 legacy/VGOS sessions)

is 4–5 mm for the horizontal components (North and East) and 10.6 mm for the Height component for the combined solution. For VGOS sessions, we derive a WRMS of 3–4 mm for the horizontal components (North and East) and 5 mm for the Height component. The repeatability of the VGOS station positions is significantly better (approximately twice) than for legacy stations. The improved repeatability of VGOS station coordinates is a positive result confirming the VGOS concept. The reliably-determined VGOS coordinates in the ITRF2020-u2023 will be an important basis for the analysis of VLBI observations, also allowing a meaningful contribution of the VGOS network to investigations of the ITRF scale parameter by comparisons between legacy and VGOS sessions. Interesting results in this regard are so far the comparison between the VLBI scale parameters w.r.t. ITRF2020 and DTRF2020, and that the VLBI scale ‘drift’ w.r.t. ITRF2020, observed in earlier years, appears to not continue beyond 2020. For EOP, we observe a comparable level of the WRMS values for x- and y-pole and dUT1 for both network session types. This leads to the conclusion that even smaller network sizes for VGOS sessions, compared to legacy sessions, do not result in less accurate EOP.

Acknowledgements

We like to thank all contributing ACs and the IVS Analysis Coordinator John Gipson for the good coopera-

tion. Furthermore, we thank the IERS ITRS Combination Centers at IGN, DGFI-TUM, and JPL for providing valuable feedback on the combined sessions.

References

- Bachmann S (2020) VLBI-based combination strategies for global geodetic reference frames. Thesis, TU Wien, Vienna, Austria.
- Hellmers H, Modiri S, Bachmann S, Thaller D, Bloßfeld M, Seitz M, Gipson J (2022) Combined IVS Contribution to the ITRF2020. In: Freymueller JT, Sánchez L (Eds.) *Geodesy for a Sustainable Earth. International Association of Geodesy Symposia*, 154, Springer, Cham, doi: 10.1007/1345_2022_170.
- Hellmers H, Modiri S, Bachmann S, Thaller D, Bloßfeld M, Seitz M, Gipson J (2023) Scale Evaluation of the ITRF2020 Solution. In: Armstrong KL, Behrend D, Baver KD (Eds.) *IVS 2022 General Meeting Proceedings. NASA/CP-20220018789*, 237–242.
- Kern L, Krásná H, Nothnagel A, Böhm J (2025) Terrestrial reference frame scale drift anomalies in VLBI and the contribution of Ny-Ålesund radio telescopes. *Earth Planets Space*, 77, 40, doi: 10.1186/s40623-025-02159-z.
- Seitz M, Bloßfeld M, Angermann D, Glomsda M, Rudenko S, Zeitlhöfler J, Seitz F (2023) DTRF2020 (Version v2) [Data set]. *Zenodo*, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8369167.
- Seitz M, Bloßfeld M, Glomsda M, Angermann D, Rudenko S, Zeitlhöfler J, Seitz F (2025) DTRF2020: The ITRS 2020 realization of DGFI-TUM. *J Geod* (under review).
- Vennebusch M, Böckmann S, Nothnagel A (2007) The contribution of Very Long Baseline Interferometry to ITRF2005. *J Geod*, 81, 553–564, doi: 10.1007/s00190-006-0117-x.

GSI Global Solution of VLBI Observation Data

S. Matsumoto, M. Ishigaki, K. Hashimoto, T. Hara, S. Kurihara

Abstract GSI has conducted global analysis since 2002 and released its results on the webpage. In the latest analysis in GSI, we used more than 7,000 VLBI sessions' database from 1980 to 2025 to estimate various parameters e.g. station positions, velocities, and the earth orientation parameters (EOPs). To improve accuracy of the estimated parameters, we made a post-seismic deformation (PSD) model describing the deformation due to the 2011 off the Pacific coast of Tohoku Earthquake for Ishioka. With the PSD model, we can estimate post-earthquake movement which is closer to the real movement and calculated the reasonable station position.

Keywords Global Solution, Post-Seismic Deformation model, Earth Orientation Parameters

1 Introduction

GSI has been involved in international VLBI observations in cooperation with the International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry (IVS) to contribute to construction of the Global Geodetic Reference Frame (GGRF) and to determine the reference point in Japan. In global analysis, various parameters

Saho Matsumoto¹ Masafumi Ishigaki¹ Kaho Hashimoto¹ Tetsuya Hara² and Shinobu Kurihara³

(1) Geospatial Information Authority of Japan (GSI), Kitasato 1, Tsukuba, Ibaraki Japan

(2) Advanced Engineering Service (AES), Tsukuba Building 7F, Takezono 1-6-1, Tsukuba, Ibaraki Japan

(3) Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism, Kasumigaseki 2-1-3, Chiyodaku, Tokyo Japan

e.g. station positions, velocities, and the earth orientation parameters (EOPs) are estimated using long-term global VLBI database. GSI has conducted global analysis since 2002 (Kokado et al. (2006)), and released its results on the webpage. In the latest analysis in GSI, we used more than 7,000 VLBI sessions' database from 1980 to 2025. We will show the results of the latest analysis and give a status report on improving our methods to obtain more accurate results of station coordinates and EOPs. In this report, we report on the method of our global analysis and show our latest solution in March 2025, and we also give an update on our study for improving accuracy of solutions.

2 Method

2.1 Observation to analysis

VLBI stations which in cooperation with the IVS across the globe participate in observations following the IVS annual schedule. Observed data are transferred to correlators via network or shipping. Correlators process the data to find fringes and calculate delay time. After the primary analysis, databases are submitted to IVS Data Centers. Analysis Centers download databases from IVS Data Centers and perform analysis to get the final solutions of the VLBI observations.

Software	CALC (Ver. 11)/ SOLVE (release 2024-10-31, revision 2024-11-27)	
A-priori	CRF	ICRF3
	TRF	ITRF2020 (Altamimi et al., 2022)
	UT1, Polar motion	usno_finals.erp
	Precession, nutation	IAU2006/2000 Precession/Nutation (Calc 11)
Physical model	Antenna axis offset	2019a.axo
	Solid earth tides, Ocean loading tides, Polar tides, ocean pole tide loading	IERS2010 conventions
	Antenna thermal deformation	Nothnagel, 2009
	Zenith Atmospheric Delay	VMF3 dry+wet mapping function (Landskron and Bohm, 2018)
Parameters for estimation	Atmospheric gradient	GSFC DAO model
	global parameters (common to all sessions in the databases): station positions, rates of change of the station positions (velocity field), radio source positions (declination/right ascension), and antenna axis offsets local parameters (estimated in each session): EOPs, zenith humid atmosphere delay, time-based changes of baseline relative to the reference station, atmospheric gradient, and clock offset.	

Fig. 1 Specifications for global analysis.

2.2 Global Solution in GSI

In GSI, we have performed global analysis continuously since 2002. In global analysis, we download VLBI databases stored in the IVS Data Center, analyze them and obtain the final solutions of the geodetic VLBI. Before the analysis, appropriate a-priori values and constraint conditions for the observing station position, velocity, and radio source positions are set as shown in Fig 1. We use software “CALC/SOLVE” developed by NASA/GSFC for analysis. There are two types of parameters to estimate in a global solution: “global parameters” and “local parameters”. The global parameters are common to all sessions in the databases, and include the station positions, rates of change of the station positions (velocity field), radio source positions (declination/right ascension), and antenna axis offsets. The local parameters are estimated in each session, including EOPs, zenith humid atmosphere delay, time-based changes of baseline relative to the reference station, atmospheric gradient, and clock offset.

3 Results of the latest biannual analysis by GSI

In our global analysis in March 2025, we analyzed databases of over 7,000 VLBI observations from 1980 to February 2025. For the latest results, refer to the website of GSI (<https://www.spacegeodesy.go.jp/vlbi/solutions/>).

Fig. 2 Rate of change in observation station position.

Fig. 3 Time series of the earth rotation speed estimated by VLBI global analysis. (a)UT1-TAI, (b) UT1-UTC

3.1 Station position & velocity

Figure 2 shows the station velocities plotted on a map estimated in the analysis. This indicates the average motion of the stations during the analysis period.

3.2 Earth Orientation Parameter (EOP)

3.2.1 Time variation

Figure 3 shows the results of UT1. Figure (a) and (b) show UT1-TAI and UT1-UTC which include the gap of leap seconds, respectively. It indicates the trend of the earth rotation has changed in the last few years.

Fig. 4 Polar motion.

3.2.2 Polar motion

Figure 4 shows the polar motion which represents the orbit of the point where the angular velocity vector of the earth rotation axis is passing the earth's surface during the analysis period (1980-2025).

4 Discussion : Study for improving accuracy of solutions

4.1 Crustal deformation around Ishioka VLBI station

Ishioka VLBI station (hereafter "Ishioka") had experienced crustal deformation due to the 2011 off the Pacific coast of Tohoku Earthquake (Mw 9.0) (hereafter "Tohoku-Oki earthquake"). Figure 5 shows the displacements of the earthquake observed by GNSS CORS of GSI. (GSI (2021)). Figure (a) shows the displacement before and after the main shock. Significant crustal deformation occurred due to the Tohoku-Oki earthquake in wide area in Japan. Figure (b) is the deformation from the next day of the main quake of the Tohoku-Oki earthquake to 10 years after. This shows that major crustal deformation continues even after the main earthquake over a wide area. Ishioka is circled in red and it seems that significant

Fig. 5 Crustal deformation due to the Tohoku-Oki earthquake. (a) displacement before and after the main shock. (b) displacement from the next day of Tohoku-Oki earthquake to 10 years after.

Fig. 6 Displacement of Tsukuba VLBI station.

deformation is occurring there. Figure 6 shows the displacement on the Tsukuba VLBI antenna until 2017 for each component, E, N, U, which is located approximately 17 km away from Ishioka. This picture also indicates that the deformation has been continuing for a long time in this region.

4.2 Making a PSD model for Ishioka

Since Ishioka VLBI station started observation in 2015 and there is no data immediately after the Tohoku-Oki earthquake, there is no post-seismic deformation (PSD) model for the earthquake adopted in the ITRF2020. We get a fitting function with position data for Ishioka VLBI antenna to make a PSD model. The

PSD model for East, North and Up component

$$L \in E, N, U$$

is described with the following function independently (Altamimi et al. (2023)).

$$\delta L(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{n^l} A_i^l \log\left(1 + \frac{t - t_i^l}{\tau_i^l}\right) + \sum_{i=1}^{n^e} A_i^e \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t - t_i^e}{\tau_i^e}\right)\right) \quad (1)$$

Where t is epoch, A is amplitude of the i th logarithmic or exponential term, and τ is relaxation time of the i th logarithmic or exponential term. There are some parametric models defined by combination of logarithmic and exponential components. By fitting this model to the VLBI data, we obtained the PSD model for Tohoku-Oki earthquake for Ishioka. Estimated parameters are described in Table 1, where A is amplitude and R is relaxation time.

Table 1 PSD model for Ishioka.

component	model	log		exp	
		A [mm]	R [year]	A [mm]	R [year]
E	3	-57.58	0.3561	397.99	2.0405
N	3	136.22	0.0358	-385.78	5.6663
U	1	22.13	1.6654		

4.3 Adopt the PSD model for Ishioka

With the PSD model from fitting function as an a-priori, we estimated the station position by the global analysis. Figure 7 shows the results of global analysis with and without PSD model for Ishioka.

4.4 Comparison of the results with / without PSD model

To verify the validity of this model, we compare the results with the GNSS CORS "ISHI" which is in the same observing station as the VLBI antenna. Figure 8 shows the Ishioka VLBI antenna position from global analy-

Fig. 7 Time series of positions of Ishioka VLBI antenna as the global solution with / without PSD model.

sis with and without PSD model and 'pseudo' VLBI antenna position calculated by GNSS ISHI's position and the local-tie vector. The global solution with PSD model (orange line) is closer to the antenna position calculated by GNSS data than the result without PSD model (blue line). Table 2 shows the comparison of position of the Ishioka VLBI antenna on January 31, 2025 between global solution with /without PSD model and GNSS result. The differences between the antenna position from the global solution and the one calculated from the position of GNSS are -6.2mm, 6.0mm, -4.8mm for results without no PSD model and -4.9 mm, 6.5mm, -2.6mm for results with PSD model for X, Y, Z compo-

Fig. 8 Ishioka position from global analysis with and without PSD model and VLBI antenna position by GNSS ISHI's position + local tie.

nents respectively. From these results, with the PSD model, we can estimate post-earthquake movement which is closer to the real movement and calculated the reasonable station position. Note that the gap on January 1st, 2024 is caused by the 2024 Noto Peninsula Earthquake (Mw 7.5). In this model, we did not take account the earthquake.

5 Summary & Future prospects

GSI has conducted global analysis biannually to estimate station positions and velocity, source positions

Table 2 Position of the Ishioka VLBI antenna on January 31, 2025.

	no PSD	PSD	GNSS+local-tie	differences	
				no PSD	PSD
X	-3959636257.79808	-3959636256.549	-3959636251.6	-6.2	-4.9
Y	3296825485.34825	3296825485.843	3296825479.36	6.0	6.5
Z	3747042563.50257	3747042565.692	3747042568.3	-4.8	-2.6

and EOPs, and release the results on webpage. To improve accuracy of the estimated parameters, we made a PSD model describing deformation associated with the Tohoku-Oki earthquake for Ishioka. With the PSD model, we can estimate post-earthquake movement which is closer to the real movement and calculated the reasonable station position. To make a model which is closer to real deformation, it is needed to consider the 2024 Noto Peninsula Earthquake. We will keep performing our global analysis, and we continue studying for improving accuracy of solutions.

References

- Altamimi Z, Rebischung P, Collilieux X, Métivier, L, Chanard K (2022) ITRF2020 [TRF datum]. IERS ITRS Center Hosted by IGN and IGP. doi: <https://doi.org/10.18715/IPGP.2023.LDVIOBNL>.
- Altamimi Z, Rebischung P, Collilieux X, Metivier L, Chanard K (2023) ITRF2020: an augmented reference frame refining the modeling of nonlinear station motions. *J Geod*, 97, 47, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-023-01738-w>.
- GSI (2021) https://www.gsi.go.jp/kanshi/h23touhoku_10years.htm. 16 June, 2025 accessed.
- Kokado K, Machida M, Takashima K (2006) Highly Precise Determination of Earth Orientation Parameter by VLBI Global Solutions. *Bulletin of the GSI*, 101, 11-18.
- Landskron D, Böhm J (2018) VMF3/GPT3: refined discrete and empirical troposphere mapping functions. *J Geod*, 92, 349-360, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-017-1066-2>.
- Nothnagel A (2009) A Conventions on thermal expansion modelling of radio telescopes for geodetic and astrometric VLBI. *J Geod*, 83, 787-792, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-008-0284-z>.

VLBI data analysis at ESA/ESOC

S. Bruni, M. Otten, E. Schoenemann, F. Gini

Abstract This contribution presents the current setup deployed by the Navigation Support Office for processing geodetic VLBI observations with the ESA Precise Navigation System (EPNS) Software. The paper reports on the status of the software development, provides a high-level validation of the analysis results and outlines future enhancements.

Keywords VLBI analysis, ESA, EPNS

1 Introduction

The Navigation Support Office at ESA/ESOC provides the geodetic framework for ESA missions and aims at supporting navigation for society at large. The Office contributes to all fields of the Geodetic Supply Chain defined by the UN (UNGGCE, 2024), notably including the contribution to the realization of the International Terrestrial Reference Frame (ITRF). The Office acts as an established Analysis Center (AC), participating to both routine and reprocessing activities of the International GNSS Service (IGS), the International Laser Ranging Service (ILRS), and the International DORIS Service (IDS). In more recent years, steps have been undertaken to extend the analysis capability beyond satellite observations by including the analysis of VLBI data. This endeavour aimed at completing the Office's portfolio with the addition of the 4th space

geodetic technique supporting the ITRF realization. In addition, it was deemed necessary to support ESA's and European independence in the generation of a fully autonomous set of Earth Orientation Parameters (EOP) estimates and predictions (Khem et al., 2023; Bruni et al., 2022), and to support the upcoming GENESIS mission.

The processing of VLBI data has been integrated in EPNS, a multi-technique analysis software supporting both the estimation of geodetic parameters, and the determination and prediction of satellite products in different regimes. This approach guarantees adherence to the international analysis standards, as EPNS is already used to generate the products submitted by the Office to the different Services of the International Association of Geodesy (IAG). In addition, it also facilitates inter-technique combination as it ensures a consistent treatment of the data provided by the independent observing systems supported by the software.

This contribution focuses on the development of the VLBI-analysis functionality within EPNS. Section 2 presents a high-level overview of the implementation, while a validation of the most recent results is illustrated in Section 3. The concluding remarks capture a general assessment of the current performance and delineate the way forwards for the project.

2 Software description

The VLBI activity at ESA/ESOC includes the analysis of both S/X and VGOS observations, with the explicit goal of supporting ESA projects and missions as well as officially contributing to the International

Sara Bruni¹ · Michiel Otten¹
(1) PosiTIm UG at ESA/ESOC Darmstadt, Germany

Erik Schoenemann² · Francesco Gini²
(2) ESA/ESOC Darmstadt, Germany

VLBI Service (IVS). EPNS is developed following the prescriptions of the IERS Conventions 2010 including relevant updates (Petit and Luzum, 2010), as well as the technique-specific guidelines issued by the IAG Services for routine operation or in response to the call for participation to the repro activities in preparation for an ITRF release/update. Prominent deviations from these prescriptions and/or specific analysis choices are commented in the following subsections.

2.1 Modelling of physical processes

While EPNS generally complies with the state-of-the-art modelling recommended by IERS for geophysical processes (e.g. solid tide, permanent tide, polar tide, ocean load, atmospheric models and mapping functions), the use of grid files is avoided as much as possible in order to save computational resources. This implies that the Global Mapping Function (GMF) is used instead of the Vienna Mapping Function (VMF) for mapping tropospheric delays and that the atmospheric loading is not removed from station coordinates. It shall be noted that the latter feature is still consistent with the ITRF2020 requirements, but does not meet the IVS standards for operational submissions. It is also expected that the processing of intensive sessions, spanning only 1h and involving a limited number of baselines, could particularly benefit from the consideration of the stated models. All other VLBI-specific models prescribed by IVS standards have been implemented. For more details on the implemented relativistic background, the reader can refer to Flhorer et al. (2017).

2.2 Parametrization

The parametrization adopted in the processing of 24h sessions is presented in Table 1. In the analysis carried out for this study, the same parametrization was used for S/X and VGOS sessions. However, VGOS sessions contain about twice the amount of observations included in S/X archives (Figure 1). As a consequence,

it would be reasonable to increase the sampling of the tropospheric delays and possibly of the clock offsets for VGOS sessions (Haas et al., 2025). In addition, further improvements of the VGOS analysis could result from using a priori source coordinates derived at VGOS frequencies (Krasna et al., 2025) in place of the S/X-based ICRF3 values. This might be particularly relevant as long as source coordinates are not estimated. Finally, it shall be noted that the parametrization was also kept constant throughout the whole analysed time span, notwithstanding changes in the ground network, in station performances, in the total amount of acquired observations and of tracked sources.

2.3 Processing strategy

The analysis of VLBI data with EPNS starts from NGScards or vgosDBs version 4 archives i.e., from datasets that have already undergone fringe fitting, have resolved ambiguities and for which ionospheric delays are already compensated (VGOS sessions) or the relevant corrections are distributed (S/X sessions). Flagged observations are not imported. Within EPNS, a pre-processing phase takes care of outlier screening and clock-break handling, and a final weighted least square adjustment generates the actual geodetic products according to the parametrization discussed in Section 2.2. A cutoff of 5° is imposed.

EPNS is designed to operate in a fully automated way. This approach significantly streamlines the generation of operational products by reducing the manpower required and ensuring consistency through automated data processing, free from individual operator bias. While manual processing can be customized to specific archives and often achieves higher performance, ESA's automated methods offer scalability and efficiency. Consequently, ESA products may exhibit slightly higher uncertainties and noise levels in geodetic parameter estimates (refer to Section 3 for the validation of the analysis results).

The unsupervised outlier detection is accomplished by means of two iterative screening steps. During each cycle, the mismatch between the actual observations and the proxy observable reconstructed on the basis of the progressively updated estimated values are checked against user-defined thresholds

Table 1 Parametrization adopted in the processing of 24h sessions.

Parameter	Representation	A priori model	Constraints
Polar motion offsets/rates	Daily value	IERS Co4 2020/ Bulletin A	45 mas/ 3mas/s
Nutation Offsets	Daily value	IERS Co4 2020/ Bulletin A	3 mas
UT1-UTC	Daily value	IERS Co4 2020/ Bulletin A	3 ms
LOD	Daily value	IERS Co4 2020/ Bulletin A	3 ms
Station coordinates	Daily value	ITRF2020-u2023	NNR + NNT over all stations
Station clocks	Quadratic + PWL every 6h w.r.t. a fixed ref clock clock breaks at epochs reported in vgosDB	-	0.1 s
Wet zenith delays	Saastamoinen (1972) with meteo data from obs file GMF mapping function (Boehm et al., 2006)	PWL every 1h	1 m
Tropospheric delays gradient	North-South and East-West	PWL 24h	1 m
Source Coordinates	Not estimated	ICRF3 (Charlot et al., 2020)	-

that vary as a function of the iteration number. The first screening step is dedicated to the identification of larger blunders ($\sim 2m$ level) and is based on a preliminary solution computed by estimating only clock and troposphere parameters. For the refined screening implemented in the second step, the full parameterization is used. It shall be noted that the identified outliers are only rejected at the end of each loop. Within the loops, observations flagged as potential outliers are re-evaluated at each iteration with the updated configuration and can be restored. Clock breaks epochs are supplied to the software via an external database that is currently being populated on the basis of the information reported in the vgosDB archives. No other clock breaks are introduced during the processing. In addition, baseline clock offsets are also not handled at the moment. As a result of the screening procedure described above, baselines with large clock offsets tend to be rejected in the analysis. Baselines affected by smaller offsets, on the other hand, often remain embedded in the solution at the risk of increasing the overall noise of the solution. Neither of these two consequences is ideal and a proper handling of baseline offsets is therefore foreseen in the next phases of software development.

In the testing setup currently deployed at ESOC, IVS Data Centers are scanned daily for newly released/reprocessed vgosDBs of sessions that took place within the previous 52 weeks. This procedure ensures that our local archive of vgosDBs is maintained reasonably synchronized with the official IVS Data Centers. In addition, newly downloaded vgosDB archives are automatically processed if they are

referred to R1/4 and VGOS-OPS sessions, as well as a subset of S/X and VGOS intensives.

3 Results

A multi-year reprocessing of S/X and VGOS data was accomplished to validate the software performance. For S/X data, the analysed period spanned 2014-June 2025 and included R1, R4, IVS-INT-1, IVS-INT-2 and IVS-INT3 sessions. For VGOS, all operational and intensive sessions (except VGOS-INT-TST) for the period 2020-June 2025 were included. For the sake of brevity, this session will focus on the results of 24h sessions, only. However, intensive sessions were included in the solution presented in Section 3.1.

A general overview of the session characteristics in terms of contributing number of observations, stations and sources is presented in Figure 1. The devised analysis strategy allowed processing 97% of the scheduled R1/4 sessions and 90% of the VGOS-OPS.

To validate the analysis results, the estimated EOPs and the time series of the station coordinates have been compared to external sources. EOP estimates have been compared with the corresponding IERS Co4 values. Average values and standard deviations are reported in Table 2. The analysis of the time series show stable performances over time, with no significant spurious signals. The only exception is a $\sim 15\mu s$ bias in UT estimates provided by R4 sessions over the period 2014-16 (currently under investigation). If those years are excluded, the average offset in UT1-UTC for

S/X sessions is reduced by a factor of 5.

Fig. 1 Overview of session characteristics for R1/R4 (a) and VGOS-OPS (b) sessions.

Table 2 Consistency between EOP estimates provided by the ESA VLBI analysis and IERS CO4 values.

	x pole (μas)	x pole rate ($\mu\text{as/d}$)	y pole (μas)	y pole rate ($\mu\text{as/d}$)	UT1-UTC (μs)	LOD (μs)	dX (μas)	dY (μas)
R1/R4								
mean	-43	-10	11	17	3.3	1.3	3.1	18
STD	190	370	260	390	19	28	120	130
V-OPS								
mean	-59	27	-21	16	-0.62	-5.2	11	-15
STD	370	380	270	350	18	27	200	170

The statistics on the overall agreement between the estimated station coordinates and the a priori ITRF2020-u2023 values is given in Figure 2. In the interpretation of the results, it shall be reminded that the estimated coordinates were not compensated for atmospheric loading, that network constraints were systematically applied over all stations, and that baseline offsets were not properly handled. As expected, most of the stations with continuous participation in the observation programs exhibit negligible offsets and lower scatter. For well-established stations, VGOS results are particularly encouraging considering that the only 5 years of data are available, that the ground network is still evolving and that our analysis strategy is not yet optimized for this group observations as discussed in Section 2.2. The large scatter of the results obtained for station 7374 is mostly driven by ~ 10 large outlier sessions for which our fully automatic processing failed to properly model the station behaviour. Concerning the S/X case, it shall be mentioned that the number of sessions in which at least 1 station exhibits abnormal coordinate variations ($> 1\text{cm}$ 1D, or 1.5cm 3D) with respect to the a priori values suddenly increases in 2023, when the number of observations per sessions was drastically reduced (Figure 1a). From 2023 onwards, also the percentage of baselines affected by 1-to-2cm offsets increased, most likely leading to an increasing noise of the solution. A clear example is the 7392-7368 baseline that, according to our results, is often biased with reference to the other baselines involving the two stations.

3.1 Ingestion in ESA ERP Service

As a further test, all the results generated by the reprocessing activity have been supplied to the ESA Earth Rotation Parameter (ERP) Software to generate a multi-technique ERP solution based exclusively on ESA products. Results are presented in Figure 3. In terms of comparison with the IERS CO4 estimates, this test product appears rather consistent with the current operational ESA ERP solution, that combines ESA's GNSS and SLR solutions with external VLBI products (namely DGFI and BKG solutions for 24h and intensive sessions, respectively). As expected,

Fig. 2 Average (markers) and standard deviations (whiskers) of the session-wise differences between estimated and a priori coordinates. The marker colour indicates how often each station participated in a session. No outlier screening was applied to the results before computing the statistics.

the largest differences appear in UT1-UTC, while pole offset are largely dominated by the GNSS contribution. The difference in UT1-UTC shows a long-term signal spanning $\sim 15\mu s$ with some shorter-term oscillations superimposed.

Fig. 3 comparison of the ESA ERP multi-technique solution based on ESA-only inputs with the IERS C4 2020 results. In the bottom panel, the corresponding estimate based on the current ESA ERP operational solution is shown for comparison (UT1-UTC only).

4 Conclusions and outlook

The implementation of the VLBI analysis capability within the EPNS software has reached an advanced stage and the performance of the devised processing strategy is in line with expectations. Solid results comparable to those of established IVS ACs are achieved for well-observed sessions, while some criticality persists for sessions that produced lower-quality datasets. Interestingly, problems seem to affect mostly the estimation of station coordinates, while EOPs are generally computed properly. The routine application of network constraints over all stations shall be revisited in case of poor performing sites. Further improvement of the analysis results is expected from the implementation of a thorough baseline screening (including the handling of baseline clock offsets) and from the consideration of atmospheric loadings. The latter is also required to enable routine submission of ESA VLBI products to the IVS Combination Centers. Preparatory work for GENESIS support shall also be undertaken, including the implementation of near-field modelling and the extension of the orbit estimation functionality of EPNS to VLBI data.

References

- Boehm J, Niell A, Tregoning P, Schuh H (2006) Global Mapping Function (GMF): A new empirical mapping function based on numerical weather model data. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 33, L07304, doi: doi:10.1029/2005GL025546.
- Bruni S, Mayer V, Otten M, Schoenemann E (2022) ESA's Earth Rotation Parameter Service *2nd EOP PCC Workshop* online - 15-16/02/2022
- Charlot P et al. (2020) The third realization of the International Celestial Reference Frame by very long baseline interferometry *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 644, A159, doi: doi:10.1051/0004-6361/202038368.
- Flohrer C, Schoenemann E, Springer T, Zandbergen R, Enderle W (2017) Update on VLBI data analysis at ESOC *Proceedings of the 23rd Working Meeting of the European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry (EVGA) 2017, Gothenburg, Sweden*, 205-2011.
- Haas R, Feng P, Elgered G (2025) Microwave radiometer observations for VGOS data processing *Working Meeting of the European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry (EVGA) 2025, Matera, Italy*
- Kehm A. et al. (2023) Combination strategy for consistent final, rapid and predicted Earth rotation parameters *Journal of Geodesy*, 97(3), doi: 10.1007/s00190-022-01695-w.
- Krasna H, Jacobs CS, Schartner M, Charlot P (2025) A celestial reference frame derived from observations with the Very Long Baseline Interferometry Global Observing System *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 693, A13, doi: doi:10.1051/0004-6361/202451996
- Petit G, Luzum B. (Eds.) (2010) IERS Technical Note 36, *Verlag des Bundesamts fuer Kartographie und Geodaesie, Frankfurt am Main*.
- Saastamoinen J (1972) Contributions to the theory of atmospheric refraction *J Geod.*, 6(3), pp. 279-298, doi: doi:10.1007/BF02521844.
- United Nations Global Geodeic Centre of Excellence (2024) Hidden Risk - Background report for decision-makers p. 5.

Stability Analysis of Source Coordinates from S/X and VGOS Station Networks Using the Arc Length Method

S. Bolotin, K. Bayer, D. Behrend, J. Gipson, C. Thomas

Abstract The VLBI network is transitioning, with most stations still using the legacy S/X system while new ones adopt the broadband VGOS system. In early 2020, the International VLBI Service (IVS) launched regular VGOS observations. This work analyzes the stability of source coordinates, independently derived from post-2020 sessions using both VGOS (VGOS-OPS) and S/X (IVS-R1, IVS-R4) networks. For each network, we generated time series of source coordinates and evaluated the arc length between pairs of radio sources per session. The arc length serves as a robust metric for our analysis because it is invariant to the Terrestrial and Celestial Reference Frames and Earth Orientation Parameters. By analyzing variations in arc lengths, we identified groups of stable and unstable sources. Finally, we compared the results from the legacy S/X networks with those from the VGOS system to assess their differences in performance and reliability.

Keywords VLBI, VGOS, radio source stability

1 Introduction

The Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) network is undergoing a significant evolution. While most stations continue to operate with the traditional S/X system, newly established stations are adopting the modern broadband VGOS system. In early 2020, the International VLBI Service (IVS), Nothnagel et al. (2017),

Sergei Bolotin, Karen Bayer, Dirk Behrend, John Gipson, Cynthia Thomas
NVI, Inc., Greenbelt, Maryland, USA

initiated regular observations with its new network of VGOS stations.

This paper examines the stability of source coordinates by analyzing data from observing sessions conducted since 2019. We independently derived coordinates using both VGOS stations (the VGOS-TEST and VGOS-OPS networks) and the legacy S/X stations (the IVS-R1 and IVS-R4 networks).

The traditional approach to studying radio source stability is based on the analysis of a time series of its coordinates. However, source positions are typically estimated simultaneously with Earth orientation parameters, resulting in a unique Celestial Reference Frame (CRF) for each session. This requires that each session's CRF solution be transformed into a single, common reference frame before any investigation of source variability can begin. To avoid this complex transformation, we have instead utilized the arc length between pairs of radio sources. The arc length is a robust metric because it remains invariant to the orientation of the chosen CRF.

By analyzing the variability of these arc lengths, our work aims to achieve two primary goals: 1) to determine stable and unstable radio sources, and 2) to compare the performance and reliability of the legacy S/X and modern VGOS systems.

2 Source Arc Length

Time series of source positions are presented in a unique celestial reference frame for each session. The arc length between two sources, however, remains invariant to the reference frame's orientation during a single VLBI session. For this reason, our analysis

focused on variations in source arc length instead of source position variations.

For two radio sources, i and j , with coordinates (α_i, δ_i) and (α_j, δ_j) , the arc length ℓ_{ij} is calculated using the following formula:

$$\ell_{ij} = \arccos [\sin \delta_i \sin \delta_j + \cos \delta_i \cos \delta_j \cos (\alpha_i - \alpha_j)]$$

For each session, arc lengths were calculated for pairs of sources, along with their standard deviations. The repeatability of each arc was then assessed. To construct the time series of arc lengths, we included only radio sources whose coordinates were estimated from at least 20 high-quality observations per session. For the assessment of arc length repeatability, we only considered arcs calculated from 25 or more VLBI sessions within each network.

3 Networks of S/X and VGOS Stations

The rapid-turnaround sessions IVS-R1 (R1) and IVS-R4 (R4) have been observed since 2002 to provide twice-weekly Earth Orientation Parameter (EOP) results. These two series continue to use networks of dual-band S/X VLBI stations today. In January 2019, the IVS initiated a pilot session series, VGOS-TEST, utilizing the new VGOS station network. After a year of successful observations, the series was transitioned into an operational one, renamed VGOS-OPS. These VGOS-OPS sessions are observed fortnightly and, as of this text, three times per month. This work incorporates VGOS observations from both series, which are collectively designated as "VO". The distribution of the stations participating in the R1, R4, and VO networks is shown in Fig. 1.

3.1 S/X Networks (R1 and R4)

The R1 session series observations are scheduled at NASA GSFC and correlated by the Bonn Correlator. These observations are conducted weekly (every Monday) with a data rate of 512 Mbps. The R4 series observations are scheduled by the USNO and processed by the USNO Correlator. The R4 data rate

Fig. 1 Stations that participated in the R1 (top), R4 (middle), and the VO (bottom) networks. Circle size depends on number of sessions (1–10, 11–100, 101–200 and 200–300).

was 256 Mbps, but this was changed to 512 Mbps on October 26, 2023. Most geodetic VLBI stations participate in both R1 and R4 sessions, although some observe more frequently in one series than the other. Many VGOS stations also participate in these rapid sessions using a mixed (S/X – VGOS) mode. The correlator typically takes 15 days or less to process these rapid sessions. A VLBI Analysis Center (NASA for R1, USNO for R4) then performs a preliminary analysis and submits the results to the IVS Data Center.

Fig. 2 Sources that were observed in the R1 (top), R4 (middle), and the VO (bottom) networks. Circle size depends on number of sessions (1–10, 11–100, 101–200 and 200–300).

3.2 VGOS Networks (VO)

The VO series observations are scheduled by different agencies, such as Haystack and NASA, and are processed by six different correlators (Haystack, Bonn, USNO, Vienna, Wettzell, and SHAO). These observations are conducted two to three times per month with a high data rate of 8192 Mbps and typically involve five to ten stations. The correlators are given a 30-day or less deadline to process the VO sessions.

4 Data Analysis of the Observations

The observation data analysis was performed using the ν Solve software, Bolotin et al. (2014), which utilizes an embedded ECMAScript for consistent data processing. A total of 310 R1 and R4 sessions, along with 184 VGOS-OPS (VO) sessions, were analyzed from the beginning of 2019 to the end of 2024.

For each VLBI network, we obtained solutions using the following parameterization: station coordinates, source positions, EOP, zenith delays and gradients, and baseline clock offsets (if necessary) were estimated as local parameters (one solution per session). Clock models and zenith delays were modeled as piecewise linear functions with a one-hour interval between nodes.

To ensure the stability of the terrestrial and celestial reference frames, No-Net-Translation and No-Net-Rotation constraints were applied to stations with more than 50 usable observations in each session. Additionally, for each session, No-Net-Rotation constraints were applied to the estimated coordinates of radio sources to fix the orientation of the celestial reference frame.

5 Arc Length Repeatability

In total, our analysis collected 2,776 arcs for 445 sources in the R1 network, 2,872 arcs for 362 sources in the R4 network, and 3,419 arcs for 445 sources in the VO network. The distribution of these radio sources is depicted in the sky in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3 illustrates the distributions of arc length repeatability as a function of arc length for each network. The VGOS network provides a larger number of arcs and a broader range of arc repeatability compared to the S/X networks.

Analysis of the arc length repeatability sets enabled us to classify radio sources into two groups: those with stable and those with unstable estimated coordinates. Some sources were also found to exhibit systematic position effects. For each VLBI network series, we identified sources falling into these categories based on the arc length analysis, with the results summarized in Tab. 1.

Fig. 4 presents time series of three arcs, each connecting a stable source to either another stable

Fig. 3 Source arc length repeatability as a function of the length of arc for R1 (left), R4 (center) and VO (right) series of VLBI sessions.

Fig. 4 Time series of arc lengths between the source 0059+581 and the sources 0133+476 (top), 1741-038 (middle), and 1124-186 (bottom). The plots illustrate arcs with low (142 μas), medium (697 μas), and high (1421 μas) arc length dispersion.

Fig. 5 Time series of arc length between 0059+581 and 3C418 radio sources derived from observations in R1 (top), R4 (middle) and VO (bottom) networks.

source, a moderately stable source, or an unstable source. Fig. 5 highlights the systematic position effects of the source 3C418 as observed across the R1, R4, and VO networks. A comparison of arc lengths from the S/X and VGOS networks reveals that VGOS results are more sensitive to source position variations.

6 Conclusions

The arc length method has proven effective in identifying both stable and unstable sources, as well as detecting sources with time-dependent position changes. The sets of stable and unstable sources are largely consistent between the S/X and VGOS networks; however, the VGOS network offers higher

Table 1 Source Arc Length Analysis: stable sources, unstable and those exhibiting systematic effects in arc length for the R1, R4, and VO VLBI session series.

	Stable sources	Unstable sources	Sources with systematic effects
R1	0016+731, 0059+581, 0133+476, 0202+319, 0215+015, 0235+164, 0458-020, 0602+673, 0613+570, 0716+714, 0727-115, 0955+476, 1053+704, 1144+402, 1749+096, 1849+670, 3C371, OJ287	0019+058, 0104-408, 0119+115, 0454-234, 0656+082, 0748+126, 0808+019, 1124-186, 1128+385, 1255-316, 1334-127, 1424-418, 1639-062, 1908-201, 2008-159, 2255-282, CTA26	0119+115, 0229+131, 2008-159, 2229+695, 3C418
R4	0016+731, 0133+476, 0202+319, 0529+483, 0552+398, 0602+673, 0613+570, 0716+714, 0738+491, 0805+410, 0955+476, 1053+704, 1144+402, 1639-062, 1732+389, 1741-038, 1846+322, 2227-088, 3C371, OJ287	0017+200, 0109+224, 0119+115, 0322+222, 0346-279, 0446+112, 0458-020, 1059+282, 1145-071, 1219+044, 1243-072, 1504+377, 1538+149, 1546+027, 1806+456, 2255-282	2229+695, 3C418
VO	0016+731, 0059+581, 0133+476, 0202+319, 0529+483, 0552+398, 0602+673, 0613+570, 0716+714, 0642+449, 0800+618, 0805+410, 0814+425, 0955+476, 1053+704, 1144+402, 1418+546, 1538+149, 1726+455, 1751+288, 1803+784, 1849+670, 2000+472, 2113+293, 2201+171, 2229+695, 3C371, OJ287	0119+115, 0119+041, 0454-234, 0606-223, 0727-115, 0808+019, 0823+033, 1124-186, 1149-084, 1213-172, 1243-072, 1243-160, 1351-018, 1406-076, 1519-273, 1546+027, 1639-062, 1749+096, 1908-201, 2008-159, 2126-158, 2149+056, 2227-088, 2255-282, 2355-106, 3C446, CTA26	0119+115, 0229+131, 0642+449, 1030+415, 1156+295, 1213-172, 1504+377, 1732+389, 2209+236, 2229+695, 3C418, 3C446

precision, enabling the detection of more subtle variations in the estimated source coordinates.

The study successfully demonstrates that the arc length method is a highly effective and robust approach for analyzing radio source stability. Unlike traditional methods that rely on individual source coordinates, this technique avoids the complexities and uncertainties associated with transforming between different session-specific celestial reference frames. The arc length, by its very nature, is invariant to these frame orientations, making it a powerful and direct metric for stability analysis.

Through this analysis, we were able to identify and classify radio sources into groups of stable and unstable sources. This classification is crucial for the ongoing maintenance and refinement of celestial reference frames. Furthermore, the method proved capable of detecting sources that exhibit subtle, time-dependent position changes, providing a more detailed picture of source behavior than simple stability classification.

A key finding of this research is the direct comparison between the two major VLBI systems. The sets of stable and unstable sources identified were largely consistent between the legacy S/X and the modern VGOS networks. However, a significant difference was observed in the precision of the two systems. The VGOS network consistently offers higher precision, which allows for the detection of more subtle varia-

tions in source coordinates that the S/X system might miss. This superior sensitivity of VGOS data to source position variations highlights the technological advantages of the new system and supports its ongoing adoption in the global VLBI network.

References

- Bolotin S., Bayer K., Gipson J.M., Gordon D., MacMillan D. (2014). The VLBI data analysis software ν Solve: development progress and plans for the future. In 8th IVS General Meeting Proc., ISBN 978-7-03-042974-2, Science Press, Beijing, China, pp. 253-257. 2014.
- Nothnagel A., Artz T., Behrend D., Malkin Z. International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry - Delivering high-quality products and embarking on observations of the next generation. *Journal of Geodesy*, Vol. 91(7), pp. 711-721, July 2017. doi: 10.1007/s00190-016-0950-5

An assessment of the Ionospheric Total Electron content estimated from VGOS

T. Nilsson

Abstract In this work, the ionospheric TEC observables from VGOS are evaluated. This is done by estimating station-wise vertical TEC (VTEC) and TEC gradients from the VGOS differential slant TEC data. These are then compared to estimates from the legacy S/X VLBI system, from GNSS, and from global GNSS TEC maps. The VTEC estimates from VGOS are found to agree with those from legacy S/X VLBI on the level 1.5–2.5 TECU and with GNSS on the level 2–3 TECU.

Keywords VLBI, VGOS, GNSS, Ionosphere, TEC, VTEC

1 Introduction

In the legacy S/X VLBI system, the ionospheric delay is corrected by forming a ionospheric free combination of observations at two frequencies (S-band, 2.3 GHz and X-band, 8.5 GHz). However, the procedure is different for the new VGOS (VLBI Global Observing System, Petrachenko et al. (2009)) system. In this system, four frequency bands in the range 3.0 GHz to 10.6 GHz are observed. The observations from these four bands are later processed together in the fringe-fitting to estimate the differential ionospheric slant TEC (Total Electron Content) as well as the (ionosphere free) group delay and delay rate (Cappallo, 2014).

In this work, the quality of the VGOS TEC observables is studied. This was done by estimating station-wise Vertical TEC (VTEC) and TEC gradients

Tobias Nilsson^{1,2}

(1) Lantmäteriet, Lantmäterigatan 2C, 801 82 Gävle, Sweden

(2) Onsala Space Observatory, Chalmers University of Technology, 439 92 Onsala, Sweden

from the slant differential TEC observables. These were assessed by comparing them to estimates from other sources: legacy S/X VLBI, GNSS, and global GNSS TEC maps.

2 Theory and data analysis

To estimate station-wise VTEC and TEC gradients from the VGOS differential TEC observable, ΔTEC , the thin ionosphere shell approximation was used. This approximation means that all the electrons of the ionosphere are approximated to be located within a thin shell at height H (in this work $H=450$ km was used). With this approximation, ΔTEC observed by stations 1 and 2 is given by the following equation:

$$\Delta TEC = m(\varepsilon_1) VTEC_1^* - m(\varepsilon_2) VTEC_2^* + B_1 - B_2 \quad (1)$$

Here $VTEC_i^*$ is the VTEC value at the ionospheric pierce point (the location where the signal crosses the ionospheric shell) for station i , m is the ionospheric mapping function (the MSLM mapping function (Schaer, 1999) was used in this work), ε_i the elevation angle, and B_i the instrumental TEC bias of station i . Following Hobiger et al. (2006), assuming that the ionosphere rotates together with the apparent rotation of the sun, $VTEC_i^*$ can be related to VTEC at the station location, $VTEC_i$:

$$\begin{aligned} VTEC_i^*(t) = & VTEC_i [t + (\lambda_i^* - \lambda_i)/15] \\ & + (\phi_i^* - \phi_i) G_i [t + (\lambda_i^* - \lambda_i)/15] \quad (2) \\ & + (\phi_i^* - \phi_i)^2 H_i [t + (\lambda_i^* - \lambda_i)/15] \end{aligned}$$

Here ϕ_i^* and λ_i^* are the latitude and longitude of the ionosphere pierce point (in degrees), ϕ_i and λ_i the corresponding values for the station location, and t the time (in hours). To model the latitudinal variations of TEC, north-south gradients of both first, G_i and second order, H_i were used, instead of just first order as used by Hobiger et al. (2006). The temporal variations of $VTEC_i$ were modeled by parameterizing it as a piecewise linear function in 30 minute intervals, while for G_i and H_i piecewise linear functions in 1 hour intervals were used.

All 24-h VGOS sessions from 2017 until early 2025 were analyzed to estimate VTEC and gradients. For each session, the station-wise VTEC and gradient values at the piecewise-linear nodes, as well as the station-wise instrumental TEC biases (assumed to be constant over each session), were estimated from the differential TEC observables in a least squares adjustment. The sum of the TEC biases were constrained to be zero to avoid the singularity associated with these terms.

For comparison, the same procedure was also used to estimate VTEC and gradients from legacy S/X VLBI sessions observed at the same times as the VGOS sessions. Furthermore, VTEC and gradients were also estimated from GNSS observations recorded by GNSS stations co-located with the VGOS stations, using a similar method. Finally, VTEC was also calculated from the IGS global ionospheric TEC maps (Hernández-Pajares et al., 2009) compared to the VGOS results.

3 Results

3.1 VTEC

Figure 1 shows the time-series of VTEC estimates from the ONSA13NE station in Onsala, Sweden, as well as the difference to the estimates from other techniques. It can clearly be seen that VTEC has been increasing significantly during the time period 2019-2025. This is a consequence of the 11-year solar cycle which was at a minimum in the beginning (2019) and reaching a maximum at the end of the period (2025). The VTEC estimates from ONSA13NE agree very well with the estimates from the co-located VGOS telescope ONSA13SW, with a mean difference of -0.009 TECU and a stan-

Fig. 1 Ionospheric VTEC estimated from VGOS data at the ONSA13NE station, as well as the differences in VTEC estimates between ONSA13NE and the co-located VGOS telescope ONSA13SW, the co-located legacy VLBI station ONSALA60, the co-located GNSS station ONS1, and VTEC calculated from the IGS global ionospheric maps.

dard deviation of the differences of 0.48 TECU. This is not surprising since both telescopes often observe the same radio source, hence the observation geometries of the two telescopes are very similar. Somewhat larger differences can be seen when comparing with legacy VLBI, GNSS, and the IGS TEC maps. Here, the differences reach up to several TECU. Larger differences seen in the recent years, which most likely is a conse-

Table 1 The statistics of the differences in VTEC estimates between VGOS and the other techniques: legacy S/X VLBI, GNSS; and IGS TEC maps. For each techniques, the number of common dat points, as well as the mean and the standard deviation (StDev) of the VTEC differences are shown. All VTEC values are in TECU.

VGOS station	Legacy station	VGOS - legacy			VGOS - GNSS			VGOS -IGS maps		
		#	Mean	StDev	#	Mean	StDev	#	Mean	StDev
GGAO12M	-	-	-	-	6518	-1.33	2.19	6518	-1.87	2.09
ISHIOKA	-	-	-	-	3890	0.37	3.33	3921	-0.29	3.52
KOKEE12M	KOKEE	6639	-1.82	5.10	8593	-2.13	6.41	8879	-2.41	4.62
RAEGYEB	YEBES40M	808	0.47	1.94	5047	-0.99	2.58	5087	-1.20	2.66
WESTFORD	-	-	-	-	6462	-0.72	2.92	8396	-1.26	2.38
WETTZ13S	WETTZELL	5314	0.22	2.27	7210	-1.78	2.52	7243	-1.30	2.31
	WETTZ13N	2067	-0.00	1.83	-	-	-	-	-	-
ONSA13NE	ONSALA60	1395	-0.37	2.90	8089	-1.70	2.39	8089	-0.77	2.45
ONSA13SW	ONSALA60	818	-0.57	2.56	6444	-1.67	2.40	6444	-0.71	2.46
MACGO12M	-	-	-	-	6958	-1.41	2.88	7007	-3.04	2.75
HOBART12	-	-	-	-	2625	3.06	5.46	2726	4.32	5.59
NYALE13N	NYALES20	339	-0.93	4.22	2001	-2.58	3.21	2001	-3.85	3.31
	NYALE13S	771	-0.84	7.14	-	-	-	-	-	-
KATH12M	-	-	-	-	893	-0.59	8.41	914	0.87	9.47
RAEGSMAR	-	-	-	-	1332	0.22	3.56	1517	-0.03	3.72
WETTZ13N	WETTZELL	.	-	-	338	-2.50	3.87	338	-2.11	3.73
YARRA12M	-	-	-	-	146	0.19	5.44	146	1.79	5.45
SESHAN13	SESHAN25	40	3.18	4.77	49	0.75	3.11	98	-0.58	6.15
URUMQH3	URUMQI	-	-	-	98	-2.30	3.70	98	-2.12	4.19
HARTVGS	-	-	-	-	88	0.80	5.31	88	0.72	5.42

quence of the ionosphere being more variable near the solar maximum.

In Tab. 1 the mean and standard deviations of the VTEC differences between VGOS and legacy VLBI, GNSS, as well as IGS TEC maps are shown. The standard deviations are in general 1.5-3 TECU for the telescope which have been operating the longest (all stations up to MACGO12M have been operational since 2020 or earlier). For newer telescopes, the standard deviations are larger, about 3-6 TECU. The reason for this is likely that these telescopes have only observed in recent years when the ionospheric activity was very high. Furthermore, higher standard deviations can also be observed for KOKEE12M, although it has been operational since 2017. However, since the telescope is located relatively close to the equator (22° latitude), the ionospheric activity above this stations is in general very high. The high standard deviations for HOBART12 and KATH12M are likely influenced by the phase-cal problems experienced at these stations, leading to noisy observables.

From Tab. 1 is can also be noted that there are in general negative biases between VGOS and GNSS, with GNSS being 1-2 TECU higher than VGOS (similar biases can be seen when comparing with the IGS TEC maps). This is consistent with the general bias detected

in studies comparing VTEC from VLBI and GNSS, e.g. Hobiger et al. (2006) and Dettmering et al. (2011). Between VGOS and legacy VLBI there is no clear systematic bias.

3.2 TEC north-south gradients

Figure 2 shows the time series of the north-south TEC gradients of first and second order estimated from VGOS data for station KOKEE12M, Hawaii, USA. It can be noted that the gradients get larger and more variable in the recent years. This is due to the increased solar activity as the solar maximum is reached, and is consistent with what is seen for VTEC. The first order gradient tends to be negative, i.e. VTEC is increasing towards lower latitudes (i.e. towards the equator as KOKEE12M is located in the northern hemisphere).

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviations of the differences of gradient estimates between VGOS and legacy VLBI as well as between VGOS and GNSS. The standard deviations of the first order gradients for the longest operating stations are around 0.1-0.2 TECU/° for the differences with legacy VLBI. For the differences with GNSS the standard deviations

Table 2 The statistics of the differences in estimated north-south TEC gradients of first and second order between VGOS and legacy S/X VLBI as well as GNSS. For each techniques, the number of common data points, as well as the mean and the standard deviation of the TEC gradient differences are shown. The first order gradients are in units TECU/° and the second order gradients in TECU/°²

VGOS station	Legacy station	VGOS - legacy					VGOS - GNSS				
		1st order		2nd order			1st order		2nd order		
		#	Mean	StDev	Mean	StDev	#	Mean	StDev	Mean	StDev
GGAO12M	-	-	-	-	-	-	3406	0.21	0.22	0.74	1.70
ISHIOKA	-	-	-	-	-	-	2017	0.37	0.38	0.77	3.87
KOKEE12M	KOKEE	3380	0.02	0.46	0.27	1.93	4400	0.39	0.80	1.14	6.36
RAEGYEB	YEBES40M	409	0.03	0.17	-0.23	1.41	2625	0.21	0.23	0.98	2.02
WESTFORD	-	-	-	-	-	-	3322	0.18	0.25	-0.10	2.26
WETTZ13S	WETTZELL	2726	-0.02	0.14	0.17	0.71	3719	0.23	0.23	1.05	1.34
	WETTZ13N	1072	-0.01	0.10	0.19	0.48	-	-	-	-	-
ONSA13NE	ONSALA60	706	0.03	0.20	0.25	0.92	4152	0.16	0.22	-0.06	1.42
ONSA13SW	ONSALA60	414	0.00	0.14	0.18	0.74	3319	0.15	0.22	-0.10	1.42
MACGO12M	-	-	-	-	-	-	3601	0.26	0.26	1.34	2.09
HOBART12	-	-	-	-	-	-	1285	-0.16	0.41	-0.90	2.47
NYALE13N	NYALES20	172	-0.04	0.36	-2.04	2.30	1029	-0.04	0.38	0.21	2.81
	NYALE13S	399	-0.06	0.44	0.37	2.61	-	-	-	-	-
KATH12M	-	-	-	-	-	-	430	-0.28	0.82	-0.06	6.28
RAEGSMAR	-	-	-	-	-	-	698	0.25	0.37	-1.92	4.11
WETTZ13N	WETTZELL	-	-	-	-	-	174	0.18	0.30	0.74	2.07
YARRA12M	-	-	-	-	-	-	74	-0.09	0.31	0.78	2.73
SESHAN13	SESHAN25	20	-0.17	0.42	-2.90	3.96	50	0.37	1.37	-4.94	13.77
URUMQI13	URUMQI	-	-	-	-	-	50	0.40	0.20	1.92	2.19
HARTVGS	-	-	-	-	-	-	25	-0.21	0.39	0.29	2.84

Fig. 2 Ionospheric north-south TEC gradients of first (top) and second (bottom) order estimated from VGOS data at the KOKEE12M station.

are slightly higher, about 0.2-0.3 TECU/°. Similarly to

what is seen when looking at VTEC, it can be observed that larger standard deviations are obtained for the newer stations, as well as for KOKEE12M.

It can be noted that there seems to be a systematic bias in the first order gradient estimates between VGOS and GNSS of about 0.2 TECU/° for the northern hemisphere stations. Furthermore, for the southern hemisphere stations the bias seems to be negative, although no clear conclusions can be drawn due to the small amount of data. Large biases can also be seen for the second order gradients, however, these does not seem to have any clear systematics.

4 Conclusions

The results indicate that the ionospheric VTEC can be estimated from the VGOS differential TEC observables. These estimates agree with those from legacy VLBI on the level 1.5–2.5 TECU and with from GNSS on the level of 2–3 TECU. The agreement is worse for times and locations with a highly variable ionosphere, as could be expected.

Since the agreement with GNSS is similar to what is generally obtained using legacy VLBI (Hobiger et al., 2006; Dettmering et al., 2011), it suggests that the VTEC estimates from VGOS are at least as good as those from the legacy VLBI system. Hence, VGOS has potential to be used as a tool to study the ionosphere. Furthermore, the results confirm that the TEC estimation performed in the fringe-fitting for VGOS is working and produces reasonable results.

References

- Cappallo, R. (2014). Correlating and fringe-fitting broadband VGOS data. In D. Behrend, K. D. Baver, & K. Armstrong (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Eight IVS General Meeting: VGOS: The New VLBI Network* (pp. 91–96). Shanghai, China: Science Press.
- Dettmering, D., Heinkelmann, R., & Schmidt, M. (2011). Systematic differences between VTEC obtained by different space-geodetic techniques during CONTO8. *J. Geodesy*, 85, 443–451.
- Hernández-Pajares, M., Juan, J. M., Sanz, J., Orus, R., Garcia-Rigo, A., Feltens, J., Komjathy, A., Schaer, S. C., & Krankowski, A. (2009). The IGS VTEC maps: a reliable source of ionospheric information since 1998. *J. Geodesy*, 83, 263–275.
- Hobiger, T., Kondo, T., & Schuh, H. (2006). Very long baseline interferometry as a tool to probe the ionosphere. *Radio Sci.*, 41(1), RS1006.
- Petrachenko, B., Niell, A., Behrend, D., Corey, B., Böhm, J., Charlot, P., Collioud, A., Gipson, J., Haas, R., Hobiger, T., Koyama, Y., MacMillan, D., Malkin, Z., Nilsson, T., Pany, A., Tuccari, G., Whitney, A., & Wresnik, J. (2009). Design aspects of the VLBI2010 system. In D. Behrend & K. Baver (Eds.), *International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry 2008 Annual Report*, NASA/TP-2009-214183. NASA Technical Publications.
- Schaer, S. (1999). *Mapping and predicting the Earth's ionosphere using the global positioning system*. PhD thesis, Univ. Bern, Switzerland.

Simulating the impact of new VLBI Intensive baselines on combined UT1-UTC solutions

J. Page, K. Oldak-Wong, M. Davis, S. Byram

Abstract In the ongoing effort to improve Earth Orientation Parameter (EOP) estimates from the IERS Rapid Service/Prediction Center (RS/PC), we simulate the inclusion of new VLBI Intensive contributions and measure changes to UT1-UTC. Recent work has been focused on diversifying Intensive baselines that are included in the RS/PC combination in an effort to improve the robustness and reliability of the UT1-UTC solution. We must study a new analysis center and/or baseline's impact thoroughly before adding it to the combined solution, so as not to unintentionally skew EOP estimates. Work is underway to redesign our Data Simulation (DataSim) package to evaluate the impact of varying observational scenarios on historical EOP combined solutions. Here we show the inclusion of VGOS INT-B (Is-Oe) baseline from both USNO and GSFC analysis centers, and the southern hemisphere intensive IVS-INT-S (Hb-Ht) in a controlled simulation to look at the effect of UT1-UTC accuracy compared to the CO4 solution.

Keywords EOP, VLBI, IERS, Intensives

1 Introduction

The IERS Rapid Service/Prediction Center (RS/PC) is responsible for providing high-quality, low-latency EOP quantities daily. Data from Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI), Global Navigation Satellite

Jessica Page¹ · Kate Oldak-Wong¹ · Maria Davis¹ · Sharyl Byram¹
(1) United States Naval Observatory
3450 Massachusetts Avenue NW
Washington, DC 20392

System (GNSS), Atmospheric Angular Momentum (AAM), and Satellite Laser Ranging (SLR) are combined using a weighted cubic spline smoothing algorithm to produce Polar Motion (x and y), UT1-UTC, Celestial Pole Offsets (dX and dY or $d\psi$, $d\epsilon$), and a calculated length of day (LOD) from the combined UT1-UTC solution. A high quality solution updated on a daily basis requires accurate, low-latency input data, where low-latency is defined as < 24 hours before the o-Day solution, and "o-Day" is defined by the midnight epoch of the combination day. The quality of a solution on a given day depends on the availability and accuracy of observations present at the time of combination. The IVS (International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astronomy) *Rapids* are 24 hour observing sessions that have multiple stations/baselines with 2-3 week latency. They provide estimates for all 5 EOPs and have the highest accuracy for UT1-UTC. The IVS 1-hour *Intensives* are less accurate than the *Rapids*, but they're available at low latency due to their small networks (2-3 stations) and short observing time. For UT1-UTC, the quality and timeliness of the *Intensives* are a crucial factor in the accuracy of the o-Day solution; if there are no available VLBI *Intensives* within the last 24 hours of the o-day solution, the combination relies more heavily on integrated LOD values from IGS and AAM. The accuracy of a VLBI *Intensive* can also significantly impact the UT1-UTC solution. Figure 1 demonstrates a hypothetical UT1-UTC solution with visual markers that indicate the data inputs. The low accuracy "alternate IVS *Intensive*" shown in faded green with the "alternate combined EOP solution" in the dot-dashed lines demonstrates the necessity of high quality *Intensive* measurements.

Since the RS/PC UT1-UTC solution for a given day cannot be validated against a 24 hour session until the Rapids observations are available, we implement standards of *redundancy* and *resiliency* to ensure we can effectively mitigate any interruptions or unexpected circumstances in the combination. Having redundant Intensives to use in the combination provides resiliency should an observation be missing due to station maintenance, poor weather conditions, etc. While factors such as baseline geometry, scheduling, and source selection are crucial for choosing Intensive baselines (Schartner et al., 2021), simulated VLBI schedules often underestimate the formal error (FE) of the observed session (Hardin & Davis, 2024). Thus a new baseline must be tested extensively before including it as an input to the RS/PC combination. A previous study (Davis & Byram, 2024) showed that an observation’s formal error does not always reflect it’s accuracy. Before adding the K2-Ws VGOS baseline into the combination, it was found that the relationship between it’s residual from the RS/PC weekly solution, and it’s reported formal error was skewed and changes to the error modeling during analysis had to be made. A new baseline must have a sufficiently long observation history to measure the statistics of residuals to a reference solution, such as the CO4 solution.

2 DataSim

Testing the effect of new contributions on the RS/PC combination requires simulating the response alongside the existing data input conditions for that time. Work is underway to upgrade the previous software (Davis & Stamatakos, 2018) used to test modifications to the RS/PC solution. Once complete, the new DataSim software will have the capability to simulate various realistic combination and prediction scenarios such as the addition or removal of Intensive baselines. This will be especially useful to rapidly test new VGOS INT baselines as more are becoming available such as the Is-Oe baseline (VGOS INT-B). Other examples of current data input scenarios that will be useful to simulate include the Southern hemisphere Intensives (e.g. IVS-INT-S), new Analysis Center contributions, and the effect of including sub-daily Intensives at a higher observational frequency. Having a simulation

package will also allow us to quickly test the impact of any potential software changes such as prediction improvements and the addition or removal of other geodetic observations.

3 Preliminary Demo

We used a “Control” case with a representative set of IERS RS/PC data inputs for all 5 EOPs and tested varying Intensive observation scenarios in hindcast simulations from July 1st 2023 to June 30th 2024 to compare to IERS CO4 data. As more VGOS Intensives such as Is-Oe become available, we can test their impact on the combined solution once their observation history is sufficiently long and consistent. The regularly scheduled Southern Intensive Hb-Ht baseline has been shown to yield comparable UT1-UTC estimates to INT1 intensives (Böhm et al., 2022) which has the potential to provide redundancy. The following list summarizes each scenario tested, where either a “GSFC”, “USNO” or “GSI” listed after a baseline addition indicates that the observation was analyzed by Goddard Space Flight Center, U.S. Naval Observatory or Geospatial Information Authority of Japan Analysis Centers, respectively.

- **Control:** Kk-Wz (GSFC, USNO), K2-Ws (GSFC), Mk-Wz (GSFC, GSI, USNO)
- **Sim 1:** Control + Is-Oe (GSFC)
- **Sim 2:** Control + Is-Oe (USNO)
- **Sim 3:** Control + Is-Oe (GSFC) + Is-Oe (USNO)
- **Sim 4:** Control + Hb-Ht (GSFC)
- **Sim 5:** Control + Is-Oe (GSFC) + Is-Oe (USNO) + Hb-Ht (GSFC)

The RMS of CO4 residuals of UT1-UTC for each simulation are shown in Table 1. Outliers $> 300\mu s$ ($\sim 1\%$) were removed before calculating the summary statistics. The CO4 residual plot for each simulation is shown in Fig. 2.

Table 1 RMS [μs] of UT1-UTC CO4 residuals for 0, 1, 5 and 7-day predictions.

RMS [μs]	Control	Sim. 1	Sim. 2	Sim. 3	Sim. 4	Sim. 5
0-Day	44	42	42	40	42	42
1-Day	63	58	59	57	63	58
5-Day	151	152	151	151	151	152
7-Day	168	167	167	167	168	170

Fig. 1 Image Credit: (Davis et al., 2023). Sketch of RS/PC data contributors for UT1-UTC combined o-day solution. The alternate marker and alternate combined solution show a scenario where a low-latency observation (e.g., Alternate IVS Intensive) reports a significantly different UT1-UTC value; the local combined-solution, including the UT1-UTC o-day solution, would be reported in our daily products with a different UT1-UTC value.

Fig. 2 UT1-UTC [μs] CO4 residuals for each simulation excluding outliers $> 300\mu\text{s}$.

4 Discussion

The UT1-UTC Co4 residuals in Table 1 demonstrate that all 5 simulations had a negligible impact on the UT1-UTC solution compared to the Control simulation. There was a 4 μs improvement in the 1-Day prediction with the addition of 2 or 3 additional baselines. While most of the Co4 residuals in Fig. 2 were $< 300\mu\text{s}$, there were a few significant outliers that demonstrate a baseline's effect on a daily solution (Fig. 3). In most of these cases, especially for the outliers near MJD=60400, there were missing Intensives from the Control simulation for 2-3 days prior to the o-Day

solution. The simulations that added Is-Oe from either GSFC or USNO Analysis Centers without Hb-Ht observations produced residuals between 0.07 and 0.15 s, while the simulations that had added only Hb-Ht or Hb-Ht with the Is-Oe observations mitigated these anomalous conditions. This provides us an example of additional baseline(s) providing resiliency under conditions where low-latency observations are missing. For the particularly noisy day on MJD=60430, the addition of Hb-Ht caused a large residual that was mitigated in simulations containing Is-Oe observations from either AC alongside Hb-Ht. In reality, solutions are human-verified before being published to the community, and significant changes on the order of 0.1 s would have been investigated and mitigated prior to publication. However, the effect of an Intensive observation on the UT1-UTC solution is evident.

5 Conclusions

The IERS RS/PC is in the process of upgrading its DataSim software to reduce the analysis period of potential new data sets. We ran preliminary simulations to demonstrate the effect of adding the VGOS INT-B and IVS-INT-S Intensive baselines into the daily solution. All 5 simulations resulted in negligible changes to the UT1-UTC o-Day solution and predictions. Overall, the Is-Oe and Hb-Ht baselines provided redundancy under the controlled simulation. An investigation into

Fig. 3 Demonstration of Co4 residuals for each UT1-UTC [μ s] solution for all simulations before outliers were removed.

the solution days with outliers showed that adding more observations can provide resiliency on problematic days. It's worth mentioning that we compared the 5 simulations to a 'Control' simulation, while in reality the DataSim software will have the capability to simulate changes to the existing RS/PC contributions.

References

- Böhm, S, Böhm, J, Gruber, J. (2022) Probing a southern hemisphere VLBI Intensive baseline configuration for UT1 determination. *Earth Planets Space*, 74, 118 (2022). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40623-022-01671-w>. doi: .
- Davis, M, Davis, M, Stamatakos, N (2023) Recent Improvements to the IERS Rapid Service/Prediction Center Combined EOP Solution. *Journées*, Nice, 11-13 Sept.,
- Davis, M and Byram, S, (2024) The IERS Rapid Service / Prediction Center Mission, Challenges, and Developments. *IVS 2024 General Meeting Proceedings*, Tsukuba, Japan doi: .
- Davis, M and Stamatakos, N, (2018) Examining the Impact of New and Modified Techniques on the IERS RS/PC o-day UT1-UTC Solution. *AGU 2018*, Art. no. G31B-0661, 2018 doi: .
- Hardin, S, and Davis, M, (2024) Investigating the relationship between simulated and observed geodetic schedules. *IVS 2024 General Meeting Proceedings*, Tsukuba, Japan doi: .
- Schartner, M, Kern, L, Nothnagel, A et al. (2021) Optimal VLBI baseline geometry for UT1-UTC Intensive observations. *J Geod*, 95, 75 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-021-01530-8> .

The importance of communication in science, with a focus on VLBI and the RAEGE project

E. Azcue, M. Moreira, L. Moura, C. Pérez-Esteban, S. Belda, M. Karbon

Abstract Effective communication in science is essential for bridging the gap between researchers and society. This is particularly true in geodesy, a field that not only advances our understanding of Earth's dynamic processes but also impacts everyday life through applications such as navigation, disaster monitoring, and climate studies. The Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS) exemplifies this commitment by integrating global geodetic efforts and promoting the transmission of geodetic knowledge to society.

Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) rely on advanced technology and international collaboration to measure Earth's rotation, positions and other critical parameters. Projects such as The Atlantic Network of Geodynamic and Space Stations (RAEGE), a collaborative Spanish-Portuguese initiative aimed at constructing, installing, and operating four fundamental geodetic stations in Spain and Portugal (Azores), require substantial investment and societal engagement, emphasizing the need for effective communication strategies.

Engaging with the general public fosters understanding and appreciation of geodesy's contributions, helping to demystify its technical aspects and highlight its relevance. Simplified explanations and relatable

applications build trust and support for projects like RAEGE. For local communities near observatories, outreach efforts—such as educational programs or open days—encourage coexistence, address concerns, and showcase mutual benefits.

Within the scientific community, clear communication ensures the dissemination of findings and fosters interdisciplinary collaboration. A key focus of communication efforts is inspiring the next generation of scientists to pursue careers in VLBI and geodesy. GGOS plays a pivotal role here by uniting geodetic initiatives and enhancing their visibility. Transparent and strategic communication also strengthens the case for sustained funding by demonstrating the scientific and societal impact of long-term projects. With these goals a GGOS affiliate, called GGOS IberAtlantic, was created to foster collaboration across the Iberian Peninsula and the Atlantic region to integrate regional geodetic observations into global systems and ensure their visibility and impact.

In this contribution the efforts in the RAEGE project to reach diverse audiences and bring science closer to the public through outreach initiatives are presented.

Keywords RAEGE, Outreach, VLBI

Esther Azcue (eazcue@transportes.gob.es)¹ · Clara Pérez-Esteban¹ · Ana Rivas¹

(1) National Geographic Institute of Spain, Madrid, Spain

Mariana Moreira² · Luis Moura²

(2) RAEGE Santa Maria Station, RAEGE Azores Association, Santa Maria – Azores, Portugal

Santiago Belda³ · Maria Karbon³

(3) Applied Mathematics Dept., University of Alicante, Alicante, Spain

1 Introduction: The Atlantic Network of Geodynamic and Space Stations (RAEGE)

Developed through a partnership between the National Geographic Institute of Spain and the Regional Government of the Azores, RAEGE exemplifies the importance of international geodetic collaboration

in the Iberian and Atlantic regions. The project aims to construct, install, and operate four Geodetic Core Sites, two in Spain (Yebees and Gran Canaria) and two in the Azores (Flores and Santa Maria), for geodetic and geodynamic research.

The RAEGE project is focused on strengthening the geodetic infrastructure within Spain and Portugal, while contributing to the Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS). Currently, only two (Yebees and Santa Maria) of the four planned stations are operational. However, in the near future, the construction of the remaining two stations in Temisas, Gran Canaria, and Flores, Azores, is expected to be completed.

In addition to infrastructure development and maintenance, RAEGE also encompasses the exploitation of the data generated, as well as the communication and dissemination of results. These efforts are designed to bring geodetic science closer to society, helping the public understand the relevance of the data and the importance of investing in geodetic infrastructure.

As part of the outreach efforts to raise awareness about the project, the official website has been redesigned to be more attractive and user-friendly, gathering all essential information about RAEGE in one place. It can be accessed at <https://raege.eu/>. Fig. 1

Fig. 1 Website of RAEGE project.

2 Outreach activities in RAEGE

RAEGE is making a strong effort to ensure that communication about its work is not only informative but also engaging and accessible to the public. An example of this effort was this poster designed as a board game, Fig. 2, inviting participants to explore the outreach ac-

tivities carried out within the project.

The game offered a fun and interactive way to learn about RAEGE's initiatives, with the ultimate prize being a 3D-printable model of a RAEGE radio telescope. This model was created with the goal of enabling other research groups to build their own replicas and use them to share the science behind VLBI (Very Long Baseline Interferometry) with broader audiences. Throughout the board game, players could discover a variety of outreach activities, each representing a different aspect of how RAEGE brings geodetic science closer to society. These activities are detailed below:

Fig. 2 Board game of the poster.

- **Square 1-4.** A summary of the status of the four RAEGE stations is presented.
- **Square 5.** In this game square, Isabel and Artur were introduced, two goats who served as gardening assistants and helped make the Santa Maria Station more welcoming. Their presence sparked curiosity and created a friendly atmosphere. Though they passed away of natural causes, they are fondly remembered for the joy they brought.
- **Square 6.** Sunset at RAEGE, Fig. 3. As part of the Live Science on Summer program, RAEGE-Az hosted "Sunset at RAEGE", an event designed to bring science closer to the community in a fun and engaging way during the summer holidays. The event was a great success, drawing the local community to the RAEGE Santa Maria station for guided tours, science and art activities, live

music, night sky observations, food, and more. This initiative underscored the importance of science communication and public engagement. Even after three years, the community still fondly remembers the night and frequently requests another edition.

Fig. 3 Sunset at RAEGE advertising.

- **Square 7.** In this game square, the participation in various science fairs is presented. During Madrid Science Week 2024, the National Geographic Institute of Spain held workshops on VLBI and GNSS, Fig.4, offering hands-on activities to introduce space geodesy to the public. RAEGE-Az also took part in SciComPT 2022, where it won Best Long Presentation for showcasing its science communication efforts and making geodesy more accessible.
- **Square 8.** School and general visits. The Yebes Observatory welcomes general visits, offering the public a chance to explore the geodetic and radio astronomy facilities. Additionally, in some cases, educational talks have been given at schools to introduce students to the world of space geodesy and scientific research. The RAEGE Santa Maria

Fig. 4 Madrid Science Week

station hosted several institutional and school visits throughout 2024, including students from local schools (3 to 18 years old), from universities, and participants from international conferences and important meetings, and governmental visits. These visits provided participants with insights into RAEGE's infrastructure and its significance for both science and society. Each visit needs to be adapted to the audience, making it clear and understandable for every visitor.

- **Square 9.** Promoting Geodesy Among Young Talents. RAEGE actively supports and promotes geodesy, especially among young talents. As part of this commitment, IGN Spain has sponsored the Spanish National Mathematics Meeting (ENEM) 2024, held in Madrid from July 22 to 26. This annual event brings together students and professionals to explore new ideas and career opportunities. The IGN-CNIG participated in various activities, including a workshop on VLBI. Additionally, IGN Spain took part in the Complutense University Summer Courses in San Lorenzo de El Escorial (July 8-9, 2024), organizing the course "Space Geodesy: A Global Approach to Measuring and Understanding the Earth.". The Complutense University Summer Courses in San Lorenzo de El Escorial are an internationally recognized academic forum that has been held annually since 1988. These courses bring together

university students, researchers, and the general public to discuss current scientific, cultural, social, and political topics through high-quality lectures, debates, and workshops. The event serves as a platform for intellectual exchange.

- **Square 10.** Virtual resources. Virtual resources are being developed to improve geodesy outreach and education. The IGN created an engaging educational video on GNSS concepts and introduced a tide gauge mascot—a droplet-shaped character with wave-like hair. RAEGE Santa Maria, in collaboration with the Municipality of Vila do Porto, produced digital materials for an event for Azorean emigrants in the USA, including a presentation, a promotional video, and a subtitled VLBI video to reach international audiences. Additionally, virtual tours are being developed for the Yebes observatory, with plans to expand to all RAEGE observatories.
- **Square 11.** Build a RAEGE Antenna yourself! A paper cutout has been created to allow you to build your own RAEGE antenna of paper! This model, Fig. 5, has been designed to provide a fun and educational way to explore the structure of a RAEGE antenna. By assembling the cutout, you can get a hands-on understanding of the antenna's design and components. It's a great way to visualize and appreciate the technology behind geodetic observation in a simple and interactive format.

Fig. 5 RAEGE antenna cutout

- **Square 12.** RAEGE website is presented.

- **Square 13.** Geodetic viewer. The National Geographic Institute of Spain is developing a geodetic product viewer that will provide a single access point to all geodesy-related resources and products. This platform will offer an integrated way to explore geodetic data, ensuring easier access to valuable information. Additionally, there will be a dedicated section for multi-technique geodetic sites, highlighting their importance in high-precision geoscientific research. The viewer is expected to be completed by the end of 2025, enhancing data accessibility and usability for researchers and professionals in the field.
- **Square 14.** RAEGE antenna 3D model. The development of a VLBI model was carried out at RAEGE Azores and later adapted at the IGN. Fig. 6. Materials: The radio telescopes are 3D printed and have mobility in azimuth and elevation. Each radio telescope is equipped with a light sensor (using 2 micro:bits). A lamp or the flash of a smartphone simulates the radio-source. Attached to the model is a screen and a laptop with a program that simulates the reception of the signal (light) at each antenna, illustrating the principle of VLBI. The antennas can be positioned in position 1, simulating a delay in the reception of the signal, from this delay can be obtained the length of the baseline. Then one antenna is moved to position 2. This simulator demonstrates that the delay is greater in the new position and calculates the baseline length based on this delay. The base of the model is printed to simulate a map of Spain/Portugal-Azores, representing the RAEGE configuration.

Fig. 6 RAEGE 3D model

3 GGOS IberAtlantic

GGOS IberAtlantic was established in 2024 as a regional affiliate spanning Spain and Portugal. It builds on long-standing collaboration between both countries (e.g. RAEGE project) and aims to serve as a unified voice to communicate scientific findings in an accessible way, allowing the public and policymakers to better understand changes occurring on our planet. By highlighting geodesy's contributions, GGOS IberAtlantic seeks to help attract new projects, funding, and skilled professionals to the field.

GGOS IberAtlantic supports GGOS goals and aims to address the low visibility of geodesy, which is currently leading to two pressing challenges in the IberAtlantic region:

- Lack of human resources: Limited public awareness makes it difficult to attract new talent to the sector, creating a major challenge for Spanish and Portuguese geodetic institutions in recruiting the next generation of experts.
- Lack of funds: Geodetic infrastructure requires significant investment for maintenance, upgrades, and daily operations. When decision-makers are not aware of geodesy's relevance, securing the necessary funding becomes difficult.

Through education, outreach, and coordinated efforts, GGOS IberAtlantic will contribute to a stronger, more sustainable geodetic infrastructure, empowering society to better understand and respond to Earth system changes.

One of its first initiatives is a summer school at the Yebes Observatory for students from Spain and Portugal, Fig. 7, teaching space geodetic techniques principles, station operations and data analysis. This school aims to introduce young people to geodesy so they can consider it as a future career option. The 1st GGOS IberAtlantic Summer School will be held from July 13th to 18th, 2025. Participants will learn about techniques like VLBI, GNSS, SLR, DORIS, Gravimetry and Local Tie measurements, with hands-on exposure to global geodetic station operations and data analysis. The program also emphasizes networking with experts in the field.

Fig. 7 GGOS IberAtlantic Summer School

4 Conclusions

In summary, this contribution shows the activities of RAEGE project and GGOS IberAtlantic in communication and outreach. Through educational activities, digital content, and international collaboration, they are making geodesy more visible, relatable, and impactful in the IberAtlantic region. By promoting space geodesy at multiple levels (from inspiring young talent and engaging the general public to informing decision-makers) these initiatives not only enhance public understanding but also foster support for long-term scientific investment.

5 Acknowledgments

This research was supported partially by Generalitat Valenciana (SEJIGENT/2021/001), the European Union — Next Generation EU (ZAMBRANO21-04) and by Spanish Project PID2020-119383GB-I00 funded by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/).

SNR simulations for Genesis VT observations

H. Sert, M. Schartner, A. Özyıldırım, R. Haas, Ö. Karatekin

Abstract The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of Genesis signals on a baseline between two VLBI Global Observing System (VGOS) telescopes is a critical factor influencing data quality and delay estimation. The SNR on a given baseline depends on various factors, including the received power flux density (PFD) at each station. In traditional VLBI observations of quasars at cosmological distances, the incoming radio signals arrive at the ground stations with approximately equal power, resulting in a uniform PFD across identical telescopes. However, in the case of a VLBI transmitter (VT) onboard an Earth-orbiting satellite, the received signal power varies across different ground stations due to the dynamic geometrical configurations between the satellite and each station. In this study, we conduct simulations over a one-day period to compute the SNR for different baselines, considering various antenna gains for Genesis Band A (3100–3300 MHz) signals.

Keywords VLBI, transmitter, SNR

1 Introduction

The uncertainty of Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) group delay measurements is intrinsically linked

Hakan Sert^{1,2} · Matthias Schartner³ · Alime Özyıldırım¹ · Rüdiger Haas⁴ · Özgür Karatekin¹

(1) Royal Observatory of Belgium

(2) Université catholique de Louvain, Earth and Life Institute

(3) ETH Zurich, Institute of Geodesy and Photogrammetry

(4) Chalmers University of Technology, Onsala Space Observatory, Space, Earth and Environment

to the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the observation, as demonstrated by Whitney (1974):

$$\sigma_{\tau} = \frac{1}{2\pi \text{SNR} \Delta \nu_{\text{RMS}}} \quad (1)$$

Here, σ_{τ} represents the uncertainty in the group delay, and $\Delta \nu_{\text{RMS}}$ denotes the effective bandwidth (i.e., the root-mean-square of the spanned bandwidth) of the receiving system. The effective bandwidth accounts for the distribution of observing frequencies across the system and is computed as

$$\Delta \nu_{\text{RMS}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\nu_i - \bar{\nu})^2}, \quad (2)$$

where ν_i is the frequency of the i -th channel, $\bar{\nu}$ is the mean frequency, and n is the total number of channels. The effective bandwidth $\Delta \nu_{\text{RMS}}$ is crucial, as a wider bandwidth reduces the group delay uncertainty by improving the frequency resolution.

The SNR measures the strength of the observed signal relative to the noise level. For quasar observations, the theoretical SNR is calculated as

$$\text{SNR} = \eta \frac{S}{\sqrt{\text{SEFD}_1 \cdot \text{SEFD}_2}} \cdot \sqrt{Nt}, \quad (3)$$

where SEFD_i is the *system equivalent flux density* for station i , η is the correlation efficiency factor — typically between 0.5 and 0.7 (Jaradat et al., 2021) —, t is the scan length (or integration time) of the observation, and S is the correlated power flux density (PFD) of the observed radio source, and N is the total data rate, taken as 2048 Mbit/s (Niell et al., 2018). For VLBI quasar observations, the typical source flux density is assumed to be $S \equiv 1 \text{ Jy} = 1 \cdot 10^{-26} \text{ W Hz}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (Nothnagel, 2021).

The SNR equation underscores the interplay between the characteristics of the radio source, the performance of the receiving antennas, and the observation parameters. Higher SNR values can be achieved through increased PFD, improved antenna efficiency, lower system noise temperatures, larger bandwidth, or longer integration times. These factors collectively contribute to reducing the uncertainty in group delay measurements, thereby enhancing the precision of VLBI observations. While the actual SNR is calculated during fringe fitting, the SNR equation can provide valuable insight into identifying areas where the system and observation layout can be optimized during the scheduling process to achieve better results (Schartner et al., 2019).

Assuming a single S , for both stations does not hold for satellite VLBI transmitter (VT) observations, as the Free Space Path Loss (FSPL) (and other possible losses) are unequal due to the varying distances between the satellite and the observing stations, which significantly affect the received signal strength. In the case of VLBI VT observations, the SNR for a baseline can be derived by combining the individual SNR values from both stations. This requires modifying the flux density term S in Eq. 3, using the relation of

$$S = \sqrt{S_1 \cdot S_2}. \quad (4)$$

This approach accounts for the unequal PFD values received at the two stations due to the different distances between the (near-field) satellite and the observing stations. Thus, SNR equation for VT observations can be given as

$$\text{SNR} = \eta \frac{\sqrt{S_1 \cdot S_2}}{\sqrt{\text{SEFD}_1 \cdot \text{SEFD}_2}} \cdot \sqrt{Nt}, \quad (5)$$

To compute the SNR of VT observations, it is therefore important to take into account the PFD for individual VLBI ground stations. This requires considerations of gains/losses for given satellite-station configurations as well as receiver/transmitter specifications.

2 Received power flux density at the ground stations

The PFD at a ground station i from a radio source is determined by the received power (P_r) and the band-

width of the signal (Δv), i.e.

$$S_i = \frac{P_r}{A_e \Delta v}, \quad (6)$$

where A_e is the effective area of the telescope defined as the physical aperture area multiplied by an efficiency factor, k , typically ranging from 0.4 to 0.6 (Jaradat et al., 2021) and set to 0.5 in this study. Given a desired power flux density S_i at the VLBI telescope, the received power is hence determined as

$$P_r [W] = 10^{-26} \cdot S_i [\text{Jy}] \cdot \Delta v [\text{Hz}] \cdot A_e [\text{m}^2], \quad (7)$$

where S_i represents the power flux density in units of Jansky. Note that the terms with squared brackets represent the units for each parameter.

The received power on a ground station can be obtained by considering all gains and losses for the given transmitter power, P_t . The Friis transmission equation (Stutzman & Thiele, 2012) provides a relationship considering VT and telescope gains and Free Space Path Loss (FSPL = $(4\pi R/\lambda)^2$) for given VT power P_t in linear form

$$\frac{P_r}{P_t} = G_t G_r \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi R} \right)^2, \quad (8)$$

where G_t and G_r are the transmitter and receiving telescope gains, λ is the signal wavelength, and R is the distance between the VT and the ground station. Telescope gain is given as (Jaradat et al., 2021)

$$G_r = k(\pi d/\lambda)^2 \quad (9)$$

where d is the diameter of telescope which is assumed to be 13.2 m in this study, and k is the aperture efficiency. Substituting the expression for P_r in Eq. 7 into Eq. 8, the required transmitter power in watt per hertz for a given bandwidth can be written as

$$\frac{P_t [W]}{\Delta v [Hz]} = \frac{\text{FSPL}}{G_t G_r} S_i \cdot 10^{-26} \cdot A_e. \quad (10)$$

Once P_t is determined, the received flux density at the telescope for different configurations can be found by rearranging Eq. 8. For a fixed P_t , the PFD at the telescope i is given by

$$S_i [\text{Jy}] = \frac{1}{10^{-26}} \frac{P_t}{A_e \Delta v} G_t G_r \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi R} \right)^2. \quad (11)$$

2.1 VT Antenna Gain

Antenna gain measures how effectively an antenna directs power in a specific direction, compared to an isotropic antenna. The antenna radiation pattern describes how power varies with direction. The solid angle, Ω , of the main lobe is given by the product of the Half Power Beam Width (HPBW) angles in two principal planes ($\Omega = \theta_{HPBW} \cdot \phi_{HPBW}$) and the directivity D of an antenna is defined as the ratio of the solid angle of an isotropic antenna to that of the directional antenna:

$$D = 4\pi/\Omega \quad (12)$$

Considering that the Earth's field-of-view from the Genesis altitude of 6000 km is approximately 62° in both planes, the required HPBW to fully cover this region is also $\theta \approx \phi \approx 62^\circ$. According to Eq. 12, this corresponds to a directivity value of approximately $D = 10$, indicating that the signal strength at boresight is about 10 times higher than that of an isotropic antenna and decreases with increasing boresight angle. Any off-axis deviation can be accounted for by the radiation pattern factor, f_{arp} , which represents how the signal power varies as a function of the boresight angle. Then the directivity for a given angular position can be obtained by

$$D_i = D \cdot f_{arp}(\theta, \phi), \quad (13)$$

which takes into account how the signal power is directed for a given boresight angle. Finally, the antenna gain G_t , considering directivity and efficiency, is given by

$$G_t = \mu D_i, \quad (14)$$

where μ is the efficiency factor of the VT antenna, set to 0.7 in this work.

We consider directional radiation patterns modeled as $\cos^n(\theta)$, where the exponent n controls the rate of signal attenuation with boresight angle. Specifically, we use patterns that produce signal drops of 0 dBi (isotropic), 3 dBi, 6 dBi, and 9 dBi at the edge of Earth's field of view, denoted as P_0 , P_3 , P_6 , and P_9 , respectively.

3 Simulations and results

We simulate a one-day orbit of the planned Genesis satellite (Delva et al., 2023), which will operate in a quasi-polar circular orbit at 6000 km altitude. An onboard VT with quasar-like signal characteristics (Karatekin et al., 2023) will be directly observable by VGOS stations. The VT signal parameters are summarized in Table 1. SEFD values for 12 VGOS stations, derived from the analysis of log-files of one year of VGOS observations (Schartner, 2025), are listed in Table 2 for Band A.

Table 1 Genesis VT signal characteristics. Only Band-A is considered in this work.

Name	Range [MHz]	Bandwidth [MHz]
A	3100-3300	200
B	5250-5570	320
C	8200-8400	200
D	9300-9800	500

Table 2 VGOS stations and SEFD (Jy) values for Genesis Band A.

Station	SEFD	Station	SEFD	Station	SEFD
GGAO12M	2800	ISHIOKA	2500	KATH12M	4500
HOBART12	4500	KOKEE12M	3400	MACGO12M	2600
NYALE13S	1800	ONSA13NE	3400	WESTFORD	3000
WETTZ13S	3000	YARRA12M	4500	RAGEYEB	1900

Using 12 VGOS stations (Table 2), we compute the power flux density (PFD) at 1-minute intervals throughout the full day of VT transmission for Band A. This analysis is performed for multiple VT power spectral density (VT-PSD) levels and four different radiation patterns. Figure 1 illustrates the PFD as a function of elevation angle, with VT-PSD levels indicated by the colorbar. Both higher VT PSD and increased antenna directivity allow achieving the same PFD at lower elevation angles, demonstrating the advantages of focused beamforming. As VT-PSD increases, the PFD received at each station also rises proportionally. Moreover, with greater directivity, the elevation dependency becomes more pronounced; in other words, the difference between the maximum and minimum PFD received across stations increases during the simulation when directivity is considered.

However, excessively high PFD values are also not desired since the emitted signal might interfere

Fig. 1 PFD as a function of elevation and VT power spectral density for four different radiation patterns.

with observations from neighboring disciplines like astronomy. The VT-PSD and associated radiation pattern must be carefully selected to maintain PFD within an acceptable range among all stations. Figure 2 shows the minimum and maximum PFD received at the stations for each VT-PSD level, with each scatter points corresponding to the minimum and maximum values of a single curve in Figure 1. The threshold range of 0.5–10 Jy reflects discussions within the VLBI working group of ESA’s Genesis Science Exploitation Team (GSET) (Haas, 2025).

The PFD levels that satisfy the threshold are confined in the gray box in Fig. 2. For the most directive antenna pattern, P_9 , none of the VT-PSD levels satisfies the desired PFD range: lower VT-PSD levels result in PFDs below 0.5 Jy at maximum distance, while higher VT-PSD levels exceed 10 Jy at minimum distance (i.e., 90° elevation). In contrast, with isotropic radiation (P_0), the difference between minimum and maximum PFD becomes less pronounced, allowing for higher VT-PSD levels. Table 3 summarizes the maximum and minimum VT-PSD allowances for each radiation pattern (highest and lowest markers in the gray box for each radiation pattern).

Table 3 Maximum and minimum VT power spectral density values delivering PFD within 0.5–10 Jy across all VGOS stations during the simulation for each radiation pattern.

Pattern	P_{tmax} [dBW/Hz]	P_{tmin} [dBW/Hz]
P_0	-104	-111
P_3	-112	-117
P_6	-115	-118
P_9	-	-

Fig. 2 Maximum and minimum PFD for all stations during the simulations for different VT power spectral density levels for each radiation pattern. The gray box confines the VT levels that deliver PFD within 0.5–10 Jy.

Using the maximum and minimum allowable VT-PSD levels for each radiation pattern, we compute the SNR of VT observations in the Band A via Eq. 5, assuming a 10-second integration time and including all baseline combinations with elevation angles above 3° . The SEFD values of Band A for each VGOS station are listed in Table 2. Although SEFD typically varies with elevation, we assume it remains constant throughout the simulation for simplicity.

Figure 3 shows the mean SNR values for each baseline during the simulation, based on both maximum and minimum allowable power spectral density for all radiation patterns, excluding P_9 , which does not satisfy the 0.5–10 Jy PFD requirement. The corresponding $\sqrt{SEFD_1 \cdot SEFD_2}$ values are shown in the bottom figure for each baseline. The results highlight that SEFD is as critical as PFD in determining the SNR. For maximum allowable VT-PSD, more isotropic antenna patterns yield higher mean SNRs due to the greater permitted transmission power spectral density. At minimum VT-PSD, directive antennas provide slightly higher mean SNRs, benefiting from their focused energy distribution.

Figure 4 provides a clear overview of the mean SNR distribution across baselines. While an SNR of 20–30 is typically sufficient for VLBI quasar observations, a higher SNR improves observational sensitivity. For the lowest VT-PSD setting, approximately 50% of the baselines achieve a mean SNR of around 25 for all radiation patterns. Under maximum VT-PSD settings, nearly all baselines exceed this threshold on average. However, realistic factors such as elevation-dependent SEFD and

Fig. 3 Mean SNR of each baselines for Band A associated with $\sqrt{SEFD_1 SEFD_2}$ factors with 10 seconds of integration time.

atmospheric attenuation are expected to reduce the effective SNR in practice.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

In this study, we considered various VT power spectral density levels and four antenna radiation patterns onboard the Genesis satellite and computed the mean SNR across all baselines in a VGOS network during a one-day simulation for the Genesis A band. The PFD at each station was constrained to be within a 0.5–10 Jy range, and power spectral density limits were deter-

Fig. 4 Percentage of mean SNR values across all baselines exceeding a given threshold.

mined accordingly for each radiation pattern. This limit excluded the most directive case (P9) due to excessive PFD.

Using the resulting minimum and maximum allowable VT power spectral density values, we computed mean SNR values with a 10-second integration time for all baselines. Even at the lowest values, approximately 50 % of baselines achieved a mean SNR around 25 for all available radiation patterns. At maximum values, almost all baselines exceeded this threshold for all radiation patterns.

However, more realistic scenarios—including elevation-dependent SEFD and atmospheric attenuation—are expected to lower the actual SNR values. Additionally, this study assumed that the full emitted bandwidth can be observed, which might not be realistic due to technical limitations. Additionally, the study only focuses on Band A, while station sensitivity in Band D is typically reduced. Future work will incorporate these effects to refine performance estimates.

References

Delva P, Altamimi Z, Blazquez A, *et al.* (2023) GENESIS: collocation of geodetic techniques in space. *Earth, Planets and Space*, 75(1), 5. Springer, doi: 10.1186/s40623-022-01752-w

Haas R (2025) personal communication.

Jaradat A, Jaron F, Gruber J, Nothnagel A (2021) Considerations of VLBI transmitters on Galileo satellites. *Advances In Space Research*. (2021,5), doi: 10.1016/j.asr.2021.04.048

Karatekin Ö, Sert H, Dehant V, *et al.* (2023) VLBI signals transmitted from Earth orbiting satellites. In: *Proc. 26th European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astronomy Working Meeting*.

Nothnagel A (2021) *Elements of geodetic and astrometric very long baseline interferometry*. TU Wien, Department of Geodesy and Geoinformation: Vienna, Austria.

Niell A, Barrett J, Burns A, *et al.* (2018) Demonstration of a Broadband Very Long Baseline Interferometer System: A New Instrument for High-Precision Space Geodesy. *Radio Science*, 53, doi: 10.1029/2018RS006617.

Schartner M, Böhm J (2019) VieSched++: a new VLBI scheduling software for geodesy and astrometry. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 131(1002), 084501, IOP Publishing, doi: 10.1088/1538-3873/ab1820.

Schartner M (2025) personal communication.

Stutzman W L, Thiele G A (2012) *Antenna theory and design*. John Wiley & Sons.

Whitney A R (1974) *Precision geodesy and astrometry via very-long-baseline interferometry*. PhD thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

On the absolute sea level at the Swedish west coast estimated by VLBI, GNSS, and tide gauges

G. Elgered and R. Haas

Abstract We analyse the existing ten year time series of sea level observations at the Onsala Space Observatory. A time series of ten years is however too short to result in a stable value for a linear trend. Therefore we compare the sea level data acquired at Onsala with those from the nearby tide gauge station Ringhals. The tide gauge at Ringhals started operations in late 1967. Using Ringhals sea level data we estimate a linear trend for the relative sea level of 0.54 mm/year. Space geodesy observations using Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) from 1980 to 2020 and Global Navigational Satellite Systems (GNSS) from 1994 to 2020 have resulted in estimates of the land uplift of 2.9 mm/year and 2.7 mm/year, respectively. Combining the relative sea level trend at Ringhals with the land uplift at Onsala result in an estimate of 3.3 mm/year for the linear trend of the absolute sea level for this region. This is in agreement with recent estimates for the linear trend of the global sea level rise during this time period.

Keywords sea level, tide gauge

1 Introduction

The geodesy Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) radio telescopes and the Global Navigational Satellite Systems (GNSS) stations at the Onsala Space Observatory are all located within a few hundred metres from the Kattegat coastline. Therefore, a collaboration be-

Gunnar Elgered, Rüdiger Haas
Chalmers University of Technology, Onsala Space Observatory,
SE-439 92 Onsala, Sweden

Fig. 1 The tide gauge station at the Onsala Space Observatory.

gun with the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) to install a tide gauge station at the observatory (see Figure 1). SMHI is responsible for the national observational network of sea level in Sweden and the data are available by open access. This station has been operational since June 2015 and its characteristics have been presented at an earlier EVGA meeting (Elgered et al., 2019). There is now a time series of the relative sea level for almost ten years. It is still a bit short to combine with geodetic height data to assess long term trends in the absolute sea level. However, the tide gauge station Ringhals, located 20 km south-south-east of Onsala has been operational since 1 November 1967. In the following we present observational data from these two stations and combine the results with recent estimates of the land uplift from VLBI and GNSS in order to derive a value for the linear trend of the absolute sea level rise in this region.

Fig. 2 Sea level observations at Onsala (top). The estimated linear trend from the start to a specific date show that seasonal and yearly variability is significant (bottom).

2 Onsala tide gauge

The tide gauge station is equipped with several sensors, three radar sensors, one laser sensor, and two pneumatic sensors (Elgered et al., 2019). The official sensor is the CS476 radar. Hourly values of the sea level are archived and available via the SMHI web pages (open access). We show the complete time series, from 00 UT 24 June 2015 to 24 UT 28 February 2025, in Figure 2. Starting five years from the first observation we also present estimates for the linear trend when adding one more month of data for each estimate. We note that the variability is significant, also towards the end of the time series, and conclude that the changing weather conditions, mainly in terms of pressure and winds from year to year, have a large influence on the overall trend.

The sea level at Onsala has roughly varied between half a metre below to one and a half metre above the average sea level. The variations are dominated by changes in weather, i.e., the pressure and the direction and the speed of the wind. An example when

Fig. 3 An example time series of the sea level at Onsala during five days in July 2019 when the weather conditions were rather stable and the tides are clearly visible.

the weather conditions are rather stable is presented in Figure 3. The tidal signal is hence rather weak, a typical peak-to-valley difference of about 20 cm.

3 Comparison: Sea level at Onsala and Ringhals

We use the existing simultaneous data (from June 2014 to February 2025) to assess the question of how representative the Ringhals tide gauge station is for the corresponding one at Onsala. The Onsala and Ringhals stations provide 84,819 and 84,329 data points, respectively. This corresponds a coverage of 99.86 % and 99.29 %, respectively. Before the comparison is done, we select only data points that are acquired on the same hour resulting in 84,235 data points, corresponding to 99.2 % of the total period. The sea level observations at Ringhals are shown in Figure 4. When comparing Figure 2 and Figure 4 we see an overall agreement but a difference in the sea level trends of about half a mm/year: 5.13 mm/year at Onsala and 5.61 mm/year at Ringhals.

Fig. 4 Sea level observations at Ringhals, c.f. Figure 2.

The mean sea level averaged over this time period is 7.1 cm at Onsala and 9.0 cm (RH2000) at Ringhals. The observations are shown together with their differences in Figure 5. We note that occasionally during high sea level, the difference is large with higher values at Ringhals.

This effect is studied further using Van de Casteele diagrams in Figure 6. The horizontal error bars in the right graph indicate the formal uncertainty assuming a gaussian distribution.

The reason for the differences during high sea level is not known. The high sea levels occur during storms,

Fig. 5 Sea level observations at Onsala and Ringhals (top) and their differences (bottom).

Fig. 6 Van de Casteele diagrams showing the differences in sea level at Onsala and Ringhals. Individual hourly observations are shown in the left graph and mean values for 10 cm intervals in the sea level at Onsala are shown in the graph to the right.

and we may speculate that the local environment, i.e., the location of the tide gauge station relative the shape of the coastline, plays a role during these occasions, see Figure 7. We estimated the sea level trends also by ignoring values of the sea level at times when one or both sites observed a sea level above a certain level. However, we find that the difference of the half mm/year remains in all cases.

Fig. 7 The locations of the tide gauge stations at Onsala and Ringhals; © maps Lantmäteriet.

4 The absolute sea level

There are several geodetic reference markers in and around the Onsala tide gauge well. Levelling of the markers in the well relative to those in the bedrock are carried out roughly on a yearly basis. All markers are, however, not visited every time. The reference marker 827a is located on the mounting plate of the main radar sensor CS476 and the markers 827 b, c, and d, are also located in the well, see Figure 8.

These results are presented in Table 1. They show a standard deviation in the range from 0.3–0.5 mm relative to the the reference marker 822, in the bedrock close to the well.

Table 1 Levelling results to the reference points in the well

Date	Height in RH2000 ^a			
	827a (m)	827b (m)	827c (m)	827d (m)
2015-02-01	2.54617	-	-	-
2015-08-13	2.545	2.487	2.544	2.487
2016-08-05	-	-	-	2.4872
2017-06-01	-	2.4870	2.5446	2.4878
2017-07-26	-	-	-	2.488
2017-08-11	-	-	-	2.4876
2019-08-20	2.5453	2.4872	2.5447	2.4877
2020-03-31	-	-	-	2.4868
2020-10-05	2.5451	2.4865	2.5440	2.4878
2021-03-12	-	-	-	2.4868
2021-07-06	2.5459	2.4874	2.5450	2.4878
2024-08-13	2.5458	2.4870	2.5447	2.4877
Mean	2.5456	2.4870	2.5445	2.4875
SD ^b (mm)	0.47	0.30	0.41	0.43

^a Assuming that the reference marker 822 is at 2.1064 m

^b SD: Standard Deviation

The complete time series of the relative sea level at Ringhals is shown in Figure 9. The linear trend estimated from these data is 0.54 mm/year. We also note a slight increase in the rate when including the data from the last ten years. This in agreement with the higher rates observed at Onsala and Ringhals using the observations from 2015 to 2025 only.

In order to derive trends in the absolute sea level the relative results need to be corrected for any ongoing vertical motion of the Earth's crust. In northern Europe this long term trend is dominated by the glacial isostatic adjustment since the last ice age, see

Fig. 8 Reference markers in the well. Marker 827a was first measured in February 2015. The additional markers 827b, 827c, and 827d were added thereafter and were first measured on August 13, 2015.

Fig. 9 Top: The complete time series of sea level observations at Ringhals. Bottom: The estimated linear trend from the start in 1967 to a specific date.

e.g. Kierulf et al. (2021). Geodetic observations as summarized in ITRF2020 (Altamimi et al., 2023) give an estimated uplift of:

- 2.7 mm/year using GNSS data (1994–2020)
- 2.9 mm/year using VLBI data (1980–2020)

It is reasonable to believe that these values for the uplift of the Earth's crust are rather constant over a several decades. This is different from the sea level trends.

Assuming that the sea level measured at Ringhals, during the 57 years of operation, is representative also for Onsala, and that the uplift at Onsala is approximately equal to that at Ringhals, means that an overall linear trend of the regional absolute sea level has been approximately 3.3 mm/year averaged over the period 1967–2025.

5 Conclusion

The sea level at a specific site or region show large variations, depending on the variability of the weather conditions from season to season and from one year to another, compared to the expected values for the long-term trends. Therefore, stable and reliable values for any trends can only be obtained by averaging either over a very large area or over a long time. The absolute sea-level rise from 1967 to 2025 in the Onsala / Ringhals area of Kattegat has been 3.3 ± 0.2 mm/year. We also see an indication that there is an acceleration towards the end of the time series. If this is true it is consistent with recent results reported for the global sea level trend (Hamlington et al., 2024).

References

- Altamimi Z, Rebischung P, Collilieux X, Métivier L, & Charnard K (2023). ITRF2020: an augmented reference frame refining the modeling of nonlinear station motions. *J.Geod.*, 97:47, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-023-01738-w>
- Elgered G, Wahlbom J, Wennerbäck L, Pettersson L, & Haas R (2019). The Onsala Tide Gauge Station: Experiences from the first four years of operation. *Proc. of the 24th European VLBI Group for Geodesy and Astrometry Working Meeting*, eds. R. Haas, S. Garcia-Espada, and J. A. Lopez Fernandez, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain, March 2019, pp. 75–79, ISBN: 978-84-416-5634-5, <https://doi.org/10.7419/162.08.2019>
- Hamlington B D, Bellas-Manley A, Willis J K, Fournier S, Vinogradova N, Nerem R S, Piecuch C G, Thompson P R, & Kopp R (2024). The rate of global sea level rise doubled during the past three decades. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 5(1), <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01761-5>
- Kierulf H P, Steffen H, Barletta V R, Lidberg M, Johansson J, Kristiansen O, Tarasov L (2021) A GNSS velocity field for geophysical applications in Fennoscandia, *J. Geodyn.*, 146, 101845, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jog.2021.101845>

EVGA

Making VLBI
Great Again!

European VLBI Group For
Geodesy and Astrometry

CHALMERS

[doi:10.5281/zenodo.18088484](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18088484)